

*Enhancing the Performance of Existing Female Enterprises in an Emerging Economy – A
Perspective of Pakistan*

AYESHA RAZZAK

B00338026

A thesis submitted to the University of the West of Scotland in fulfilment of the requirement for
the degree of Doctor of Business Administration

September 2022

Acknowledgement

Allah, who is the Most Merciful and Most Compassionate, deserves the highest praise and thanks for guiding this dissertation in a good way.

My deepest thanks go out to my parents for all the prayers, love, and concern they've shown me throughout my entire life, and especially throughout the process of writing my dissertation. If it weren't for their support in the form of prayers and encouragement, I never would have been able to complete my studies. The same thankfulness is extended to my family.

My deepest gratitude goes out to my husband and my son for all the support, love, and patience they showed me while I was working on my dissertation. Their support and encouragement were extremely helpful in keeping me motivated to carry out this research.

I would like to extend my sincerest gratitude to my lead supervisor, Mona Althonayan, for her invaluable insights, assistance, guidance, and direction that she provided during the various stages of this research. It would not have been feasible to complete the assignment without her insightful comments and suggestions. She was generous with her knowledge, time, and expertise, freely and sincerely given. I will never forget how she has always been there to provide me with inspiration and motivation when I needed it.

My deepest gratitude goes out to all my friends, who have been so kind and encouraging during this entire process.

Last but not least, I want to thank and praise Allah for all of the good things He has done for me and throughout my life.

Declaration

I, Ayesha Razzak, declare that this dissertation, "*Enhancing the Performance of Existing Female Enterprises in an Emerging Economy – A Perspective of Pakistan,*" is the independent work of the author. This research project is original and has never been submitted previously, in whole or in part, for any other academic award. The material that has been acquired from other sources has been duly acknowledged in the thesis.

Abstract

In addition to contributing to job creation, female business owners play a significant role in advancing the global economy, fostering economic progress, and promoting diversity in entrepreneurship. Despite these contributions, women's potential remains largely untapped in various nations, including Pakistan. While research on female entrepreneurship is predominantly conducted in industrialised countries, there is a paucity of studies in emerging nations like Pakistan, which may not accurately depict the true scenario of female owned businesses in developing countries marked by prevalent patriarchal societies. Additionally, the lack of a conceptual model for the factors influencing the performance of female owned SMEs in Pakistan is a critical research gap that needs to be filled. Therefore, this study aims to develop a model of firm performance success factors in order to facilitate business success or transactions for women in Pakistan. Despite government efforts to promote measures for female entrepreneurship in Pakistan, the ratio of female entrepreneurs has not seen significant change. Consequently, the framework of this study concentrates on aspects of performance success, specifically focusing on internal factors influencing performance.

Drawing from the resource-based view of the firm as a primary theoretical framework, this study has recognised four crucial factors influencing firm performance, derived from six firm performance models. These factors include entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, competency approach, and human capital. Consequently, the research constructs and tests a conceptual model of both firm-level and individual-level factors influencing the performance of female business owners in Pakistan. To achieve the research objective, a positivism philosophy was embraced, employing a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach. This research utilised a survey strategy to test the proposed hypothesis, followed by a semi-structured interview to gain deeper insights into the quantitative findings. A total of 307 questionnaires were employed in the quantitative phase, while 15 qualitative interviews were conducted with successful female business owners in Pakistan. Partial least squares-structural equation modelling was used to investigate the quantitative data, and thematic analysis was employed for the interpretation of the semi-structured interviews.

This research also challenges existing measures and research methods that originate in wealthy countries and are being used in less developed contexts, thereby extending the boundaries of knowledge. For instance, entrepreneurial orientation is commonly believed to enhance firm performance, but empirical evidence contradicts this widely held belief, emphasising the context-specific nature of this relationship. The findings also offer empirical evidence that, in a particular context, the significance of entrepreneurial competencies is of cardinal importance. This study further adds to the body of knowledge on entrepreneurial competencies by demonstrating that formal education and business training contribute to competency development. The results align with the qualitative phase, which identified additional factors influencing firm performance, including family support, networking, self-

confidence, and a skilled workforce. Ultimately, the study proposes recommendations for implementing mechanisms that can enhance women's entrepreneurial performance while also addressing limitations, suggesting avenues for future research, and discussing implications.

Table of Contents

Chapter One: Introduction	1
1.1 Introduction.....	1
1.2 Statement to Research Problem	3
1.3 Research Gap	5
1.4 Aim and Objectives of the Study	9
1.4.1 Objectives of the Investigation	9
1.4.2 Research Question.....	10
1.5 Research Methodology Synopsis	10
1.6 Why Pakistan is an Interesting Area for the Purpose of Present Study	11
1.7 Significance of the Study	12
1.8 Thesis Organisation	13
Chapter Two: Literature Review.....	14
2.1 An Overview	14
2.2 Defining Entrepreneurship.....	14
2.3 Israel Kirzner: The Universal Entrepreneur	15
2.4 Definitions of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan Context	16
2.5 Female Entrepreneurship and Its Origins.....	17
2.6 Motivational Reasons to Pursue Entrepreneurship	19
2.7 Women Owned Enterprise in Emerging Economies	21
2.8 Theories of Entrepreneurship.....	23
2.8.1 Economic Entrepreneurship Theories	23
2.8.2 Psychological Entrepreneurship Theories.....	24
2.8.3 Sociological Entrepreneurship Theory.....	24
2.8.4 Anthropological Entrepreneurship Theory	24
2.9 Factors Impacting SMEs Performance	25
2.9.1 Firm Characteristics and Resources (Firm-Related Factors)	25
2.9.2 External Environment (Environmental Factor).....	26
2.9.3 The Individual Entrepreneur (Individual-Related Factor)	27
2.10 Factors Impacting Female Entrepreneurship Performance	28
2.10.1 Social Structures Factors.....	28
2.10.2 Institutional Factors.....	29
2.10.3 Gender Related Factors.....	29
2.10.4 Personal Factors	30
2.10.5 Firm Characteristics Factors	30
2.11 Evaluation of the Existing Firm Performance Model	31
2.11.1 Human Capital Model.....	31
2.11.3 Entrepreneurial Success Model.....	34
2.11.4 Entrepreneurial Orientation Model	35

2.11.5 Three Strategic Capabilities Model.....	37
2.11.6 The Self-Concept Traits, Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance Model.....	38
2.12 Resource-Based View: A Theoretical Perspective.....	40
2.13 Factors Adopted form Models Influencing Firm Performance.....	41
2.14 Linking Derivation Factors with Firm performance: The Proposed Conceptual Framework ..	44
2.14.1 Human Capital (Individual-Level Construct)	45
2.14.2 Learning Orientation (Individual-Level Construct)	47
2.14.3 Entrepreneurial Orientation (Firm-Level Construct)	49
2.14.4 Entrepreneurial Competencies (Firm-Level Construct).....	52
2.14.5 Performance Measure in SMEs.....	55
2.15 Linking Individual-Level and Firm-Level Constructs	57
2.16 Summary	57
Chapter Three: Conceptual Framework.....	59
3.1 An Overview	59
3.2 Hypothesis Development	59
3.2.1 Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Competencies	59
3.2.2 Entrepreneurial Competencies and Firm Performance	60
3.2.3 Entrepreneurial Orientation, Entrepreneurial Competencies and Firm Performance	60
3.2.4 Entrepreneurial Competencies and Learning Orientation.....	62
3.2.5 Learning Orientation and Firm Performance	62
3.3 Summary	63
Chapter Three: Research Methodology	64
4.1 An Overview	64
4.2 Research Philosophy/Paradigm.....	64
4.2.1 Ontology Stance.....	64
4.2.2 Epistemology Stance.....	64
4.2.3 Rationale Behind the Chosen Paradigm.....	65
4.3 Research Approach	66
4.3.1 Deductive Approach	66
4.3.2 Inductive Approach.....	67
4.4 Research Design.....	67
4.5 Research Strategy.....	68
4.6 Data Collection Methods	69
4.7 Methods for Quantitative Data Collection	72
4.7.1 Survey Design.....	72
4.7.2 Data Collection Techniques	72
4.7.3 Sampling and Popualtion	73
4.7.4 Questionnaire Design.....	74
4.7.5 Design of Survey Questionnaire	75

4.7.6 Pilot Study.....	82
4.7.7 Method of Data Analysis	82
4.8 The Necessity for Additional Investigation	83
4.9 Methods of Qualitative Data Collection	84
4.9.1 Interviews.....	84
4.9.2 Development of Interview Guide.....	85
4.9.3 Sampling Strategy	85
4.9.4 Qualitative Sample Size	86
4.9.5 Sample Recruitment.....	86
4.9.6 Adoption of Thematic Data Analysis Technique.....	88
4.9.7 Addressing Validity and Reliability Issues in Qualitative Research.....	89
4.10 Ethical Consideration.....	91
4.11 Summary.....	91
Chapter Five: Data Analysis and Results.....	93
5.1 An Overview	93
5.2 Useable Questionnaires.....	93
5.2.1 Data Screening	93
5.2.2 Missing Values.....	94
5.2.3 Unengaged/Straight Lining Data.....	94
5.2.4 Assessment of Outliers.....	94
5.2.5 Normality Test	95
5.3 Common Method Variance.....	96
5.4 General Description Results.....	97
5.4.1 Female Entrepreneurs' Age Group.....	97
5.4.2 Female Business Owners' Education Attainment	97
5.4.3 Business Training Attended by Female Business Owners.....	98
5.4.4 Female Business Owners' Prior Work Experience.....	98
5.4.5 Female Entrepreneurs' Years of Business Operation	99
5.4.6 Distribution of Female Business Owners by Sector	100
5.4.7 Female Business Owners Firm size	100
5.5 Signifying HOC	101
5.6 The First Stage: Assessment of Measurement Model.....	102
5.6.1 Internal Consistency Reliability.....	102
5.6.2 Convergent Validity.....	106
5.6.3 Factor/Outer Loading.....	107
5.6.4 Average Variance Extracted (AVE).....	107
5.6.5 Achieving Convergent Validity After Removal of Low Indicator	107
5.6.6 Discriminate Validity Test.....	109
5.6.7 The Fornell and Larcker's (1981) Criterion	110

5.6.8 Cross Loading Criterion.....	111
5.6.9 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) Criterion	114
5.7 Second Stage: Estimation of Higher-Order Constructs (HOC)	116
5.7.1 Formative Higher-Order Construct (HOC) Validation	117
5.8 Structural Model Evaluation and Testing Hypothesis	121
5.8.1 Step 1: Evaluate Collinearity Issues.....	122
5.8.2 Step 2: Determining the Relevance and Significance of Structural Model Relationships (β)	122
5.8.3 Step 3: Level of R^2 assessment (Coefficient of Determination).....	125
5.8.4 Step 4: Effect size (f^2) Assessment	126
5.8.5 Step 5: Predictive Relevance (Q^2 value) Assessment by Blindfolding Method	127
5.8.6 Step 6: Out-of-Sample Predictive Power: PLSpredict Assessment	128
5.9 Summary	131
Chapter Six: Qualitative Data Analysis	133
6.1 An Overview	133
6.2 Human Capital –Does it Plays any Role in Developing Entrepreneurial Competencies?	133
6.2.1 Education Attainment	133
6.2.2 Previous Work Experience.....	134
6.2.3 Business Training.....	135
6.3 Linking Competencies to Firm Performance	136
6.3.1 Relationship Competencies.....	136
6.3.2 Organising Competencies	137
6.3.3 Opportunity Competencies	139
6.3.4. Commitment Competency	140
6.3.5 Conceptual Competency	140
6.3.6 Strategic Competency	141
6.4 Entrepreneurial Orientation – Does EO Matter?.....	142
6.4.1 Risk-taking	143
6.4.2 Innovativeness.....	143
6.4.3 Proactiveness.....	144
6.5 Entrepreneurial Competencies and Learning Orientation.....	145
6.6 Learning Orientation and Firm Performance	146
6.7 Summary	147
Entrepreneurial.....	147
Chapter Seven: Discussion of Findings	150
7.1 An Overview	150
7.2 Human Capital as an Antecedent of Entrepreneurial Competencies	151
7.3 The Direct effect of EC on EO.....	152
7.4 The EO and Firm Performance Relationship.....	153
7.5 The EC and Firms Performance.....	155

7.6 The EC and LO Relationship.....	159
7.7 The LO and Firm Performance Relationship.....	160
7.8 The Mediating Effect of EO on the Relationship Between EC and Firm Performance.....	161
7.9 Success Factors of Female Firm Performance in Pakistan	162
7.9.1 Networking	162
7.9.2 Skilled Work Force	162
7.9.3 Positive Role of Family Members or Husband	163
7.9.4 Self-Confidence	164
7.10 Revised Conceptual Framework	164
Chapter Eight: Conclusion and Recommendation	166
8.1 An Overview	166
8.2 Research Objectives.....	166
8.3 Research Contribution and Novelty.....	168
8.3.1 Contribution to Theory.....	168
8.3.2 Managerial Implication	170
8.3.3 Contribution to Policy and Practice	171
8.4 Recommendations.....	172
8.5 Limitation of the Study	174
8.6 Future Research Direction	175
8.7 Summary.....	176
Appendices A: Ethical Approval Form.....	231
Appendices B: Participants Sheet	232
Appendices C: Participants Consent Form	234
Appendices D: Research Questionnaire.....	235
Appendices E: Interview Questions	246
Appendices F: Descriptive Statistics.....	248
Appendices G: Normality Test	251
Appendices H: Common Method Variance.....	252
Appendices I: Correlation between EC and EO.....	255
Appendices J: Correlation between EC and Firm Performance.....	256
Appendices K: Correlation between EO and Firm Performance	257

List of Table

Table 1. 1 Gender Gap	4
Table 1. 2 Research on Female Owned Firm in SAARC Nations	5
Table 1. 3 Thematic Categories of the Main Theoretical Themes and Associated Authors	7
Table 2. 1 SMEs Definitions by Various Authorise in Pakistan.....	17
Table 2. 2 Derivation of Factors Influencing Firm performance	43
Table 2. 3 Competency Domain Definitions	55
Table 4. 1 Methodological Trends in Gender Based Entrepreneurship	71
Table 4. 2 Human Capital Scales Items	76
Table 4. 3 Entrepreneurial Orientation Scales Items	77
Table 4. 4 Entrepreneurial Competencies Scales Items	78
Table 4. 5 Learning Orientation Scales Items.....	80
Table 4. 6 Firm Performance Measurement Scales	81
Table 4. 7 Interviewee's Profile	87
Table 5. 1Female Entrepreneurs Age Group	97
Table 5. 2 Female Business Owners' Education Attainment	98
Table 5. 3 Business Training Attended by Female Business Owners.....	98
Table 5. 4 Work Experience of Female Business Owners.....	99
Table 5. 5 Female Business Owners' Years of Business Operation.....	99
Table 5. 6 Distribution of Female Business Owners by Sector	100
Table 5. 7 Number of Employees	101
Table 5. 8 Assessment of Internal Consistency (Cronbach's Alpha, Rho_A and CR).....	102
Table 5. 9 Assessment of Discriminate Validity using Fornell and Larcker's (1981) Criterion	110
Table 5. 10 Cross Loading Criterion.....	111
Table 5. 11 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) Criterion.....	115
Table 5. 12 Lateral Collinearity Assessment	119
Table 5. 13 Significance Level Between the Formative LOC and HOC	120
Table 5. 14 Structural Model Assessment and Testing Hypothesis (Direct Relationship)	122
Table 5. 15 Testing Mediation	125
Table 5. 16 Total Variance Explained in Endogenous (Dependent) Constructs.....	126
Table 5. 17 Explanatory Power; the Effect Size (f^2).....	127
Table 5. 18 Guideline for Interpreting PLSpredict	129
Table 5. 19 PLSpredict Assessment of Manifest Variables.....	129
Table 5. 20 Hypothesis Results.....	130
Table 6. 1 Relationship between Research Questions, Qualitative and Quantitative Findings	147

List of Figures

Figure 2. 1 Human Capital Model	32
Figure 2. 2 The Model of SME Competitiveness	34
Figure 2. 3 Entrepreneurial Success Model	35
Figure 2. 4 Entrepreneurial Orientation Model.....	36
Figure 2. 5 Three Strategic Capabilities.....	37
Figure 2. 6 Three Strategic Capabilities Relationship	38
Figure 2. 7 Self-Concept Traits, EO and Firm Performance Model	39
Figure 3. 1 The Proposed Conceptual Framework.....	63
Figure 4. 1 Six-point Likert scale.....	75
Figure 4. 2 Thematic Analysis Stages.....	88
Figure 5. 1 Reflective Model Assessment	102
Figure 5. 2 Stage-One Measurement Model Assessment	106
Figure 5. 3 AVE relevance Testing and outer Loading Guideline.....	108
Figure 5. 4 Discriminate Validity Assessment.....	109
Figure 5. 5 SmartPLS Graphical Output: Second Stage Model.....	116
Figure 5. 6 EC HOC Redundancy Analysis.....	117
Figure 5. 7 EO HOC Redundancy Analysis	118
Figure 5. 8 Steps of Structural Model Assessment	121
Figure 7. 1 Key Success Factors of Female Firm Performance	150
Figure 7. 2 The Refined Conceptual Framework of Firm Performance	165

Abbreviations

ADB – Asian Development Bank

CFA – Confirmatory Factor Analysis

DHA – Defence Housing Authority

EC – Entrepreneurial Competencies

EO – Entrepreneurial Orientation

GEM – Global Entrepreneurship Monitor

GOP – Government of Pakistan

HDI – Human Development Index

HOC – Higher-Order Construct

LO – learning Orientation

LOC – Lower-Order Components

OECD – Organisation for Economic Co-operation and development

OL – Organisational Learning

PKR – Pakistani Rupees

PLS-SEM – Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling

RBV – Resource-Based View

SBP – State Bank of Pakistan

SEM – Structural Equation Modelling

SMEDA – Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority

SEM – Small and Medium Enterprise

TEA – Total Early-Stage Entrepreneurial Activity

UN – United Nation

UNDP – United Nations Development Programme

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Entrepreneurship frequently emerges as an alternative to conventional career paths, not only acting as a catalyst for innovation but also offering solutions to societal unemployment (Costa et al., 2016). This, in turn, contributes to global economic development (Gieure et al., 2020). As emphasised by Fellnhofer and Kraus (2015), policymakers commonly perceive entrepreneurship as a key driver of technological advancement and economic growth. The extent of entrepreneurial activities is often regarded as the primary differentiator between developed and less developed nations (Khoshmaram et al., 2020). Hence, encouraging entrepreneurship can expedite the socio-economic development process in less developed nations.

Women business owners worldwide are swiftly and significantly influencing society, recognised for attributes like leadership, management, and networking skills. Despite these strengths, female business owners face numerous challenges in operating their ventures, irrespective of their economic involvement. The predominantly male entrepreneurial culture worldwide marginalises women and perpetuates the stereotype that they are incapable of managing their own businesses (Ekanem, 2015). Additionally, neither the media nor academics acknowledge women's unique contribution (Trequattrini et al., 2019). SMEs owned by women, especially in developing countries, play a vital role in advancing their nation's economic growth, generating new employment opportunities, and enriching the diversity of entrepreneurship (Xheneti et al., 2019b). Therefore, entrepreneurship presents women with avenues for achievement and success (Eddleston and Powell, 2008).

According to the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor Report (GEM, 2018), a substantial number of women worldwide have opted for entrepreneurship as a career path. Research suggests that businesses initiated by women have made noteworthy contributions to the growth of numerous developed nations (Cesaroni and Sentuti, 2018). Yet, the potential of female led SMEs in many nations, including Pakistan, remains largely untapped. This is due to the underutilisation of women's entrepreneurial potential in developing nations, where they often lack the essential infrastructure and institutional support to launch new startups (World Bank, 2017). Additionally, the OECD report affirmed that women's participation in business is significantly lower than that of men in many countries (Halabisky, 2018).

Female entrepreneurs commonly enter conventional sectors, particularly in the service and retail industries. Correspondingly, their businesses often remain small in terms of growth, revenue, employment, and investment (Roomi, 2011; Ruiz-Arroyo et al., 2012). Studies have revealed constraints on female business owners' access to social, human, and capital resources during the initiation and development phases of their businesses. Consequently, it is imperative for female entrepreneurs to acknowledge, acquire, and cultivate their skills and capabilities to attain a sustained competitive advantage.

Academics have been stressing for a long time how important enterprising skills and traits are for building innovatively engaged human resources. Hence, the exploration of how individuals engage in innovative thinking and behaviour has become a significant focus for strategy creators, instructors, and specialists aiming to support independent entrepreneurial activities undertaken by individuals or organisations (Hisrich et al., 2007). For instance, Edelman et al. (2010) and Carter et al. (2003) note that people desire to undertake an entrepreneurial role to achieve self-realisation, generate more wealth, gain independence, and play influential roles in society. As indicated by Hisrich (2014), “entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the accompanying financial, psychic, and social risk, and receiving the resulting rewards.”

Entrepreneurship holds significance by fostering financial efficiencies, sustaining business levels, creating new job opportunities, and offering innovations to the public. Therefore, entrepreneurs detect and cultivate business opportunities within an environment characterised by uncertainty and dynamics. Nevertheless, the perception of uncertainty has varied over time (Schmitt et al., 2018). While it is undeniable that external influences impact SME development in entrepreneurship, this factor alone does not fully explain the success or failure of SMEs, instead, an entrepreneur's skills and abilities contribute significantly to firm performance. As asserted by Mitchelmore et al. (2014), the success of a firm is intricately linked to its owners and individuals abilities.

Within the paradigm of entrepreneurship research, the psychological influence on entrepreneurial choice as a career has been the most studied area. While previous studies have established a connection between the psychological traits of entrepreneurs and their behaviour and success (Baum et al., 2014), this approach has faced criticism due to inconsistent results in replication studies (Rauch and Frese, 2007). The inability to identify a definitive set of dispositional characteristics for profiling entrepreneurs within the entrepreneurship domain has led some scholars to shift their attention to entrepreneurial behaviours.

Recognising the prevalent use of individual-level analysis in prior studies, recent research has shifted towards examining firm-level behaviours to elucidate entrepreneurial performance (Poon et al., 2006). The rationale behind this shift lies in the belief that behaviours lend meaning to the entrepreneurial process and allow for more effective managerial intervention (Anderson et al., 2015; Covin and Slevin, 1991). In light of these considerations, this study investigates both individual and firm-specific factors that may influence the performance of female SMEs. Significantly, the study develops and tests a conceptual model for understanding individual and firm-level factors influencing performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan. Similarly, the study adopts the resource-based view (RBV) perspective as its theoretical foundation. Employing a sequential mixed-method approach, this study seeks to enhance our understanding of the factors influencing the firm performance of female

entrepreneurs. The study underscores that focusing solely on individual- or firm-level constructs in isolation provides only a partial insight into comprehending women's venture performance. Consequently, examining individual entrepreneur constructs (such as human capital) as antecedents to key firm-level constructs (like entrepreneurial competencies) offers a more holistic understanding of the drivers of firm performance in Pakistan.

The findings of this study are anticipated to guide the recalibration of support policies, introducing intervention strategies focused on empowering women entrepreneurs with the potential to drive growth. The success of more women owned businesses in developing countries can make a significant contribution to economic development, underscoring the importance of this study. Recognising the vital role played by women owned small businesses in any economy, it becomes crucial to investigate and comprehend the factors that could impact the success of such enterprises. This knowledge can then inform measures that have the potential to enhance the likelihood of success for these businesses, thereby contributing to economic progress.

The subsequent sections provide further insights into the research, including the statement of the research problem (Section 1.2), identification of literature gaps (Section 1.3), formulation of research objectives and questions (Section 1.4), a synopsis of the research methodology (Section 1.5), an explanation of the rationale for selecting Pakistan as the study area (Section 1.6), an exploration of the significance of the study (Section 1.7), and an overview of the subsequent chapters (Section 1.8).

1.2 Statement to Research Problem

Despite the growing awareness that, without women's participation in public life, no country can advance, female entrepreneurship still needs to be studied in greater depth. They are underestimated, and for researchers in developing nations, Pakistan in particular, the lack of a data base is troublesome as the majority of female entrepreneurs are largely informal, home-based, and not registered with an official body (World Bank, 2017). The socio-economic status of women varies drastically across various parts of Asia. Moreover, the unequal distribution of basic nutrition and healthcare contributes to greater health issues among women (Sen, 2017). Furthermore, Pakistan exhibits the widest gender wage disparity globally, according to the World Economic Forum's 2017 report, which ranked the country second lowest (143) in the South Asian region. In contrast, Bangladesh and India secured ranks of 47 and 108, respectively, on the global gender gap index (Daily Times, 2017). Table 1.1 illustrates the gender gap ratios of Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan.

Source: Dakhan (2019)

Research on women's business ownership in underdeveloped nations is notably scarce in comparison to studies conducted in Western nations. Consequently, theories and models originating from Western contexts may inadequately capture the conditions of emerging contexts, particularly where family dynamics significantly differ (Al-Dajani and Marlow, 2010). This holds true in the context of Pakistan, where the landscape of female entrepreneurship differs not only from that of female-owned businesses in the West but also from that of other developing nations, owing to substantial variations in family dynamics.

Globally, there is a notable increase in SMEs, including those owned by women. For instance, in Spain, SMEs account for 99.9% of all enterprises, contributing to 65.7% of the country's GDP (Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2015). However, Pakistan lags behind with one of the lowest percentages globally. According to Quresh (2019), female entrepreneurs in Pakistan make up only 1% of the total, primarily due to several challenges they face, including limited access to finance and markets. The "Women's Entrepreneurship" study by the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) for 2016–2017 revealed a 10% increase in women's rates of total early-stage entrepreneurial activity (TEA) over the previous two decades (Kazmi, 2018). Likewise, a women owned business in Pakistan is usually small, with an investment of less than Rs 0.5 million and a turnover of less than Rs 1 million (Ananke, 2015). Aslam et al. (2013) assert that female entrepreneurs encounter various issues affecting their productivity, such as challenges in hiring qualified employees, obtaining financing, and operating in inadequate or inefficient markets. For example, in Pakistan, women face limited access to the internet and banking facilities. In contrast, the women's sector constitutes nearly 45% of the Indian population (Vinesh, 2014), while in Pakistan, women make up only 20.2% of the labour force (World Bank, 2022). The information presented indicates that in Pakistan, the majority of entrepreneurs are not productive enough to prosper and contribute meaningfully to the well-being of the nation's economy, making the examination of factors determining SME performance critical.

Moreover, a significant gap in existing literature persists due to the absence of a conceptual model for comprehending the factors that impact the performance of female-owned enterprises in developing nations, especially in the context of Pakistan. The establishment of such a conceptual model carries the potential to deepen our understanding of the elements influencing the performance of female

entrepreneurship. Consequently, the present research seeks to formulate and validate a conceptual framework that integrates both individual-level and firm behavioural factors to elucidate the performance of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan.

Firm behavioural factors encompass dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and entrepreneurial competencies (EC), while individual-level factors incorporate components of human capital and learning orientation (LO) to assess firm performance. Importantly, this study adopts the resource-based view of the firm as its theoretical foundation. The research makes a valuable contribution to the literature by advancing our comprehension of the heterogeneity within the self-employed demographic, specifically female entrepreneurs. The focus extends to broadening insights into the antecedents and consequences of EO and EC.

This research not only aims to fill a critical knowledge gap but also holds practical significance. By illuminating the factors influencing the performance of female owned businesses, it establishes a foundation for stakeholders and policymakers to develop targeted interventions and more effective programs. Ultimately, this can contribute to enhancing the performance of women owned businesses and, in the long term, augmenting their economic contributions.

1.3 Research Gap

Despite the abundance of literature on women owned firms, there is a necessity for further research into the factors influencing female entrepreneurship and its impact on firm performance in developing nations, especially within specific cultural contexts like Pakistan. For instance, Rashid and Ratten (2020), using the SCOPUS database, conducted a systematic literature review (SLR) on female entrepreneurship in SAARC nations, examining and analysing English-language peer-reviewed publications. They found just 30 papers from the respective SAARC countries had been published in the past 23 years (1996–2018), as shown in Table 1.2. The authors conducted a comprehensive literature analysis on women owned firms and found that very little research had been done on the area, especially in South Asian countries.

Table 1. 2 Research on Female Owned Firm in SAARC Nations

Source: Rashid and Ratten (2020)

In a similar vein, Correa et al. (2021) conducted a meta-analysis of women owned firms in developing and emerging nations. Using the Web of Science and Scopus databases (Social Science Citation Index), a systematic literature review was performed over a ten-year timeframe (2010–2020). Out of 465 papers, a total of 77 were selected for content analysis. The analysis resulted in the generation of fourteen non-exhaustive thematic categories from these 77 articles, producing 212 records. These categories include entrepreneurial performance, business competencies, entrepreneurial characteristics, entrepreneurship, challenges, gender, fostering entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial motivation, business success, networks, capital, entrepreneurial orientation, institutionalism, and others, as illustrated in Table 1.3. Their findings indicate that the majority of publications primarily focus on understanding the challenges faced by female business owners, while little attention is given to exploring their entrepreneurial attributes. Similarly, qualitative research emerges as the predominant approach, with less emphasis on mixed-methods studies. It follows that the amount of relevant literature on women owned businesses in general and Pakistan in particular is relatively lower, especially in developing countries (Hossain et al., 2020; Correa et al., 2021). Significantly, there are far fewer studies available on emerging economies that have recently undergone significant sociocultural and political unrest, creating challenging environments for business activities (Welsh et al., 2018a).

In both economic and social spheres, men in Pakistan wield more power than their female counterparts. Entering the workforce or starting a business is nearly impossible for women in Pakistan's patriarchal society because the domestic role of caring for children and the elderly confines them to the family home (Lindvert et al., 2017). Women constitute half of Pakistan's population, but due to persistent gender discrimination, they make up only a small proportion of the country's work force. The majority of the studies on women owned SMEs have primarily concentrated on western settings, which have a culture that values individualism, while in Pakistan people are known to have a collectivist culture. Surprisingly, no study to date has examined the factors influencing the performance of Pakistani women entrepreneurs. Despite numerous previous studies evaluating the performance of female-owned firms, there is not a single study addressing the factors influencing the performance of female business owners in Pakistan, owing to the country's specific culture (Zeb and Ihsan, 2020). This study fills that need by investigating the factors impacting the performance of Pakistani female entrepreneurs in the context of the country's distinctive sociocultural environment. While academics have extensively studied female entrepreneurship in Pakistan, the majority of research has focused on the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs in Pakistan (Roomi and Parrott, 2008; Hafizullah et al., 2012); women's empowerment (Noor et al., 2021); motivation (Hanif et al., 2017); and working environment or gender-based problems (Rehman and Roomi, 2012; Lindvert et al., 2017). Yet, numerous other factors affecting female entrepreneur performance have received little attention in the study of Pakistani female entrepreneurship.

Additionally, the utilisation of mixed-method approaches in research, especially in developing nations, has been infrequent, according to Correa et al. (2021). In response to this, this seeks to address this gap by adopting a mixed-method approach, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. This research not only aims to employ mixed-methods but also addresses various literature gaps identified in the field. This includes the need for further exploration into the cognitive processes of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan, focusing on personality traits, business experience, and educational attainment in navigating challenging environments (Roomi et al., 2018). Additionally, the study examines further the entrepreneurial behaviours of female entrepreneurs, as suggested by Gieure et al. (2020). Furthermore, a notable gap in understanding competencies within female-owned enterprises, identified by Mitchelmore and Rowley (2013), is also a focal point for this research. This study also responds to calls from Canina et al. (2010) and Welter et al. (2017) for contextualising entrepreneurship research and advocating for more behavioural approaches to understanding small firm performance. It also responds to Correa et al.'s (2021) suggestion for additional investigation into entrepreneurial attributes, such as entrepreneurial orientation, impacting women owned firms, particularly in developing countries. Additionally, the study addresses the limited knowledge about the antecedents of entrepreneurial orientation, given the scarcity of research on EO drivers (Dele-Ijagbulu et al., 2020; Wales, 2016). Lastly, within entrepreneurship studies, the scarcity of research into integrated individual and firm behaviour relationships will be explored (Canina et al., 2010; Seet et al., 2021).

Table 1. 3 Thematic Categories of the Main Theoretical Themes and Associated Authors

<i>Categories</i>	<i>Articles (77)</i>	<i>Records (212)</i>	<i>Themes Highlighted</i>	<i>Authors</i>
Business Competence	--	19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Marketing ❖ Entrepreneurial creativity ❖ Innovation ❖ Others 	Brixiova et al. (2020); Osei and Zhuang (2020); Minimol (2020); Sihotang et al. (2020); Ghouse (2019); Gooptu and Chakravarty (2018); Zainol et al. (2018) Batool and Ullah (2017); Langevang (2017); Zainol et al. (2017); Welsh et al (2017); Kimosop et al. (2016); Gundry et al. (2014).
Business Success	5	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Factors associated with women's business success 	Amrita et al. (2018); Baranik et al. (2018); Hendratmi and Sukmaningrum (2018); Sen (2018); Batool and Ullah (2017).
Capital	--	14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Financial capital ❖ Spiritual capital ❖ Human capital ❖ Social capital 	Osei and Zhuang (2020); Reza et al. (2020); Setini et al. (2020); Rekarti et al. (2019); Baranik et al. (2018); Zainol et al. (2018); Lindvert et al. (2017); Zainol et al. (2017); Muniady et al. (2015); Roomi (2013).
Challenges	25	31	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Work-family balance ❖ Access to finance 	Cooke and Xiao (2021); Jaim (2021); Alecchi (2020); Alene (2020); Brixiova et al. (2020);

			❖ Culture	Selamat and Endut (2020); Shakeel et al. (2020); Al-Dajani et al. (2019); Fis et al. (2019); Mathew (2019); Solanki (2019); Tlaiss and Kauser (2019); Xheneti et al. (2019a); Martiana (2018); Welsh et al. (2018b); Ghouse et al. (2017); Kuschel et al. (2017); Lindvert et al. (2017); Marques et al. (2017a); Welsh et al. (2017); Zainol et al. (2017); Welsh et al. (2016); Roomi (2013); Roomi and Harrison (2010).
Entrepreneurial Characteristics	--	12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Business leadership ❖ Psychological traits ❖ Cognitive traits ❖ Entrepreneurial profile ❖ Others 	Cooke and Xiao (2021); Reza et al. (2020); Shakeel et al. (2020); Vasan (2020); Tlaiss and Kauser (2019); Kakabadse et al. (2018); Batool and Ullah (2017); Ghouse et al. (2017); Marques et al. (2017a); Ramadani et al. (2013).
Entrepreneurial Motivations	--	14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Push and pull factors ❖ Influence of family on business creation ❖ Several diffuse factors 	Cooke and Xiao (2021); Alene (2020); Ghouse (2019); Solanki (2019); Hendratmi and Sukmaningrum (2018); Ng and Fu (2018); Martiana (2018); Welsh et al. (2018b); Batool and Ullah (2017); Cantu et al. (2017); Marques et al. (2017a).
Entrepreneurial Orientation	3	3	❖ Entrepreneurial orientation	Mandongwe and Jaravaza (2020); Purnamawati et al. (2020); Gundry et al. (2014).
Entrepreneurial Performance	25	30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Impact on general economic development ❖ informal businesses ❖ Micro-companies ❖ Business development 	Cooke and Xiao (2021); Alene (2020); Olu-Owolabi et al. (2020); Reza et al. (2020); Shakeel et al. (2020); Sihotang et al. (2020); Vasan (2020); Ennis (2019); Maziriri et al. (2019); Ngoasong and Kimbu (2019); Gonzalez (2018); et al. (2018); Sen (2018); Thapa and Xheneti (2018); Welsh et al. (2018b); Zainol et al. (2018); Kuschel et al. (2017); Langevang (2017); Welsh et al. (2017); Zainol et al. (2017); Kimosop et al. (2016); Muniady et al. (2015); Altan-Olcay (2014); Roomi (2013).
Entrepreneurship	8	22	❖ Entrepreneurs reflection in micro, small and medium-size companies	Jaim (2021); Alene (2020); Onalan and Magda, (2020); Onyusheva and Meyer (2020); Selamat and Endut (2020); Al-Dajani et al. (2019); Maziriri et al. (2019); Amrita et al. (2018); Gooptu and Chakravarty (2018); Kakabadse et al. (2018); Mehtap et al. (2018); Marques et al. (2017a); Altan-Olcay (2014);

				Gundry et al. (2014); Ghani et al. (2014); Ghani et al. (2013); Ramadani et al. (2013); Roomi (2013); Roessingh and Nuijten (2012); Warnecke et al. (2012); Siringi (2011); Roomi and Harrison (2010).
Fostering Entrepreneurship	--	15	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Relevance of several initiatives to promote entrepreneurship ❖ Relevance of public policies influence 	Cooke and Xiao (2021); Alecchi (2020); Alene (2020); Jabeen and Faisal (2018); Ghouse et al. (2017); Zainol et al. (2017); Altan-Olcay (2016); Caputo et al. (2016); Mbaruku and Mutalemwa (2015); Ghani et al. (2014); Ramadani et al. (2013); Warnecke et al. (2012) Roomi and Harrison (2010).
Gender	--	20	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Role associated with each gender ❖ Female empowerment 	Alecchi (2020); Brixiova et al. (2020); Purnamawati et al. (2020); Onyusheva and Meyer (2020); Owalla and Ghafri (2020); Selamat and Endut (2020); Vershinina et al. (2020); Mathew (2019); Tlaiss and Kauser (2019); Gooptu and Chakravarty (2018); Martiana (2018); Thapa and Xheneti (2018); Kuschel et al. (2017); Altan-Olcay (2016); Gundry et al. (2014); Warnecke et al. (2012).
Institutionalism	6	8	Institutionalism	Alecchi (2020); Thapa et al. (2020); Vershinina et al. (2020); Langevang et al. (2018); Xiong et al. (2018); Lock and Smith (2016).
Networks	5	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Related to social embeddedness 	Alecchi (2020); Vershinina et al. (2020); Ngoasong and Kimbu (2019); Kuschel et al. (2017); Welsh et al. (2017).
Others	--	14	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Feminist theory ❖ Ecological modernisation theory ❖ others 	Mandongwe and Jaravaza (2020); Osei and Zhuang (2020); Purnamawati et al. (2020); Thapa et al. (2020); Tlaiss and Kauser (2019); Ghouse et al. (2017); Lindvert et al. (2017); Zainol et al. (2017); Altan-Olcay (2014); Gundry et al. (2014); Siringi (2011).

Source: Adapted from Correa et al. (2021)

1.4 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The overall aim of this research is to identify the key success factors having a substantial influence on the performance of female entrepreneurship in Pakistan and develop a conceptual framework underpinning the success factors to maximise the performance of Pakistani women entrepreneurs.

1.4.1 Objectives of the Investigation

The purpose of this investigation is to accomplish the following objectives:

The main research question is, “*How can the performance of women owned SMEs be enhanced?*”

- *To evaluate the effects of entrepreneurs competencies on firm performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan.*
- *To determine the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on firm performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan.*
- *To determine if human capital variables (i.e., education attainment, previous work experience, and business training) serve as antecedents of entrepreneurial competencies.*
- *To determine how entrepreneurial orientation affects the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and firm performance.*

1.4.2 Research Question

The following research questions will be addressed in the present study:

1. *How do the entrepreneurial competencies reported in the literature (i.e., opportunity, commitment, strategic, conceptual, organising, and relationship) affect performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan?*
2. *How does entrepreneurial orientation (i.e., risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness) affect the performance of women owned SMEs in Pakistan?*
3. *How does human capital (i.e., education attainment, previous work experience, and business training) affect entrepreneurial competencies and ultimately firm performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan?*
4. *Does entrepreneurial orientation mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and firm performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan?*

1.5 Research Methodology Synopsis

Given the aim and objective of the research, this study delved into a comprehensive examination of factors widely acknowledged and considered crucial for the firm performance of female entrepreneurs. Grounded in a positivism paradigm, the research employed a sequential mixed-method approach. Using a non-random sampling technique, specifically a convenient and snowball sampling strategy, the researcher distributed 400 questionnaires, of which 345 returned and 307 were accepted after meticulous data scanning procedures. The questionnaire, available in both English and Urdu, was administered through a face-to-face survey conducted in Lahore, the capital of Punjab province. To collect responses, a six-point Likert scale was employed in the questionnaire instrument, which underwent a pilot test before distribution to actual female entrepreneurs. Likewise, to ensure reliability and validity, the study conducted confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to test the measurement model, and structural equation modelling (SEM) was employed to assess the structural modelling and empirically test the hypothesis relations. Recognising the inherent limitations of relying solely on quantitative techniques to comprehend the phenomenon under investigation, the author believes that

static results require further explanation because a single method is not always dependable. Therefore, to understand the ground realities, a qualitative approach was adopted.

1.6 Why Pakistan is an Interesting Area for the Purpose of Present Study

For numerous reasons, research on Pakistani women's entrepreneurship is a stimulating and compelling undertaking. First, women owned businesses in Pakistan are ideal for further study because this area is so under-researched (Rashid and Ratten, 2020). Furthermore, the patriarchal culture in Pakistan perpetuates a number of discriminatory practices and socio-cultural beliefs, so female business owners are not valued and do not have equal access to opportunities as their male counterparts (Lindvert et al., 2017). Obstacles could be overcome if support mechanisms were available to existing and aspiring businesswomen (Roomi and Parrott, 2008).

Secondly, the economic potential of Pakistan's female entrepreneurs is not fully realised due to a lack of resources such as information technology (IT), land, capital, office space, and agency support. Although women make up nearly half of Pakistan's population, barely 1% of the country's entrepreneurs are female (Quresh, 2019). Hafizullah et al. (2012) claim that in patriarchal Pakistan, women are expected to play conventional roles, such as housewives. For women who want to start their own business, these culturally ingrained ideas about men's superiority pose significant obstacles. In order to understand the factors that support the performance of enterprises, it is necessary to have an in-depth awareness of the firm performance factor, which is covered in great detail in Section 2.10.

Third, due to the lack of support from male family members, women in Pakistan experience a dearth of social capital and restricted mobility. Research by Rehman and Roomi (2012) suggests that more institutional and family assistance is needed in Pakistan to create and foster female entrepreneurship. Additionally, government agencies, media, and policymakers should act to increase access to business facilitation and development services, including regional, provisional, and national networks, in order to help female entrepreneurs integrate into the mainstream economy. As asserted by Hafizullah et al. (2012), gender bias embedment is the primary cause of the challenges and issues faced by Pakistani female entrepreneurs. This inferior status of women in society is brought about by feudal, tribal, and regional cultures that are based on religion. Therefore, women are undervalued as economic agents.

Finally, previous studies conducted by Shabbir and Di Gregorio (1996), Roomi and Parrott (2008), and Hafizullah et al. (2012) note that in Pakistan, the notions of "*Izzat*" and "*Purdah*" are the primary causes of the difficulties faced by female business entrepreneurs. These studies claim that if doubts are cast on a woman's good reputation, their chances of a marriage proposal will be lessened. Therefore, women are not allowed to work with men or go out, placing restrictions on their mobility. In Pakistan, this study is of the utmost importance and interest since it is vital to examine how existing and aspiring female entrepreneurs can conquer the patriarchal socio-cultural environment and enhance the performance of their businesses.

1.7 Significance of the Study

The recognition of female-owned businesses as a vital source of global entrepreneurial diversity is growing. However, economic and socio-cultural challenges in emerging nations, such as Pakistan, often hinder them from reaching their full potential (Lindvert et al., 2017; Roomi et al., 2018). In Pakistan, women encounter explicit gender-based barriers that significantly impede their talents, not only hindering the development of women's entrepreneurship but also dissuading them from initiating their own businesses. Female entrepreneurship is in decline in Pakistan, and the country will never be able to compete internationally unless the country's female participation in the economy increases (Quresh, 2019).

This research is expected to make significant contributions to the existing literature in multiple ways. The primary focus of the present study is to develop a conceptual model that links both individual- and firm-level factors influencing the performance of women owned SMEs in Pakistan. The study employed a resource-based view of the firm as a theoretical perspective and employed factors like competency approach, entrepreneurial orientation, human capital, and learning orientation to examine the performance of female entrepreneurship in Pakistan.

The conclusions drawn from this research are anticipated to be highly beneficial for identifying factors and their various combinations that optimise performance in the context of female entrepreneurship. The study has theoretical implications, as it has the potential to introduce novel knowledge to the field of entrepreneurship, specifically exploring different levels within entrepreneurship from a female perspective. Unlike previous female entrepreneurship studies that have primarily examined either the socio-economic characteristics of women or the characteristics of their businesses, this research integrates both individual-level factors and firm behaviours to assess how high performance can be achieved by women owned firms in Pakistan. Therefore, this study will advance knowledge regarding women's entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship in general.

From a practical standpoint, the outcomes of this study can assist female entrepreneurs in Pakistan who operate in the retail and service industries. The focus should be directed towards competency training, as it plays a crucial role in advancing their success and efficiency. The practical significance lies in the ability to identify individual traits and corporate behaviours that drive entrepreneurial pursuits and success, a value that is applicable globally, particularly in developing nations. Consequently, comprehending the various levels of entrepreneurship can facilitate the development and implementation of governmental and educational policies aimed at supporting entrepreneurs in improving their firm performance. In particular, this research will contribute to policymakers' understanding of the connections between individual and firm-level factors within the context of a slow-growth regional economy undergoing a radical transformation from a reliance on retail and services to one centred on innovation.

1.8 Thesis Organisation

This thesis is organised into eight chapters, which are summarised below.

Chapter One is the introduction to the entire research. It provides details about the research problem and also describes the study aim, followed by research objectives and research questions. The significance of the study is also discussed in this chapter.

Chapter Two begins by defining entrepreneurship in general and female entrepreneurship in particular. It explores female entrepreneurs' motivation to start a business and highlights female entrepreneurship in emerging economies. Additionally, the chapter reviews literature concerning the factors impacting firm performance, giving special attention to the context of female entrepreneurship and the broader influences on small businesses. Additionally, this chapter critically evaluates various models to pinpoint significant factors affecting the performance of female entrepreneurs' firms, while also highlighting the theoretical perspectives guiding the current research.

Chapter Three revolves around building a conceptual framework grounded in the competency approach, entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientation (LO), and human capital theory. This framework explores both firm-level and individual-level factors that exert influence on the performance of SMEs owned by women. The hypotheses to be tested are also proposed in this chapter.

Chapter Four covers the philosophy adopted, the various research methodologies used, and their justification for adoption in this study. After a review of mixed-method approaches and how they help meet the research goal, the methods for gathering data and analysing data are discussed.

Chapter Five discusses the empirical work and tests the proposed hypothesis using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) with structural equation modelling. The findings of the hypotheses are used to build the questionnaire for the qualitative phase.

Chapter Six represents the result of transcribed data (the qualitative phase). For analysing the data, thematic analysis techniques were employed, and themes were generated. Female business owners' viewpoints on the hypothesis were discussed.

Chapter Seven provides an in-depth discussion on factors that are considered significant to enhancing the performance of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan. Based on the analysis of both quantitative and qualitative phases, the proposed conceptual framework is refined, and a final model is proposed.

Chapter Eight is the last chapter, which not only summarises the findings of the thesis but also addresses the theoretical and empirical contributions. It also offers a set of recommendations and suggestions to policymakers, followed by an explanation of the limitations of the study and suggestions for future research.

Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 An Overview

The key objective of this chapter is to comprehensively examine and discuss relevant literature to ascertain the factors that impact the performance of female entrepreneurship. The chapter commences by defining entrepreneurship in Section 2.2, followed by a review of Israel Kirzner's concept of "the universal entrepreneur" in Section 2.3. Section 2.4 delves into the definitions of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in the context of Pakistan, while Section 2.5 explores a review of female entrepreneurship and its origins. Motivational reasons for women to pursue entrepreneurship are discussed in Section 2.6, and Section 2.7 focuses on women owned enterprises in emerging economies. Furthermore, the chapter critically evaluates various entrepreneurship theories (see Section 2.8), factors affecting SME performance in general (see Section 2.9), and factors influencing female owned firm performance specifically (see Section 2.10).

The chapter analysis six firm performance models in Section 2.11 to identify key factors contributing to firm performance. The theoretical foundation is presented in Section 2.12, whereas Section 2.13 discusses the factors adopted from models influencing firm performance in female entrepreneurship. Section 2.14 considers how the derivate factors integrate with firm performance and establishes a conceptual framework. The linkage between individual-level and firm-level constructs is illustrated in Section 2.15. Lastly, the chapter concludes with a summary provided at the end.

2.2 Defining Entrepreneurship

Schumpeter (1934) provided one of the earliest definitions of entrepreneurship, suggesting that "entrepreneurship is the creation of new combinations." Cole (1968) characterised entrepreneurship as "purposeful activity aimed at initiating, maintaining, and developing a profit-oriented business." While Kirzner (1973) defined entrepreneurship as "a process of discovery". According to Gartner (1985), entrepreneurship involves the creation of new organizations. In the view of Gartner (1985), the concept of entrepreneurship has four key perspectives, which include the process involved in establishing the business, the surrounding environment, individual characteristics initiating the business, and the business that they create. Kao (1993) viewed "entrepreneurship as the process of doing something new and something different for the purpose of creating wealth for the individual and adding value to society." Similarly, Shane and Venkataraman (2000) define entrepreneurship as a business domain where an individual's assess and explore diverse avenues to capitalise on market opportunities, generating innovations such as new products, production processes, organisational structures, services, and advancements in existing enterprises, marketing strategies, or processes through the establishment of new businesses. The difficulty with the variety of definitions for entrepreneurship is that, while each encapsulates a facet of the concept, none presents a comprehensive overview. Moreover, the concept is associated with multiple disciplines (e.g., psychology, management, sociology, etc.), each with its

specific concepts and rules, further contributing to the complexity. Therefore, it can be said that entrepreneurship is a multidimensional notion (Bula, 2012).

Consequently, extensive research has been conducted on the topic of entrepreneurship, encompassing a broad spectrum of subjects within its diverse dimensions. One reason for this is that there is strong evidence of a shift in economic activity from large to small firms in the 1970s and 1980s. Remarkably, this trend remains highly apparent in the 21st century (Box et al., 2016), where the majority of new firms are small, in developing countries, and firms are typically of a smaller scale. Hence, a significant portion of the entrepreneurship literature is dedicated to exploring the dynamics of small and medium enterprises (Naude, 2010). Likewise, entrepreneurship is a multidisciplinary field, incorporating perspectives from various disciplines such as management, sociology, psychology, economics, and anthropology (Carlsson et al., 2013). This poses a challenge in obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the field, as the literature is dispersed across diverse disciplines and, consequently, published in various journals. Small businesses, due to their characteristics of adaptability, swift responsiveness to market changes, innovation, and closer customer engagement in comparison to larger enterprises, further contribute to this complexity. Nevertheless, SMEs offer a unique contribution to every economy. Empirical findings highlight that SMEs serve as a vital source for generating employment, fostering innovation, and contributing to economic development (OECD, 2017a). Furthermore, entrepreneurship functions as a catalyst for change, playing a role in stimulating the industrial revolution. Hence, SMEs play a crucial role in promoting sustainable, diversified, and long-term economic growth (Box et al., 2016). To illustrate, SMEs constitute approximately 90% of businesses globally and contribute over 50% to global employment. In emerging economies, formal SMEs contribute up to 40% to the GDP. When considering informal SMEs, these figures become even more substantial (World Bank, 2022). Hence, their contribution is undeniably substantial in both developed and developing nations.

2.3 Israel Kirzner: The Universal Entrepreneur

The entrepreneur, as defined by Kirzner (1973), is an individual who unearths previously undetected profit opportunities. Entrepreneurial discovery initiates a process in which these newly discovered profit opportunities are then acted on in the marketplace until market competition eliminates the profit opportunities (Pidiha and Singh, 2015). Kirzner (1973) asserts that opportunities are readily available in society for anyone with the "alertness" to recognise them, rather than exclusively created by special individuals. According to his viewpoint, opportunities arise due to the market being in a state of disequilibrium caused by flawed decision-making frameworks, leading to shortages and surpluses (Kirzner, 1973). It is within these shortages and surpluses that entrepreneurial opportunities can be located. Unlike the Schumpeterian entrepreneur who creates opportunities, the Kirzner entrepreneur, is primarily focused on identifying and uncovering existing opportunities.

For this study, Kirzner's (1973) definition and perspective are adopted for two key reasons. Firstly, it acknowledges entrepreneurship as a serendipitous process based on the alertness that characterises entrepreneurs. Secondly, the definition is grounded in the notion that an entrepreneur does not create anything new; instead, they discover and seize existing opportunities. The examination of firm performance is also grounded in the assumption that individuals secure entrepreneurial profit on the basis of knowledge and information gaps that arise between people in the market. In this view, the entrepreneur is an alert person, discovering opportunities by acting as an arbitrageur or a price adjuster in the market, capitalising on knowledge or information asymmetries. By discovering opportunities and acting on them, every entrepreneur can initiate a new venture with the expectation of witnessing its evolution into a more successful enterprise than its initial establishment.

2.4 Definitions of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Pakistan Context

Defining SMEs also poses a challenge for researchers in the entrepreneurship field, with variations persisting from country to country. This is unsurprising given the continuous lack of agreement on the definition of entrepreneurship itself. Divergences in the definition of SMEs exist among countries and even within the same country, varying based on their contribution to economic development and prevailing social conditions. To illustrate, Singh et al. (2008) have noted that diverse factors and criteria, such as the number of employees, age, size, location, asset worth, sales volume, organisational structure, ownership, and utilisation of innovation and technology, are employed to define SMEs. While Lee and Yuhua (2016) note that various countries use distinct criteria, such as investment, sales, assets, or employment, to define SMEs, the prevailing basis for defining SMEs by the European Commission is commonly centred on employment, with numerous countries adopting 250 employees as the threshold (Box et al., 2016).

SMEs in Pakistan are also no exception, with no uniform definition of SMEs; hence, the definition of SMEs varies among different sources, including the Federal Bureau of Statistics, which classifies SMEs on the basis of the number of employees only, while the Punjab Small Industries Department's classification of an SME is based on fixed assets only. In contrast, the Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority (SMEDA) and the State Bank of Pakistan (SBP) provide a comprehensive definition of SMEs, which encompasses the number of employees, total assets, and annual turnover (Ishaq, 2022). SMEDA defines SMEs as companies with a maximum of 250 employees, paid-up capital not exceeding Rs. 25 million, and annual sales not surpassing Rs. 250 million (Raza et al., 2018). In a similar vein, the State Bank of Pakistan defines SMEs as "a business entity, ideally not being a public limited company, and having employees not more than 250 in the case of a manufacturing concern and 50 in the case of a trade or services concern, and also fulfilling one of the following criteria: (i) total assets at cost excluding land and buildings up to PKR 50 million in the trade or service concern; (ii) total assets at cost excluding land and buildings up to PKR 100 million in the manufacturing concern; (iii) net sales not exceeding PKR 400 million as per the latest financial statements in any case." This

study utilises SMEDA's definition of SMEs, which includes enterprises with up to 250 employees. Table 2.1 below presents the specific definitions of SMEs as provided by various institutions in Pakistan.

Table 2. 1 SMEs Definitions by Various Authorise in Pakistan.

<i>Institution in Pakistan</i>	<i>Criteria</i>	
<i>Punjab Small Industries Corporation</i>	Fixed Assets (excluding land and building)	Up to PKR 20 million
<i>Federal Bureau of Statistics</i>	Number of Employees	Less than 10
<i>State Bank of Pakistan (SBP)</i>	Number of Employees • Manufacturing • Trading/Service	
	Total Assets (excluding land and building) • Manufacturing • Trading/Service	Up to PKR 100 million Up to PKR 50 million
	Annual Turnover	Up to PKR 400 million
<i>Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority (SMEDA)</i>	Annual Turnover	Up to PKR 250 million
	Total Assets	Up to PKR 25 million
	Number of Employees	Up to 250

Source: Adapted from (Raza et al., 2018)

2.5 Female Entrepreneurship and Its Origins

Over the past 30 years, there has been a significant growth in scholarly interest in women's entrepreneurship, with studies on the topic spanning numerous disciplines, methodologies, and countries. While women have owned businesses for decades, published academic research only dates back to the late 1970s and early 1980s (Santos et al., 2018). Jennings and Brush (2013) underline three significant milestones in the research field of women's entrepreneurship. In 1997, the Entrepreneurship and Regional Development Journal released the first special issue exclusively focused on women's entrepreneurship. Second, in 1998 and 2003, the inaugural policy- and academic-focused conferences dedicated to the field were held, organised by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development and Diana International. Nonetheless, only in 2009 did the specialised journal, the International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship, launch. The historical inattention to female entrepreneurship, as evidenced by the aforementioned milestones, has been rectified in recent years with the rapid growth of the field, leading some (Birkner et al., 2018) to describe female entrepreneurship research as "to be in its teens."

As per Jennings and Brush (2013), the exploration of women's entrepreneurship has its origins in two distinct, occasionally intersecting realms of research: the gender and occupation literature and the feminist theories. The literature on gender and occupations scrutinises the societal role of women and

acknowledges their occupational segregation (Civera and Meoli, 2023). These studies commonly reveal labour markets that are segregated by gender, where men and women occupy different occupations. When compared to men, women typically find themselves in low-level roles that are associated with lower salaries, skills, and status for women (Carranza et al., 2018). Moreover, the literature on gender and occupations contributes to women's entrepreneurship research, indicating that individuals opt for self-employment as a push factor in response to limited opportunities available in the labour market. For instance, “glass ceiling” career difficulties and discrimination in the labour market may lead women to opt for self-employment as a career (Gawel and Mroczek-Dabrowska, 2022). In certain nations, it is perceived that embarking on self-employment is comparatively simpler than overcoming obstacles to obtaining formal employment. Another observation is that women may choose self-employment due to the flexibility it provides in balancing work and family obligations, which may not be feasible in traditional employment (McGowan et al., 2012).

Feminist theories encompass two distinct yet mutually sharing perspectives for women’s empowerment, namely liberal feminism and social feminism (Bhatt and Garikipati, 2019). According to liberal feminist theory, men and women are fundamentally equal beings. Nevertheless, Ahl (2006) argues that women, in comparison to men, are disadvantaged in terms of resources such as education and work experience owing to explicit discrimination or structural barriers. Advocates of this theory contend that although equal rights should not be withheld based on one's biological sex, the gendered structuring of society places women at a disadvantage (Jennings and Brush, 2013). Studies consistent with this line of thought include those that have examined the possibility that men have more relevant education and experience compared to women and the discrimination of women by lenders.

Unlike liberal feminist theory, social feminist theory holds that males and females differ inherently due to differences arising from early and ongoing socialisation. Nevertheless, these differences do not suggest the inferiority of women to men, as women may cultivate distinct yet equally effective traits (Witbooi and Ukpere, 2011). Research from a social feminist perspective highlights entrepreneurship studies aligning with this view, which often utilise socialised traits and values as the foundation for comparing men and women. Therefore, it can be said that these disparities, when present, may have minimal influence on business performance (Watson, 2020; Marlow and McAdam, 2013). Hence, the core aim of feminist scholarship has been to remove legal and institutional barriers that hinder women from equal participation with men in society. Although there has been a lot of improvement, historical regulations that limited women's economic participation paved the way for the establishment of institutional and societal norms that limit their ability to be entrepreneurs (Jaim, 2021b), yet there is a long way to go as firms owned by women are often smaller, less diverse, and less extensive than those owned by men. This disparity is based on gender variations in education, work experience, networks, and access to financial resources. By illuminating the more silent feminine personal end of entrepreneurship, the aforementioned viewpoints shed light on what makes women entrepreneurs

unique. Hence, women's entrepreneurship needs to be analysed and understood in its country-specific and social context.

2.6 Motivational Reasons to Pursue Entrepreneurship

Women's motivations for pursuing self-employment have been extensively discussed in Western literature, but less in non-Western literature. Female entrepreneurs are not a homogenous group; they may possess various skills and competencies, have different social backgrounds, and constitute a diverse group (Danho et al., 2021), and are thus influenced by a wide range of factors when embarking on a venture. Female entrepreneurs pursue entrepreneurship for a variety of reasons, including a desire for independence (McGowan et al., 2012), dissatisfaction with corporate jobs or the glass ceiling that obstructs their career progress (Ismail et al., 2012), family factors (Kirkwood and Walton, 2010), unfair treatment at work (Saddique, 2018), economic/monetary reasons (Al-Dajani and Marlow, 2010), and work/life balance (Rehman and Roomi, 2012).

Socio-economic milieus play a crucial role in low-income nations in understanding why women become entrepreneurs. To illustrate, Afza and Rashid (2009) assert that women owned firms can significantly impact economic development in Pakistan, but due to the patriarchal forces that expect women's dependency and subordination, they face far greater obstacles in starting and managing their own firms since they are seen in the roles of homemakers and childminders (Roomi et al., 2018). This diversification of female roles continues to be a challenge in many emerging and transforming nations. Researchers like Markovic (2007) assert that policies such as maternity leave, childcare benefits, shorter work weeks, and health care are needed at work but aren't provided. It follows that organisations do not pay enough attention to the working conditions or benefits that women in developing countries need. Similarly, women are paid less than men when securing similar jobs with the same level of education (Insights, 2016). Among other factors, the abovementioned elements are the ones that lead women to utilise their basic skills and come up with home-based businesses in order to overcome the economic burden. Therefore, women opt for entrepreneurial careers as they create better incentives, including financial returns, and maintain a balance between work and life by thinking of different enterprising activities that suit their family needs.

Similarly, Brush et al. (2009) argue that "motherhood" has a larger impact on women than on men when pursuing a career. The authors are of the view that opportunity recognition is linked to the environment in which entrepreneurship takes place. Therefore, opportunity identification allows women to pursue their careers in different sectors. Thus, the macro environment shapes and creates opportunities, and women think up different ways to make their businesses grow.

Overall, for embarking on a venture, the motivation factors differ across nations. For instance, Chu et al. (2007) found that in emerging economies like Kenya and Ghana, financial motivation and self-employment outweighed personal fulfilment. Likewise, Jamali's (2009) study on female entrepreneurs

in Lebanon found that they are motivated by factors such as financial independence, creativity, independence, challenge, and autonomy. Benzing and Chu (2005) have illustrated that in India, entrepreneurs who belong to developed regions have the 'desire to be their own boss' (autonomy and independence) as a vigorous motivation element. In addition, Shabbir and Gregorio (1996) have made substantial contributions to research, particularly in Pakistan. They categorise females into three groups by adopting a symbolic "interactionist approach." The first group includes those females who want to prove that they are productive members of society. These satisfaction seekers have no previous work experience and are mostly housewives with the intention of starting their own business. The second group includes women who are security seekers. In this group, women opt to be entrepreneurs because they want to improve or maintain their economic and social status. Lastly comes the freedom seeker category, where women demand freedom to choose the type of work and surroundings, the flexibility of working, and the individuals they want to work with. Most recently, Roomi et al. (2018) identified role models, glass ceilings, family and flexibility, being their own boss, economic necessity, and the desire to do something as the top motivators for female entrepreneurs in Pakistan to start a business.

Numerous researchers (e.g., Ryan et al., 2011; Tlaiss, 2013) have identified pull and push factors as prevalent motivations for starting a business among women, where research reveals that the pull factor of an entrepreneurial idea is the most motivational reason for the majority of women embarking on a new venture. For instance, Hughes (2006) found that the desire to have flexibility in work-life balance and financial gains are the basic motivations for starting a business. Likewise, Rotondo et al. (2003) identified that elements like geographic location, socio-economic status, prior experience of a job, and educational attainments may vary among women depending upon the pull and push factors' intensity. However, Jamali (2009) noted that in pursuing entrepreneurship, especially in low-income countries, both push and pull factors are significant. The "push" element that leads women to become entrepreneurs in order to survive due to job loss (retrenchment) or unemployment falls under the category of "necessity" entrepreneurs. Recognising a business opportunity, having a role model or mentor, or the availability of government assistance that encourages women to pursue entrepreneurship as a career option fall under the category of "opportunity" entrepreneurs and are referred to as "pull" factors (Irene, 2016).

According to Ghosh and Cheruvalath (2007), women owned enterprises in developing nations make up only one-fifth of "opportunity entrepreneurs," and this appears to be true in the case of female entrepreneurship in Pakistan, where 89% of female-owned businesses are necessity entrepreneurs. (World Bank, 2017). Although opportunity-driven women entrepreneurs represent a small proportion, they are responsible for producing the majority of new jobs. Opportunity-driven entrepreneurs make themselves visible, and for this reason, they are able to grow and sustain. Commitment to "time and money" in business is another factor that drives opportunity-driven entrepreneurs to business success, which enables them to understand the business environment.

Another aspect that needs to be considered is that in nations with a high birth rate and low income, women-led enterprises thrive; thus, economic aspects cannot be disregarded. Due to little or no employment availability, entrepreneurship is a lifeline for women in such nations. It allows them to escape from the institutional and cultural restraints and still provide for their families. Females in nations like Pakistan, where the per capita income is low, have little or no choice to start a business; thereby, female entrepreneurs appear to have "necessity" aspirations. Unlike in developing nations, job stability and welfare payments are more stabilised in wealthier countries, which enables entrepreneurs to have "opportunity" aspirations with fewer "necessity" entrepreneurs (Alam et al., 2021). Yet, while women operating their businesses tend to be "necessity entrepreneurs" in Pakistan, their motivation does not seem to affect their business performance. The next section discusses female entrepreneurs in emerging nations.

2.7 Women Owned Enterprise in Emerging Economies

In Asian developing nations, the advent of female self-employment has immense potential for transfiguring society and emancipating women. However, the potential for economic progress remains significantly untapped in many South Asian nations, including Pakistan, where the degree of industrialisation is low and income per capita is determined by the degree of economic progress. In South Asian nations, it has been demonstrated that countries like Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Nepal, the Maldives, India, and Bhutan comprise less than 10% of women entrepreneurs (Tambunan, 2009). About 2.4% of a total of 3.2 million enterprises in Pakistan represent women owned businesses (Syed, 2012), and most recently, only 10% of early-stage entrepreneurial activity in the female population has increased in the last 20 years in Pakistan (Kazmi, 2018).

Nevertheless, gender equity is often cited as a common yardstick to measure the level of women's entrepreneurship, which is often lower in low-income countries compared to wealthier nations. While low-income countries vary in terms of economic development depending on various elements, including political, cultural, and social factors combined with the level of income per capita, it would be unrealistic to measure the level of women's entrepreneurial progress with gender equity. The fact that in many nations, especially low-income countries, a lack of accurate gender-discriminate social indicators means it is not easy to measure the level of women's entrepreneurship as a gender equity measure consists of many dimensions (Tariq, 2016).

In recent decades, East Asia has emerged as the most successful region in terms of economic advancement (Malcolm, 2014). Within this region, women's labour force participation is notably high, characterised by a minimal gender gap and substantial employment opportunities for both males and females. However, certain nations, such as Indonesia, lack sufficient literature on female-owned enterprises and national data (Tambunan, 2009). For example, the prevalence of female-owned enterprises in Indonesia has seen a rapid increase, propelled by the substantial growth in per capita

income during the New Order era (1966 -1998). Despite the fact that the proportion of self-employed females is lower than their male counterparts, the surge in female entrepreneurship can be attributed to factors like increased awareness and educational levels among women (Tambunan, 2009).

Although the entrepreneurial process in a developing country is the same for both genders, in practice, women face multiple problems of varying magnitudes and dimensions that prevent them from reaching their full potential as entrepreneurs. By definition, entrepreneurship means control of one's actions and life, and it is this autonomy that women in that society have been denied. Tambunan (2009) acknowledges that the situation in South Asia is worse than in other parts of Asia. The complex interplay of numerous elements (such as education, religion, psychological well-being, and socioeconomic status) has contributed to the low status of women in South Asian societies (Tariq, 2016). In addition, female-owned enterprises in South Asia, including Bangladesh, India, Nepal, and Pakistan, are unrecorded due to their informal status (Suleymenova and Syssoyeva-Masson, 2017). Such businesses are deprived of market opportunities and inadequate social security regulations and are vulnerable (i.e., low-paid jobs, particularly for women). Due to this informality, women have fewer equal opportunities, basic human rights, and economic independence than men, which puts female-owned businesses far behind (Jayachandran, 2015).

Secondly, in many rural areas of developing Asian nations, women's orthodox belief that only they should have the advantage of higher education still predominates. According to this idea, women are no longer valuable in society after marriage because they remain with their husbands and families for the rest of their lives (Tambunan, 2009). Nevertheless, despite the fact that this thinking is still prevalent in rural communities, it depends on the family's economic and educational status (Jayachandran, 2015). For instance, when parents or husbands are well educated or the family is better off economically, orthodox beliefs about women's education are expected to have less of an impact.

Thirdly, women can only operate their businesses to an extent because of prevailing traditional, religious, legal, cultural, and customary constraints. Especially in remote tribal areas of Pakistan, where long-held orthodox beliefs, tribal traditions, and social and cultural practices in the name of religious teaching prevent women from working outside the home (Roomi et al., 2018). In such a society, it is obligatory for women to adhere to their traditional gender roles as housewives, carers of the elderly, and child rearing and are prohibited from becoming entrepreneurs, doing jobs that involve contact with men, or leaving the house alone. Such an attitude or behaviour in society makes women less willing to engage in economic activities than men. Even if these women own a small firm, crucial business decisions are outsourced to other family members or their spouse, giving less autonomy to the female entrepreneur, resulting in diminished firm performance (World Bank, 2017). Such behaviour diminishes the nurturing of entrepreneurial talent among women and prevents them from engaging in entrepreneurial activities.

Fourthly, gender-biased practices are common in many South Asian nations, including Pakistan, where men are viewed as the family head and, consequently, the inheritor of family assets, such as houses, land, or enterprises (Tariq, 2016). Lack of access to assets or unequal inheritance practices in South Asia puts women in a position where they are unable to secure formal credit due to collateral requirements (Wellalage and Locke, 2017). In addition, Teoh and Chong (2007) found that in emerging economies, despite the existence of numerous industry associations and diverse women's groups, female entrepreneurs still face a lack of peer support networks compared to their male counterparts. This is merely because women are preoccupied with family, business, and household jobs and might be unable to join such associations.

It is a fact that SMEs account for the vast majority of new jobs in Asian developing economies and employ well over 90% of the labour force. Female entrepreneurs prevail in low-income and traditional activities, i.e., they are concentrated in a few industries. They choose private companies because of their low expertise, little capital, and ease of entry and departure (Roomi, 2011; Tariq, 2016). This means that women in South Asia embark on business due to push factors such as unemployment, a need for sufficient income to meet daily family expenditure, poverty, and safety measures, for example, at the time of emergency or an anticipated emergency if the husband is unemployed or laid off (Tambunan, 2009).

2.8 Theories of Entrepreneurship

When elucidating the field of entrepreneurship, scholars have proposed numerous sub-fields within various disciplines, stemming from management, sociology, psychology, anthropology, or economics (Carlsson et al., 2013). A brief review of different theories of entrepreneurship and factors related to a firm's performance that previous scholars have developed, together with the critiques and reasons for not using these theories, is illustrated in this section.

2.8.1 Economic Entrepreneurship Theories

Economic research on entrepreneurship is rooted in classical, neo-classical, and Austrian approaches. Schumpeter (1934), an economist, was the first to talk about the role of an entrepreneur. He emphasised the entrepreneur as a force of creative destruction or an innovative pathbreaker, leading to the emergence of a new process that signifies the transformation of the market economy. In the context of the economy, Schumpeter (1934) focused extensively on human actions intertwined with knowledge. His work served as a catalyst for economic growth. Nevertheless, Schumpeter's work was intellectually motivated by a non-classical framework that failed to explain the entrepreneurship process. The neo-classical approach ignored the role of entrepreneurial activity for the economy and viewed firms as "black box" production functions. Moreover, these approaches argue for perfect competition, with everyone having all the information they need for perfect decision making (Carlsson et al., 2013). Although these approaches provide an overall picture of entrepreneurs, it is not enough to provide a

comprehensive picture to the reader, and it is clear that the assumption of the neoclassical theory of entrepreneurship is unrealistic and implies a perfect world (Khuraibet, 2015).

2.8.2 Psychological Entrepreneurship Theories

The role of personal characteristics is emphasised when defining entrepreneurship through the psychological theories of entrepreneurship. McClelland (1961) developed psychological theories, and much of the discussion has focused on the personal element of motivation to understand business through individual characteristics, for instance a need for achievement, locus of control, risk-taking propensity, and a deep need for power. However, studying entrepreneurship as related to personality traits remains controversial (Gartner, 1985; Chell et al., 2008). This is due to the fact that personality traits appear to be different or fail to reliably differentiate between the personality traits of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs (e.g., managers) and only explain a small portion of the variance in entrepreneurial success.

2.8.3 Sociological Entrepreneurship Theory

As with other entrepreneurship theories, sociological theories differ in terms of their focus on traditional society because they analyse entrepreneurial activities (Reynold, 1992). Reynold highlights that environmental conditions have an important influence on the survival and success of businesses. Some of the environmental factors, such as government legislation, the political system, competition, employees, and the customer base, may have an impact on the survival of start-up firms (Markovi, 2007). Similarly, for some individuals who become entrepreneurs, the decisive factor that motivates them to start a business lies in their sociological background. For example, entrepreneurs from marginalised or minority groups who go on to serve as an example for generations to come may often go against all the odds to break through their disadvantageous background (Randa, 2020, p. 457).

Nevertheless, several sociological factors in the modern entrepreneurial setting have transformed. For example, in every business sector, digitalisation is picking up pace rapidly, and to drive bigger change in society, various governments are facilitating entrepreneurs by bringing about change in their aspirations and attitudes. Consequently, to encompass these factors, there is a need to develop newer sociological theories of entrepreneurship (Chetty, 2020).

2.8.4 Anthropological Entrepreneurship Theory

Anthropologists consider social processes and entrepreneurship to be cultural processes. The origin, customs, development, and beliefs of a community are the perspective of anthropological entrepreneurship theory (Simeh, 2011). Here the emphasis is on the culture in the community (Randa, 2020, p. 459). This theory centres on the concept of social and cultural context, suggesting that in the survival, growth, and creation of a successful business, social and cultural context play a major role. Further, certain cultural practices bring about entrepreneurial attitudes such as innovation, thus creating new businesses. For instance, entrepreneurial attitudes and behaviours are often forged by ethnicity and

also by the cultural environment, i.e., culture reflects political, social, ethnic, economic, and ecological complexities in individuals (Mitchell et al., 2000).

After reviewing and discussing various theories of entrepreneurship, the following section discusses factors influencing SMEs in general.

2.9 Factors Impacting SMEs Performance

Various theoretical perspectives contribute to the investigation of entrepreneurial firms' performance. Literature at the SME level (e.g., Caca, 2010; Simpson et al., 2012) illustrates that factors influencing firms fall into three broad categories affecting business performance: firm characteristics and resources (resource-based view and organisational behaviour), external business environment (factors linked to the external environment), and individual entrepreneurs or individual-related factors (psychology, traits, and entrepreneurship theory). Multiple theoretical perspectives inform the research on the performance of entrepreneurial firms. Despite the absence of a unified SME success theory, these elements are widely acknowledged as determinants of business performance (Lampadarios et al., 2017) and are further discussed in the subsequent sections.

2.9.1 Firm Characteristics and Resources (Firm-Related Factors)

A variety of variables, including the firm's characteristics and resources, impact firm performance. In the realm of entrepreneurship literature, the most extensively examined firm attributes include firm size and age, often treated as control variables in research models. According to Krasniqi and Mustafa (2016), firm growth is related to firm size and age. Past research has generally reported finding a negative association between firm age and performance (Davidsson et al., 2010, p. 34). Accordingly, the argument is that firms' growth rates decline as they get older. However, some scholars, such as Alegre and Chiva (2013), have reported inconclusive results on this matter.

- ***Firm Size***

A firm necessitates diverse resources, including personnel, facilities, and money, and firm size influences the accumulation of these resources. Consequently, empirical evidence suggests that firm performance is also affected (Baum et al., 2001; Krasniqi and Mustafa, 2016). Compared to small firms, large organisations have a clear advantage regarding access to knowledge, experience, economies of scale, and key resources (Raju et al., 2011). Therefore, one might expect them to perform better; however, when considering growth dimensions of performance, this is not always the case. For instance, Hamilton (2012) and Blackburn et al. (2013) found a negative relationship between business growth and size, while Alegre and Chiva (2013) note that firm performance is not affected by firm size. The negative link between firm size and growth could be attributed to the fact that founders of small firms, compared to larger organisations, are closer to the market, making them more flexible and responsive to business opportunities (Steffens et al., 2009). Hence, these associations have yielded mixed results.

- ***Firm Resources***

In small firms, another critical determinant of performance is the firm's resources. Galbreath and Galvin (2008) illustrate this notion by asserting that firms compete, and the basis upon which they compete is firm resources. That study found that firm resources act as an important determinant in understanding the performance of firms in the service sector rather than manufacturing firms. Barney (1991) describes firm resources as anything that is controlled and improves the effectiveness and efficiency of the firm, like firm attributes, organisational processes, knowledge, information, capabilities, all assets, etc. In line with Barney's (1991) definition, resources can further be classified into three types: first, human capital (e.g., training and experience); second, physical capital resources (e.g., geographical location, equipment, and technology); and third, resources from firm capital (e.g., planning, external, and internal relationships). Likewise, business resources defined by Javalgi and Todd (2011, p. 1005) are resources containing "all non-human and human, along with intangible and tangible assets that are possessed by the firm and permit a firm to generate and apply strategies that add "value." It follows that for business to be successful, resources are fundamental, while few (e.g., Edelman et al., 2005; Brush and Chaganti, 1999) assert that they are essential for the performance of a firm.

- ***Financial Resources***

Financial resources have been highlighted as one of the crucial indicators of firm performance within an SME context. Inadequate financial resources are often identified as the leading cause of new business failure. At times of managerial mistakes or unfavourable market conditions like slow start-ups or market downturns, the availability of financial resources not only serves as a shield but also aids in the development of products, marketing, or services (Heirman and Clarysse, 2006, p. 201), which can eventually enhance the performance of a firm (Coleman, 2016; Chandler and Hanks, 1998). Capital subsidies may impact performance in both direct and indirect ways. Wide-ranging planning and better training are examples of indirect effects, while direct effects include elements like pursuing ambiguous strategies, the ability to buy time, and fulfilling the financial requirements generated by growth (Tzelepis and Skuras, 2006; Cooper et al., 1994). In a similar vein, Bradley et al. (2011) assert that the availability of capital subsidies can serve as a safeguard against shocks that may endanger vulnerable and small ventures. It follows that nascent firms with adequate financial capital have a greater chance of being profitable, surviving, and expanding as resources become available to buffer the business against adverse conditions. However, firm ability can be constrained in terms of executing promising ideas due to the absence of such resources, thereby decreasing their profitability (Parker and Praag, 2006).

2.9.2 External Environment (Environmental Factor)

Firms do not operate in isolation; they have to respond and adapt according to the external business environment. The entrepreneur, the firm, and the key success indicators of firms are all profoundly

impacted by the external business environment (Simpson et al., 2012). There is a significant relationship between environmental factors and firm performance, including socio-political factors such as support and assistance from the government (Sheng et al., 2011), business location (Waugh, 2019), resource availability such as capital credit (Jaim, 2021b), adequate business support from institutions (Dhaliwal, 2007), a good attitude from sub-culture for entrepreneurs (Roomi and Harrison, 2010), and economic variables such as per capita income (Verheul et al., 2006). However, the impact of environmental factors varies for different firms, depending on the sector they operate in. In small business research, commonly cited industry sector factors include the influence of customers and suppliers, market attractiveness (level of competition intensity), availability of opportunities, technological sophistication, and market demand.

2.9.3 The Individual Entrepreneur (Individual-Related Factor)

Earlier studies have frequently highlighted and linked entrepreneurial behavioural characteristics, demographic and psychological traits, as well as managerial skills, to the performance of SMEs (Man et al., 2002). Psychological theories, pioneered by McClelland (1961), have been central to this discourse, with a significant focus on the personal motivation aspect of comprehending business through individual characteristics such as locus of control, need for achievement, risk-taking propensity, and a profound desire for power. However, the examination of entrepreneurship in relation to personality traits remains a topic of controversy (Gartner, 1985; Chell et al., 2008, p. 198). Hisrich et al. (2007), for example, assert that personality traits appear to be different or fail to reliably differentiate between the personality traits of entrepreneurs and non-entrepreneurs (such as managers) and relate only limited variance to entrepreneurial success. Another criticism made by Chell et al. (2008) is the non-availability of any criteria or measure to decide if an individual has a low or high acceptance of risk, a need to achieve, or a locus of control risk. She pointed out that the trait-based perspective is based on the assumption that a person's traits are always expressed in the same way, which in reality is not possible.

Moreover, when attempting to measure an entrepreneur's personality traits, several methodological problems arise. These problems include the following: subjective judgement is needed as the characteristics are not stable; cultural and environmental effects are overlooked; the training, education, and learning role is ignored; and issues of social class, race, age, and gender may be neglected. In other words, an individual trait neglects the importance of situational factors, as psychological theories focus on "*who the entrepreneur is*" rather than "*what an entrepreneur does.*" Therefore, without considering the external environmental factors, research solely on psychological perspectives is bound to fail, especially when information is incomplete (Burns, 2013, p. 45). In addition, Audretsch and Hinger (2014, p. 27) concluded that research on personality traits has come to an empirical dead end. The preceding section discussed issues affecting the performance of small businesses in general. The

following will provide a summary of past research on the factors that affect the performance of women owned businesses.

2.10 Factors Impacting Female Entrepreneurship Performance

Due to the distinct nature of female owned SMEs compared to their male counterparts, there is a significant interest in examining the factors influencing their performance. For instance, Hazudin et al. (2015) claim that male and female entrepreneurs differ in key business success factors, motivations for starting a business, and the underlying obstacles they face. Likewise, Isa et al. (2016) make a similar point, arguing that differing socialisation processes lead to distinct perceptions of opportunities and, consequently, different entrepreneurial behaviours in men and women. Additionally, in the literature, a prominent argument is that female entrepreneurs, when compared to males, have smaller firms (Robichaud et al., 2015; Fuller-Love, 2008, p. 300), tend to grow less quickly (Cliff, 1998; Coleman, 2016, p. 379), generate less revenue (Ligaya, 2018; Cassar, 2006), and are less profitable (Fairlie and Robb, 2009; Barbara and Candida, 2002). The primary explanation for underperformance and lower participation in female enterprises is the "female underperformance hypothesis" (Watson, 2020). This hypothesis is, however, challenged by a growing number of studies (Marlow and McAdam, 2013; Zolin et al., 2013), stating that differences in characteristics exist when considering male and female firms. Consequently, female owned firms are equally successful as male-owned firms when adequate performance measures and appropriate control variables are included in performance investigations.

Interestingly, empirical studies have often failed to distinguish firm ownership by gender, instead treating entrepreneurs in a general sense when exploring the connections between performance and capabilities (Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014). Previous research has identified several categories of factors influencing the performance and success of female owned firms. These categories encompass aspects such as firm characteristics, institutional factors, personal factors, gender-related factors, cultural factors, social factors, and business competencies and skills. The following section delves into the literature related to these factors.

2.10.1 Social Structures Factors

One of the most significant factors affecting female entrepreneurship is social structure. To illustrate, women in many societies are portrayed as child carers, remain in the private sphere of the household, and are seen in their traditional family role, while in some societies, family duties tend to be the first and foremost responsibilities (Roomi et al., 2018; Jamali, 2009). As a result, less time is available to invest in firms, and this often results in small and underperforming businesses (Roomi et al., 2009). Women may be restricted to working in specific fields, and their motives and career aspirations may be shaped, in part, by the underrepresentation of women in high management positions, which persists in many nations (WGEA, 2019). Moreover, the research evidence suggests that women's underperformance in business is also attributed to the fact that they operate in traditional sectors (which

require a low level of investment) and are characterised by having few resources and opportunities with a high level of competition (Marlow and McAdam, 2013; Roomi, 2011). The female owned firms' performance is also influenced by the favourability of the entrepreneurship sub-culture. For instance, the support mechanism at home, the level of credibility attributed to female entrepreneurship, and societal role expectations all play a part in the well-being of such a firm (Vossenbergh, 2013). In addition, seeking advice, maintaining confidentiality, autonomy in business decisions, and relationships with friends and family are often considered vital sources of information, which can have a positive impact on business (Neneh, 2017).

2.10.2 Institutional Factors

The operation, performance, and success of firms owned by women are also impacted by the institutional environment of the nation. Entrepreneurial choices are not made in a vacuum but rather are founded on a meticulous analysis of the available support structures and institutional context (Chowdhury et al., 2019). For instance, Sobel (2008) identified that the type and quality of entrepreneurial outcomes depend primarily on institutions. There is an ample amount of research suggesting that women owned firms' access to capital is a commonly cited problem and remains challenging for them (Jaim, 2021b). The literature has highlighted some barriers faced by female-owned firms in accessing formal credit, including difficulty in filling out the loan application form (Gobbi et al., 2005), inability to provide collateral (Jaim, 2021b), lack of personal guarantees (Shoma, 2019), lack of financial literacy (Xu and Zia, 2012), and in some countries, married women by law require permission of their husband to access a loan (Safavian, 2012). Unfortunately, inadequate financial resources can be a substantial barrier to a business's success (Mahmood, 2011). Another institutional factor that has been cited in research on female entrepreneurship is the "*lack of government support*" in developing countries (Tambunan, 2009). Support from the government can be related to business regulations, employment law, licencing procedures, taxation policies, support provided by government agencies in terms of access to capital, and the training of employers (Benzing et al., 2009).

2.10.3 Gender Related Factors

Gender related factors also have an impact on the performance of women owned firms. "*Risk-taking propensity*" is one of the essential elements that are deemed to influence entrepreneurship, and this varies with gender. Some studies propose that female entrepreneurs are generally more risk-averse compared to their male counterparts (Coleman, 2016, p. 384; Lim and Envick, 2013), thus more reluctant to take on business debt and less inclined to engage in fast-paced business growth (Bird and Brush, 2002). Therefore, the low growth rate in female owned firms is attributed to the low tolerance for risk taken by female business owners.

"*Network affiliation*" is another gender related factor in women owned firms that is linked to performance. The presence or absence of networks influences firm performance, and these intricate

social relationships are deeply embedded in entrepreneurship (Ummah et al., 2019). Business networking is considered to be a key source of resources (West and Noel, 2009) that allow business owners to exploit opportunities like building legitimacy (Olamide and Ogbechie, 2021) and organising resources for their business. The prevalent reasoning is that entrepreneurs who are better connected accrue more resources. This is shown to improve entrepreneurial effectiveness without capital investment (Slotte-Kock and Coviello, 2010).

However, researchers studying networks say that males and females approach social networking differently (Yen et al., 2020). For instance, female business owners, compared to male entrepreneurs, are less likely to know individuals who have started their own firm (Terjese and Ratten, 2007, p. 49). Likewise, owing to family responsibilities, female firm owners tend to have less time for maintaining and developing contracts (Diaz-Garcia and Brush, 2012) and usually prioritise personal networks (e.g., friends and family) over professional networks (Ekanem, 2015).

2.10.4 Personal Factors

Another set of factors examined in the literature in connection to the performance of female business owners is personal factors affecting the entrepreneur. For instance, Brush and Hisrich (1991) investigated the antecedent influence on the growth and survival of female-owned businesses by examining the impact of four groups of variables: business skills, work experience, education, and personal qualities (such as motivation and firm founder age). This study found that financial skills (cash management and financial controls), prior entrepreneurial experience, business skills (e.g., strength in idea generation), and the ability to interact with people all contribute to the survival of a business. Similarly, Alene (2020) analysed twenty-three studies and found that educational level, previous entrepreneurial experience, age, and marital status were the most frequently used variables as performance predictors. In a similar vein, Lerner and Almor (2002) identified certain aspects of women business owners' skills, for example, managerial, financial, and marketing, as crucial elements in understanding venture performance.

2.10.5 Firm Characteristics Factors

The characteristic of female entrepreneurship is the final category of factors investigated in relation to performance. In this context, "*the size*" and "*the age*" of the business, as well as the type of industry in which the firm operates, have been linked with its performance. For instance, Watson (2020) and Ruiz-Arroyo et al. (2012) identified that female firms are concentrated in the conventional female gender-dominated sectors, such as services, sales, and retail, due to the minimal capital investment requirements. These companies typically experience intense competition, are smaller in size, and hence have limited profit and growth potential. Therefore, compared to those of their male counterparts, the majority of female entrepreneurs' firms tend to be smaller in size (OECD, 2017b). Additionally, Watson

(2003) argues that the underperformance in women's entrepreneurship might be due to the age of the business and suggests that female owned firms might be younger than male owned businesses.

The detailed examination of each factor is grounded in a comprehensive review of the literature on female entrepreneurship and the determinants of firm performance. From the above review, it is evident that researchers have employed different factors when studying female entrepreneurship. Recognising these factors that impact performance was vital for identifying theories and constructing an appropriate conceptual framework. This is particularly important because, in the context of developing countries, the literature has faced criticism for its limited understanding of female-owned businesses (Jamali, 2009; Welter, 2011). Similarly, despite extensive studies on female entrepreneurship in western nations, the factors influencing the performance of female entrepreneurship in developing nations remain theoretically underdeveloped. The next section provides a review of various models utilized in studying the performance of female entrepreneurs.

2.11 Evaluation of the Existing Firm Performance Model

In the SME context, Man et al. (2002) regard business performance as the definitive criterion for measuring success or failure. Consequently, this section aims to examine six models pertaining to women's entrepreneurial performance. The objective is to foster a comprehensive understanding of the factors underlying firm performance models in various research studies. According to Jabareen (2009), a conceptual framework is a network of interconnected concepts that collectively offer a thorough comprehension of a phenomena or phenomenon. Miles et al. (2014) assert that a conceptual framework, whether depicted graphically or narratively, clarifies the essential elements for examination, encompassing key factors, variables, or constructs and the presumed interconnections among them. These frameworks may exhibit varying degrees of complexity, ranging from simplicity to elaboration, and can be either commonsensical or theory-driven, as well as descriptive or causal. In contrast, a model represents a set of components within a process, system, or subject area, typically developed for the purpose of understanding, analysing, improving, and/or replacing the process. A model must explicitly specify the structure and formal relationships among components. Therefore, a model aids in comprehending a process or behaviour, predicting outcomes, or analysing problems (Kim et al., 2008). This study adheres to the above guidelines in developing a suitable conceptual framework.

2.11.1 Human Capital Model

The Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016) model examines human capital dimensions influencing the performance of female ventures. It encompasses factors such as prior employment experience, business training, field of education, and higher educational qualifications, as depicted in Figure 2.1. The authors believe that the performance of female entrepreneurs relies heavily on innate ability. Therefore, the differences in human capital could be attributable to factors such as education level, quality of education, innate ability, experience, and training. The literature (e.g., Man et al., 2002) also indicates

that the demographic characteristics of a business owner play a key role in the ability to stay competitive and lead a firm to success.

More importantly, evidence suggests that higher-educated entrepreneurs tend to make better decisions about how to run a business, thereby minimising the risk (Alene, 2020), emphasising the importance of this dimension. The other two dimensions, i.e., business training and prior business experience, also prove crucial. For instance, a lack of training may prevent females from exploring their personal entrepreneurial competence, whereas prior work experience equips the owners to discover and seize opportunities, analyse market trends, and make smart choices concerning client demands. Consequently, education level, business training, and prior work experience are deemed vital factors in explaining firm performance and will be used in the present study.

The “area of education” construct will not be adopted in the present study as the investigator considers level of education and area of education to be interchangeable terms. While the model shows some insight into human capital components, it is not without criticism as it is entirely based on the human capital components and neglects other factors crucial to women business owners' performance.

Figure 2. 1 Human Capital Model

Source: Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016)

2.11.2 Model of SME Competitiveness

In their model, Man et al. (2002) incorporated the concept of "competitiveness" and fused it with an entrepreneur's "competencies" to explore the link between entrepreneurial characteristics and SME performance, aiming to establish a theoretical rationale. The model distinctly delineates competitiveness into three components: potential, process, and performance. It further outlines four qualifying features for competitiveness: relativity, controllability, long-term orientation, and dynamism. Building upon these principles, Man et al. (2002) developed a model comprising four constructs: competitive scope, organisational capabilities, entrepreneurial competencies, and firm performance, as depicted in Figure 2.2.

Competitive scope constructs encompass external environmental factors, while organisational capabilities constructs represent internal firm factors, jointly constituting the potential dimension of

competitiveness. The model, illustrated in Figure 3.2, clearly illustrates that entrepreneurial competencies not only impact firm performance but also influence internal and external potential dimensions. This suggests that entrepreneurs, by interpreting environmental conditions, setting goals, and taking action, accelerate venture performance. They also create organisational capabilities by leveraging all internal potential venture resources. According to Man et al. (2002), entrepreneurial competencies differ from quantifiable variables like educational background, experience, and age. Instead, they are higher-level characteristics such as knowledge, skills, and personality traits essential for successful job performance. The authors believe that behaviour is closer to performance than other entrepreneurial characteristics like personality traits, motivation, or intentions. Consequently, Man et al. (2002) identified six domains of entrepreneurial competencies, namely strategic, conceptual, commitment, relationship, opportunity, and organising, which are grounded in the process or behavioural perspective.

The competitive scope construct is concerned with a firm's long-term performance and is perceived as a multidimensional concept in the model. Similarly, organisational capabilities are related to the firm's internal capabilities. Sanchez (2012) tested this model and revealed that entrepreneurial competencies impact firm performance directly and indirectly. Although Man et al. (2002) viewed competitive scope and organisational capabilities as being essential, these constructs may be less applicable in small businesses. This is because competitiveness is a notion associated with large corporations' long-term performance. Both constructs necessitate established organisational structures, systems, and processes, whereas female entrepreneurs use informal management practices, operate in traditional sectors, and, in most instances, have few or no employees.

Women entrepreneurs may encounter significant resource constraints in developing "*competitiveness*." Notably, Man et al.'s (2002) entrepreneurial competence construct alone has been empirically examined in multiple studies (Lans et al., 2011; Zainol and Mamun, 2018). Yet the entire model is seldom used for empirical testing, possibly due to its limited applicability. This set of competencies will also be used in the present study. Moreover, the influence of organisational capabilities is mainly focused on large enterprises, and their drivers are rarely studied in small firms (Inan and Bititci, 2015), particularly female entrepreneurship. This suggests that deploying competitiveness constructs (i.e., competitive scope and organisational capabilities) might be challenging in female-owned firms due to a lack of inadequate resources, established systems, and structure.

Source: Man et al. (2002)

2.11.3 Entrepreneurial Success Model

The model of entrepreneurial success developed by Ahmad et al. (2010) comprises three key constructs: entrepreneurial competencies, perceived business environment, and entrepreneurial success. The study seeks to evaluate the impact of entrepreneurial competencies (EC) and the moderating effect of the perceived business environment on the entrepreneurial success of SMEs. Ahmad et al. (2010) conducted empirical testing of their model, including both male and female entrepreneurs in their study.

The entrepreneurial competencies construct, illustrated in Figure 2.3, encompasses eight dimensions: strategic, conceptual, opportunity, relationship, personal, learning, familism, and ethical. Drawing inspiration from Chandler and Jansen (1992), Ahmad et al. (2010) conceptualised entrepreneurial competencies based on three distinct generalist roles of an entrepreneur: "*entrepreneurial, managerial, and functional.*" The authors argue that an entrepreneur's productivity is optimised when they possess a well-balanced set of skills for fulfilling the responsibilities associated with these roles. The "*entrepreneurial role*" covers domains like conceptual, strategic, learning, and opportunity competencies, while the "*managerial role*" specifically includes relationship competencies. This distinction is crucial, as these competencies are regarded as "*externalised elements*" that can be acquired through training and learning (Saeed, 2012, p. 83). Conversely, the function role comprises personal, ethical, and familial competencies recognised as "*internalised elements*" that are an individual's personality or intrinsic parts of their character and deeply embedded personal characteristics, hence less

susceptible to change through training. Hence, the functional role domain was deemed inappropriate for use in the present study due to the difficulty of altering internalised elements (Ahmad et al., 2017).

Ahmad et al. (2010) also examined the impact of the business environment, observing that in dynamic and hostile environments, entrepreneurial competencies become crucial for business success. While external influences play a role in SMEs' performance, they alone cannot explain the success or failure of small businesses. In fact, a firm's failure is contingent on foundational characteristics such as the owner's insight, planning, and managerial skills (Gupta et al., 2013). Consistent with this perspective, Man et al. (2002) argue that all externally measured factors are subjective when assessed by an entrepreneur. As a result, this study will adopt the managerial role and entrepreneurial role domains, while the perceived business environment construct will not be considered.

Figure 2. 3 Entrepreneurial Success Model

Source: Ahmad et al. (2010)

2.11.4 Entrepreneurial Orientation Model

Lumpkin and Dess (1996) developed a multidimensional model to measure venture performance, emphasising its nature as a firm-level phenomenon. The model comprises four constructs: entrepreneurial orientation (EO), environmental factors, organisational factors, and performance, illustrating two directions of influence in Figure 2.4 below. The authors contend that characterising a firm as entrepreneurial would require factors that extend beyond the confines of the EO construct, such as environmental and organisational factors. Figure 2.4 demonstrates how endogenous influences (organisational elements) and exogenous influences (environmental elements) impact the relationship between EO and its performance domain.

Lumpkin and Dess (1996), drawing on the pioneering work of Miller (1983), conceptualised EO as being driven by five (not three) dimensions and added two more: competitive aggressiveness and autonomy. While Miller (1983) describes EO variables as the continuous exhibition of risk-taking proactiveness and innovation, Lumpkin and Dess (1996) introduced the notion of dimensional heterogeneity, which demands individual evaluation of each EO dimension. Therefore, the authors

extended Miller's (1983) unidimensional perception of EO (innovation, proactiveness, and risk-taking) into a multidimensional view by introducing autonomy and competitive aggressiveness into the list of influencing factors. EO, as defined by Lumpkin and Dess (1996), encompasses processes, practices, and decision-making activities leading to new entries, including entry into existing or new markets, new services/products, or innovations in technology or business models that lead to. Unlike strategic content, EO represents a broader strategic orientation based on organisational and environmental factors rather than concentrated on a specific type of strategy (Rauch and Frese, 2000).

Despite its merits, the model by Lumpkin and Dess (1996) faces criticism. For instance, the model did not lend itself to empirical testing by the authors; therefore, it requires further exploration of the relationship between all EO dimensions and their environmental and organisational factors to predict performance. Similarly, the model does not define how individual EO dimensions can be mapped onto firm performance (Hughes and Morgan, 2007). Yet, both EO constructs are widely accepted in the literature (Covin and Wales, 2018). This study adopts Miller's (1983) conceptualization, focusing on innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness. The investigator is of the view that an owner's level of autonomy and competitive aggression appear to be an "attitude" rather than a "behaviour" towards firm performance, and attitude is related to intrinsic parts of the individual's personality or character. Therefore, the EO domain in this study includes risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness.

Figure 2.4 Entrepreneurial Orientation Model

Source: Lumpkin and Dess (1996)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

2.11.5 Three Strategic Capabilities Model

Drawing on a resource-based approach, Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014) come up with a model for achieving superior performance in female-owned enterprises. Their study seeks to understand how "Three Strategic Capabilities" (LO, EO, and MO) influence the creation of competitive advantages and contribute to enhanced performance in women-led businesses. The model and its relationships are depicted in Figure 2.5b. The authors argue that for a business to gain a long-term competitive edge, its capabilities and resources must be heterogeneous and difficult to imitate. They argue that, unlike "supplementary capabilities," "elementary capabilities" are strategically essential. Elementary capabilities not only represent a competitively unique activity but also enable businesses to deliver essential customer benefits that contribute to sustainable competitive advantage. Based on these arguments, the authors classify EO, LO, and MO as "elementary capacities," asserting that these capabilities are not only essential to firm strategy but often serve as a means to attain competitive advantage and, consequently, enhance performance. This concept is illustrated in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2. 5 Three Strategic Capabilities

Source: Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014)

One notable aspect of the model presented by Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014) is its simplicity. Additionally, it was empirically tested in a developing country and is primarily meant to assess the performance of female owned businesses.

Source: Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014)

While this model offers valuable insights into the resources (EO) and capabilities (LO) of female-owned businesses, it is not without flaws. Small firms can benefit from the MO strategy due to its proximity to clients and the ease with which they can tailor their business responses to local client needs (Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014). However, drawbacks related to the scarcity of resources exist, particularly in women's entrepreneurship. For instance, customers' desires and needs can be identified using the MO strategy, but this involves a significant investment in market research. Small businesses are almost certain to need the assistance of an outside market research agency if they lack the requisite expertise or staff (Burch, 2019). Moreover, research suggests that a firm's performance is influenced by its MO capabilities to a certain extent, beyond which MO becomes less beneficial (Jancenelle et al., 2022). Consequently, it seems that the MO construct is less effective in analysing the performance of female-owned enterprises compared to other constructs and will not be adopted in the present study.

2.11.6 The Self-Concept Traits, Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance Model

The model developed by Poon et al. (2006) employed variables at both the firm-level and individual-level to explain the performance of entrepreneur-led firms, encompassing both male and female participants. In this study, an entrepreneur is defined as an individual who is driven to find, analyse, and explore business opportunities; to be imitative and innovative; to organise and transform resources for business use; and to embrace failure or risk. The authors argue that for a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial process, it is essential to establish a relationship between specific firm-level behaviours and dispositional characteristics to explain and predict results at the firm-level. Poon et al. (2006) specifically chose three self-concept traits: internal locus of control, achievement motive, and generalised self-efficacy, as individual-level exogenous variables, as illustrated in Figure 2.6. In terms of firm-level behavioural factors, the authors selected entrepreneurial orientation (EO).

Poon et al. (2006) describe EO as a process (behaviour) variable that affects venture performance through influencing self-selected traits.

The study also tested the mediating role of EO between the internal locus of control and generalised self-efficacy, as shown in Figure 2.6. Poon et al. (2006) view that attributes such as generalised self-efficacy and internal locus of control impact the strategic decisions (EO) made by entrepreneurs in the face of a competitive market. They argue that entrepreneurs with a robust internal locus of control are more inclined to take risks, proactively initiate changes, pursue new opportunities, and experiment with new ideas. However, the study revealed that EO did not act as a mediator between the internal locus of control and firm performance. Instead, only generalised self-efficacy demonstrated significant effects on firm performance through its influence on entrepreneurial orientation. Individual entrepreneurial traits such as internal locus of control, achievement motive, and generalised self-efficacy are considered more crucial during the startup phase. Whereas for an existing business, these individual traits are of secondary importance, and firm-level attributes become more prominent. Consequently, the current study will exclusively employ the entrepreneurial orientation construct.

Source: Poon et al. (2006)

Upon reviewing the aforementioned models, it becomes evident that various studies have attempted to develop diverse models for analysing firm performance. It is also noted that many studies have not explicitly distinguished between male and female firm performance models. While these models provide valuable insights into factors deemed significant for understanding firm performance in general and female entrepreneurship in particular, they have limitations that hinder their consistency and utility as tools for comprehensively assessing the factors influencing female enterprise performance.

Hence, it is reasonable to conclude that there is no singular, unified model capable of capturing all the complexities involved in understanding the factors contributing to female business performance.

Therefore, this study proposes an integrated framework by incorporating the most effective elements from one or more models and considering the specificities that may exist in diverse social, economic, and cultural environments, particularly in developing economies like Pakistan. Therefore, an integrated conceptual framework for firm performance is formulated, specifically tailored to the context (Pakistan) and gender (female entrepreneurs).

2.12 Resource-Based View: A Theoretical Perspective

The conceptual framework proposed in this study is grounded in the “*Resource-Based View*,” serving as the theoretical foundation. The adoption of the resource-based view (RBV) in business research is widely acknowledged, and its extensive utilisation is regarded as enduring and timeless (Walker et al., 2015). This study also adopts the RBV as the theoretical basis for the conceptual framework. The RBV as a theoretical foundation focuses on a firm's competitiveness and performance through the effective leveraging and combination of all available resources (Roxas and Chadee, 2011). In the field of management, the RBV is a dominant approach, influencing domains within management research such as human resource management, technology management, organisational theory, and international management (Foss, 2011). At its core, RBV explores the connection between a company's strategic relevance and its resources and capabilities (Lee and Carter, 2012).

Barney (1991) posits that resource-based view considers a firm as an assemblage of resources whose characteristics significantly shape its competitive advantage and, consequently, its performance. Instead of concentrating on the products themselves, RBV underscores the worth of the unique resources (and competencies) that a firm possesses. Thus, the theory asserts that these capabilities and resources play a pivotal role in enabling firms to gain a competitive advantage and achieve superior performance.

This concept contends that an entity's performance is most effectively explained by the skills, resources, and assets it possesses (Madhani, 2010). It further elucidates that firms can attain and sustain a competitive advantage, leading to superior performance, by possessing resources (tangible or intangible) characterised as “*inimitable*,” “*rare*,” “*non-substitutable*,” and “*valuable*” (Kuada, 2015). In the context of small businesses, the abilities, skills, and competencies of the business owner are critical assets for success (Mitchelmore et al., 2014), as all major decisions are made and implemented by the firm owner. Additionally, in entrepreneurship literature, a small firm is often considered an extension of the entrepreneur (Lee-Ross and Lashley, 2015). Given that all aspects revolve around the founder, the human capital possessed by the founder is frequently regarded as pivotal to the success of the small firm (Segal et al., 2010).

As highlighted by Barney (1991), resources encompass elements like management skills, organisational processes, and knowledge. Among diverse firm resources and skills, the competencies of female entrepreneurs represent capabilities deeply embedded in the daily operations of an entity, making them challenging for rivals to replicate (Ahmad et al., 2010). Although female entrepreneurs may pursue

various skills, this study specifically argues that "entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, entrepreneurial competencies, and human capital" are the VRIN capabilities that empower women entrepreneurs to establish a sustainable competitive advantage and achieve superior performance. Firms effectively utilising these capabilities may surpass competitors in the marketplace. The current research, therefore, focuses on these resource categories.

2.13 Factors Adopted from Models Influencing Firm Performance

Drawing on the research gap, recognising key shortcomings in the literature, and acknowledging the inadequacy of existing firm performance models, key factors influencing female entrepreneurship firm performance are identified. In the present study, the proposed conceptual framework combines and integrates components from the models of Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016), Man et al. (2002), Lumpkin and Dess (2006), and Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014). These factors include components of human capital (education attainment, previous work experience, and business training) adopted from the Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016) model, entrepreneurial orientation (risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness) adopted from Lumpkin and Dess (2006), Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014), and Poon et al. (2006) models, entrepreneurial competencies (organising, relationship, commitment, strategic, conceptual, and opportunity) adopted from the Man et al. (2002) model, and learning orientation adopted from the Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014) model. The framework also explores the interrelationships among these factors. An overview of all the adapted key factors is given in Table 2.1, and the framework underpinning this study is illustrated in Figure 3.1. The following section provides an overview of the key constructs adopted in developing the conceptual framework.

The "***Entrepreneurial Orientation***" construct is considered an important factor in the proposed integrated conceptual framework of firm performance. EO is acknowledged as an intangible organisational resource characterised as being valuable, rare, distinct, and having inimitable capabilities. These attributes set a firm apart from its competitors, leading to a competitive advantage and the creation of wealth (Pratono and Mahmood, 2015). Consequently, the entrepreneurial behaviour associated with EO is recognised for bringing novel ideas to fruition. Individuals engaged in entrepreneurial activities exhibiting high EO are characterised as those that involve bringing together a unique set of resources to generate value. As a result, EO fosters innovation and a growth-oriented mindset among entrepreneurs, encompassing processes, practices, and decisions that effectively address current and future opportunities (Jyoti et al., 2011). In this study, Miller's (1983) conceptualisation of EO, encompassing risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness, is adopted. This choice aligns with the prevailing research trend, where scholars investigating the EO construct in small firms commonly utilise Miller's (1983) framework. This approach has also been employed in the current study.

Another significant factor that can influence firm performance in female entrepreneurship is "***Human Capital***," as it consists of tacit and explicit knowledge. This has been widely acknowledged as a pivotal

resource for success in entrepreneurial enterprises (Hasan and Almubarak, 2016). Education, a key element of human capital, stands out as a contributor to enhancing competencies. For instance, a higher level of education not only cultivates analytical and computational skills but also refines communication abilities. In essence, education is a human capital investment, as it tends to elevate an individual's productivity levels, consequently improving their earning potential (Robeyns, 2006).

Training, another essential element of human capital, is geared towards enhancing an individual's skills, behaviour, and performance, often tailored for a specific job or purpose. Similarly, previous work experience is also a vital component of human capital, indicating its capacity to provide founders with industry knowledge, management knowledge, and entrepreneurial knowledge. This, in turn, enables a better understanding of specific technologies, customers, markets, and products (Reuber and Fischer, 1999).

The proposed integrated conceptual framework also conceptualises “*Entrepreneurial Competencies*” as a pivotal factor in achieving high performance. Entrepreneurial competencies play a crucial role by furnishing entrepreneurs with knowledge about effective business operations and fostering awareness of the potential positive or negative impacts of their behaviour (Ahmad, 2010). Likewise, entrepreneurs can attain a competitive advantage through their abilities, overcoming constraints associated with their firm size (Ahmad, 2010). This is because research indicates that competencies exert a more profound influence on women owned enterprises compared to those owned by men (Manolova et al., 2007). Man et al. (2002) identify key areas of competencies that individuals must integrate into their skill set to succeed in entrepreneurial activities. These include organising, commitment, strategic, conceptual, relationship, and opportunity, all of which are also incorporated in the current study. The author argued that utilising this approach offers a valuable means to explore entrepreneurial characteristics with enduring effects and closer ties to organisational performance.

“*Learning Orientation*” is the last factor in the integrated conceptual framework. Within the entrepreneurial process, learning and knowledge acquisition prove crucial, offering avenues for developing the necessary knowledge and skill sets required to perform business tasks. Previous research suggests that an entrepreneur's competence significantly contributes to fostering a learning orientation. To illustrate, an entrepreneur's managerial and entrepreneurial roles can facilitate an entrepreneur in two ways. Firstly, the managerial role enables effective communication of organisational goals, motivates members to collaborate synergistically, and fosters a conducive environment for learning orientation. Secondly, the entrepreneur's role in creating appropriate systems for organisation and supporting activities can enhance knowledge and encourage learning, both of which are vital for growth. (Kungwansupaphan and Siengthai, 2014). Consequently, learning transforms the perspective through which firms perceive and interpret the world. In terms of gender, studies have indicated a tendency for women to engage in a single-loop learning process (Ekanem, 2015). For instance, female entrepreneurs are often engaged in “routinised” learning, which contributes to increasing confidence. Similarly,

Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014) observe that empathy and communication skills can cultivate the capabilities of female entrepreneurs, thereby facilitating the dissemination and creation of knowledge throughout the organisation. In essence, learning facilitates behavioural changes that result in improved performance.

Table 2. 2 Derivation of Factors Influencing Firm performance

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Literature Reference</i>
<i>Learning Orientation</i>		Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014); Wang (2008); De Clercq et al. (2013); Turk et al. (2020); Rhee et al. (2010); Nybakk (2012) Tajeddini (2011); Mutonyi et al. (2020).
<i>Entrepreneurial Orientation</i>	Innovativeness	Wach et al. (2018); Wang and Yen (2012); Nasution et al. (2011); Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014); Fuentes-Fuentes et al. (2015); Aftab, et al. (2021); Anderson et al. (2015).
	Risk Taking	Omisakin et al. (2016); Reijonen et al. (2015); Sajjad et al. (2020); Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014); Fuentes-Fuentes et al. (2015); Zeb and Ihsan (2020); Aftab et al. (2021); Anderson et al. (2015).
	Proactiveness	Lumpkin and Dess (1996); Keh, et al. (2007); Brettel et al. (2015) Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014); Fuentes-Fuentes et al. (2015); Aftab et al. (2021); Anderson et al. (2015).
<i>Human Capital</i>	Education Attainment	Jiao et al. (2021); Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016); Mandawa, (2016); Martin, et al. (2013); Santarelli and Tran (2013); Sapienza and Grimm (1997); Jiang et al. (2012); Prasad et al. (2013); Alene (2020); Gupta and Mirchandani (2018); Mozumdar et al. (2020); Passaro et al. (2018); Welsh et al. (2018a).
	Previous Work Experience	Adom and Asare-Yeboah, (2016); Jiang et al. (2012); Jiao et al. (2021); Mandawa (2016).
	Business Training	Alene (2020); Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016); Mandawa (2016); Roomi and Harrison (2010); Gielnik et al. (2017); Mozumdar et al. (2020).
<i>Entrepreneurial Competencies</i>	Opportunity	Man et al. (2002); Ahmad et al. (2010); Mandawa (2016); Zainol and Mamun (2018); Zainol et al. (2018); Fastre and Gils (2007); Ibidunni et al. (2021); Tehseen and Anderson (2020); Rahman et al. (2016); Tehseen et al. (2020); Lans et al. (2011).
	Commitment	Man et al. (2002); Mandawa (2016); Zainol and Mamun (2018); Fastre and Gils (2007); Rahman et al. (2016); Lans et al. (2011).
	Relationship	Mandawa (2016); Ahmad, et al. (2010) Man, et al. (2002); Zainol and Mamun (2018); Fastre and Gils (2007); Ibidunni et al. (2021); Rahman et al. (2016); (Lans, et al., 2011).
	Organising	Man, et al. (2002); Mandawa (2016); Zainol and Mamun (2018); Fastre and Gils (2007); Ibidunni et al. (2021); Lans et al. (2011).

	Conceptual	Ahmad et al. (2010); Mandawa (2016); Man et al. (2002); Zainol and Mamun (2018); Fastre and Gils (2007); Ibidunni et al. (2021); Tehseen and Anderson (2020); Tehseen et al. (2020); Lans et al. (2011).
	Strategic	Ahmad et al. (2010); Man et al. (2002); Zainol and Mamun (2018); Fastre and Gils (2007); Ibidunni et al. (2021); Tehseen and Anderson (2020); Rahman et al. (2016); Tehseen et al. (2020); Subagyo et al. (2020); Lans et al. (2011).

Source: Author

2.14 Linking Derivation Factors with Firm performance: The Proposed Conceptual Framework

Scholars in the entrepreneurship field have argued that studying entrepreneurs as individuals is worthwhile because they are the energisers of the entrepreneurial process and that there is no entrepreneurship without the entrepreneur. Similarly, academics have contended that it is critical to link individual dispositional features to observable firm-level behaviours to fully grasp the entrepreneurial process (Poon et al., 2006). In the present research, learning orientation (Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014) and human capital components such as education attainment, previous work experience, and business training are studied at the individual-level (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016). The firm-level constructs encompass six sets of EC, namely commitment, relationship, conceptual, opportunity, strategic, and organising (Man et al., 2002), and three domains of EO, risk-taking, proactiveness, and innovativeness (Miller, 1983).

Evidently, there is a theoretical and logical basis as to why human capital components, EC, EO, and LO, need to be studied together. For instance, Lumpkin and Dess (1996) described EO as a "*deliberate act*," and viewing from the strategic choice perspective, the ability of entrepreneurs to make strategic choices, or "*capacity to act*," should be a significant addition to any research on the EO construct (Lahiri, 2014). Entrepreneurs are considered the custodians of diverse internal business resources in SMEs and are the main driving force of internal activity. The capacity to act on opportunities, learning, conceptual thinking, and personal effectiveness are all aspects of entrepreneurial behaviour and skills and how these affect the performance of the firm (Ahmad et al., 2010). Similarly, a firm's resources should be immobile, heterogeneous, rare, sustainable, and valuable to create a competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). "*Competencies and knowledge*" can be one such component that satisfies the firm's resource criteria (Zainol and Mamun, 2018). However, a structure is required for these competencies to be "locked in" and used rationally within a particular firm. Human capital components and EC allow for the creation of knowledge resources, whereas EO acts as the lock-in potential because it works on the mechanisms of process, practice, and decision-making (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996). In other words, an entrepreneur can draw upon human capital components to develop their competencies, allowing them to create knowledge resources that assist them in making strategic choices that can have an impact

on firm performance. The subsequent sections offer detailed reviews of all the factors central to the proposed conceptual framework.

2.14.1 Human Capital (Individual-Level Construct)

Human capital is an investment in the knowledge, skills, and abilities gained from experience, training, and education, which in turn adds value to a career (Becker, 1964; Harris et al., 2015). The extensive body of literature highlights human capital as a critical factor in SME growth (Shoubaki et al., 2019). In the context of nascent businesses, human capital is viewed as particularly valuable due to the multiple avenues it offers to boost firm performance. For instance, in the entrepreneurship process, human capital can alleviate the burden of the liability of being a pioneering business, which entrepreneurs inevitably face (Jiao et al., 2021). As per Zhang and White (2016), it can ease the restraints on business owners' access to key resources. In the entrepreneurship context, Unger et al. (2011) note that human capital improves the entrepreneur's ability to acquire resources, such as financial capital, and aids in the ability to discover opportunities and acquire new skills and knowledge. Along these lines, Hsiao et al. (2016) claim that the cognitive ability and productivity of an individual can be significantly increased through human capital. It follows that individuals' human capital, in terms of a higher level of skills, knowledge, and ability, will offer leveraged business performance (Jiang et al., 2013).

At times, human capital is associated with the number of years of a person's education and is considered a more significant factor in human capital accumulation (Ogundari and Awokuse, 2018). It also encompasses components like technical or non-technical training regimens and experiences obtained from on-the-job training or practical learning that augment skill development (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016). Based on a detailed review of the literature on how human capital is measured, the author intends to look at human capital in terms of business training, level of education, and previous work experience as an intangible resource and see how they relate to the development of competencies in female owned firms.

2.14.1.1 Education

Literature suggests that through education, an entrepreneur can successfully manage their firm, as it equips an individual with the necessary skills and knowledge. Within a given context, learning and problem-solving abilities are likely to improve as a result of an entrepreneur's educational experience (Verheul et al., 2009). Higher entrepreneurial education is pursued with the aim of equipping individuals with the specific skills, knowledge, and essential learning initiatives they need to successfully face financial and managerial difficulties (Fayolle and Gailly, 2015). Investment in education and training equips individuals with better skills and productivity than their counterparts, thereby expecting a higher payoff (McCracken et al., 2017). Marvel et al. (2016) reported that human capital endowments, for example, education, aid in the building of cognitive abilities, knowledge, and competencies (human capital outcomes) that are valuable in undertaking business activities. Studies

have linked education to information-processing capacity, i.e., an individual's cognitive skills and abilities are reflected in their education level, and a high level contributes to enhancing information processing and the ability to discriminate between various stimuli (Baumuller, 2007, p. 231). It follows that the education of an entrepreneur is a key component of venture creation and entrepreneurial success. In a similar vein, Altinay and Wang (2011) assert that higher education attainment enhances an entrepreneur's computational and analytical abilities, along with their communication skills. Likewise, in the prospect of managing a new business, Jiang et al. (2012) claim that the entrepreneur with a higher level of education may build up shareholders' confidence and, in the context of the future productivity of the business, it signals potential lenders, customers, and employees (Backes-Gellner and Werner, 2007). It follows that education results in higher earnings, which robustly impacts the RBV of the firm (Jayawarna et al., 2014).

2.14.1.2 Previous Work Experience (Generic)

Managerial experience and job experience (as an employee) are considered generic experiences by prior studies (Debrulle and Maes, 2015; Furlan, 2019). Soriano and Castrogiovanni (2012) portray experience as skills and knowledge acquired through repeated exposure to different situations and observation over time. Various studies have highlighted the importance of prior work experience in explaining entrepreneurial intention, self-efficacy, and decision-making (Morris et al., 2012), venture performance (Mandawa, 2016), and innovation (Nag et al., 2020). Similarly, learning by doing or routinised learning has enhanced female entrepreneurial judgement and confidence (Ekanem, 2015). In addition, experience seems to be significant in predicting changing environments and uncertainty, as it makes it easier to plan ahead by obtaining all the necessary information. For instance, Nielsen (2014) noted that in an uncertain environment, industry experience is essential since the ability to adjust to changing conditions is contingent on the established network and the knowledge obtained in the industry. Likewise, Prasad et al. (2013) consider experience an essential resource in predicting the business venture growth of female entrepreneurs in India. They concluded that for Indian female business owners, competence earned from prior experience is a crucial factor in determining competitive advantage. Further, Dimov (2010) illustrated that entrepreneurs with industry experience are equipped with important sources of information like cost structure, pricing, revenue, market share, and profitability, which seems to be true in attracting suppliers, customers, or enhancing market credibility due to their previous employment network contacts (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016).

2.14.1.3 Business Training

Training has been acknowledged as a key component in the development of human capital worldwide. Boukamcha (2015) expresses that training improves a person's cognitive abilities and knowledge, which are crucial to business. Training, as per Zigon (2002), is an entire process that can modify an individual's behaviour to meet specific or pre-determined patterns. Training is an approach or way of honing an individual's skills, knowledge, and abilities to boost output (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016).

It follows that individuals with business training or education are more likely to be successful than their counterparts in recognising and seizing business opportunities. In every business endeavour, training provides a means to improve human capital's competencies for firm success. For instance, Byabashaija and Katono (2011) emphasise that business training should improve an individual's creativity, flexibility, imagination, perception of opportunity changes, and conceptual thinking ability. Similarly, business training not only makes entrepreneurs conscious of available business opportunities and ambiguity but also creates awareness of how to cope with them. Furthermore, Savitha et al. (2014) investigated entrepreneurial behaviour factors and found that women who received investment training were more likely to engage in entrepreneurial behaviour. In addition, business training has been connected to female entrepreneurs' creativity, branding, product self-education, and networking (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016). In a similar vein, Roomi and Harrison (2010) revealed that training can ease the impediments encountered by female entrepreneurs, allowing them to develop competencies and capital. According to a meta-analysis conducted by Martin et al. (2013), business training is beneficial in boosting motivational and cognitive outcomes that lead to increased performance and business start-up.

2.14.2 Learning Orientation (Individual-Level Construct)

Learning is widely recognised as a crucial component in today's knowledge-based economy, where it serves as a means to improve the quality of an organisation, group, or individual. "Learning orientation" (LO) is a broad, subjective concept that encompasses many aspects of learning. Numerous studies (Chang and Ku, 2009; Slater and Narver, 1995) agree that greater performance can be attributed to changes in behaviour that are fostered by learning. The LO portrayed by Rhee et al. (2010) is the adoption of a basic learning process. They argue that if a small business is less focused on learning than its competitors, it will struggle to survive. A learning orientation assists ventures in obtaining, disseminating, and sharing information (Wang, 2008) so that learning-oriented firms can have a deeper understanding of the organisational elements that influence the acceptance of technology and market knowledge (Tidd, 1997). In a similar vein, Nybakk (2012) describes LO as the degree to which an entity is devoted to learning, intra-organisational knowledge sharing, open-mindedness, and shared vision. However, the culture of a firm provides the context for learning, and this context, or learning environment, is provided by the firm (Palos and Stancovici, 2016). Nonetheless, organisational cultural elements can sway the outcomes of organisational learning (OL) since organisational culture is shaped by a company's values (Grant, 2015). Most notably, learning orientation and organisational learning are two distinct but related concepts. For instance, OL is considered a time-focused process involving information acquisition and performance enhancement (Garvin, 1993), whereas LO is reflected in organisational values (Baker et al., 2022). As a result, firm performance can be boosted through learning orientation because it can not only modify organisational learning modes but also foster an ideal learning atmosphere (Yuan et al., 2018).

Individuals react differently to experiences based on their LO. Individuals' ability to learn from both vicarious and direct experiences is greatly influenced by the LO. A person's ability to synthesise their experiences into knowledge is reflected in their level of LO, which indicates how well they can draw from their experiences. Such individuals are more likely to relish new opportunities and challenges to further equip their competencies. Consequently, such individuals, even in difficult situations, persist in their efforts to prioritise task mastery. Given the significance of these implications in the context of entrepreneurship, past research has recognised LO's importance as a contextual component (Turk et al., 2020). For instance, De Clercq et al. (2013) found LO to strengthen the impact of perceived entrepreneurial ability and attractiveness on entrepreneurial intention. Likewise, Uy et al. (2017) note that LO exacerbates the negative impacts of spin on the psychological well-being of early-stage entrepreneurs.

Learning and knowledge are two distinct concepts. Learning is a process that results in the development of potentially relevant knowledge, and knowledge is ephemeral and needs to be updated and revised constantly (Dixon, 2017). Numerous scholars (Ekanem, 2015; Baker and Sinkula, 2007) have identified two forms of learning, namely, adaptive learning (lower-order learning or single-loop learning) and generative learning (higher-order learning or double-loop learning). Businesses employ adaptive learning for refining routine, existing knowledge, and procedures and to comprehend the fundamental concept of cause-and-effect relations among the firm and environment (Chiva, 2014). In contrast, individuals in generative learning are required to question their assumptions and behaviours.

Studies have identified certain disparities in the learning experiences of men and women. For instance, male entrepreneurs are inclined to adaptive learning as they like challenges and depart from industry norms, while female business owners are oriented towards generative learning as they prefer "routinised" learning that builds confidence (Ekanem, 2015). While higher-order (adaptive) learning enhances a business's performance by enabling the creation of a variety of routines, the absence of generative learning can lead to delays in responding to new challenges, inflexibility, and an overreliance on existing routines, as generative learning is crucial for driving competitiveness. Yet, both types are important for an individual to learn through experience (Garcia-Morales et al., 2009).

For instance, male entrepreneurs are inclined to adaptive learning as they like challenges and depart from industry norms, while female business owners are oriented towards generative learning as they prefer "routinised" learning that builds confidence (Ekanem, 2015). Even though higher-order (adaptive) learning enhances a business's performance by allowing the creation of a range of routines, the absence of generative learning can result in delays in responding to new problems, inflexibility, and overdependence on existing routines because generative learning drives competitiveness. Yet, both types are important for an individual to learn through experience (Garcia-Morales et al., 2009).

While numerous studies conceptualise LO as a corporate behaviour, Baker et al. (2022) refer to LO as a dynamic capability. Similarly, to explain learning, Mutonyi et al. (2020) cited three forms of learning orientation as a key factor in knowledge development: work avoidance orientation, learning orientation, and performance orientation. Meece et al. (1988) show that work avoidance-oriented individuals have a strong tendency to complete their work tasks with minimal effort. Jha and Bhattacharyya (2013) describe learning-oriented individuals as ones who not only perceive knowledge as treasured and valuable but are also highly motivated to learn. In contrast, Lu et al. (2012) depict performance-oriented individuals as those who avoid negative evaluations and have a strong desire to impress others with their accomplishments. The LO perception of Jha and Bhattacharyya (2013) is of particular importance since it focuses on individual adoption and implementation. Learning encourages individuals to experiment with various solutions and enables them to acquire new knowledge by exerting extra effort (Lu et al., 2012). Studies, such as those by Jha and Bhattacharyya (2013) and Lu et al. (2012), indicate that individual LO accelerates commitment, competency, and knowledge, correlating with innovation. Consequently, LO can be seen as a key capability for generating advantages due to its four VIRN attributes. (Sanzo et al., 2011).

2.14.3 Entrepreneurial Orientation (Firm-Level Construct)

Within the entrepreneurship literature, "Entrepreneurial Orientation" (EO) has gained widespread scholarly support as a significant antecedent of venture performance, and it is widely acknowledged that entrepreneurial orientation is crucial to the survival and growth of businesses. A few scholars (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005; Anwar et al., 2022) have emphasised that for venture performance, EO is considered a key resource. According to Wales et al. (2011b), EO represents a firm-level strategic-making process or the strategic orientation of a venture. Along these lines, Lumpkin and Dess (1996) reflect EO as a manager style to act entrepreneurially in terms of business decision-making, methods, processes, and practice, indicating an inherent link between organisational activities or behaviours and EO, which appear compatible with EO (Anderson et al., 2009). Likewise, Rauch and Frese (2000) depict EO as one of the three components of business strategy, together with strategy content and strategic process. The authors are of the view that, unlike strategic process and strategic content, which are concerned with a specific type of strategy, EO is a general strategic orientation that is contingent on organisational and environmental factors. EO is generally conceptualised as a combination of three dimensions in numerous studies, namely: proactiveness, risk-taking, and innovativeness. It was originally conceptualised by Miller (1983) and characterised as an enterprise that undertakes risky ventures by taking part in product market innovation and beats competitors to the punch by coming up with proactive innovation. In fact, many studies, such as Anderson and Eshima (2013), Brettel et al. (2015) and Fuentes-Fuentes et al. (2015), have used Miller's (1983) three-dimensional model as a basis. Nevertheless, a few researchers (e.g., Lumpkin and Dess, 1996) created a multidimensional EO model and therefore extended the EO concept by constructing two additional dimensions, i.e., competitive

aggressiveness and autonomy. Moreover, Lumpkin and Dess (1996) advocate that the notion be restricted to small businesses, despite the fact that Miller's initial notion was not limited to small ventures and intended to encompass a broad spectrum of business activities (Miller, 2011; George and Marino, 2011). However, Lumpkin and Dess (1996) advocate that the notion be restricted to small businesses. Nonetheless, in the literature, both EO dimensions are widely acknowledged, yet within the context of this study, Miller's (1983) entrepreneurial orientation is employed due to its widespread conceptualization in mainstream EO research. The EO dimensions are discussed briefly below.

2.14.3.1 Innovativeness

From a particular industry-specific environment and from a firm perspective, an organisation can have multiple reasons to act entrepreneurially. In this regard, less innovative ventures may lose a skilled workforce, cede market share to competitors, or continue to operate inefficiently. Innovation was initially described at a firm-level by Schumpeter (1942), who referred to it as an economic process of "*creative destruction*" in which new wealth is created within an existing market by improving an existing product or service or by developing a new product or service, causing a shift in the use of resources (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996; Kraus et al., 2012). According to Covin and Miles (1999), innovation is an essential component of business strategy; hence, a business cannot exist without innovation. To the authors, other dimensions of EO are consequences of innovation. Omisakin et al. (2016) state that fostering a culture of innovation facilitates the development of new services or products. Ventures can increase their profitability and market performance through their commitment to processes and product innovation. Thus, innovative firms usually have an edge over their competitors because innovation gives them a broader base of knowledge and skills. Without innovation, start-ups rely on traditional ways of doing business. Therefore, innovativeness empowers young organisations by distinguishing themselves from other firms, thus preventing failure linked with scale diseconomies, resource shortages, etc. (Lee et al., 2001). Along these lines, Genis-Gruber and Ogut (2014) entail that, in response to external environmental change, businesses have to be innovative for them to achieve success and develop their market position (Akman and Yilmaz, 2019). Similarly, changes in the venture's external conditions can also lead to new opportunities, and in order to capitalise on them, new strategies must be implemented (Javalgi and Todd, 2011). This implies that innovativeness is the key to survival for businesses since it is the source of novel ideas that lead to the improvement or creation of new products, especially in a competitive labour market (Lumpkin et al., 2010). For this reason, the concept of innovativeness is very important when studying small businesses in particular and entrepreneurship in general.

2.14.3.2 Risk Taking

The uncertainty that an entrepreneur tolerates in the process of seeking venture opportunities and investing a considerable amount of resources in highly uncertain projects that are prone to failure is often referred to as the risk-taking dimension (Kraus et al., 2012; Omisakin et al., 2016). The uncertainty

and risk associated with self-employment are the principal elements that differentiate entrepreneurs from others (Koudstaal et al., 2016). Similarly, risk-taking has been perceived as a feature of both entrepreneurial firms (Nasution et al., 2011) and of entrepreneurs (Guo and Jiang, 2020), with the common perception being that entrepreneurs who are willing to take risk are more likely to seize market opportunities that lead to lucrative business deals and higher returns, therefore positively linking to firm success (Lumpkin and Dress, 2001; Frese et al., 2002). However, managing and identifying risk appropriately by the entrepreneurs in the external environment is critical for the firm's performance (Delmar, 1996). Lumpkin and Dess (1996) believe that every business engages in some degree of risk-taking within EO. Entrepreneurial behaviour is not merely a set of characteristics and attributes of an entrepreneur; it also requires them to take calculated risks in all business aspects. Zehir et al. (2016) note that entrepreneurial activities have been concentrated on risky behaviours since attempting new things or being innovative, differentiating the venture from its rivals, and taking advantage of market prospects often include some risk. Therefore, entrepreneurial firms are exposed to three types of risks, namely personal, financial, and business risk-taking. Financial risk, as the name suggests, pertains to getting finance generally, whereas personal risk accompanies decisions with an uncertain outcome and may impact the entire firm, and business risk is the risk of venturing into the unknown (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005; Hardaker et al., 2015). Along these lines, Alalawi (2020) asserts that risk does not appear to be solely a feature of an individual personality but rather appears to be influenced by the setting of the organisation, particularly when an entrepreneur attempts to enact a business idea despite minimal chances of success or invests in a firm with high profits or losses. Furthermore, risk-taking as an entrepreneurial attribute has been found in some research (e.g., Nasution et al., 2011) to have an impact on innovation creation, technology, and diffusion.

2.14.3.3 Proactiveness

A business's proactiveness is its proclivity to launch new services and products as well as its capacity to make timely judgements regarding whether or not to offer new services or products. Similarly, Lumpkin and Dess (1996) assert that the ability of entrepreneurs to predict and seek opportunities by taking the initiative and engaging in emerging or new markets is referred to as "*proactiveness*." According to Keh et al. (2007), it is a characteristic of aggressive and proactive techniques used to shape and modify the external business environment in which they operate by anticipating future demand and staying ahead of the competition by introducing new services or products. In a similar vein, Dess and Lumpkin (2005) stated that factors such as predicting emerging problems, examining trends, anticipating changes in demand, or customers' future demands are not sufficient for a firm to be proactive; rather, they need to take action or act on new knowledge before their rivals. Therefore, adopting a proactive approach to align with the successful initiatives of pioneers can lead to a competitive advantage. Likewise, Mandawa (2016) implies that in terms of improving a firm's performance, the proactiveness dimension is more critical, particularly at the embryonic stage of a

firm's growth. Similarly, Hughes and Morgan (2007) assert that awareness of customer needs and responding to market signals are two characteristics of proactive firms. Anticipating the moves of competitors is another major advantage of proactive firms, thus maintaining a first-mover advantage (Lechner and Gudmundsson, 2014). Nevertheless, in order to put into effect a proactive strategy that may result in internal development and expansion of the enterprise, careful monitoring and scanning of the environment is essential (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005). Although proactive enterprises are known to be industry leaders because they move to take advantage of new opportunities and being proactive is closely linked to being innovative (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996), a competitive edge is not always guaranteed to industry leaders because launching new services or products may not yield the expected return (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005). Yet, some scholars (Hughes and Morgan, 2007; Wang and Yen, 2012) found a strong positive link between SME performance and proactiveness, while others (Nasution et al., 2011) found a strong link between proactiveness and innovation.

2.14.4 Entrepreneurial Competencies (Firm-Level Construct)

Entrepreneurs in small firms retain resources that are a unique mix of personal skills that are critical for venture well-being (Bamiatzi et al., 2015). An entrepreneur's significant role played in small firms implies that the failure or success of the enterprise is contingent on their abilities (Ibidunni et al., 2021; Lerner and Sigal, 2001). In recent years, there has been a significant shift in the focus of entrepreneurship research towards a competency-based approach to assessing business success. According to Man and Lau (2005), the entrepreneurial competency approach is the most contemporary method for examining how entrepreneurs' behaviour influences the success of firms. This response addresses the limitations of trait-based theories and their approaches. It is highlighted that traits like "the need for achievement" and "internal locus of control" among business owners have not demonstrated robust support for their impact on venture success, as indicated by studies (Baum et al., 2001; Tehseen and Ramayah, 2015). Since the inception of the competency approach, numerous scholars have used it to investigate the venture success criteria of an entrepreneur (see, e.g., Ahmad et al., 2017; Mandawa, 2016; Solesvik, 2012).

Various research has proffered several definitions for what constitutes "competency," leading to confusion and thereby representing a major challenge in the competency literature. Therefore, the genuine significance of the concept of competency has led to confusion. The terms "*competence*" and "*competency*" are frequently used interchangeably, despite the scholars' acknowledgement of them as two distinct concepts. Competence, as defined by Rowe (1995), is a standard or skill of performance, whereas behaviour that leads to performance being accomplished is acknowledged as competency. It is noteworthy that differences exist between acquired and innate competencies (Silverstein, 2019). Attitudes, traits, social roles, and self-image are all examples of innate competencies and are sometimes referred to as "internalised elements," whereas practical and theoretical learning acquired through education or work, i.e., knowledge, skills, and experience, are examples of acquired competencies and

are frequently referred to as "externalised elements" (Saeed, 2012). Man and Lau (2005) opine that it is "nearly impossible to change" the internalised aspects. However, through intervention programmes and their continued practice, i.e., education and training, the externalised elements can be achieved. When considering SMEs, particularly the manager/owner of a venture, these competencies (externalised elements) are often treated and studied as characteristics of entrepreneurs (McGregor and Tweed, 2001).

The originating theories and related competency approach emanate from management studies and view skills and competencies as a cluster needed by a manager for carrying out certain duties. In this way, close ties can be evident in the literature where there is a strong link between other fields and the competency literature, such as management and leadership competencies (Mitchelmore and Rowley, 2010). Therefore, the entrepreneurial competency concept can be tracked back to groups of literature originating from "entrepreneurship," "competency," and "competence." Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010) conducted a comprehensive literature analysis and discovered that multiple studies in various contexts over the last two decades have attempted to create a list of entrepreneurial competencies. According to them, this has resulted in the emergence of several models and entrepreneurial competencies lists with varying degrees of classification. For instance, terminology like "expertise" or "skills" has been embraced by some academics, yet overall they all add to the discipline of entrepreneurial competencies. As a result, the entrepreneurial competencies concept has been described in various yet similar ways (Ahmad et al., 2010; Mitchelmore and Rowley, 2010; Mandawa, 2016). Most notably, Baum et al. (2001) portray competencies as characteristics of an individual like skills, knowledge, and/or abilities needed to perform a specific job, whereas Bird (2019) widens the entrepreneurial competencies perspective and defines them as the underlying characteristics such as generic and specific knowledge, skills, traits, motives, social role, and self-images that bring about a firm's birth, survival, or growth. In recognition, Kiggundu (2002) asserts that entrepreneurial competencies are clusters of entrepreneur attributes, including skills and expertise, knowledge, personality, talents, beliefs, attitudes, and behavioural tendencies that are aimed at achieving sustainable and successful enterprise. EC, as defined by Inyang and Enuoh (2009), is a cluster of related phenomena like the skills, attitudes, knowledge, and abilities of individual characteristics needed to perform a specific task and can be attained through managerial training and development. Similarly, Hunt (1988) claims that several factors, including an individual's self-concept, personality, traits, skills, knowledge, and motivation, are functions of competent behaviour. Likewise, within the context of SMEs, Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010) provide another intriguing conceptualisation, reporting that an entrepreneur's capabilities and those of his or her collaborators in using, acquiring, and developing successful resources for his or her business purpose depend on the specific context in which the firms operate. It is important to note the two distinct features of entrepreneurial competency highlighted by Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010), which researchers should be mindful of: first, competencies can be acquired, indicating individuals may not inherently possess them, and second, these competencies vary

based on the situation and context, including geographical location, gender, or culture. Within the present study context, the latter feature is of particular interest because it implies that there may be disparities in how venture performance can be related to entrepreneurial competencies in non-Western nations (the context of this study) and in Western nations (where numerous studies have been conducted). In addition, the author observes that an individual's background, such as social role, personality, self-image, and traits, are all components of entrepreneurial competencies and that there may be an overlapping link between entrepreneurial competencies.

From the above discussion, it is obvious that within the competency literature, one of the major challenges is the prevalence of multiple competency definitions. As a result, in the literature, different operationalisations of entrepreneurial competence have been established. To illustrate, Baum et al. (2001) classified competencies into two categories, namely, specific and general competencies. Here, specific competencies are referred to as industry-specific knowledge and technological know-how skills needed to run a business, whereas general management skills, which are not industry-specific, are said to be general competencies such as exercising authority, oral presentation, and decision-making. Following extensive literature research, Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010) adopted a broader perspective and produced the following list of competencies by analysing the entire literature that were assessed by various academics to be significant for business owners: management skills, comprising organisational and coordination skills and the ability to develop management systems, analytical and conceptual competencies, comprising the ability to coordinate activities, idea generation, motivation and delegation skills, customer management skills, commitment and leadership skills, decision-making skills, hiring skills, opportunity recognition includes exploiting and formulating strategies and the ability to take advantage of opportunities.

In their summary of the role of an entrepreneur, Ahmad et al. (2010) say that a business owner should be competent in a wide range of areas, such as strategy, opportunities, concepts, and learning. On the other hand, Man et al. (2002) introduce a competency approach that focuses on the process or behavioural aspect of firms. EC, as considered by them, are high-level characteristics comprising knowledge, skills, and personality traits and are therefore viewed as an entrepreneur's overall ability to perform a job successfully. Man et al. (2002) identified six components of EC, namely organising, opportunity, strategic, conceptual, relationship, and commitment. For the present study, the adoption of this competency approach is based on the fact that it comprises competencies mostly proposed by other researchers and also because of its comprehensiveness. Another reason for adopting the Man et al. (2002) competency dimensions is that they were found to have an effect on a venture's performance, either directly or indirectly (Mitchelmore and Rowley, 2010). For the purposes of this research, the EC will be defined by Man et al. (2002). These definitions are shown in Table 2.3 below.

Table 2. 3 Competency Domain Definitions

<i>Entrepreneurial Competencies</i>	<i>Definition</i>
<i>Commitment Competencies</i>	Competencies that make the entrepreneur want to move the business forward by taking the initiative and taking on more responsibilities at work.
<i>Opportunity Competencies</i>	Those competencies that are associated with locating and creating market opportunities through a variety of different means.
<i>Relationship Competencies</i>	The ability to communicate well with both internal and external stakeholders on an individual-to-group or person-to-person basis, e.g., employees, suppliers, customers, includes the ability to have effective communication, persuasion, and relationship-building skills, which are essential to build relationships that will be advantageous.
<i>Organising Competencies</i>	Those competencies that pertain to the management of a variety of resources, including those that are human, technological, external, internal, financial, and physical resources.
<i>Strategic Competencies</i>	Those competencies that are necessary for formulating, analysing, and putting into action the company's various strategies.
<i>Conceptual Competencies</i>	The ability to think cognitively and analytically in order to arrive at decisions and find solutions to issues.

Source: Adapted from Mandawa (2016)

Nevertheless, there is a problem with the application of the competency approach in entrepreneurship research. This criticism is based on the premise that entrepreneurs and managers may not require the same set of skills in order to operate their enterprises successfully, as it is commonly acknowledged that entrepreneurs require a more diverse collection of skills than managers do (Alvarez and Busenitz, 2001). However, Man et al. (2002), on the other hand, say that because a business owner is both an entrepreneur and a manager, they need both entrepreneurial and managerial skills to run a business successfully.

Despite its importance, scholars (Brinckmann, 2008; Mitchelmore and Rowley, 2010) note that the discussion of entrepreneurial competencies in the entrepreneurship literature is still in its infancy. In particular, Mitchelmore and Rowley (2010) say that research examining the competencies and skills of business owners is not only context-dependent but also scarce, with only a few concentrating on female owned enterprises. Hence, there have been calls for additional studies to be conducted in this area for the purpose of gaining additional statistical validation.

2.14.5 Performance Measure in SMEs

In small business research, the topic of performance measurement is of particular importance. This is because it enables business practitioners and researchers to explore or investigate ways in which these small enterprises can be further developed, as they account for the majority of jobs in most nations and make a meaningful contribution to the economy. Mandawa (2016) notes that the bulk of studies on performance measures stem from strategic management research and organisational theory. From a strategic perspective, performance is frequently viewed as a firm's success or failure. Even though there

isn't a general agreement on what "success" means or how to measure it in business (Ahmad and Seet, 2009), success is often linked to reaching its goals and objectives, no matter how it is looked at.

Performance, according to the Oxford English Dictionary, is the process or act of carrying out a function or task (Khan and Ramachandran, 2012). Simpson et al. (2012) viewed performance as "the result of any action or the outcome of any activity," while Ensley (2014, p. 5) viewed performance as "the ability to create wealth." Similarly, Ermolayev and Matzke (2007, p. 391) conceptualised performance as "the number or series of activities directed towards an outcome." This means that there is general agreement on the concept of measuring and analysing performance as a multi-dimensional variable involving many different variables (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996; Rauch et al., 2009; Simpson et al., 2012; Wasim, 2021). In the same way, academic research (Chandler and Hanks, 1993; Haber and Reichel, 2007; Miller, 2011; Vij and Bedi, 2016) recommends using both subjective and objective performance measures, especially when studying small businesses.

In terms of measuring performance, the literature identifies three major streams, such as organisational, financial, and strategic (Peng, 2011, p. 38). Within the organisational stream, three fundamental approaches are recognised for measuring performance: the multiple consistency approach, the system approach, and the goal-based approach. While the multiple consistency approach addresses the interests of diverse stakeholders in evaluating company performance and overcomes the weaknesses of the other two approaches, it may not be suitable for small firms due to their uniquely close operational nature (Murphy et al., 1996). The financial stream centres around the traditional accounting-based approach, which comprises dimensions like profitability and sales growth rate. In contrast to the financial and organisational streams, the strategic stream not only incorporates multiple constituencies beyond performance assessment but also includes operational and financial performance (such as market share and product quality) (Murphy et al., 1996; Peng, 2011). In a similar vein, scholars have alerted researchers that when developing the performance construct, if studies adopt a narrow range or single dimension (e.g., multiple profitability indicators), it can result in misleading normative or descriptive theory development (Lumpkin and Dess, 1999; Agca et al., 2012). This means that studies should employ measurement constructs that have both financial and nonfinancial indicators, which entail all aspects of business performance, to better explain the findings.

In the literature on entrepreneurship, the performance construct is often operationalised by metrics including firm growth (market share, annual sales volume, number of employees), profitability (ROI, profit, etc.), and survival or business volume (Haber and Reichel, 2007; Agca et al., 2012; Simpson et al., 2012; Boso et al., 2013). In prior studies, researchers often employed performance indicators such as annual revenue, sales growth, sales return, number of employees, and employee growth (Zin and Manaf, 2019, p. 213). Rauch et al. (2009) conducted a meta-analysis and found that there was no difference between archival financial performance, perceived non-financial performance, and financial

performance. Yet, in empirical research, the incorporation of both financial and non-financial indicators has been highlighted and suggested as a measure of performance (Rauch et al., 2009; Agca et al., 2012; Simpson et al., 2012). This is because the business management and performance literature, according to Vij and Bedi (2016), shows no consensus among scholars in terms of performance assessment since a variety of objective and subjective forms of measurement have been utilised.

Scholars confront a major challenge in measuring the performance of small businesses. There is a wide range of performance indicators employed in entrepreneurship research, which makes cross-study comparability more difficult (e.g., Murphy et al., 1996; Agca et al., 2012). Similarly, the absence of historical data, source bias, inconsistent record-keeping, business owners reluctance to disclose objective facts and figures, and the level of diversity used in performance measurement all contribute to the list of obstacles associated with obtaining small firms' performance information. Based on the above discussion, it is obvious that acquiring and accessing performance data for small firms is a challenging endeavour.

The present study employed subjective measures of firm performance for three reasons. First, subjective measures have been adopted by numerous scholars in examining firm performance (see, e.g., Ahmad et al., 2010; Agca et al., 2012; Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014; Fuentes-Fuentes et al., 2015). Secondly, in Pakistan, there is a dearth of statistics and official data on female entrepreneurship as well as manipulation of the data, as the data on female led firms is relatively restricted (Rehman and Roomi, 2012) and, thirdly, subjective measures are justifiable (Vij and Bedi, 2016). In addition, this study adopted the established measures to ensure data reliability and validity.

2.15 Linking Individual-Level and Firm-Level Constructs

In contrast to the model proposed by Lumpkin and Dess (1996), which focuses on firms rather than individuals level, numerous entrepreneurship studies concentrate on constructs at the individual level, such as an entrepreneur's learning, traits, or human capital, and their influence on performing the tasks inherent to entrepreneurial business. The simultaneous examination of both individual-level and firm-level characteristics is rare, thereby losing the richness that both have to offer.

The conceptual model underlying this research is depicted in Figure 3.1. In summary, individual human capital components are expected to influence entrepreneurial competencies, subsequently driving entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and enhancing firm performance. Similarly, entrepreneurial competencies are anticipated to impact the three components of EO. In turn, EO, entrepreneurial competencies, and learning orientation (LO) are predicted to drive overall firm performance.

2.16 Summary

The purpose of this chapter is to reflect on various entrepreneurship theories and models employed by scholars in understanding the firm performances of female entrepreneurship. This chapter begins by defining entrepreneurship, followed by a review of various motivational aspects of females to start a

firm, and a critical review of female-owned firms in the emerging economy, precisely in relation to South Asian nations. Following an extensive review of female entrepreneurship in general and Pakistan in particular, it becomes evident that the situation in Pakistan not only diverges from Western nations but also differs from other developing countries. The prevailing patriarchal forces in Pakistani society ensure the subordinate status of women to men, irrespective of the female's region or class.

This chapter also delves into factors affecting performance in SMEs in general and female entrepreneurship in particular. An extensive amount of literature suggests that factors impacting SMEs' performance can be categorised into three main groups: individual-related factors, firm-related factors, and environmental factors. Nevertheless, individual-level and firm-level factors are identified as having the most influence on SMEs' performance, while external factors predominantly affect larger firms. Entrepreneurs act as guardians, enabling the internal resources of the organisation to be utilised in order to achieve organisational success. Hence, SME performance and growth are heavily dependent on the role of an entrepreneur. Similarly, examination of factors influencing female enterprises and their performance reveals that empirical studies often do not differentiate firm owners by gender, treating them in a generalised sense when examining the relationship between performance and capabilities among entrepreneurs. The chapter also provides details on various entrepreneurship theories, including economic, psychological, sociological, and anthropological theories, and explains why they were not adopted in the present study.

Likewise, an analysis of various firm performance models is conducted to identify key determinants of women entrepreneurs' firm performance. Consequently, six firm performance models are analysed, and based on the research gap, shortcomings in the literature, and existing models, four firm performance factors are derived: human capital, entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, and entrepreneurial competencies, to measure the performance of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan. Human capital and learning orientation are viewed as individual-level constructs, while firm-level constructs include three components of EO (proactiveness, risk-taking, and innovativeness) and six sets of competencies (organisation, relationship, commitment, strategy, conceptual, and opportunity). The study adopts the resource-based view as the theoretical foundation underpinning the proposed conceptual framework. The next chapter exclusively focuses on building relationships among the constructs and hypotheses for the current study.

Chapter Three: Conceptual Framework

3.1 An Overview

This chapter provides a visual representation of a conceptual framework illustrating individual-level and firm-level factors that impact the performance of SMEs owned by women. As mentioned in the preceding chapter, the conceptual framework is founded on human capital components, learning orientation, entrepreneurial orientation, and the competency approach. Section 3.2 delves into the academic advancements regarding the relationships among human capital, entrepreneurial competencies, entrepreneurial orientation, and learning orientation. Following this, a summary of the chapter and the conceptual framework of the study is presented in Section 3.3.

3.2 Hypothesis Development

After reviewing the literature and based on the research objectives, several hypotheses are articulated. The following section discusses the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial competencies, learning orientation, and female firm performance.

3.2.1 Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Competencies

EC is understood to encompass numerous factors, and all can be traced back to a common source. Hence, one can argue that empirical data bears witness to the fact that they are certainly connected to competencies. One such example is Man and Lau's (2005) comprehensive analysis, which identified two similar yet distinct sources of EC: first, an entrepreneur's background characteristics (e.g., self-image, attitude, personality, traits, and social role); and second, practical or theoretical learning combined with work experience (e.g., skills, knowledge, and experience). Individual character and personality, which are aspects of internal attributes, fall under the former category, whereas the latter category is external attributes, aspects that an entrepreneur can obtain by means of learning and training (Sae, 2012, p. 83) and are the focus of the present study. Along these lines, Bird (2019) contends that factors such as education, industry-specific experience, and prior work experience should be evaluated, as they hold the potential to foster entrepreneurial competencies. She elaborates that due to the behavioural nature of EC, they are not only acquirable but can be refined over time through appropriate training and development. This perspective finds support in several additional studies. For instance, Umar et al. (2019) and Mandawa (2016) found a positive and significant effect of EC on level of education. Similarly, Krueger and Brazeal (1994) submit that an entrepreneur's perceived competencies and their ability to exploit or recognise opportunities are enhanced by prior work experience. In these lines, Haynes (2003) asserts that an entrepreneur's understanding and knowledge of industry and the business environment are enhanced by education, thereby polishing the capabilities and skills of an entrepreneur. In addition, Segal et al. (2010) contend that entrepreneurs have the capabilities and competencies to produce results if they possess a synergistic, potent combination of industry managerial experience and education. Likewise, Man and Lau (2005) found that EC can be derived from a combination of work and practical or theoretical learning, i.e., experience, skills, and knowledge. It is

worth noting that research into the EC's antecedents is scarce. Drawing on the above argument, the present study developed the following hypothesis:

H1a: Level of education positively contributes to the development of entrepreneurial competencies.

H1b: Previous work experience positively contributes to the development of entrepreneurial competencies.

H1c: Business training positively contributes to the development of entrepreneurial competencies.

3.2.2 Entrepreneurial Competencies and Firm Performance

A significant relationship between firms' performance and EC has been generally reported in empirical studies, while a few (Ahmad et al., 2010) assert that in SMEs, EC acts as a key driver of success. To illustrate, studies indicate that EC are essential indicators of firm success and growth, particularly as they relate to profitability. Empirical evidence has shown the impact of EC on the performance of a business in particular. For instance, a positive relationship was reported by Aftab et al. (2021) and Pulka et al. (2021) between EC and firm performance. A broader perspective was taken by Bolarinwa and Okolocha (2016), who viewed EC as creative thinking and interpersonal skills that can not only enhance firm performance but also serve as critical strategic opportunities for organisations. An organisation's sustainable performance and competitive advantage can be attributed to these intangible yet valuable capabilities (Peric et al., 2017). A study by Baum et al. (2001) found general competencies like opportunity and organisational skills of CEOs to be indirectly affecting business performance, while technical and industry skills had a significant direct association with business performance. Studies have also empirically revealed that EC influences firm growth. For instance, Dawa et al. (2021) and Chandler and Hanks (1994) found a direct correlation between the EC and firm growth. Similarly, Ahmad et al. (2010) examined the environmental influence on the EC and business success and discovered that, in addition to the direct association, the impact of the EC on firm success was less in a stable and benign environment than in a hostile and dynamic one. Other variables, like the context in which firms operate (Capaldo et al., 2004) and a firm's stages of development (Gasse et al., 1997), have been found to influence the relationship between firm success and entrepreneurial competencies. Based on the literature, it is proposed that:

H2: The entrepreneurial competencies have a positive and direct effect on firm performance

3.2.3 Entrepreneurial Orientation, Entrepreneurial Competencies and Firm Performance

Many studies (e.g., Covin and Wales, 2018; Lumpkin et al., 2009) have portrayed EO as a good indicator of entrepreneurial behaviour. Similarly, numerous studies indicate that EO improves performance, thus advocating a significant and strong association between firms' performance and EO (Fuentes-Fuentes et al., 2015; Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014; Rauch et al., 2009). Nevertheless, multiple studies produce inconclusive or mixed outcomes (Su et al., 2011; Tang et al., 2008; Wiklund

and Shepherd, 2005). For instance, Zahra (1993) found that EO is disadvantageous towards higher business performance in terms of growth, survival, and profitability but contributes potentially to non-financial gains and firms' capital, thereby having a direct effect on achieving a competitive advantage. Similarly, a positive relationship between firm performance and EO dimensions was highlighted by Lee and Chu (2013), particularly in a dynamic environment. On the contrary, a few scholars (e.g., Mandawa, 2016; Hart, 1992) reported a negative influence between EO and firms' performance, while others (e.g., Runyan et al., 2008; Stam and Elfring, 2008) did not find an association between the two constructs.

The EO of a firm is said to be characterised by the entrepreneur's role, their personality, and their competencies (Camuffo et al., 2012). Wales et al. (2011) revealed that a substantial amount of research into the antecedents of EO addressed the characteristics of the top management team and the CEO as potential EO antecedents. This means that, despite scholars' consensus on the relationship between the EO and firm performance, additional factors need to be incorporated to obtain the desired outcome, as inherited innovative capacity and risk-taking ability do not guarantee success (Courrent et al., 2018). Furthermore, Soininen et al. (2013) argue that EO can be an individual-level product instead of a determinant of firm-level outcomes. This notion illustrates how the characteristics of the entrepreneur play a part in the relationship between EO and performance. Similarly, a variety of competencies and resources are needed for implementing any competitive strategy (Lechner and Gudmundsson, 2014). This aspect is of significant relevance because EO is defined by innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness, which are considered top managers' strategies (Poon et al., 2006). Yet, in the strategy literature, the characteristics of top management have been empirically related to numerous facets of strategy, including innovation strategy. Similarly, the mediating influences have been explicitly investigated in recent literature in the EO and performance relationship, such as knowledge integration and market orientation (Karami and Tang, 2019). However, there is a lack of empirical studies suggesting a mediating relationship between EO in EC and firm performance, yet Poon et al. (2006) and Baum et al. (2001) found empirical evidence that the relationship between personality traits and firm performance is mediated by competitive strategy. Likewise, Aftab et al. (2021) found support that EC mediates the relationship between EO and firm performance. Traits affect competencies, as per Baum et al. (2001), since people practice what they enjoy, and this in turn enhances their skills. Based on the above argument, it is proposed that:

H3: Entrepreneurial competencies positively contributes to entrepreneurial orientation.

H4: Entrepreneurial orientation positively contributes to firm performance.

H5: Entrepreneurial orientation mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and firm performance.

3.2.4 Entrepreneurial Competencies and Learning Orientation

The ability of an entrepreneur to facilitate learning is directly related to their competencies. However, few scholars have paid attention to the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and learning orientation, yet studies have found that a focus on individual learning orientation can enhance commitment, competence, knowledge, and motivation (Jha and Bhattacharyya, 2013; Gong et al., 2009). There are many distinct roles that entrepreneurs must play to run a successful business in a fast-changing and dynamic environment. Beaver and Jennings (2005) identified two key roles that are considered important for a business owner, namely entrepreneurial and managerial. Kungwansupaphan and Siengthai (2014) found that business owners' entrepreneurial competency and managerial competence have a positive effect on learning orientation. Scholars assert that entrepreneurs who are competent can put learning into practice in their current situation (Man, 2006; Man and Lau, 2000). For entrepreneurs in resource-constrained countries, taking on the entrepreneurial role requires them to be exposed to the rapidly changing and uncertain nature of the business environment. As a result, entrepreneurs perceive continuous learning as essential for their firms' growth and survival in such an environment. This realisation motivates them to prioritise learning and establish a learning orientation within their enterprises. According to Kungwansupaphan and Siengthai (2014), a firm with a learning orientation is the consequence of the entrepreneur's managerial skills, since they play a crucial role in establishing an organisational system suited to allow continuous learning activities. Therefore, this study proposes the following:

H6: Entrepreneurial competencies positively influence learning orientation.

3.2.5 Learning Orientation and Firm Performance

Entrepreneurs must adapt, respond, and stay oriented towards learning to remain competitive. Since learning is related to the processing of complex information and the absorption of new knowledge emanating from hypercompetitive environments, the impact of LO on firm performance, in most instances, is found to be empirically positive. For instance, Calantone et al. (2002) investigated the relationship between LO, business performance, and business innovation, revealing that LO plays a vital role in both business performance and innovation. A study focusing on small manufacturing companies was conducted by Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006), where they observed a positive relationship between LO and the current firm's performance. This conclusion, meanwhile, was moderately supported, making it inconclusive. As a result, additional research is suggested to determine the impact of LO on performance. In a similar vein, Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014) investigated the effect of LO on female entrepreneurship in Mexico and confirmed a positive association between both constructs. Likewise, both forms of learning, i.e., acquisitive and generative learning, were found to positively contribute to firm performance (Gupta et al., 2020). It follows that firms that learn from their surroundings are better able to respond to market shifts and enhance the quality of their goods and services than their rivals (Lonial and Carter, 2015). Based on the above literature, it is proposed that:

H7: Learning orientation has a direct and positive effect on firm performance.

3.3 Summary

The study introduces hypotheses and explores the relationships between various constructs. Specifically, human capital components such as education attainment, business training, and previous work experience act as antecedents of EC. The entrepreneurial competencies construct influences both EO and LO in the study. Likewise, entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial competencies, and learning orientation constructs can influence the firm performance of female entrepreneurs. Figure 3.1 illustrates the conceptual model presented in the study. The upcoming chapter will provide a summary of the research approaches used in data collection and analysis for the study.

Figure 3. 1 The Proposed Conceptual Framework

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

4.1 An Overview

Finding the right approach for a study is one of the most important and challenging aspects of any research study. This chapter discusses the adopted paradigm, research methodology, and data collection methods employed in meeting the aim and objective of the study. The chapter is divided as follows: The research paradigm and research approach are discussed in Sections 4.2 and 4.3. Research design, research strategy, and quantitative data collection methods are elaborated in Sections 4.4, 4.5, and 4.6, respectively. Section 4.7 explains the methods of quantitative data collection, while Section 4.8 covers the necessity for additional investigation, followed by methods of qualitative data collection in Section 4.9. Finally, ethical considerations and a chapter summary are given in Sections 4.10 and 4.11.

4.2 Research Philosophy/Paradigm

The researcher's worldview is mirrored in his or her research philosophy, which includes a number of important assumptions. Appropriate knowledge development of research philosophy is vital, particularly its underlying assumptions, as it can significantly affect the quality of research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). Each philosophy is often referred to as a paradigm. The term "paradigm" refers to an investigator's philosophical way of thinking or his worldview, which later guides the investigator in research data interpretation (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Denzin and Lincoln (2017) describe three aspects of a paradigm, namely: ontology (the nature of reality), epistemology (how that reality becomes known), and methodology (certain methods or processes to achieve knowledge of reality). Different research paradigms and the rationale behind adopting a certain paradigm are discussed in this section.

4.2.1 Ontology Stance

Ontology focuses on the "nature of reality." Research conducted under an ontology assumption shapes the way we study or see our research objectives (Saunders et al., 2023). To illustrate, Hatch (2018) asked their study participants to describe their view of reality while researching the concept of ontology. The study participants, depending on their experience, describe reality differently as "objective" or "subjective." The objectivist ontology shares the view that social reality exists independent of human interpretation, conceptions, or social actors and is associated with the positivist approach. Whereas subjectivism shares the view of multiple context-specific realities, which are constructed through human interactions, perceptions, and social actors or actions of observers. Moreover, subjectivism is linked with an interpretivism or constructivism approach (Koporcic and Tornroos, 2019).

4.2.2 Epistemology Stance

This stance pays attention to the knowledge that is considered necessary to be acceptable in a particular field of study (Saunders et al., 2023). Hence, it addresses "what forms the basis of our knowledge and how we can learn about reality" and is concerned with "ways of learning and knowing about the world" (Ritchie et al., 2014). Multiple enquiries exist in terms of paradigms or epistemological positions, and

one way of distinguishing them is by understanding the epistemological elements of one's paradigm in relation to epistemological, ontological, and methodological positions (Otoo, 2020), which are as follows:

- Epistemological position: What is the association between the subject and the observer (inquirer) and what can be knowable?
- Ontological position: What is the form and nature of reality and what can be known about it?
- Methodological position: How could the inquirer continue to discover what they believe can be known?

The present study embraces a positivist epistemology; nevertheless, two other important alternate paradigms of inquiry are pragmatism and interpretivism (Wilson, 2014).

4.2.3 Rationale Behind the Chosen Paradigm

Literature in the wide field of entrepreneurship served as the foundation for the current study's focus on four main theoretical perspectives: entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, human capital, and competency approach. These theoretical perspectives find their roots in multiple disciplines, including psychology, organisational theory, strategic management, and management literature, thus embracing various epistemological positions. However, the traditional paradigmatic approach to small firms has mainly been positivist (Mandawa, 2016). The positivistic approach has also been adopted in the current study's epistemological perspective. The investigator in the present study is unaffected by the subject under investigation and portrays social reality objectively (Bryman and Bell, 2015). The nature of entrepreneurial research, particularly entrepreneurial behaviours, is the main reason for adopting a positivistic epistemological perspective. The exploration of entrepreneurial behaviour is grounded in psychological metrics, and to get a complete picture of entrepreneurial behaviour, a general pattern of regularities is needed that requires the use of quantitative methods (Rahman, 2017). Furthermore, few of the constructs (e.g., the competencies of an entrepreneur and the concept of EO and LO) used in the present study have used questionnaires from prior research, which are also positivist in nature. Thus, adopting a positivist approach allows the researcher to keep up with the comparability of previous research.

The researcher is of the opinion that these variables are capable of being empirically quantified, that is, looking at evaluating the direct effect of EC, EO, and LO on a firm's performance, and that this measure needs to be comparable across different industries, sectors, and businesses. The researcher believes in the natural existence of firms' EO, LO, and entrepreneur competencies. However, female entrepreneurs' perceptions are used to measure those variables. The investigator holds the view that the actual firm's EO, LO, EC, and human capital are not products of the female entrepreneur's mind. For example, every

female entrepreneur may have an entirely distinct perception of the EO level of their business, but the fact is that the level of EO is only one at a certain value. In this study, the viewpoint of female entrepreneurs is used solely to measure the variables' values and not to create those values.

The present study aims at understanding individual and firm-level constructs, i.e., EO, EC, LO, and human capital, affecting the performance of female-owned firms in Pakistan. The researcher examines reality through an objective lens of the behaviour of institutional and social actors, i.e., independent of institutions and social actors. The conceptual framework proposed in this study is built on prior studies and uses statistical methods to test it empirically. The aforementioned constructs are investigated using hypotheses based on existing literature and a conceptual framework. According to Collis and Hussey (2014), the positivism approach favours reliability and validity as a way of investigating phenomena in an objective manner. As a result, the positivist paradigm is an adequate philosophical paradigm for the current investigation.

4.3 Research Approach

According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), research approaches can be characterised as plans and procedures for conducting research that span the steps from broad assumptions to specific approaches to data gathering, analysis, and interpretation. Deciding on an appropriate research approach is crucial for addressing philosophical inquiries regarding the nature of reality. The principles used to select the approach are based on the methods that are commonly used for information collection, the factors of interest in the inquiry, reasonable considerations (time, money, and access), and the type of information required to answer the examination questions. The present research focuses on female entrepreneurship, entrepreneurial behaviours, and firm performance. Ghauri et al. (2020) suggest a subjective approach is ideal for behavioural studies, such as taking the participant's prior knowledge into account. However, care should be taken in selecting an appropriate philosophical stance and research approach. Therefore, prior to data collection, the chosen approach and research design are defined by the degree of clarity regarding the theory. Research approaches can be categorised into two types, namely "*Inductive*" and "*Deductive*" reasoning.

4.3.1 Deductive Approach

This strategy makes use of scientific reasoning and puts forth the testing hypotheses that were developed based on the literature review. Deductive reasoning typically begins with the formulation of a question or an overarching theory that requires testing. Data is gathered by the researcher related to a topic of interest, and hypotheses are formulated that are tested or examined quantitatively to revalidate the theory (Bryman, 2016). The creation of a hypothesis should allow variables to be measured or testable, thereby allowing the hypothesis to be either rejected or confirmed. Through the use of this method, researchers are able to define the link between the variables that have been examined and determine whether or not those results need to be modified (Keith, 2014).

4.3.2 Inductive Approach

The use of inductive reasoning is most often associated with qualitative research. An inductive method should be utilised if there is a requirement for multi-perspective and in-depth investigations into a human or social issue. This is so that the findings can be presented. The researcher will collect data by making detailed or precise observations (for example, by conducting interviews) and then use data analysis to construct a theory (Bryman, 2016). Due to the greater number of complicated factors that are involved in this process, there is some degree of uncertainty involved (Keith, 2014). This approach is based on the presumption that the foundation for acquiring new knowledge is science, which derives from observation (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

The present study centres on investigating the causal relationship between the research variables, making it most aligned with an explanatory mixed-method design. When investigating the relationship between latent variables, this study embraced a positivist-deductive approach. However, with the adoption of an exploratory mixed-method approach, both quantitative (deductive-hypothetical testing) and qualitative (inductive) research methodologies are utilised. The rationale for adopting an explanatory mixed-method design lies in its substantial positive impact on result validity. It aids in organising and supporting the results, ensuring that each method reinforces the other, thus ensuring that the results are an accurate reflection of the situation that is current in the study sample and in the society, they are part of (Kumar, 2014).

4.4 Research Design

Research design, as depicted by Kumar (2014), is a "road map" that aids in achieving findings and conclusions by linking empirical data to research questions and research objectives. Throughout the research process, research design guides an investigator to collect, interpret, report, and analyse research findings (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017).

Research designs are typically articulated as "*Exploratory, Descriptive and Experimental design*" (Sreejesh et al., 2014). Exploratory design is required when the phenomenon under study has little information or is little known. It is featured as the starting point for constructing a theory. This design is flexible in nature, aiming at explaining an uncertain situation with the focus of getting an insight into a phenomenon or discovering new ideas. However, this approach's major drawback is that it generally does not offer a decisive outcome due to its initial conceptualisation and unstructured basis, which have not been explored by previous scholars (Jebb et al., 2017). Descriptive studies, as opposed to exploratory studies, are more formal and generally structured with clearly defined hypotheses or investigative questions. A research gap is found in the literature, and through the guidance of the existing theory, distinctive research questions are formed to address the research gaps, i.e., to challenge, support, reject, or extend the existing theory (Gali, 2018).

An experimental design is generally linked to natural science research. Here, the theorist controls the study conditions, is aware of the effects and causes under study, and intends to find a causal relationship between variables. A descriptive method, on the contrary, is applied to depict the relationship between variables, particularly when the investigator has a well-structured and justified problem statement with a clearly defined hypothesis. The hypothesis developed paves the way for a greater understanding of the phenomenon and the research questions outlined (Blumberg et al., 2014).

The philosophical stance, the research question, and the objective of the research define the selection of an appropriate research design. In the current study, "***Descriptive Design***" is considered appropriate because the research is centred on describing the relationship and the effect of EC, EO, LO, and human capital on the performance of female entrepreneurship in Pakistan. Additionally, to achieve research objectives, a descriptive design can be structured to employ various methods, including surveys, interviews, and naturalistic observations, in different combinations (Sreejesh et al., 2014). In this research, employing a descriptive design, the researcher utilised a survey and an interview strategy as the tools to address the research question and achieve the overarching objectives of the study. The current study has developed a conceptual framework with the inclusion of a clear outline of hypothesis development, and to answer the research questions, surveys and interviews were conducted with female entrepreneurs. Hence, adopting a descriptive design is considered an appropriate choice by the researcher. It is worth noting that experimental research design is uncommon in the social sciences (Gali, 2018). Furthermore, a cross-sectional time framework was used in the present study due to time restrictions and the cost of completing the study. The various research methodologies adopted in the present study are outlined in the following section.

4.5 Research Strategy

When conducting research, an important part is to have a precise plan to gather appropriate data to answer the research question. Therefore, clear guidance is illustrated in the research strategy about the tools and methods adopted to collect data and how an investigator intends to collect data, and this should be in agreement with the adopted research philosophy, paradigm, and research approach (Saunders et al., 2023). In the field of business and management studies, multiple research strategies are employed, such as surveys, ethnographies, grounded theories, experiments, action research, case studies, and longitudinal studies. Strategies like experiments and surveys lean towards positivism and deductive reasoning, while strategies like grounded theory and ethnography fall under interpretivism and deductive reasoning. Nonetheless, a few strategies, such as a case study, can be a part of both philosophical paradigms to a certain extent (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Considering the research aim, research objective, and research paradigm, this study employed a survey strategy, which is a non-experimental research method and a widely used approach that relies on questionnaires. The survey strategy is a common method in business research and is often associated with a deductive approach (Saunders et al., 2023).

4.6 Data Collection Methods

Two primary categories of data collection are commonly utilised: qualitative and quantitative methods. A multiple or mixed-method is also considered, which comprises both qualitative and quantitative elements. The qualitative method of data collection leans towards interpretivism and is considered an inductive approach. In terms of data collection and analysis, it emphasises words rather than quantification. This allows an investigator to get a deeper understanding of phenomena, i.e., explore and understand how groups or individuals see human or social issues (Saunders et al., 2023).

The quantitative research strategy of data collection leans towards positivism and considers a deductive approach (Antwi and Kasim, 2015). This method uses a sample of a large population to evaluate data by conducting statistical analysis. Theories are tested by analysing the relationship between variables to validate the data. The major strength of this method is that it can establish a causal relationship. Besides, this method is considered quantifiable, reliable, and repeatable (Sampathirao, 2016). Nevertheless, it is less useful for documenting participants' personal meanings and their internal perspectives about a new phenomenon or exploring new phenomena.

Because of the strengths and weaknesses inherent in qualitative and quantitative research, a mixed-method approach is gaining prominence in research practices. This strategy appears to enable the utilisation of diverse strengths while mitigating some of the associated weaknesses. Adopting a mixed-method approach would play a particularly important role in enhancing the study's reliability. As asserted by Leavy (2017), when the research objectives are to describe, evaluate, and explain the phenomenon being studied in great detail, a mixed-method approach should be employed. Moreover, mixed-method approaches have gained popularity, particularly when a single paradigm is unable to address the research questions (Timans et al., 2019).

Creswell and Creswell (2018) assert that the philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks are the driving force in the integration of a mixed-method approach involving both qualitative and quantitative data in the study. This integration is intended to provide additional insights, thereby enhancing the overall understanding of the research. Bryman (2016) categorised the mixed-method approach based on two main factors: dominance and sequence. Similarly, four main features are identified by Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) to understand the decisions and characteristics of mixed-method approaches, i.e., dominance (priority) of each method, purpose (or intent) for mixing, level of interaction between each strand, and sequencing of qualitative, quantitative, or simultaneously. Drawing on the above factors, Creswell and Plano Clark (2018) classified six mixed-methods designs: the embedded design, the explanatory sequential design, the exploratory sequential design, the convergent parallel design, the multiphase design, and the transformative design. Based on the study

philosophy, the present study is built within the methodological stance of the "*Sequential Explanatory Mixed-Method Approach*."

Hollstein (2014) identified two distinct phases of the mixed-methods sequential explanatory approach: a quantitative phase and a qualitative phase. At first, the quantitative data is gathered and examined by the researcher. Whereas the qualitative (text) data are gathered and examined second in the sequence to elaborate on or explain the outcome obtained from the quantitative phase. The qualitative phase follows the quantitative phase, connecting the study's intermediate stages. This approach is justified by the notion that quantitative data offer a general understanding of the research problem, while qualitative data refine and explain statistical results by delving into participants' views more deeply (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017).

The current study aims to develop a new model for female entrepreneurship performance in Pakistan. The strategy of the explanatory mixed-method approach is employed so that the results produced in the quantitative phase can be confirmed by employing a qualitative study. The second phase will be to refine and explain those statistical results in depth. The discussion of the study will be produced based on the quantitative and qualitative data findings of the study. The researcher is of the view that adopting a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach will enable capitalisation on the strengths and minimisation of the limitations inherent in both qualitative and quantitative approaches. This methodology is expected to yield more reliable results compared to employing a single-method study, whether purely quantitative or entirely qualitative, as it incorporates both statistical data and participant narratives.

Despite being widespread across various disciplines, mixed-methods research has received limited attention in entrepreneurship studies (Molina-Azorin et al., 2012), particularly in the context of female entrepreneurship research in developing countries (Correa et al., 2021). McDonald et al. (2015) acknowledge entrepreneurship as a field of inquiry. Yet, it was not until 1980 that scholars started to debate entrepreneurship as a separate discipline in its own right (Landstrom and Benner, 2010). Over time, entrepreneurship has grown into a significant field of study that looks into who, how, and what factors affect opportunities to create new services or goods that are found, evaluated, and used (Kiril, 2014, p. 101). To explore methodological issues, Coviello and Jones (2004) conducted a systematic literature assessment of 55 academic studies published between 1988 and 2002 on entrepreneurship. In a similar vein, Brush (1992) examined 55 published articles on women business owners and laid the path for future research in this field. A thorough evaluation of the literature on the relationship between gender and entrepreneurship was undertaken by Henry et al. (2016) across a 30-year period in order to uncover methodological approaches. The authors note that quantitative strategies, namely surveys, questionnaires, and the use of large industrial sample sizes, were found to be the predominant strategies, while qualitative studies ranked the least, as outlined in Table 4.1 below. Similarly, many studies have

analysed the literature on entrepreneurship to identify strategies used to answer business questions. Scholars such as Creswell and Plano Clark (2017) assert that mixed-methods approaches provide a better understanding of research problems than either approach alone.

In addition, McKim (2017) notes that the mixed-method approach enables scholars to engage in dynamic interaction with new practice in a highly applied subject, especially in the social sciences. While qualitative study findings are often challenging to generalise compared to the outcomes of quantitative studies, which may lack depth and understanding, incorporating a mixed-methods strategy can alleviate the limitations associated with relying solely on a single approach. Employing a mixed-methods strategy can address the limitations associated with relying solely on a single approach. Lastly, the adoption of a mixed-methods strategy can enhance the reliability and validity of research findings (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2017).

The current study aims to construct a conceptual framework that explores the behavioural aspects influencing the performance of female led firms in the Pakistani context. It utilises components such as learning orientation, entrepreneurial orientation, competency approach, and human capital to investigate their interrelationships. Additionally, the study adopts the resource-based view as its theoretical foundation. Employing a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach, the study seeks to not only gain a profound understanding of the investigated phenomenon but also to augment the reliability, validity, and generalisability of the findings.

Table 4. 1 Methodological Trends in Gender Based Entrepreneurship

	Topics	Sectors	Regions	Methodological approach	Type
Period I: 1983-1992 (n = 40 papers)	Women entrepreneurs' profiles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Age ▪ Marital status ▪ Education ▪ Experience ▪ Traits and attitudes 	Mainly: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Manufacturing ▪ Construction ▪ Banking (few papers) ▪ Service and retail sectors 	Articles have an Anglo-Saxon bias, with more than half the studies from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Most of the studies focused on one country ▪ United Kingdom ▪ United States 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Purposeful (5) ▪ Random (6) ▪ Convenience sampling (21) ▪ Purely qualitative (4 studies) ▪ Mixed-methods ▪ Quantitative 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exploratory ▪ Descriptive
Period II: 1993-2002 (n = 81 papers)	Dominant topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Entrepreneurship programs (1) ▪ Traits (2) ▪ Networking (2) ▪ Attitudes/intentions (4) ▪ Start-up processes, family and management practice. ▪ Performance (20 studies) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Services/ retail <p>Most of the studies didn't specify the type or sector of business studied.</p>	Papers are mainly: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ UK and US focused (52) Some studies have emerged from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Europe ▪ Asia ▪ Middle East ▪ Australasia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Convenience (3) ▪ Purposive (13) ▪ Random sampling (49) ▪ Quantitative (64 studies), with the balance being qualitative or mixed-method based 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exploratory (few) ▪ Descriptive ▪ Explanatory
Period III: 2003-2012 (n = 214 papers)	Dominant topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ethnic/ minority (17) ▪ Motivation (17) ▪ Performance (19) ▪ Finance (33 studies) Emerging topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Training and education ▪ Contextual influences ▪ Family and female entrepreneurial identity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Many studies are neither sector specified nor sectoral focussed. ▪ If specified than mainly focussed on services, manufacturing, or technology. 	Geographical focus on "three" with (n 108): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ United States ▪ United Kingdom ▪ Australasia ▪ Expansion to include regions like Africa and Sub-Sahara. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mixed-methods (31) ▪ Qualitative (73) ▪ Quantitative (110) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Descriptive ▪ Explanatory

Source: Adapted from Henry et al. (2016)

4.7 Methods for Quantitative Data Collection

As outlined in Section 4.5, a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach is employed, and, therefore, this study adopted both a quantitative and qualitative approach to get more insight into the phenomenon under investigation. The following section will elaborate on the data collection methods employed in the quantitative approach, followed by those adopted in the qualitative approach.

4.7.1 Survey Design

In the selection of the data collection instrument, the choice depends merely on time availability and the associated cost. Similarly, research questions, research objectives, and philosophical stance determine the methods of data collection. As the present study adopted a positivism paradigm with a deductive approach and sequential explanatory research design, a survey method was considered suitable to collect the cross-sectional data. Saunders et al. (2023) assert that the survey can be conducted in a number of ways, such as through the mail, phone meetings, computer-mediated media like the internet, fax, or email, and the "drop and collect" method.

In practice, for identifying respondents and confirming their participation, multiple data collection methods can be employed. For instance, Mandawa (2016) adopted a face-to-face approach for data collection from female entrepreneurs in Zambia, while Khuraibet (2015) used a dual approach of online and paper format, which was delivered and collected to complete their study's survey in Kuwait. Online surveys carried out by software have gained popularity because they require few resources (less time and less money), are convenient to fill out, and allow privacy. Internet-based surveys generate faster responses from respondents and often have a lower rate of missing data (Pamela, 2018). One limitation of such an approach is the potential bias against respondents who do not have access to the internet. Likewise, telephone surveys have gained popularity as a way to capture large amounts of data. Saunders et al. (2023) hold that telephone surveys, as opposed to postal surveys, generate responses. However, this method of data collection can be time-consuming, particularly with excessively long questions (Khuraibet, 2015).

Therefore, in the present study, the researcher adopted a drop-and-collect and face-to-face survey approach for data gathering because the respondents may not be highly educated or may feel completing the questionnaire is time-consuming. Another reason for this approach was the various restrictions in place due to the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as limited time and money.

4.7.2 Data Collection Techniques

Research questions, research objectives, and study design act as guides in collecting data. There are two types of data sources: "**Primary**" and "**Secondary**" data. The term primary data refers to the unprocessed information that the researcher collects specifically for a specific purpose (Wilson, 2014). In the present study, primary data is collected via questionnaires (quantitative) distributed to respondents (female entrepreneurs) in Pakistan. However, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, only drop-

and-collect surveys were conducted, while semi-structured interviews were conducted through Zoom software in order to finish the research. The following section will provide a detailed understanding of the techniques used and the justification of their content. The researcher relied on e-books, online journals, online databases, articles, and official government publications to acquire secondary data (Wilson, 2014) for the literature review and the theoretical basis of this study.

4.7.3 Sampling and Population

In any research, an accurate sample is of paramount importance because a flawed sample can lead to a set of biased results that would misrepresent the research question outcome. Sampling involves selecting individuals from a defined population under study, i.e., female owned firms in the present research. The sampling technique is chosen based on financial resources, time availability, sample nature, and research question (McDaniel et al., 2018). For this research, a non-random or non-probability sampling approach (e.g., convenience and snowball) is used to gather information from Pakistani female entrepreneurs. Convenience sampling is a strategy that involves the selection of participants who are conveniently available to participate in a study (Saunders et al., 2023). This method of data collection has also been used in prior entrepreneurship research (e.g., Ahmad, 2007; Mitchelmore and Rowley, 2013), particularly when data collection from a large population is challenging or a sufficient level of response is difficult to elicit. Snowball sampling entails the investigator initially contacting those potential respondents who possess the characteristics relevant to the research area and then, by using these female entrepreneurs' referrals, identifying and inviting other respondents to participate in the survey. Therefore, in this study, data from female entrepreneurs was collected using a combination of snowballing and convenience sampling (Bryman, 2016).

For various reasons, snowball and convenience sampling were embraced. First, in Pakistan, there is a scarcity of statistics and precise data on female business owners (Rehman and Roomi, 2012), and due to the lack of an official database, convenience sampling was aided by snowball. Secondly, gaining access to female firm owners was extremely difficult due to COVID-19, and this fact also influenced the decision on the sampling approach. The reason for this is not a lack of formal data on female business owners, but rather that, in some cases, if data is available, it is not always updated. To obtain the official SME list and data for identifying potential respondents, I personally approached various institutions like the Government of Pakistan's Small and Medium Enterprise Development Authority (SMEDA) and the Women's Chamber of Commerce. Unfortunately, officials at these institutions simply refused to provide the list or share the data. Hence, to identify female firm owners, I decided to use my personal network and identify business owners through referrals by using convenience and snowball sampling.

Non-probability sample strategies can be criticised for being biased due to a lack of randomness and human judgement in the sample selection. However, it is considered appropriate due to the inadequate or non-availability of a sample frame for probability sampling (Bryman, 2016). Notably, unlike

industrialised countries, there is not a lot of information on businesses in transition economies, including Pakistan, which can be used to make a sampling framework. As a result, the researcher believes that the survey technique and the sampling framework should be context-specific thereby, adoption needs to be made in a country where industry players are still growing, small enterprises are often informal, and there is a lack of established databases.

In any empirical research, appropriate sample size determination is the key to accurate data analysis. The sample size—whether it be too large or too small—could have an impact on the reliability of the findings. For the purpose of this study, female business owners from the city of Lahore in Pakistan were chosen to participate. As was indicated before, the organisation that works with small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) couldn't provide a number of active female entrepreneurs in Lahore, Pakistan; consequently, the sample size for the present study was based on articles. Therefore, a sample size of 307 female entrepreneurs was identified for the sake of completing the study. This sample size is consistent with Ali et al.'s (2019) research related to the performance of female entrepreneurs in SMEs in the province of Punjab. The next section addresses the questionnaire sample criteria.

4.7.4 Questionnaire Design

A questionnaire can be viewed as a simple research instrument for collecting and organising information from respondents through a self-administrated survey filled in by respondents themselves (Bryman, 2016). A questionnaire can be made based on an analysis of the results of previous fieldwork, a questionnaire that already exists in relevant literature, or a clearly defined research question (Dewis, 2018; Hyman et al., 2006). For instance, Mandawa (2016) used a previous questionnaire to understand individual levels and business behaviours in relation to firms' performance in female entrepreneurship. The questionnaire was pretested and revised after a pilot study.

Close-ended/structured or open-ended/unstructured are two common types of questionnaires used in surveys. In contrast to closed-ended questions, open-ended questions provide respondents with a greater degree of freedom while responding (Bryman, 2016). However, open-ended questions' responses are hard to code and summarise, and they tend more towards exploratory research. Unlike open-ended questionnaires, close-ended questionnaires that encompass Likert-scale, scale, or multiple-choice questions are often employed in social science studies because of their construction, simplicity, and nature. Moreover, participants can select from a wide range of options on the Likert scale to show their strength of feeling about something (Dornyei and Dewaele, 2022).

A structured questionnaire is used in the present study, which is invariably associated with quantitative research and a survey approach to gather data. Collecting data via questionnaires has been a widely used tool in business studies (Ghauri et al., 2020). A structured questionnaire is a set of questions that focus on numbers (how many? how often? how satisfied?). It often comprises several types of questions, perhaps linked to a respondent's beliefs and opinions about an event. Such a questionnaire type often

uses the "*Likert scale*" as a format to rate the degree of agreement among respondents. This measures the degree of agreement related to a particular issue or case. Researchers frequently employ a 5-point or 7-point rating scale to measure responses. However, in order to measure the participants' responses, this study used a Likert scale with six points. As seen in figure 4.1, the 6-point Likert scale, which is quite similar to the 5-point and 7-point versions, advances from a weaker endorsement to a stronger endorsement. However, in contrast to other scales, the 6-point Likert scale does not include a neutral or middle category. This is what sets it apart from other scales. Neutral categories can pose statistical issues in the sense that they do not fit statistical models well or are disordered when they are analysed on rating scales. In addition, a questionnaire should only contain questions that respondents can answer; hence, a neutral category is unnecessary and should be confirmed through piloting (Nemoto and Beglar, 2014). Additionally, the choice of the number of scale points in a study is determined by the investigator's objectives and interests. For instance, Townsend et al. (2010) developed only one item for each variable, using a five-point scale to measure experience, skills, and self-confidence. In contrast, Irene (2016) created a list of 100 items (questions) to measure various aspects of competencies.

Figure 4. 1 Six-point Likert scale

1	2	3	4	5	6
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Slightly agree	Agree	Strongly agree

Source: Nemoto and Beglar (2014)

As mentioned earlier, in terms of data collection, the present study adopted a drop-and-collect and face-to-face survey approach for data gathering by distributing structured interviews to participants as the best option for data collection. Adopting a survey strategy will aid in understanding the nature of association among the constructs, i.e., human capital, EO, LO, EC, and performance of firms within the context of Pakistan. The structured questionnaire targets a large population for data collection (Saunders et al., 2023). Also, there are several measurement scales for EO, EC, LO, human capital, and firms' performance in the literature that can be used for this study.

4.7.5 Design of Survey Questionnaire

After extensive research on relevant literature, the design of the survey instrument came into being. It is noteworthy that Urdu is the national language of Pakistan and is widely spoken throughout the country. Nevertheless, the country's official language is English, which is dominantly used by businesses. Both English and Urdu were used to prepare the questionnaire (see Appendix D), and it consists of six parts.

- 1) Part A of the survey questionnaire focuses on the demographic variables of the female business owners (i.e., age, level of education, work experience, and business training)

as well as business general information (i.e., industry sector, size of the business, and number of years of establishment).

- 2) Part B of the questionnaire focuses on human capital, i.e., education, previous work experience, and training.
- 3) Part C of the questionnaire focuses on the entrepreneurial orientation dimensions (i.e., proactiveness, risk-taking, and innovativeness).
- 4) Part D of the questionnaire addresses dimensions of entrepreneurial competencies (i.e., relationship, organising, strategy, opportunity, commitment, and conceptual).
- 5) Learning orientation is covered in Part E of the questionnaire.
- 6) Lastly, Part F of the questionnaire addresses firm performance indicators.

The subsequent sections delve into the discussion of the adapted questionnaires utilised in the present study, which centre on components of entrepreneurial competencies, learning orientation, human capital, entrepreneurial orientation, and firm performance variables.

4.7.5.1 Measurement Items of Human Capital

In the context of this study, human capital is operationalised in terms of the female business owners' education attainment, business training, and prior work experience. In previous studies, numerous scholars (Lerner et al., 1997; Prasad et al., 2013; Alene, 2020) have used demographic variables as a proxy to represent human capital. Although measures such as years of education and experience are a way to leverage archival data, they would not measure the study outcome. The impact of education attainment and previous work experience should be relevant to the phenomena under investigation. Therefore, the level of education and previous work experience measurements were developed by the researcher, as illustrated in Table 4.2. The item was built after an extensive review of the literature and based on the researcher's general knowledge. As per Stockemer's (2019, p. 52) suggestion, a researcher's general interests, intuition, and knowledge can be used to draft a questionnaire. To measure the training construct, the Barcala et al (1999) study was considered, and the relevant items were adopted and modified to fit the current study outcome. Only important measurement items were used, as not all of the items were relevant to the study. The human capital scale comprises nine items, of which three measure the education construct, three measure the prior work experience construct, and three measure the training construct. A 6-point Likert scale is adopted to measure human capital dimensions. The language of the statements was kept simple to help the respondents better understand the statements. The following Table 4.2 demonstrates the measurement items for human capital.

Table 4. 2 Human Capital Scales Items

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Measurement Item</i>	<i>References</i>
<i>Education</i>	EDU_HC_1	My education has help me in identifying and seizing business opportunities.	Researcher

	EDU_HC_2	My area of education has help me in handling various business challenges independently.	Researcher
	EDU_HC_3	My education has equipped me with a wide range of skills and knowledge that is useful in running my business.	Researcher
Previous Work Experience	EXP_HC_1	My job experience has equipped me in handling daily business operation.	Researcher
	EXP_HC_2	I can solve my business problems based on my previous job experience.	Researcher
	EXP_HC_3	My job experience has help me to stay organised in my business.	Researcher
Business Training	TRA_HC_1	My training has affected on greater customer satisfaction.	Barcala, et al. (1999)
	TRA_HC_2	My training has helped me in acquiring knowledge on business skills.	Barcala, et al. (1999)
	TRA_HC_3	Training is necessary for the development of any business.	Barcala, et al. (1999)

Source: Researcher

4.7.5.2 Measurement Items of Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)

The EO variable in the present study is a three-dimensional reflective-formative second order construct that incorporates a firm's innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking as developed by Miller (1983) and is used by numerous authors, e.g., Brettel and Rottenberger (2013); Anderson et al. (2015); and Parveen et al. (2016). This study utilised a nine-item EO scale adopted from Hughes and Morgan (2007) and Lans et al. (2016) to measure the EO construct, while the global single-item measure was adopted from Anderson et al. (2015). Following the pilot study, the language of a few measuring items was simplified for less educated respondents as the wording was difficult to understand. A 6-point Likert scale is adopted to measure human capital dimensions. A 6-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (6) was considered. Participants in the survey were asked to select the number that best reflected their feelings about each item. The language of the statements was kept simple to help the respondents better understand the statements. The following Table 4.3 demonstrates the EO latent variables.

Table 4.3 Entrepreneurial Orientation Scales Items

Construct	Indicators	Measurement Items	References
Proactiveness	PRO_EO_1	My business is usually the first to introduce new product/service which other firms copy.	Lans et al. (2016)
	PRO_EO_2	If our business see opportunity, we like to respond before other firms do.	Lans et al. (2016)
	PRO_EO_3	Our business is good at finding profitable opportunities.	Hughes and Morgan (2007)
Innovativeness	INN_EO_4	My firm is always making an effort to improve and introduce new ideas in business	Hughes and Morgan (2007)

	INN_EO_5	My business is creative in the way of doing business.	Hughes and Morgan (2007)
	INN_EO_6	My business research new ways to do things.	Hughes and Morgan (2007)
Risk-Taking	RIS_EO_7	My business always looks for new opportunities and gives it a go.	Hughes and Morgan (2007)
	RIS_EO_8	Taking risk is seen as a positive trait in my business.	Hughes and Morgan (2007)
	RIS_EO_9	In my business, I take calculated risks with new ideas.	Hughes and Morgan (2007)
Global Single Item of EO	EO_GSL	In general, my business is innovative, actively looking for new products or services, and willing to take risk.	Anderson et al. (2015)

Source: Researcher

4.7.5.3 Measurement Items of Entrepreneurial Competencies (EC)

This study employed six sets of EC, namely commitment, conceptual, opportunity, organising relationships, and strategic competencies. Following the approach of Tehseen et al. (2020), EC in this study is conceptualised as a reflective-formative second-order construct. EC is measured using the scale developed by Man et al. (2008), which was also adopted by Lans et al. (2011), with a few modifications to accommodate the needs of the sample, such as simplifying English in a few measurement items. Several researchers, including Ahmad et al. (2010), Irene (2016), Mandawa (2016), Tehseen et al. (2020), and Ibidunni et al. (2021), have utilised these measures. This scale was also utilised in the present study to measure EC; however, the researchers only included 28 out of the original 53 items in this research as not all of the items were relevant to the study. The second reason was to keep the questionnaire short and to save respondents' time when completing it. The researcher performed a pilot study to confirm two things: first, that only less relevant questions were eliminated; and second, that a reduced number of items would still capture EC. Additionally, EC scale items were taken from well-established measurement scales, which further analysed the reliability and validity of the items. The EC measurement scales with references are shown in Table 4.4 below.

Table 4. 4 Entrepreneurial Competencies Scales Items

Construct	Indicators	Measurement Items	References
Commitment	COM_EC_1	I am going to do everything I can to make my business work.	Man et al. (2008)
	COM_EC_2	To help my businesses succeed, I make a lot of sacrifices on a personal level.	Mandawa (2016)
	COM_EC_3	I have no plans to leave this business.	Man et al. (2008)

	COM_EC_4	Most of my time is spent working at my business to make it successful.	Man et al. (2008)
Organising	ORG_EC_1	I decide how the business will run.	Man et al. (2008)
	ORG_EC_2	To get the job done, I organise my staff.	Man et al. (2008)
	ORG_EC_3	I motivate my workers by giving them bonuses, meals, money for transportation, etc.	Man et al. (2008)
	ORG_EC_4	I take steps to solve day-to-day issues and problems that my business faces.	Mandawa (2016)
	ORG_EC_5	I plan how various resources in the firm, such as funds and staff, will be organised.	Man et al. (2008)
Strategy	STA_EC_1	I make sure that what I am doing now meets my long-term business goals.	Man et al. (2008)
	STA_EC_2	I monitor my business progress in reaching my long-term business goals.	Man et al. (2008)
	STA_EC_3	I am aware of the future trends in the market and how they could affect my business.	Man et al. (2008)
	STA_EC_4	I often look at short-term, day-to-day tasks in the context of long-term goals and see how they fit together.	Man et al. (2008)
Conceptual	CON_EC_1	I know how ideas, issues, and monitoring impact business in general.	Man et al. (2008)
	CON_EC_2	I am willing to take moderate risks in my work.	Man et al. (2008)
	CON_EC_3	I monitor the profit of my risky investments.	Man et al. (2008)
	CON_EC_4	I make business decisions with careful planning.	Tehseen et al. (2020)
	CON_EC_5	I remain proactive and be open to changes.	Tehseen et al. (2020)
Relationship	REL_EC_1	By being friendly to consumers, I make them feel welcome.	Man et al. (2008)
	REL_EC_2	I encourage feedback from customers and use it to improve our service.	Man et al. (2008)
	REL_EC_3	I settle arguments between employees.	Mandawa (2016)
	REL_EC_4	I keep in touch with customers and staff on a daily basis.	Man et al. (2008)
	REL_EC_5	I respond quickly to customer complaints.	Mandawa (2016)
	REL_EC_6	I talk with our customers about things like prices.	Man et al. (2008)
Opportunity	OPP_EC_1	I offer services or products that customers want but are not offered by my competitors.	Man et al. (2008)
	OPP_EC_2	I find out what products or services my customers want.	Man et al. (2008)
	OPP_EC_3	I capture profitable business opportunities.	Man et al. (2008)

	OPP_EC_4	I am always on the lookout for products or services that really help customers.	Man et al. (2008)
<i>EC Global Single Item Measurement</i>	EC_GSL	The extent to which you think you have all of the above skills to run your business.	Tehseen et al. (2020)

Source: Researcher

4.7.5.4 Measurement Items of Learning Orientation (LO)

LO is an essential component due to its relevance to how individuals learn from both direct and vicarious experience. Sinkula et al.'s (1997) conceptualisation of LO is well-recognised, and numerous authors (e.g., Wang (2008); Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014); Lonial and Carter (2015)) have utilised their developed scale to measure LO. However, the researcher found this scale to be inappropriate for this research for two reasons. Firstly, Sinkula et al.'s (1997) LO measurement scale was initially developed for large organisations instead of small firms, and secondly, the present study targets small businesses, which are often necessity-driven, use informal management practices, and have been reported to have either no or few employees (World Bank, 2017). Consequently, the researcher opted to employ Vandewalle's (1997) scale to assess the LO construct.

Vandewalle (1997) measured LO on a six-item scale. In their studies, De Clercq et al. (2013) and Turk et al. (2020) re-tested the same scale and found support for its reliability and validity. The present study also employed this scale to measure learning orientation. Therefore, all six items were used to make the LO construct. The rationale for adopting this scale is that it measures individuals' propensity to acquire new skills (De Clercq et al., 2013). Similar to other variables, this construct also uses a 6-point Likert scale identical to other constructs to ensure uniformity. The language of the statements was altered where appropriate to make respondents better understand the statements. Table 4.5 below shows the scale item used.

Table 4.5 Learning Orientation Scales Items

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Measurement Items</i>	<i>References</i>
<i>Learning Orientation</i>	LEO_1	I often read things (articles, internet, books, etc.) to improve my knowledge and business skills.	Clercq et al., (2013)
	LEO_2	I like to take on challenging tasks from which I can learn a lot.	Clercq et al., (2013)
	LEO_3	I am willing to take a risk because I care about improving my skills.	Clercq et al., (2013)
	LEO_4	I often look for opportunities to develop new skills and knowledge.	Clercq et al., (2013)
	LEO_5	I like doing hard and challenging things that can help me learn new skills.	Clercq et al., (2013)

	LEO_6	I like to work in situations where I need a lot of skill and talent.	Clercq et al., (2013)
--	-------	--	-----------------------

Source: Researcher

4.7.5.5 Measurement Items of Firm Performance

The evaluation of business performance is a critical area, especially in small firms' research. Owing to the nature of small firms and due to a lack of historical data, inconsistent record-keeping, and a lack of financial reporting obligations, performance measurement is challenging (Rehman and Roomi, 2012; Mandawa, 2016). Although many scholars (Miller, 2011; Vij and Bedi, 2016) have suggested using both subjective and objective measures to evaluate firm performance, subjective measures of firm performance are the most widely used methods, and numerous scholars have adopted them in their studies (Hughes and Morgan, 2007; Ahmad et al., 2010; Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014). Subjective metrics are especially helpful for evaluating the performance of small businesses when obtaining objective data on performance is difficult or impossible due to the lack of a legal requirement to report financial information. For instance, Vij and Bedi (2016) found that obtaining objective data is very difficult for an outsider as the respondents are unwilling to provide sensitive information. Thus, in this study, objective firm performance measures were incorporated from Irene (2016), which comprises both financial and non-financial performance measures. However, only the most commonly adopted items were used to measure the firm's performance. The main rationale behind this is to keep the questionnaire short and to save respondents' time when filling it out. Similarly, instead of measuring the firms' performance for a one-year period, the researcher used a three-year period due to COVID-19. To measure the firms' performance, a 6-point Likert scale was adopted to ensure uniformity with the rest of the construct scale. The language of the items was simplified for the respondents, as shown in Table 4.6 below.

Table 4. 6 Firm Performance Measurement Scales

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Measurement Items</i>	<i>References</i>
<i>Firm Performance</i>	PER_1	Customer is satisfied with the service and products.	Irene (2016)
	PER_2	I have been successful in maintaining relationships with our existing customers.	Irene (2016)
	PER_3	I am satisfied with the overall performance of my business.	Irene (2016)
	PER_4	Compared to my competitors, my firms' sales have increased over the past three years.	Irene (2016)
	PER_5	Compared to my competitors, my firms' market share has increased over the past three years.	Irene (2016)

Source: Researcher

4.7.6 Pilot Study

Once the key constructs were operationalised, the developed survey instrument was pre-tested to achieve four goals: first, to determine its face validity; second, to determine the time required to complete the questionnaire; third, to assess participants' ease in responding to the questions; and fourth, to test the language for accuracy. As recommended by Bryman (2016), conducting a pre-test of survey instruments allows the researcher to assess potential issues arising from factors like confusing or threatening phrasing, the use of technical terms, respondents' comprehension, and their willingness to provide sensitive information. Two methods were adopted in testing the survey instrument. Initially, the questionnaire was circulated among fellow researchers, and based on their feedback, the questionnaire was revised. Secondly, the questionnaire was distributed to five female firm owners who are operating businesses in the service sector in Pakistan. These participants provided feedback on any challenges they ran into. It was noticed that some survey items needed to be clarified, especially by amending the sentence structure and vocabulary of a few measurement items. As a result, simple wording was used, and the statement was reviewed to better fit the requirements of the context. Nevertheless, the gathered data could not be subjected to confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) due to the pilot study's limited sample size. The majority of the measurement items came from studies and had undergone validity and reliability testing. Consequently, this did not pose a significant constraint.

The researcher created an interview protocol, aligning its content with the research questions, research objectives, and quantitative findings from the quantitative phase. The purpose of the subsequent qualitative phase was to delve into and expand upon the outcomes from the preceding quantitative phase of the study. The author aimed to comprehend why specific variables, such as EO and previous work experience, did not significantly contribute to female firm performance in Pakistan. The researcher initially developed the questionnaire in English and then translated it into Urdu. The researcher conducted a pilot test of the interview protocol with two participants who had successfully established businesses in Lahore, Pakistan. The investigator in the present study incorporated questions with the purpose of identifying and rectifying any issues relative to the clarity of themes, omissions, duration, and general impressions of interviewees in the course of the interview. All two participants in the pilot study stated that the interview questions were clear and fully comprehensible. Based on the pilot interview analysis, minor changes were required, and the final set of questions was clearer and better aligned with the quantitative phase of the study.

4.7.7 Method of Data Analysis

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is employed in the current study in order to establish the constructs reliability and validity. The study also utilised the “*Structural Equation Modelling*” (SEM) technique to investigate the hypothesis developed and its association with the explanatory variables. CFA is a member of the extended group of methods called SEM and plays a major role in the validation of measurement models in path or structural analysis (Brown, 2015).

The use of the CFA technique in examining the relationships between variables and their structure is a common practice among researchers. According to Hair et al. (2017), CFA is an appropriate multivariate data analysis approach if the investigator has adapted or adopted pre-tested latent variables with the intention of testing a hypothesis. As the present research is testing hypotheses of existing theories and pre-existing measurement scales, CFA is the appropriate approach for analysing constructs in this study. Based on the aforementioned statement, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is unsuitable for this.

CFA is a popular statistical technique in applied research used for assessing the underlying link between latent constructs (Brown, 2015). According to the CFA approach, researchers are required to first construct an underlying structure and then evaluate whether or not the observed data "fits" this predetermined model or structure. By doing this, confirmatory factor analysis offers a paradigm for resolving issues linked to traditional methods of determining the validity and reliability of a measure (Mueller, 2012).

The CFA approach can be used for a wide range of purposes, including measurement invariance evaluation, construct validation, the detection of method effects, and psychometric evaluation. This approach studies the underlying relationship between latent variables and observed variables by utilising variance and co-variance to analyse the data (Hoyle, 2014). As a result, the CFA technique was selected as the technique to investigate how latent variables are related to one another in this study. A variety of software programmes, either licenced or free, are available that can be used to analyse the structure of the models; for instance, SmartPLS, Stata, LISREL, lavaan for R, Amos, EQS, and Mplus (Kline, 2016). In the present research, IBM's Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25 is utilised for initial analysis of data such as demographic items, and later SmartPLS software (version 4) was used to access the measurement model and later the structural model in Chapter 5.

Following the completion of the CFA, and in order to test the hypothesis, structural equation modelling (SEM) was utilised. SEM, according to Civelek (2018), is a technique that uses a range of statistical approaches to evaluate a set of indicators. These indicators or constructs are correlated and evaluated in order to comprehend and explicate their theoretical relationships. As noted by Kline (2016), structural equation modelling is superior to more traditional methods of research such as ANOVA and descriptive statistics due to the fact that it enables numerous analysis of each variable and the constructs.

4.8 The Necessity for Additional Investigation

Following the gathering and analysis of quantitative data, it was established that entrepreneurial orientation (i.e., risk-taking, innovation, and proactiveness) has no significant association with female firm performance. This appears to be unexpected, as firms with EO are better equipped to spot potential sources of competitive advantage by identifying available opportunities and setting themselves apart from their rivals (Anwar et al., 2022; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005). Similarly, previous work

experience is found to be positive but has an insignificant relationship with entrepreneurial competencies. This finding gave rise to the formulation of new inquiries to comprehend the reasons behind the apparent insignificance of entrepreneurial orientation and prior work experience in the context of Pakistan. Consequently, to gain a more in-depth understanding of these findings, qualitative research was conducted (Bryman and Bell, 2015). In doing so, female business owners who have been successfully running their businesses for more than a decade were interviewed since they would be better able to shed more light on the phenomenon under investigation. Furthermore, these successful female business owners possess a wealth of knowledge in various areas, including the acquisition of financial resources, human resources, and knowledge of government regulations and policies (for example, training and attitudes).

4.9 Methods of Qualitative Data Collection

Research on entrepreneurship has utilised both quantitative and qualitative methods (Molina-Azorin et al., 2012). The research paradigm, research objective, and research question, as well as the nature of the inquiry and the ability to approach a large sample size, all contributed to the decision to use quantitative research as the predominant approach for this investigation. Additionally, the significance of qualitative research cannot be understated when it comes to understanding the underlying phenomena (Hlady-Rispal and Jouison-Laffitte, 2014). Qualitative research investigates broad phenomena rather than specific variables by asking open-ended questions such as what, why, or how. Unlike quantitative study, which is a regressive approach, qualitative study comes in the form of speech, stories, sentences, or words (Merriam and Tisdell, 2015), and such forms of data can be easily captured either by written notes or electronic means via video or audio recording during a conversation or interview (Sally et al., 2019). Even though face-to-face interviews are more likely to build rapport (Bryman, 2016), electronic interviews can be used when respondents are in different geographical locations (Khan and MacEachen, 2022).

In qualitative research, there is not a definitive "right" or "wrong" method (Guest et al., 2013), as researchers make assumptions based on their beliefs about the social world and the subject of study. Consequently, the population being investigated may vary, and researchers can use diverse approaches to acquire that knowledge (Ritchie et al., 2014).

4.9.1 Interviews

When conducting research, the sort of information needed determines the type of interview. Unstructured and semi-structured interviews are commonly used in conducting interviews. According to Bernard (2017), semi-structured interviews are similar to unstructured interviews as both have a freewheeling quality. Nonetheless, an interview guide is prepared for a semi-structural interview. In the current study, the semi-structured interview method was employed, with the schedule as a guide. A written list of topics and questions that needed to be covered in this study in a particular order was

prepared. The interview guide will assist in investigating the factors that enabled successful female entrepreneurs to overcome obstacles, accelerate their performance, and develop their businesses in Pakistan.

A semi-structured interview has been chosen for the qualitative part of the study because it is the most appropriate method for obtaining information about the results of the hypothesis and how the already existing variables/constructs, i.e., entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial competencies, human capital, and learning orientation, apply to the existing female entrepreneurs in the Pakistani context. Since the aim of this study is to build a conceptual framework for Pakistani female entrepreneurs and not generate a theory from the data (Guest et al., 2013), an in-depth interview is not the appropriate research approach.

Another alternative technique of data collection in a qualitative approach is the focus group. The main advantages of this approach are that it is less costly and that it enables the generation of detailed information in a short period of time (Bougie and Sekaran, 2019). Additionally, the interaction between participants in a focus group permits the investigation of complex human behaviours and motivations (Pedersen and Lind, 2017). Focus groups have many advantages, yet the current study consists of gathering information about female entrepreneurs' business performance as well as their individual capabilities, which some participants may not feel comfortable sharing in a group because of the sensitive nature of the data being collected.

4.9.2 Development of Interview Guide

The research question, research objective, and hypothesis results were used to develop the interview guide, which covers questions related to human capital and learning orientation variables (the individual factors) as well as firm behaviour characteristics (entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial competencies) that influence female firm performance. The interview guide was developed based on the results of the hypothesis (see Appendix E) as well as pre-defined themes, such as the human capital, EO, LO, and EC dimensions. Prior studies in human capital, EO, LO, and EC, such as those of Ahmad (2007), Irene (2016), and Mandawa (2016), were utilised in the process of developing the interview guide. This was done to ensure that the interview guide was compatible with the study's aims and objectives, as well as to confirm the hypothesis and acquire a deeper understanding of how the above-mentioned factors aid in improving the performance of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan.

4.9.3 Sampling Strategy

To gather comprehensive information from participants, the current study utilised a purposive sampling strategy during the qualitative data collection phase. This approach, essential for obtaining in-depth insights, involves the use of non-probability sampling techniques to select an information-rich sample that best explains the statistical results. As outlined by Ritchie et al. (2014), non-probability sampling involves selecting respondents based on specific characteristics, where the probability of having a

respondent from each case is unknown. This characteristic-based selection is the distinguishing factor in non-probability sampling. While probability sampling proves advantageous when the population is known and easily accessible, non-probability sampling is employed in situations where the population is either unknown or not readily accessible. (Bryman, 2016). In non-probability sampling, five different types of sampling strategies are employed, namely self-selection sampling, purposive sampling, quota sampling, convenience sampling, and snowball sampling (Saunders et al., 2023). In present study, the investigator adopted purposive sampling aided by snowball sampling.

Choosing participants who are most likely to provide valuable insight, ideas, or in-depth information about the phenomenon under investigation is known as "purposeful sampling" (Saunders et al., 2019). As emphasised by Patton (2015), a robust and purposeful sampling strategy is necessary to acquire information-rich cases and gain knowledge about specific issues. As a result, purposive sampling was used to identify female business owners who could shed light on the hypothesis findings. The researcher adopted a purposive sample for numerous reasons. Firstly, as mentioned above, the purposeful technique was adopted for the selection of participants who could reflect on their experience and rich information to gain knowledge of the phenomenon. Secondly, due to the lack of an official database and a scarcity of statistics on female business owners in Pakistan (Rehman and Roomi, 2012), prospective sampling was facilitated through snowball sampling.

4.9.4 Qualitative Sample Size

With the aim of moving from the quantitative phase to the qualitative phase, the researcher was aware that instead of large samples, the qualitative approach uses small sample sizes (Boddy, 2016). According to Moser and Korstjens (2018), the research questions, availability of resources, time allocation, and data collection methods determine the sample size needed in a qualitative approach. As a result, there are no set guidelines for selecting an adequate sample size in qualitative research (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016). For instance, Rehman and Roomi (2012) and Roomi et al. (2018) employed a purely qualitative approach with a sample size of 20 female entrepreneurs, while Dakhan (2019) in his study of aspiring female entrepreneurs adopted a sequential explanatory mixed-method design and employed only 5 semi-structured interviews in its qualitative phase. Therefore, the sample size of 15 female entrepreneurs was considered sufficient for this study, surpassing the minimum sample size recommended by Baker et al. (2012), which was approximately 14 interviews.

4.9.5 Sample Recruitment

Flexibility was considered in establishing the recruitment criteria in the questionnaire sample. The inclusion criteria included:

- i. Female firms only
- ii. Enterprises with fewer than 100 employees

- iii. Stand-alone firm (does not include firms that are home-based, part of large organisations or franchises)
- iv. Successful firms
- v. Firms older than 10 years
- vi. Firms situated in Lahore city

For this study, the sample consists of Pakistani females who founded their own businesses. The investigator considered electronic methods (Zoom) of data collection as the best option because of the unforeseen circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic. In the same way, the interview question guide was produced in both Urdu and English for the interviewee's convenience and to make it easier for them to answer. Table 4.7 shows the interviewees' profiles.

Table 4. 7 Interviewee's Profile

Sr. No.	Interviewee	Business Type	Age Group	Qualification	Age of Business
1	WE-1	Academy	40-50	Master's degree	15
2	WE-2	School	40-50	M.Phil. degree	20
3	WE-3	School	50-60	Master's degree	20
4	WE-4	Boutique	30-40	Master's degree	14
5	WE-5	Boutique	30-40	Master's degree	18
6	WE-6	Boutique	30-40	M.Phil. degree	16
7	WE-7	Cloth shop	30-40	Bachelor	11
8	WE-8	Bakery	40-50	D Pharmacy	12
9	WE-9	Takeaway Business	40-50	Bachelor	12
10	WE-10	Book Shop	30-40	Bachelor	15
11	WE-11	Accountant	40-50	ACCA	18
12	WE-12	Law Consultant	50-60	LLB	22
13	WE-13	Graphic Designer	30-40	Master's degree	14
14	WE-14	Beauty salon	40-50	Master's degree	15
15	WE-15	Gift Shop	30-40	Bachelor	12

4.9.6 Adoption of Thematic Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis is viewed as the technique of reassembling or reconstructing the collected data in a way that is both comprehensive and meaningful. There are numerous research approaches available for analysing the shared experiences and opinions of individuals, and thematic analysis is one of the most commonly used approaches to analysing qualitative data (Bryman, 2016). Therefore, to analyse the transcribed data, the thematic technique was used in the present study. It is an important technique for smoothly identifying, analysing, and summarising qualitative data so that relevant or meaningful patterns or themes can be revealed from the transcribed interviews (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Figure 4.2 depicts the stages of thematic analysis used in this study.

Figure 4. 2 Thematic Analysis Stages

Source Dakhan (2019)

4.9.6.1 Data Familiarisation

This study collected qualitative data electronically after obtaining verbal and written consent. Since the interview was recorded, it could be analysed in greater detail at a later stage. The statistically significant results of the qualitative phase were used as a basis to design the interview guide in the qualitative phase. This gave a solid foundation for developing an adequate interview guide and investigating the phenomenon in further depth. Additionally, the participants' facial expressions were analysed by the researcher to comprehend their emotions. Later, the researcher repeatedly and carefully listened to the recording to enable word-to-word transcription. After going through this whole process, the response data was well understood.

4.9.6.2 Code Generation

At this stage, the researcher read the transcribed interviews multiple times in order to identify similarities, relevant, interesting, and unique information that participants provided. A reflective code was assigned to the novel information that was highlighted. A code, as described by Clarke and Braun (2013), is a label given to the highlighted novel information. Codes aid in the understanding of a

response. The transcripts were carefully examined and understood before the coding systems were developed.

4.9.6.3 Making of Themes

As soon as the transcribed interviews had all been coded, themes were generated. Rather than focusing on discrete codes, at this point, the focus shifts to more generalised themes. In other words, to gain a clearer understanding of how interviewees respond to the same topic, the transcripts were grouped into relevant themes based on similar answers. At first, the overarching themes derived from the quantitative data were highlighted, and later the researcher emphasised newly emergent themes. Lastly, a thorough examination assisted in the classification of sub-themes that existed within the larger themes.

4.9.6.4 Review Themes

Once the themes have been developed, the researcher re-examines and re-organises all of the themes in light of their importance to the study. Revisiting the developed themes is imperative because this stage ensures that themes incorporate related information, are distinct in nature, and are well-developed (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Only key themes were identified from the transcribed interview, as not all the data was relevant. However, additional important themes relevant to the study were also discovered for future research.

4.9.6.5 Labelling Themes

Different themes were given labels or names at this point, and each theme was given a distinct description. A second, thorough examination was carried out to look for any themes that were repeated or were missing. On a sequential basis, themes were organised to tell a tale about the phenomena to readers, with a particular emphasis on the unique findings.

4.9.6.6 Reporting Results

Following the end of the fifth phase, reporting of the results took place. In this process, all the themes were prepared with their respective codes and pictures so that the analysis could be carried out. A cross-tabulation was done to determine the influence that each theme had on the other themes. At this point, the researcher should have linked the themes with the study objectives, which should have been defined in the first chapter. The findings are discussed in detail in Chapter 6.

4.9.7 Addressing Validity and Reliability Issues in Qualitative Research

The objective of any research is to generate knowledge that is both reliable and valid. Whether qualitative or quantitative, the reliability and validity of each research study can be assessed by examining the conceptualisation of the study, the approaches taken in collecting data, analysing and interpreting it, and the manner in which findings are presented. It is important to note that the criteria for determining validity and reliability in a qualitative approach differ from those in a quantitative design. In quantitative studies, the focus is on hypothesis testing, whereas qualitative studies aim to gain

new insights by delving deeper into the understanding of the context, phenomena, and individuals. In qualitative studies, researchers ensure trustworthiness by adhering to criteria such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Cypress, 2017; Bryman, 2016).

4.9.7.1 Credibility

In qualitative research, credibility entails the researcher seeking validation from respondents, and questions such as 'How authentic are the findings?' are tied to credibility (Bryman, 2016). It deals with the issue of whether the explanation fits the description and whether the description is credible. To enhance credibility in this study, the accuracy and authenticity of a participant's lived experience were ensured through member-checking. This process involves validating the accuracy of information and understanding by returning transcribed transcripts to participants. This approach enables the researcher to identify any discrepancies that could undermine the collection of a rich and realistic narrative.

4.9.7.2 Transferability

How generalisable is the research in relation to “other contexts, settings, events, groups, or people” or “can the findings be extrapolated to other situations?” is what transferability addresses (Bryman, 2016). To enhance transferability, the study employs the purposive sampling method. The researcher has also maintained a thick description. Providing a thick description and robust data with a wide possible range of information through the detailed and accurate descriptions of the female entrepreneurs will allow the researcher to acquire the potential transferability of findings to other relevant areas.

4.9.7.3 Dependability

Dependability addresses whether the study outcomes align with the information obtained or if the findings can be applicable in different instances (Bryman, 2016). As far as dependability is concerned, the researcher has maintained a comprehensive record of the study. This includes feedback from supervisors, transcripts, interviews, drafts created and rejected, and other pertinent data, all securely stored. Furthermore, throughout the research process, the researcher remained unbiased, i.e., avoiding the influence of personal values or theoretical inclinations. Each participant's consent will be obtained to enable the researcher to record the interviews and will be transcribed after the interview. The recording and transcribed readings will serve as records of the exact words spoken by the participants during the interviews.

4.9.7.4 Confirmability

Confirmability is employed to ascertain the neutrality of the research and ensure that the researcher has not misrepresented the data and analysis. To uphold confirmability, the researcher will not allow personal preference to come into the study and refrain from guiding the study in a particular direction. Transparency in reporting methods and findings is crucial. Hence, a professional supervisor and a colleague with expertise in qualitative research will review the research, providing suggestions to maintain objectivity.

4.10 Ethical Consideration

The word "ethics" comes from the Greek word "ethos," which means "character," and it refers to the importance of morality in research (Starc, 2017). Research ethics is a collection of values and guidelines used while conducting studies with people as subjects (Michalos, 2014). Procedural ethics and ethics in practice are the two dimensions with which research ethics is concerned (Hernandez and Ngunjiri, 2016; Guillemin and Gillam, 2004). According to Edwards and Mauthner (2002), ethics are fundamental to study as they are ingrained in a person's behaviour and morals. A framework for ethical behaviour was created before the start of this study, following the University of the West of Scotland's (UWS) declared standards. The Director of Studies and this ethical code of conduct were discussed before formal approval from the school's ethics committee was requested. As a result of the application's success, the committee authorised the start of data collection (a copy of the ethical approval is included in Appendix A). Every data collection phase was conducted per the UWS ethical code of conduct.

4.11 Summary

The key aim of this chapter was to delve into the various research approaches undertaken. To fulfil the research aim and objective, a positivism paradigm was adopted in this study. The chapter begins by introducing key categories of research philosophy, followed by a justification of the chosen epistemological position (positivist). Given the utilisation of both quantitative and qualitative methods, the study embraced both deductive (for hypothesis testing) and inductive (for interviews) research approaches.

The research design leaned towards a descriptive approach, as the focus was on elucidating the relationship and impact of EC, EO, LO, and human capital on firm performance. The data collection methods employed a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach, executed in two stages. The initial phase involved a quantitative study, aiming to empirically test the conceptual model and analyse hypotheses. Subsequently, a qualitative study was conducted through interviews to elucidate the results of the hypotheses. A survey strategy method was employed for the quantitative approach, aligning with the deductive approach and positivism paradigm. The research used a drop-and-collect and face-to-face survey approach, with a sample size of 307 female entrepreneurs. Participants' responses were measured using a 6-point Likert scale, and the survey questionnaire was prepared in both English and Urdu.

For the qualitative part, the study utilised purposive sampling, a non-random method facilitated by snowball sampling. Semi-structured interviews were chosen to gain a profound understanding of the phenomena under investigation. Flexibility was maintained in establishing the recruitment criteria for the questionnaire sample. A sample size of 15 female entrepreneurs was deemed sufficient, and the interview questions were prepared in both English and Urdu; however, the interview was conducted online. Thematic analysis was the chosen method for analysing qualitative data. To address validity and reliability concerns, the study ensured trustworthiness by adhering to criteria such as credibility,

transferability, dependability, and conformability. The findings from both methods are discussed in the subsequent chapter.

Chapter Five: Data Analysis and Results

5.1 An Overview

An overview of the various stages of data processing and findings is presented in this chapter. The present study employed “*Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling*” (PLS-SEM) to assess the hypothesis. The researcher adopted a two-stage (disjoint) approach to evaluate the HOC in this study. The PLS-SEM approach consists of two components: (1) the measurement model and (2) the structural model. First, the assessment and validation of the measurement model (the outer model) is considered, which demonstrates the relationship between the constructs and their indicators (Sarstedt et al., 2019). This is the first stage of the disjoint two stage approach. The second stage starts with the EC and EO higher-order construct (HOC hereafter) specification, estimation, and validation. Finally, in the structural model (the inner model), the results of the hypothesis relationship are presented.

The chapter embarks on the data screening process as discussed in Section 5.2. Following this, Section 5.3 covers the common method variance, and descriptive statistics results are shown in Section 5.4. Section 5.5 gives an overview of the disjointed two-stage approach. Section 5.6 is the first stage of a disjointed two-stage approach where the assessment of first-order and lower-order components is analysed for reliability and validity. Section 5.7 is stage two, where the EC and EO HOC are validated, followed by Section 5.8, which evaluates the structural model and reveals the hypothesis results. The chapter summary is presented in Section 5.9.

5.2 Useable Questionnaires

In this study, the researcher distributed a total of 400 questionnaires over a two-month period. As said earlier, drop-and-collect and face-to-face methods of data collection were used to collect the data. A total of 345 questionnaires were received. However, only 330 questionnaires were acceptable for data preparation and data analysis. The remaining questionnaires were considered unfit and were excluded from the study as numerous respondents did not match the research criteria or provided incomplete answers, particularly questions related to firm performance. This represents an 86.2% response rate for usable questionnaires for this study. The data was collected from Lahore, Pakistan. The sampling data comprises female entrepreneurs from the service industry. The following section discusses the process of data screening, handling of missing data, assessment of outliers, and testing of normality.

5.2.1 Data Screening

The process of preparing the data for analysis is known as data screening. Given the usage of primary data through structured questionnaires, the data must be further scrutinised to check for missing values, outliers, unengaged values (inconsistent or straight-lining answers), and data normality (Hair et al., 2017, p. 80) before any further analysis can be performed. A self-administered questionnaire is used to collect the primary data. The responses are coded and put into IBM SPSS Statistical Version 25 so that different screening tests can be run on them.

5.2.2 Missing Values

When many social science research projects rely on survey approaches to collect data, missing data is often a concern. This happens when a respondent unintentionally or purposefully chooses not to answer one or more questions, leading to the creation of missing data. The researcher can either discard that particular questionnaire with a missing value or retain it, depending on the extent of the missing data. This is because missing values in excess of a given proportion, such as 15% of an observation, can be problematic (Hair et al., 2017), and if a larger percentage of responses are incomplete, attention should be paid to the missing data patterns (Pallant, 2016). In a similar vein, Hair et al. (2017) suggest that although responses with $\leq 5\%$ missing values can be replaced with mean scores, this, however, will reduce the validity of the data. Therefore, a strict filtration process was employed in this study, which eliminated 16 responses from a total of 330 because the percentage of missing data for the response variable was greater than 5%. Moreover, no missing data was replaced with a mean value, as none of the responses were found to have a missing value of less than 5%.

5.2.3 Unengaged/Straight Lining Data

Once the missing data is detected, the next step is the identification of unengaged value, i.e., straight lining or inconsistent answers (Hair et al., 2017). When a participant gives the same response to all of the questions in the questionnaire, it is known as an unengaged value. For instance, the questionnaire that consists of multiple-choice questions provides seven different answers (e.g., a 6-point Likert scale) to choose from. When a participant chooses to mark the option "4" for answering the complete question, it indicates that the participant wants to fill out the questionnaire as soon as possible but does not want to give any thought to the answer. The researcher used the function of standard deviation in SPSS in order to identify unengaged values in the data. Upon completion of the process, unengaged data is indicated by a zero value for the standard deviation. The zero value of the standard deviation suggests that participants are providing identical responses to the questions, leading to straight-line or unengaged data. Such responses can lead to bias in data as they may deteriorate both the validity and reliability of survey responses (Kim et al., 2019). Three responses are excluded from the data collection based on this process. Thus, a total of 311 questionnaires were left at this stage.

5.2.4 Assessment of Outliers

After the identification and deduction of unengaged data, the next process is finding outliers from the collected data. To this end, both multivariate and univariate analysis were carried out for the purpose of detecting extreme values that markedly deviate from the remaining cases or observations in the collected data. Hair et al. (2017) describe outliers as an extreme or unusual response value, either to a particular question or to all of the questions. A variety of factors can lead to outliers, including incorrect data entry, odd responses from participants, sampling from an irrelevant population, and an undefined number of missing values in statistical analysis (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2016). Outliers must be removed from the data set since their persistence can result in numerous errors and inconsistencies that

can reduce the statistical analysis's effectiveness (Alshboul et al., 2021). The standardised score approach was utilised by converting the score per variable to a standard score (z score) in order to identify single variables with extreme values or univariate outliers with a cut-off value between -3.29 and 3.29 ($p < 0.01$), as indicated by Tabachnick and Fidell (2016). Based on this process, four questionnaires were excluded, and a total of 307 questionnaires were left at this stage.

Finally, this study employed the Mahalanobis distance test to identify multivariate outliers. This test is based on the chi-square distribution, which calculates the mean value (i.e., the distance between variables) from a common or centroid point. The common/centroid point is a point at which the means of all variables coincide (Dakhan, 2019). The variable measured in this study is fourteen. Therefore, the degree of freedom is fourteen as well. By just looking at the P-value (below 0.001 or $p < 0.001$), any outlier can be easily identified. In the Mahalanobis distance test, all numbers were greater than 0.001, and, at this stage, no outliers were identified. Therefore, 307 data sets remain at this point.

5.2.5 Normality Test

Another assumption of SEM analysis is the normality of the data. Nonetheless, when handling larger datasets, this assumption is the least significant (Darlington and Hayes, 2016) because there is a lower possibility of deviation (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2016). Moreover, Hair et al. (2017) note that analysis like regression and correlation can be carried out even with abnormally distributed data, and a linear relationship exists between the variables. The symmetrical (normal) distribution of a data set can be assessed by visually inspecting the probability plot diagram or histogram or by evaluating the statistical values of skewness and kurtosis. (Wilson, 2014). The data is regarded as normally distributed if the points on the curve are uniformly distributed on both sides (e.g., symmetrical). According to Hair et al. (2017), kurtosis is a measure that reflects the "peakedness" of the distribution, whereas skewness will provide information regarding symmetry. To determine the normality of data statistically, the 'z-value' is calculated from skewness and kurtosis by dividing the statistical value by the standard error. While Thomas and Thomas (2017) suggest that the z-values of skewness and kurtosis must fall between +1.96 and -1.96 for the data to be considered normally distributed, Kline (2016) concludes that in terms of the skewness index and kurtosis index, an absolute z-value greater than ± 3 and ≥ 8 is considered extreme for the skewness and kurtosis index.

Despite the aforementioned argument, many studies have shown that PLS-SEM can provide consistent and precise assessment even with non-normal data (Reinartz et al., 2009; Wetzels et al., 2009). This is because the statistical properties of PLS-SEM are quite resilient when it comes to model estimations for data with both extremely non-symmetrical and normal distributional properties (i.e., skewness and/or kurtosis), as PLS-SEM relies on non-normal data and hence makes no assumptions about normal distribution (Hair et al., 2017). Nevertheless, data normality is recommended for better and more consistent findings, despite the fact that PLS-SEM generally does not make any assumptions about the

data distributions (Hair et al., 2017). In a similar vein, Blashill (2010) asserts that with a sample size greater than 200, the standard errors of kurtosis and skewness do not result in significant differences in an analysis.

In this study, the normality of the data was assessed by calculating the z-values of skewness and kurtosis. Using an absolute z-value of +8 as the threshold criterion for examining the univariate kurtosis values, it was determined that none of the kurtotic variables exceeded the critical value (see Appendix F). Nevertheless, the univariate skewness z-value falls above the ± 3 threshold criterion, signifying the non-normality of the data. Byrne (2016) states that in SEM, evidence of kurtosis is usually indicative of a problem compared to skewness. In this study, the normality of the variables was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilks and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests. The "Sig" values, all less than 0.05, indicate that the variables are not normally distributed (see Appendix G).

5.3 Common Method Variance

In this study, all the information for both dependent and independent variables was collected from a single respondent (female entrepreneur) with the same instrument (a questionnaire). Within a given study, when a single key informant is employed to collect data on different variables by means of a self-administered questionnaire (Wang, 2008), where the same survey instrument is used to measure both dependent and independent variables (Lonial and Carter, 2015), the potential for common method variance arises. According to Renko et al. (2009), the study findings can be biased by the common method variance because it can either deflate or inflate the relationship between constructs (Antonakis et al., 2010).

To mitigate the impact of common method bias, this study employed several remedial strategies recommended by numerous scholars (Podsakoff et al., 2012; Viswanathan and Kayande, 2012). At first, the researcher designed the survey instrument (questionnaire) carefully, as the endogenous and exogenous construct measurement scales were derived from several sources with distinct measurements. Secondly, prior to attempting the survey, participants were informed that their choices (answers) would be treated confidentially, and, as for the statement (items) presented against each question, respondents were made aware that there was no right or wrong response to the survey statement. Lastly, reliable scales were employed in this study and were modified in order to make them simple and easy for respondents to understand. Additionally, throughout the survey, the researcher remained present to address any comprehension (understanding) or language issues.

A common method variance issue occurs when a single factor accounts for the maximum variance, i.e., above the threshold of 50% (Podsakoff et al., 2003). This study adopted "Harman's single-factor test," a common technique adopted by several researchers (see, e.g., Lonial and Carter, 2015; Wang, 2008). The single first factor accounts for 21.110% of the total variance extracted based on Harman's single-

factor test result (see Appendix H), which is lower than the 50% threshold value. Given a result outcome, the present research rules out the probability of common method bias.

5.4 General Description Results

In a given study, the respondents' demographic characteristics information is crucial for the purpose of generalisation, as it determines whether or not respondents are true representatives of the targeted population (Salkind, 2010). Four broad categories are used to establish the respondent's demographic profile: 1) age of female business owners; 2) level of education; 3) work experience; and 4) the business's general characteristics, including firm size, sector, and number of years of operation, which are discussed in the subsequent sections.

5.4.1 Female Entrepreneurs' Age Group

Table 5.1 represents the age group of female entrepreneurs and is measured using five categories. The age group of 36 to 45 years (33.2%) has the majority of the respondents, followed by 46 to 55 years (27%). Taking into account the age group, the aggregate represents 60.2% of the total sample. The least represented age group is under 25 years old in the sample. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that respondents have adequate experience and sufficient knowledge to respond to all questions.

Table 5.1 Female Entrepreneurs Age Group

<i>Female entrepreneurs age group</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Under 25 years	25	8.1	8.1
25 to 35 years	62	20.2	28.3
36 to 45 years	102	33.2	61.6
46 to 55 years	83	27	88.6
Above 55 years	35	11.4	100
Total	307	100	

5.4.2 Female Business Owners' Education Attainment

According to the data in Table 5.2, the educational attainment of female entrepreneurs falls into six distinct categories. It was found that the majority of the respondents, i.e., 103 (33.6%), hold a bachelor's degree. The next highest category is a college degree, representing 80 (26.1%) respondents of the sample, followed by the high school, master's degree holders, and professional qualification categories, making about 46 (15%), 42 (14%), 29 (9.4%), and 6 (2%) respondents, respectively. The descriptive statistics entail that 145 (47.6%) respondents hold a bachelor's or master's degree in the sample. Therefore, it is reasonable to presume that women are choosing business as a career because of the

flexibility in hours of work that paid jobs cannot provide. Nevertheless, only six respondents fall under the category of primary education. It is therefore reasonable to assume that female entrepreneurs in the sample are educated, and this result also demonstrates the education patterns of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan.

Table 5. 2 Female Business Owners' Education Attainment

<i>Female Business Owners' Education Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Primary school	6	2	2
High School (5 to 10)	46	15	16.9
College	80	26.1	43
Bachelor's degree	103	33.6	76.5
Master's Degree	43	14	90.6
Professional Qualification	29	9.4	100
Total	307	100	

5.4.3 Business Training Attended by Female Business Owners

This study also sought to establish whether respondents had attended any training sessions in the form of workshops, meetings, or seminars related to their area of operation. The table below demonstrates that about 80.8% have attended some business-related training. Only a few of the respondents, 59 out of 307 participants, have never attended any such training. The results are displayed in Table 5.3 below.

Table 5. 3 Business Training Attended by Female Business Owners

<i>Business training</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Trained	248	80.8	80.8
Non-trained	59	19.2	100
Total	307	100	

5.4.4 Female Business Owners' Prior Work Experience

Female business owners' prior work experience is measured by asking the respondents if they had any job experience prior to starting their current business. The data indicates that before venturing into entrepreneurship, all of the respondents had years of experience in various industries. The findings illustrated that about 277 (90.2%) of female entrepreneurs have over a year of employment experience.

This indicates that female entrepreneurs did pursue a career in formal employment before embarking on their own business. The largest portion of respondents, comprising 102 individuals (33.3%), belongs to the category of 1–2 years of experience, with the subsequent group being female entrepreneurs with 3–5 years of experience, accounting for 75 respondents (25.4%). As illustrated in Table 5.4, about 100 female entrepreneurs had employment experience of more than 5 years. Yet only 30 respondents (9.8%) in the sample had experience of less than a year before establishing their own business.

Table 5. 4 Work Experience of Female Business Owners

<i>Work experience</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Less than 1 year	30	9.8	9.8
1 – 2 years	102	33.3	43
3 – 5 years	75	25.4	67.4
6 – 10 years	57	18.6	86
11 – 15 years	24	7.8	93.8
Over 15 years	19	6.2	100
Total	307	100	

5.4.5 Female Entrepreneurs' Years of Business Operation

Around 41.4% of respondents in this sample have been running their businesses for around 6 to 8 years. As seen from the table below, the number of years of business operation has been measured using five categories ranging from "less than 2 years" to "above 15 years" of business operation. A significant proportion of respondents, the majority, have been in business operations for 6–8 years, with 87 participants in the 3–5 year range. Additionally, there are 43 participants (14%) who have been in business for less than 2 years. However, a smaller number, 49 respondents, have a business history exceeding 9 years. Among these, 26 participants (8.6%) have been operating their businesses for 9–15 years, while approximately 23 individuals (7.6%) have been running their businesses for over 15 years. The results clearly demonstrated that in this study, the firm-level factors being measured and their impact on female business performance are heavily contingent on the respondents' experience, seniority, and knowledge, as well as the quality of the responses received.

Table 5. 5 Female Business Owners' Years of Business Operation

<i>Years of Business Operation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Less than 2 years	43	14	14

3 – 5 years	88	28.7	42.7
6 – 8 years	127	41.4	84
9 – 15 years	26	8.6	92.5
Above 15 years	23	7.6	100
Total	307	100	

5.4.6 Distribution of Female Business Owners by Sector

Female entrepreneurs in Lahore, Pakistan, operate across various sectors, as illustrated in Table 5.6. The distribution of respondents in different service sectors is presented below. The retail sector comprises the largest segment within the study sample, accounting for 36.5%, followed by personal care (33.6%), health care (11.4%), and legal/professional services (9.8%). In contrast, the education sector has the smallest representation, constituting only 8.8% of all the service sectors in the sample.

Table 5. 6 Distribution of Female Business Owners by Sector

<i>Service Industry</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
Education	27	8.8	8.8
Retail	112	36.5	45.3
Personal care	103	33.6	78.8
Health Care	35	11.4	90.2
Legal/Professional service	30	9.8	100
Total	307	100	

5.4.7 Female Business Owners Firm size

In this study, business size is determined based on the number of employees. According to Table 5.7, a significant portion of the surveyed firms had approximately three to four (3–4) employees, constituting around 44.3% of the sample, followed by those with one to two (1-2) employees. All participating firms are categorised as micro-enterprises according to the SMEDA definition in Pakistan. As observed in the table below, only 2.6% of firms fall into the category of nine to ten (9–10) employees.

Table 5. 7 Number of Employees

<i>Number of Employees</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Cumulative Percent</i>
1-2	127	41.4	41.3
3-4	136	44.3	85.7
5-6	26	8.5	94.1
7-8	10	3.3	97.4
9-10	8	2.6	100
Total	307	100	

5.5 Signifying HOC

EC and EO are two HOCs in this study, and to estimate and validate them, this study has employed SmartPLS software (version 4). Several approaches have been proposed by researchers to estimate, specify, and validate a HOC in PLS-SEM. According to Sarstedt et al. (2019), the two-stage (embedded or disjoint) and the extended repeated indicator methods are the most widely used approaches. The disjointed two-stage technique was employed in this study to specify and validate EC and EO reflective-formative HOC. Both of these approaches have been evaluated by Becker et al. (2012) in a large-scale simulation study for reflective-reflective (Type I) and reflective-formative (Type II) HOC. Their study concluded that the two-stage approach in the path model provides improved parameter recovery for paths leading from exogenous constructs to the HOC and from the HOC to endogenous constructs. Consequently, the researcher opted for the disjoint two-stage method to assess, specify, and estimate the reflective-formative HOC for EC and EO in this study.

It is necessary to first complete the specification, estimation, and assessment of both the lower-order components and HOC, which in this case are EC and EO, before testing the hypothesis in the structural model (Sarstedt et al., 2019). In the disjoint two-stage approach, the first stage involves estimating only the lower-order components of both the first-order and the higher-order constructs concerning internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity, excluding the HOC. It is noteworthy that the researcher then needs to save the construct scores, but only those of the EC and EO LOC to be used in stage two. In stage two, the saved scores are used to build the EC and EO HOCs (Sarstedt et al., 2019).

5.6 The First Stage: Assessment of Measurement Model

Stage one begins with the assessment of first order and LOC in the measurement model. The assessment of the quality criteria starts with the evaluation of (1) internal consistency, (2) convergent validity, and (3) discriminate validity, as illustrated in figure 5.1.

Figure 5. 1 Reflective Model Assessment

Source: Hair et al. (2017)

5.6.1 Internal Consistency Reliability

Internal consistency, as per Hair et al. (2017), is a way to gauge reliability, i.e., the correlation between different indicators of the same construct. This study adopted three measures of internal consistency reliability, namely Cronbach’s alpha, composite reliability, and Dijkstra-Henseler’s rho. **Cronbach’s alpha** is a reliability measurement that is predominantly used to analyse the homogeneity of a scale and provides an estimate of the multiple items’ internal consistency. As proposed by Hair et al. (2010), a Cronbach’s alpha of 0.70 is deemed good, while a value of 0.60 or above is considered acceptable. However, in Cronbach’s alpha, every item is assumed to be equally related to the relevant construct. Unlike Cronbach’s alpha, compound reliability (P_C) is less biased since each indicator works towards its relevant construct. Therefore, this study employed composite reliability and Dijkstra-Henseler’s rho criterion as additional internal consistency metrics to address Cronbach’s alpha deficit. Similar to Cronbach’s alpha, **Composite Reliability (CR)** is also a predominately used internal consistency reliability measure. According to Hair et al. (2017), in CR, internal consistency levels between 0.70 and 0.90 are regarded as adequate or good, while values below 0.60 are deemed unreliable. The third internal consistency measure used in the present study is **Dijkstra and Henseler’s (rho_A)**. According to Dijkstra-Henseler’s rho criterion, the internal consistency measure must be greater than 0.70 (Dijkstra and Henseler, 2015). The following Table 5.8 satisfies all the internal consistency results.

Table 5. 8 Assessment of Internal Consistency (Cronbach’s Alpha, Rho_A and CR)

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Latent Variables and Items</i>	<i>Outer Loading</i>	<i>Cronbach’s Alpha</i>	<i>Rho_A</i>	<i>CR</i>	<i>Average Variance Extracted (AVE)</i>
<i>Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)</i>						

<i>Risk-Taking</i>	RIS_EO_1	0.902	0.851	0.859	0.909	0.770
	RIS_EO_2	0.844				
	RIS_EO_3	0.885				
<i>Innovativeness</i>	INN_EO_1	0.915	0.797	0.944	0.870	0.693
	INN_EO_2	0.863				
	INN_EO_3	0.707				
<i>Proactiveness</i>	PRO_EO_1	0.901	0.857	0.891	0.911	0.774
	PRO_EO_2	0.839				
	PRO_EO_3	0.908				
<i>Entrepreneurial Competencies (EC)</i>						
<i>Commitment</i>	COM_EC_1	0.861	0.809	0.850	0.874	0.639
	COM_EC_2	0.601				
	COM_EC_3	0.850				
	COM_EC_4	0.856				
<i>Organising</i>	ORG_EC_1	0.706	0.766	0.770	0.844	0.522
	ORG_EC_2	0.739				
	ORG_EC_3	0.564				
	ORG_EC_4	0.796				
	ORG_EC_5	0.785				
<i>Strategic</i>	STA_EC_1	0.877	0.827	0.871	0.883	0.654
	STA_EC_2	0.806				
	STA_EC_3	0.841				
	STA_EC_4	0.701				
<i>Conceptual</i>	CON_EC_1	0.860	0.837	0.852	0.891	0.671
	CON_EC_2	0.811				
	CON_EC_3	0.824				

	CON_EC_4	0.779				
	CON_EC_5	0.171 (n/a)				
Relationship	REL_EC_1	0.831	0.809	0.822	0.869	0.575
	REL_EC_2	0.820				
	REL_EC_3	0.533 (n/a)				
	REL_EC_4	0.816				
	REL_EC_5	0.726				
	REL_EC_6	0.578				
Opportunity	OPP_EC_1	0.766	0.798	0.803	0.868	0.621
	OPP_EC_2	0.792				
	OPP_EC_3	0.801				
	OPP_EC_4	0.792				
Human Capital						
Education	EDU_HC_1	0.838	0.809	0.816	0.887	0.723
	EDU_HC_2	0.853				
	EDU_HC_3	0.859				
Experience	EXP_HC_1	0.875	0.855	0.856	0.912	0.775
	EXP_HC_2	0.870				
	EXP_HC_3	0.896				
Training	TRA_HC_1	0.862	0.829	0.835	0.897	0.744
	TRA_HC_2	0.859				
	TRA_HC_3	0.867				
Learning Orientation	LEO_1	0.847	0.868	0.882	0.900	0.602
	LEO_2	0.806				
	LEO_3	0.697				

	LEO_4	0.731				
	LEO_5	0.791				
	LEO_6	0.773				
<i>Firm Performance</i>	PER_1	0.859	0.872	0.877	0.912	0.722
	PER_2	0.861				
	PER_3	0.860				
	PER_4	0.820				
	PER_5	0.346 (n/a)				

*n/a**: factors excluded from the measurement model due to lower loadings

As seen in the above table, all the measurements of internal consistency are reliable and valid. The constructs represent consistently good reliability, such as values of Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.766 to 0.868. Similarly, Dijkstra and Henseler's (*rho_A*) internal consistency reliability for all 14 latent constructs has been achieved and is above the 0.70 threshold, indicating high consistency reliability. Similarly, the *Pc* (Construct Reliability) exceeds the satisfactory threshold of 0.70 and ranges from 0.844 to 0.912. Figure 5.2 shows the first-order and LOC assessments (without their higher-order constructs) that must be estimated in the first stage of the separate two-stage approach. 0.844 to 0.912. Figure 5.2 shows the first-order and LOC assessments (without Figure 5.2 shows the first-order and LOC assessments (without their higher-order constructs) that must be estimated in the first stage of the separate two-stage approach.

Figure 5. 2 Stage-One Measurement Model Assessment

5.6.2 Convergent Validity

Hair et al. (2017) depict convergent validity as the degree to which a measure correlates positively with alternative measures of the same constructs. In other words, convergent validity describes the extent to which or the closeness of each indicator relates to (or converges on) the underlying construct as opposed to indicators measuring other constructs (Bhattacharjee, 2012). By examining the "Outer Loadings"

and the "*Average Variance Extracted (AVE)*," the convergent validity of a construct can be determined.

5.6.3 Factor/Outer Loading

The reliability of an indicator is referred to as the proportion of each item's outer loading or indicator variance that aids in determining the meaning of the latent variable. The item's outer loading or indicator's reliability is evaluated by determining the extent to which an item or group of items' outer loading is consistent with what it wants to capture by the construct (Wunderlich, 2013). As proposed by Hair et al. (2017), the standardised outer loading or the indicator reliability acceptable value is said to be achieved when all the outer loading is significant, i.e., the outer loading of an indicator is equal to or greater than 0.708, indicating that at least 50% of an indicator's variance is able to explain a latent variable (*note that 0.70 or close enough to 0.708 is usually considered to be*).

5.6.4 Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

The AVE is a metric which explains the variance of the indicators with its latent construct. In other words, average variance extracted (AVE) is said to be the grand mean value of all indicators that are captured by its construct (Hair et al., 2017). AVE is commonly used to establish the construct's convergent validity. The criterion proposed by Hair et al. (2017) is that an individual construct or variable should have a minimum value of 0.5 or higher to establish convergent validity, i.e., the individual construct should explain more than half of the variance of its indicators ($AVE \geq 0.50$).

5.6.5 Achieving Convergent Validity After Removal of Low Indicator

Researchers in social science often obtain loadings below 0.70 or weaker outer loadings, especially when employing newly developed scales. However, lower outer loadings should not be automatically deleted; instead, the effects of such deletion should be examined on composite reliability (CR) and content validity (Hair et al., 2017). Also, indicators should be deleted carefully, particularly those with an outer loading of between 0.40 and 0.70, only when such elimination accelerates the AVE and CR threshold values. However, indicators with outer loadings of less than 0.40 should not be retained and should be removed from the structure (Hair et al., 2011). It is worth noting that no more than 20% of the indicators should be removed from the model (Hair et al., 2013). Figure 5.3 is used to decide whether to keep or get rid of an indicator when using AVE.

Figure 5. 3 AVE relevance Testing and Outer Loading Guideline

Source: Hair et al. (2017)

The reflective measurement model in this present research was evaluated using a dataset named the Female Entrepreneurship Performance Survey (n = 307). In the data set, three exogenous constructs (along with their indicators) are variables of "**Human Capital**", namely *education* (EDU_HC_1, EDU_HC_2, and EDU_HC_3), *training* (TRA_HC_1, TRA_HC_2, and TRA_HC_3), and *experience* (EXP_HC_1, EXP_HC_2, and EXP_HC_3).

The endogenous constructs (along with their indicators) are entrepreneurial competencies, entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, and firm performance. "**Entrepreneurial Competency**" has six components, namely: *opportunity* (OPP_EC_1, OPP_EC_2, OPP_EC_3, and OPP_EC_4), *relationship* (REL_EC_1, REL_EC_2, REL_EC_3, REL_EC_4, and REL_EC_5, REL_EC_6), *organising* (ORG_EC_1, ORG_EC_2, ORG_EC_3, and ORG_EC_4), *commitment* (COM_EC_1, COM_EC_2, COM_EC_3, and COM_EC_4), *conceptual* (CON_EC_1, CON_EC_2, CON_EC_3, CON_EC_4, and CON_EC_5), and *strategic* (STA_EC_1, STA_EC_2, STA_EC_3, and STA_EC_4). Similarly, "**Entrepreneurial Orientation**" has three constructs, namely: *risk-taking* (RIS_EO_1, RIS_EO_2, and RIS_EO_3), *innovativeness* (INN_EO_1, INN_EO_2, and INN_EO_3), and *proactiveness* (PRO_EO_1, PRO_EO_2, and PRO_EO_3). "**Learning orientation**" consists of six indicators (LEO_1, LEO_2, LEO_3, LEO_4, LEO_5, and LEO_6). "**Firms Performance**" comprises five indicators (PER_1, PER_2, PER_3, PER_4, and PER_5). It is noteworthy that entrepreneurial

competency and entrepreneurial orientation are reflective-formative HOCs. Human capital components, learning orientation, and firm performance are the first-order constructs.

Table 5.8 provides each indicator's outer loadings, CR and AVE. It can be observed from Table 5.8 that not all the latent scores or the outer loadings meet the minimum threshold value of 0.70. The outer loadings of less than 0.04 were eliminated from the model due to their lack of good fit in the model. Hence, *CON_EC_5* and *PRE_5* (i.e., 0.151 and 0.333) were immediately deleted from the model. Besides this, a total of five indicators have an outer loading of ≥ 0.40 but < 0.70 . Such indicators can be retained if the constructed AVE value is greater than the 0.50 threshold. Therefore, *COM_EC_2*, *ORG_EC_3*, and *STA_EC_4* were retained as their underlying constructs' AVE were ≥ 0.50 .

In terms of relationship competency, two indicators, *REL_EC_3* (0.534) and *REL_EC_6* (0.570), were above the threshold of 0.04 yet below the 0.07 value. Similarly, the constructed AVE value was below 0.05, and it became necessary to remove one indicator. After the removal of *REL_EC_3*, the relationship construct achieved the desired AVE, i.e., > 0.50 . Thus, no further deletion was needed, and the *REL_EC_6* indicator was retained in the model. The author also ensures that not more than 20% of the indicators have been deleted from the model (Hair et al., 2017). Table 5.8 exhibits a total of 57 original indicators, and only 3 indicators are removed from the model, making 5.26% (3/57) of the deletion percentage, which is below the 20% criterion level. It can be concluded that for each of the 14 constructs, convergent validity is established as all the assigned indicators have $AVE \geq 0.50$. The next section discusses the discriminatory validity of the constructs.

5.6.6 Discriminate Validity Test

Discriminant validity refers to the distinct or uniqueness of a construct, i.e., the degree to which individual indicators differentiate themselves from another construct by an empirical standard (Hair et al., 2017). This entails that there is no correlation between the measure or construct under investigation and the other constructed measures. Therefore, the uniqueness of occurrences that are not reflected by other constructs in the model is captured by this method (Hair et al., 2013). Discriminant validity in SmartPLS software (version 4) can be assessed in three ways, as illustrated in figure 5.4 below.

Figure 5. 4 Discriminate Validity Assessment

5.6.7 The Fornell and Larcker's (1981) Criterion

In Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criterion, the square root of the AVE of each construct is compared with the square value of the remaining latent variables between the said constructs. To achieve discriminant validity, the latent variable square root of the AVE on the diagonal must be greater than the squared correlation of the remaining latent variables between the said constructs or with any other construct on the off-diagonal box (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 5. 9 Assessment of Discriminate Validity using Fornell and Larcker's (1981) Criterion

	Commitment	Conceptual	Education	Experience	Performance	Innovativeness	Learning	Opportunity	Organising	Proactiveness	Relationship	Risk-taking	Strategy	Training
Commitment	0.799													
Conceptual	0.272	0.819												
Education	0.246	0.184	0.850											
Experience	0.150	0.220	0.252	0.880										
Performance	0.422	0.354	0.202	0.255	0.850									
Innovativeness	0.092	0.151	0.004	0.181	0.117	0.833								
Learning	0.175	0.239	0.244	0.639	0.374	0.159	0.776							
Opportunity	0.520	0.288	0.205	0.241	0.396	0.147	0.216	0.788						
Organising	0.539	0.420	0.214	0.182	0.407	0.137	0.212	0.552	0.723					
Proactiveness	0.102	0.231	0.077	0.258	0.128	0.642	0.289	0.178	0.130	0.880				
Relationship	0.603	0.447	0.119	0.199	0.485	0.184	0.232	0.540	0.617	0.128	0.758			
Risk-taking	0.045	0.088	0.011	0.150	0.081	0.625	0.171	0.139	0.087	0.573	0.102	0.877		
Strategy	0.336	0.277	0.086	0.154	0.301	0.064	0.190	0.258	0.365	0.059	0.347	0.090	0.809	
Training	0.208	0.242	0.190	0.572	0.417	0.165	0.664	0.234	0.257	0.192	0.319	0.186	0.216	0.862

As illustrated in Table 5.9, the square root of **AVE** for each latent construct (value in bold) is found to exceed its corresponding inter-construct correlation in the off-diagonal position, thereby establishing discriminant validity. Overall, the reflective lower order constructs AVEs square roots of commitment (0.799),

conceptual (0.818), education (0.847), experience (0.880), innovativeness (0.833), learning orientation (0.775), opportunity (0.788), organising (0.720), performance (0.849), proactiveness (0.879), relationship (0.757), risk-taking (0.876), strategic (0.808), and training (0.863) constructs measures are all unique and valid. Both the columns and rows of off-dialogue variables show that each construct's value is higher than its other latent variables, proving discriminative validity in this study.

5.6.8 Cross Loading Criterion

Another traditional way to evaluate discriminant validity is through cross-loading. Here, on the associated construct, the outer loading of an indicator must be greater than any of its correlations (i.e., its cross loading) on other constructs (Hair et al., 2017). Ramayah et al. (2018) affirm that the indicators of different constructs shouldn't be interchangeable if the manifest construct is bigger from its designed construct than that of other constructs.

Table 5. 10 Cross Loading Criterion

	Commitment	Conceptual	Education	Experience	Innovativeness	Learning	Opportunity	Organising	Performance	Proactiveness	Relationship	Risk-taking	Strategy	Training
COM_EC_1	0.861	0.222	0.199	0.164	0.076	0.168	0.440	0.436	0.362	0.083	0.503	0.074	0.274	0.194
COM_EC_2	0.601	0.087	0.140	0.028	0.068	0.034	0.344	0.339	0.196	0.022	0.361	0.024	0.173	0.106
COM_EC_3	0.850	0.251	0.174	0.137	0.103	0.153	0.427	0.462	0.358	0.118	0.509	0.038	0.284	0.174
COM_EC_4	0.856	0.263	0.260	0.118	0.053	0.166	0.451	0.476	0.391	0.084	0.535	0.008	0.318	0.176
CON_EC_1	0.208	0.860	0.148	0.230	0.137	0.246	0.261	0.315	0.358	0.199	0.385	0.094	0.235	0.263
CON_EC_2	0.235	0.811	0.128	0.156	0.141	0.165	0.258	0.394	0.248	0.182	0.374	0.071	0.220	0.179
CON_EC_3	0.245	0.824	0.206	0.151	0.118	0.156	0.241	0.391	0.277	0.197	0.391	0.065	0.259	0.178
CON_EC_4	0.208	0.779	0.119	0.173	0.097	0.203	0.179	0.287	0.259	0.177	0.313	0.051	0.193	0.154
EDU_HC_1	0.179	0.154	0.838	0.271	-0.011	0.276	0.158	0.135	0.217	0.072	0.056	0.012	0.121	0.199
EDU_HC_2	0.222	0.163	0.853	0.184	0.030	0.196	0.183	0.187	0.149	0.077	0.107	0.050	0.033	0.164

EDU_HC_3	0.222	0.151	0.859	0.197	-0.009	0.163	0.180	0.217	0.156	0.050	0.132	-0.032	0.074	0.129
EXP_HC_1	0.119	0.176	0.181	0.875	0.173	0.545	0.188	0.169	0.191	0.231	0.176	0.125	0.187	0.502
EXP_HC_2	0.153	0.186	0.244	0.870	0.123	0.571	0.261	0.178	0.264	0.190	0.173	0.110	0.100	0.517
EXP_HC_3	0.123	0.221	0.238	0.896	0.186	0.568	0.182	0.132	0.214	0.264	0.175	0.164	0.120	0.488
INN_EO_4	0.122	0.163	0.006	0.191	0.915	0.146	0.160	0.139	0.128	0.559	0.215	0.499	0.064	0.153
INN_EO_5	0.036	0.127	0.020	0.149	0.863	0.156	0.084	0.107	0.110	0.564	0.115	0.570	0.067	0.158
INN_EO_6	0.043	0.041	-0.036	0.070	0.707	0.074	0.113	0.078	0.003	0.516	0.081	0.592	0.005	0.082
LEO_1	0.186	0.225	0.192	0.491	0.122	0.847	0.204	0.186	0.342	0.266	0.221	0.181	0.205	0.623
LEO_2	0.098	0.205	0.170	0.492	0.123	0.806	0.220	0.163	0.308	0.240	0.143	0.133	0.157	0.582
LEO_3	0.077	0.143	0.148	0.456	0.124	0.697	0.107	0.131	0.227	0.187	0.162	0.126	0.090	0.427
LEO_4	0.093	0.145	0.195	0.446	0.187	0.731	0.099	0.134	0.232	0.224	0.148	0.140	0.079	0.477
LEO_5	0.138	0.166	0.200	0.532	0.094	0.791	0.136	0.193	0.317	0.192	0.155	0.084	0.156	0.452
LEO_6	0.194	0.205	0.228	0.553	0.111	0.773	0.204	0.165	0.287	0.231	0.240	0.129	0.163	0.497
OPP_EC_1	0.387	0.211	0.166	0.146	0.080	0.135	0.766	0.410	0.320	0.110	0.424	0.134	0.207	0.113
OPP_EC_2	0.412	0.281	0.165	0.208	0.138	0.198	0.792	0.456	0.369	0.170	0.477	0.104	0.205	0.213
OPP_EC_3	0.436	0.178	0.150	0.210	0.114	0.215	0.801	0.455	0.283	0.114	0.403	0.121	0.226	0.249
OPP_EC_4	0.403	0.231	0.166	0.189	0.125	0.120	0.792	0.413	0.265	0.162	0.389	0.079	0.173	0.146
ORG_EC_1	0.394	0.238	0.138	0.108	0.032	0.154	0.388	0.706	0.258	0.003	0.422	0.042	0.357	0.158
ORG_EC_2	0.368	0.267	0.188	0.094	0.107	0.121	0.424	0.739	0.280	0.093	0.454	0.083	0.254	0.180
ORG_EC_3	0.273	0.533	0.134	0.125	0.175	0.156	0.244	0.564	0.273	0.200	0.375	0.022	0.101	0.163

ORG_EC_4	0.459	0.237	0.161	0.197	0.093	0.186	0.498	0.796	0.334	0.090	0.520	0.073	0.337	0.243
ORG_EC_5	0.438	0.225	0.148	0.116	0.071	0.138	0.420	0.785	0.307	0.062	0.433	0.089	0.272	0.165
PER_1	0.418	0.329	0.229	0.256	0.065	0.352	0.377	0.405	0.859	0.143	0.440	0.076	0.299	0.403
PER_2	0.334	0.279	0.114	0.177	0.094	0.311	0.347	0.344	0.861	0.053	0.427	0.021	0.281	0.339
PER_3	0.337	0.318	0.184	0.233	0.095	0.318	0.296	0.368	0.860	0.088	0.395	0.081	0.239	0.353
PER_4	0.338	0.273	0.151	0.194	0.153	0.286	0.321	0.254	0.820	0.152	0.382	0.102	0.194	0.313
PRO_EO_1	0.115	0.218	0.091	0.231	0.586	0.251	0.155	0.102	0.122	0.901	0.096	0.517	0.084	0.169
PRO_EO_2	0.099	0.155	0.078	0.201	0.563	0.214	0.116	0.095	0.086	0.830	0.142	0.540	0.049	0.123
PRO_EO_3	0.062	0.224	0.042	0.243	0.555	0.288	0.187	0.140	0.123	0.908	0.112	0.479	0.026	0.200
REL_EC_1	0.562	0.294	0.136	0.182	0.070	0.193	0.427	0.517	0.447	0.056	0.821	0.028	0.339	0.259
REL_EC_2	0.512	0.351	0.082	0.149	0.158	0.146	0.466	0.504	0.427	0.098	0.820	0.094	0.251	0.253
REL_EC_4	0.514	0.290	0.090	0.163	0.105	0.210	0.454	0.559	0.420	0.009	0.816	0.012	0.318	0.255
REL_EC_5	0.408	0.253	0.027	0.114	0.151	0.169	0.428	0.417	0.293	0.149	0.726	0.121	0.213	0.260
REL_EC_6	0.244	0.548	0.115	0.141	0.240	0.164	0.248	0.310	0.213	0.203	0.578	0.156	0.174	0.172
RIS_EO_7	0.053	0.115	0.041	0.160	0.564	0.157	0.148	0.063	0.064	0.530	0.111	0.902	0.027	0.183
RIS_EO_8	0.029	0.041	-0.042	0.100	0.572	0.110	0.100	0.059	0.054	0.468	0.088	0.844	0.098	0.117
RIS_EO_9	0.036	0.070	0.021	0.131	0.515	0.178	0.115	0.104	0.094	0.508	0.070	0.885	0.114	0.183
STA_EC_1	0.311	0.265	0.065	0.145	0.072	0.195	0.210	0.296	0.323	0.076	0.303	0.093	0.877	0.185
STA_EC_2	0.240	0.279	0.072	0.124	0.102	0.103	0.169	0.299	0.216	0.064	0.284	0.102	0.806	0.175
STA_EC_3	0.297	0.197	0.087	0.160	0.013	0.202	0.264	0.344	0.225	0.023	0.296	0.058	0.841	0.227

STA_EC_4	0.222	0.120	0.053	0.024	0.005	0.073	0.194	0.229	0.177	0.013	0.229	0.015	0.701	0.076
TRA_HC_1	0.162	0.203	0.116	0.513	0.120	0.548	0.191	0.192	0.366	0.184	0.254	0.155	0.178	0.862
TRA_HC_2	0.196	0.185	0.212	0.500	0.146	0.597	0.198	0.219	0.365	0.179	0.251	0.196	0.166	0.859
TRA_HC_3	0.180	0.233	0.162	0.471	0.158	0.573	0.213	0.249	0.349	0.138	0.312	0.136	0.211	0.867

All the indicators' outer loading can be seen in Table 5.10, and the highest outer loading value is highlighted and in bold. It is observed that the construct or indicators assigned to a specific construct are greater than other constructs or their cross-loadings. Therefore, all construct loads are high on their assigned constructs, and the cross-loading value is below the outer loading, as indicated in Table 5.10. This signifies that the constructs are distinct from each other, thereby achieving discriminant validity. The next step is to check the discriminant validity with the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) criterion.

5.6.9 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) Criterion

Although the Fornell-Larker criterion and cross-loadings analysis are widely used in applied research, neither method reliably detects discriminant validity issues (Hair et al., 2017). Henseler et al. (2015) identified that both approaches, including the cross-loading Fornell-Larker criterion, fail to detect or are insufficiently sensitive to reliably detect the lack of discriminate validity in variance-based structural equation modelling. Hence, Henseler et al. (2015) devised the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlations as a better and more reliable way to measure the validity of a discriminant.

HTMT is cited as an estimation of indicator correlations between constructs and correlations within indicators of the same constructs. In essence, HTMT measures statistically how much two latent variables distinguish if they are perfectly measured or what the true correlation is between two constructs if they are perfectly reliable with no error (Hair et al., 2017). Consequently, the HTMT approach ensures that each construct is truly distinct from one another in a study and is a more comprehensive and less constrained approach to discriminate the validity criterion (Voorhees et al., 2016).

According to the HTMT criterion, a lack of discriminant validity can be concluded if the HTMT value is greater than an exact threshold level. Nevertheless, the threshold for HTMT is debatable in the existing literature. Hensel et al. (2015) have proposed that discriminant validity is achieved when the HTMT value is below the 0.85 threshold value. However, Teo et al. (2008) adopted a less stringent value and proposed a threshold value of 0.90. Hence, discriminate validity is established if the HTMT value is less than:

- HTMT value is below threshold of 0.85 or/and
- HTMT value is below threshold of 0.9

Table 5. 11 Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) Criterion

	Commitment	Conceptual	Education	Experience	Performance	Innovativeness	Learning	Opportunity	Organising	Proactiveness	Relationship	Risk-taking	Strategy	Training
Commitment														
Conceptual	0.315													
Education	0.297	0.223												
Experience	0.168	0.256	0.307											
Performance	0.485	0.406	0.241	0.292										
Innovativeness	0.104	0.160	0.039	0.198	0.134									
Learning	0.190	0.270	0.296	0.740	0.421	0.183								
Opportunity	0.647	0.347	0.254	0.287	0.468	0.176	0.245							
Organising	0.680	0.526	0.267	0.219	0.489	0.160	0.254	0.699						
Proactiveness	0.128	0.266	0.097	0.300	0.146	0.787	0.328	0.207	0.159					
Relationship	0.729	0.559	0.157	0.239	0.567	0.212	0.276	0.663	0.774	0.172				
Risk-taking	0.059	0.099	0.066	0.175	0.096	0.800	0.196	0.167	0.105	0.678	0.137			
Strategy	0.395	0.318	0.108	0.167	0.338	0.082	0.200	0.316	0.455	0.072	0.415	0.106		
Training	0.249	0.281	0.235	0.680	0.488	0.190	0.773	0.280	0.315	0.223	0.386	0.220	0.245	

As demonstrated from the above table, all the HTMT values are below the required threshold value of HTMT, i.e., 0.85, and thus it can be stated that discriminant validity has been achieved for the construct in this study. The next section is the measurement of EC and EO reflective-formative HOC.

5.7 Second Stage: Estimation of Higher-Order Constructs (HOC)

Unlike the repeated indicator approach, no HOC is drawn in the disjoint two-stage approach at stage one (see figure 5.2). Initially, all the LOC reliability and validity are assessed in the first stage. Once the reflective measurement models first order and the LOC satisfy all assessment criteria (convergent validity, internal consistency, and discriminate validity; see Section 5.6), the latent variable score of the lower order components, i.e., the EC and EO constructs, is saved. In stage two, the LOC latent variable scores obtained from stage one are used to build the EC and EO HOC (Sarstedt et al., 2019), as demonstrated in figure 5.5. At stage two, the EC and EO HOC assessments begin. Both the HOCs need to be validated before testing the hypothesis in the structural model (Sarstedt et al., 2019). Consequently, EC and EO reflective-formative HOC will be examined by determining their convergent validity (redundancy analysis), collinearity and relevance of the weights, and significance (Hair et al., 2019).

Figure 5. 5 SmartPLS Graphical Output: Second Stage Model

5.7.1 Formative Higher-Order Construct (HOC) Validation

Notably, the latent variable scores of EC-LOC (opportunity, relationship, organising, commitment, and strategic conceptual) and EO-LOC (risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness) acquired from stage one are utilised to validate the EO and EC reflective-formative HOC in stage two. Sarstedt et al. (2019) describe a three-step process for validating reflective-formative HOC, which is discussed below.

5.7.1.1 Step 1: Assess Convergent Validity of EC and EO Formative HOC

In order to validate formative HOC, convergent validity is performed, which is achieved by running a redundancy analysis (Hair et al., 2019). According to Hair et al. (2017), a redundancy analysis determines the extent to which a construct (formative measure) correlates highly with a reflective measure of the same phenomenon or construct. In redundancy analysis, each formative specified construct is related to an alternative single item measurement of it. A global single-item measure acts as a criterion construct that captures the respondent's general assessment of that formative specific construct (Hair et al., 2017). Here, the formative model serves as an exogenous construct linked to an endogenous construct (i.e., global single-item) that measures the same phenomenon (Cheah et al., 2018).

In the first stage of validating EC and EO formative second-order constructs, a redundancy analysis is performed to assess their convergent validity (Sarstedt et al., 2019). To carry out the redundancy analysis, the EC and EO (exogenous) constructs are related to an alternative global single-item (endogenous) measurement, as shown below.

Figure 5. 6 EC HOC Redundancy Analysis

As figure 5.6 indicates, the EC construct comprises six lower-order components, namely commitment, conceptual, opportunity, organising, relationship, and strategic. These components are the latent variable scores of lower-order components that were saved and later added as new variables to the dataset. Running a redundancy analysis on the alternative single-item measure yields a path coefficient of 8.375 (running 5000 subsamples), which is evidently higher than the 0.7 threshold (Sarstedt et al.,

2019). Consequently, EC HOC convergent validity has been established and can be used for further analysis.

Figure 5. 7 EO HOC Redundancy Analysis

The EO construct as illustrated in figure 5.7 now contains three components, namely risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness, which are created using the latent variable score of the lower-order components obtained from stage one. The assessment of the formative EO second-order construct begins with running a redundancy analysis, i.e., measuring EO with an alternative single-item measure of entrepreneurial behaviour. The global single-item, as asserted by Cheah et al. (2018), is intended to capture the essence of the construct it purports to measure. The redundancy analysis yields a point estimate of 8.606 (run 5000 subsamples), which is evidently higher than the 0.7 threshold (Cheah et al., 2018). Therefore, EO HOC convergent validity has been established and can be used for further analysis. The next step is linked to potential collinearity issues.

5.7.1.2 Step 2: Assessment of Multicollinearity Issue Among LOC of the HOC

Multicollinearity can influence the estimation of weights and, consequently, their statistical estimation. Formative indicators with high collinearity are a critical issue. In practice, collinearity can have an impact on analysis outcomes in two ways. Firstly, standard error accelerates due to boosts in collinearity. More specifically, in PLS-SEM analysis, this is particularly problematic in smaller sample sizes where the standard error is normally greater because of sampling error. Second, weights can be wrongly estimated due to high collinearity and sign reversal of the weaker indicators, which can lead to a false conclusion (Hair et al., 2017).

- **Checking Potential Collinearity Issues**

In this study, multicollinearity is checked among all the lower-order constructs of EC (commitment, conceptual, organising, strategic, opportunity, and conceptual), EO constructs (risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness), and first-order constructs (i.e., education, training, experience, and firm performance). When assessing lateral collinearity among constructs, a VIF value of 5 or greater is considered "critical," whereas a VIF value of 3.3 or greater is considered "possible." However, ideally,

the VIF value should be smaller than 3, the threshold value (Hair et al., 2019). Table 5.12 shows the VIF value of all constructs in the study.

Table 5. 12 Lateral Collinearity Assessment

<i>Lower-Order Components</i>	<i>Entrepreneurial Orientation</i>	<i>Entrepreneurial Competencies</i>	<i>Education</i>	<i>Experience</i>	<i>Training</i>	<i>Learning Orientation</i>	<i>Firm Performance</i>
<i>Innovativeness</i>	2.041						
<i>Proactiveness</i>	1.854						
<i>Risk-Taking</i>	1.788						
<i>Commitment</i>		1.812					
<i>Conceptual</i>		1.327					
<i>Opportunity</i>		1.668					
<i>Organising</i>		1.995					
<i>Relationship</i>		2.171					
<i>Strategy</i>		1.220					
<i>EDU_HC_1</i>			1.826				
<i>EDU_HC_2</i>			1.757				
<i>EDU_HC_3</i>			1.717				
<i>EXP_HC_1</i>				2.157			
<i>EXP_HC_2</i>				1.936			
<i>EXP_HC_3</i>				2.471			
<i>TRA_HC_1</i>					2.001		
<i>TRA_HC_2</i>					1.943		
<i>TRA_HC_3</i>					1.774		
<i>LEO_1</i>						2.719	
<i>LEO_2</i>						2.429	
<i>LEO_3</i>						2.274	
<i>LEO_4</i>						2.429	
<i>LEO_5</i>						2.003	

LEO_6						1.887	
PER_1							2.172
PER_2							2.287
PER_3							2.300
PER_4							1.935

All the constructs in Table 5.12 have a VIF value below the threshold values of 5 and 3.3 (Hair et al., 2017), establishing that the issue of collinearity is not a concern in this study. The inner VIF values of the antecedent constructs, i.e., education, training, and experience, along with their master variables (treated as endogenous variables in PLS), i.e., EC, EO, and learning orientation, as well as their endogenous variables (dependent variable), firm performance, have a VIF value well below the threshold of 3.3, suggesting that all the constructs are distinct from each other in this study and multicollinearity is not a critical issue.

5.7.1.3 Step 3: Examining the Formative Indicators for Their Relevance and Significance

In the third step of validating the EO and EC HOC, the relationship between HOC and its lower-order dimensions was examined by running a 5000 subsamples bootstrap to determine their relevance and significance. Cheah et al. (2018) state that these links represent the weights of the HOC, yet they are shown as path coefficients in the PLS path model, as demonstrated in Table 5.13.

Table 5. 13 Significance Level Between the Formative LOC and HOC

<i>Formative Construct Relationship</i>	<i>Outer Weights</i>	<i>T-Value</i>	<i>P-Value Significance</i> <i>(p<0.05)</i>	<i>Outer Loading</i>	<i>P-Value Significance</i> <i>(p<0.05)</i>	<i>Decision</i>
<i>Innovativeness → EO</i>	0.452	1.247	0.212	0.848	0.000	supported
<i>Proactiveness → EO</i>	0.714	2.198	0.028	0.947	0.000	supported
<i>Risk-taking → EO</i>	-0.100	0.285	0.776	0.592	0.007	supported
<i>Commitment → EC</i>	0.169	1.297	0.195	0.701	0.000	supported
<i>Conceptual → EC</i>	0.380	3.283	0.001	0.721	0.000	supported
<i>Strategic → EC</i>	0.171	1.516	0.130	0.539	0.000	supported
<i>Organising → EC</i>	0.085	0.643	0.520	0.736	0.000	supported
<i>Relationship → EC</i>	0.286	2.015	0.044	0.828	0.000	supported
<i>Opportunity → EC</i>	0.293	2.456	0.014	0.736	0.000	Supported

In light of the findings shown in Table 5.13, it is clear that all of the formative indicators, with the exception of innovation, risk-taking, commitment, strategic, and organising, exhibit statistical significance at the 5% level. When the outer weight of a formative indicator is not significant, Hair et al. (2017) suggest that indicators need to be interpreted in accordance with their respective outer loadings, and the indicator must be held and taken into consideration as absolutely necessary if the outside loading is significant and greater than 0.50. Using this information, it is evident that the outer loadings of innovation (0.848), risk-taking (0.592), commitment (0.701), strategic (0.539), and organising (0.736) are significant and outperform the 0.50 threshold. Hence, all the indicators of the formative construct are retained, even if their outer weights are insignificant, and can be further utilised for the evaluation of structural models.

5.8 Structural Model Evaluation and Testing Hypothesis

Once the validity and reliability of both the LOC and HOC in the measurement model (the outer model) have been established as reported in the previous section, the following section embarks on the structural model assessment, where the developed hypothesis is analysed. Further to the measurement model evaluation, Hair et al. (2017) assert that in the process of structural model evaluation, the PLS-SEM evaluates the structural model based on heuristic criteria, determining the model's predictive capabilities. This is in contrast to the goodness-of-fit measure metric, which is carried out during the process of measurement model evaluation. The structural model comprises six steps as key criteria, as exhibited in figure 5.8, which are applied in the next sections. These criteria are the initial step involved in the assessment of structural model assessment for collinearity issues; the second step takes in the relevance and significance of the structural model relationships; the third step involves the assessment of the level of R^2 value; the fourth step includes the effect size (f^2); the fifth step is related to the assessment of predictive relevance Q^2 and the q^2 effect size; and finally, the sixth step is the PLS predict.

Figure 5. 8 Steps of Structural Model Assessment

Source: Hair et al. (2017)

5.8.1 Step 1: Evaluate Collinearity Issues

The VIF measure is used in the investigation to determine whether or not there is any collinearity in the sample being studied. According to the VIF measure, all of the lower-order components are significantly lower than the VIF threshold value of 3. The results are highlighted in great detail in Section 5.7.1.2.

5.8.2 Step 2: Determining the Relevance and Significance of Structural Model Relationships (β)

The assessment of a structural model begins with the estimation of the hypothesised relationship among the constructs (i.e., the path coefficients). As mentioned earlier, the latent score of LOC is used to create the EC and EO HOC, and later their relationship is estimated in stage two, i.e., the structural model (Sarstedt et al., 2019), as demonstrated in figure 5.5. To test the relationships significance, a bootstrap (5000 sample) is run (Hair et al., 2017), and the empirical *p-value* and *t-value* are computed by the bootstrap standard error for all structured path coefficients. To validate hypothesised paths, the *t-value* (or *p-value*) must be significant. There is a significant level of 0.05 (or $p < 0.05$) for parameters with an absolute t-value greater than the 1.96 threshold. A significant level of 0.01 (or $p < 0.01$) is indicated when the t-value is greater than the 2.58 threshold. Similarly, in cases where the significant level is 0.001 (or $p < 0.001$), the t-value is greater than the 3.26 threshold. PLS analysis of the structural model gives path coefficients, so the bootstrapping function was used to make path coefficients, t-statistics, and the test of significance level for all paths. The results are shown in Table 5.14.

Table 5. 14 Structural Model Assessment and Testing Hypothesis (Direct Relationship)

Hypothesis	Relationship	Path Coefficient	t-Values	p-Values	95% BC _a confidence interval	Decision (p<0.05)?
H1a	Education → EC	0.166	2.574	0.010	[0.038, 0.290]	Yes
H1b	Experience → EC	0.084	1.231	0.218	[-0.050, 0.213]	No
H1c	Training → EC	0.266	3.761	0.000	[0.109, 0.389]	Yes
H2	EC → Firm Performance	0.483	8.829	0.000	[0.366, 0.584]	Yes
H3	EC → EO	0.227	3.865	0.000	[0.083, 0.319]	Yes
H4	EO → Firm Performance	-0.036	0.649	0.517	[-0.156, 0.060]	No
H6	EC → Learning Orientation	0.301	5.947	0.000	[0.181, 0.378]	Yes
H7	Learning Orientation → Firm Performance	0.238	4.642	0.000	[0.142, 0.342]	Yes

5.8.2.1 Results

Hypothesis 1a - 1c, investigating the direct relationship of education on the development of EC.

H1a investigates whether education attainment has a significant impact on the development of entrepreneurial competencies. The results in Table 5.14 reveal that female business owners' education attainment has a positive and robust direct effect on their entrepreneurial competencies' development. The result is shown as path coefficients, i.e., (β) of 0.391 and a t-value of 2.574, and therefore supports hypothesis 1a.

H1b proposes that the previous work experience of female business owners has a significant positive impact on the development of entrepreneurial competencies. The results depicted in Table 5.14 reveal that previous work experience has an insignificant effect on EC with a path coefficient (β) of 0.084 and a t-value of 1.231, less than the ± 1.96 threshold. Thus, hypothesis 1b is not supported.

H1c suggests that business training has a positive direct impact on entrepreneurial competencies' development. As demonstrated in Table 5.14, the path coefficient (β) of 0.266 has a t-value of 3.761, which is above the threshold of ± 1.96 . The results ultimately support hypothesis 1c.

In this study, three antecedents of EC are proposed, namely, education attainment, previous work experience, and business training. On the basis of the above findings, it is evident that business training is a robust antecedent of entrepreneurial competencies, followed by education attainment. However, it turns out that previous work experience has no significant relationship with the development of EC.

Hypothesis 2 – investigation of a direct association between EC and firm performance

The results in Table 5.14 also exhibit that EC is a strong predictor of firm performance and thereby supports H2. Notably, among all other hypotheses, EC has the strongest path coefficient ($\beta = 0.483$) with a t-value of 8.829, which is way above the threshold of ± 1.96 . The results support hypothesis 2 and are in agreement with the current literature.

Hypothesis 3 – investigation of a direct association between EC and EO

The H3 proposes that EC have a direct and positive impact on EO. Table 5.14 demonstrates that H3 has a path coefficient (β) of 0.227 and a t-value of 3.865, which is clearly above the threshold of ± 1.96 . The findings therefore support hypothesis 3.

Hypothesis 4 -- investigation of a direct association among EO and firm performance

The results illustrate that entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance have a statistically negative but insignificant relationship, as demonstrated in Table 5.14. The path coefficient (β) of -0.036 and the

t-value of 0.649 are well below the threshold of ± 1.96 . Therefore, the findings, in turn, do not support hypothesis 4.

Hypothesis 5 – investigation of mediating effect of EO on the relationship between EC and firm performance

The mediation effect of EO on EC and firm performance is shown in Table 5.15. The results reveal a statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$) mediating role of EO ($\beta = -0.008$, $t = 0.585$, $p = 0.559$), and therefore EO did not mediate the relationship between EC and firm performance.

Hypothesis 6 – investigating a direct impact of EC on learning orientation.

It is hypothesised that EC has a positive and direct impact on learning orientation. The results, as illustrated in Table 5.14, reveal a robust relationship with a path coefficient (β) of 0.301 and an absolute t-value of 5.947, surpassing the required criteria (i.e., $+1.96$). The findings, in turn, lend support to hypothesis 6.

Hypothesis 7 – investigating a direct association among learning orientation and firm performance

The final hypothesis of the study proposes a positive relationship between learning orientation and firm performance. The data in Table 5.14 reveals a positive and statistically significant association between learning orientation and firm performance, with a path coefficient (β) of 0.238 and a t-value of 4.642. This t-value significantly exceeds the criteria, providing support for Hypothesis 7.

As a result, H1a, H1c, H2, H3, H6, and H7 are supported, whereas H1b, H4, and H5 are not supported at the 5% level of significance.

5.8.2.2 The Mediator Analysis

The proposed conceptual framework also comprises a mediator, namely EO. The association between EC and firm performance is mediated by EO. However, Zhao et al. (2010) opine that a mediator must meet certain requirements in order to prove that mediation is happening and to determine whether it is fully or partially mediating.

Three paths exist in the assessment of a mediator: the independent and the mediator variable; the independent and the dependent variable; and the mediator and the dependent variable. In the context of mediation, a condition of partial mediation would be the scenario in which the predictor (independent variable) may have less of an impact on the dependent variable in the occurrence of a mediator. In the same way, the condition is referred to as "full mediation" if the predictor (independent variable) has its complete effect on the mediating variable but has no meaningful effect on the dependent variable.

A mediation analysis was carried out to determine the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on mediating the relationship between entrepreneurial competences and firm performance. The findings, which are

presented in Table 5.15, indicate that there is a statistically significant total effect of EC on firm performance (H3: $\beta=0.547$, $t=10.995$, $p<.001$). With the inclusion of the mediating variable (EO), the relationship between EC and firm performance still remained statistically significant ($\beta=0.483$, $t=8.829$, $p<.001$). However, the indirect effect of EC on firm performance through EO was found to be insignificant ($\beta=-0.008$, $t=0.585$, $p=0.559$). In light of these findings, it is clear that there is no mediating effect and that there is only a direct effect of EC on firm performance, as exhibited in Table 5.15.

Table 5. 15 Testing Mediation

Hypothesis	Total effect (EC → Firm Performance)		Direct effect (EC → Firm Performance)		Indirect Effect EC on firm performance					Decision
	Path Coefficient	P-value	Path Coefficient	P-value	Relationship	Path Coefficient	T-value	P-value	95% BC _a confidence interval	
H5	0.547	0.000	0.483	0.000	EC → EO → Firm Performance	-0.008	0.585	0.559	[-0.042, 0.015]	No Mediation

5.8.3 Step 3: Level of R² assessment (Coefficient of Determination)

Since the goodness-of-fit test is not considered an established global metric inside a PLS-SEM framework (Hair et al., 2017), researchers must report R² values (coefficient of determination) in their models for all endogenous constructs when utilising the PLS-SEM approach (Hair et al., 2019). The R² (coefficient of determination) is the most commonly used statistic for measuring the predictive power of a model. R² is determined as the squared correlation between the actual and predicted values of a given endogenous construct. More precisely, R² shows how much variance exists in the endogenous constructs explained by all of the exogenous constructs related to them. According to Hair et al. (2017), the R² effect has a range between 0 and 1 and exhibits a higher level of predicative accuracy when the value is greater. Given the complexity of models and the wide range of fields that have adopted R², it is difficult to establish a guideline for acceptable R². However, Chin (2010) suggests that values (R²) that are deemed acceptable are 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19, indicating substantial, moderate, and weak levels of predictive accuracy for endogenous latent variables.

5.8.3.1 Endogenous constructs R² values interpretation

Although the model recognises four endogenous components (EC, EO, LO, and firm performance), firm performance is the primary endogenous construct. The firm performance endogenous construct produces an R² value of 0.349, which demonstrates a reasonable level of predictive accuracy, as exhibited in Table 5.16. This explains that the predictors EC, EO, and LO in the exogenous constructs jointly explain 34% of the variance in the endogenous construct. Following this, the R² values of EC (0.155), EO (0.051), and LO (0.090) can be addressed as weak levels of predictive accuracy.

Table 5.16 Total Variance Explained in Endogenous (Dependent) Constructs

Constructs	Variance Explained (R ² value)
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	5.1 percent
Entrepreneurial Competencies (EC)	15.5 percent
Learning Orientation	9 percent
Firm Performance	34 percent

5.8.4 Step 4: Effect size (f^2) Assessment

Although the *p-value* displays whether or not an effect exists, it, however, fails to reveal how big the effect is. Both the *p-value* (statistical significance) and the effect size (substantive significance) are imperative outcomes to be presented when reporting and evaluating studies (Sullivan and Feinn, 2012). According to Hair et al. (2017), the effect size (f^2) in a model explains that when a specified (independent) exogenous variable is omitted from the model, the change in R² value can be used to examine whether the omitted construct has a substantive impact on the independent (endogenous) construct. The influence of effects can be substantial (0.35), moderate (0.15), or minimal (0.02) on the exogenous latent variables (Jony and Serradell-Lopez, 2021). The effect size (f^2) formula is as follows:

Here:

f^2 = effect size

R^2_{included} = Value of R² with the particular exogenous variable

R^2_{excluded} = Value of R² without the particular exogenous variable

5.8.5.1 Effect Size (f^2) Interpretation and Reporting of this Study

Table 5.17 below depicts the f^2 effect size results and exhibits that in terms of the relationship between EC → performance (f^2 =0.317) have a medium effect size while education → EC (f^2 =0.033), training → EC (f^2 =0.035), EC → EO (f^2 =0.055), EC → Learning Orientation (f^2 =0.099) and Learning Orientation → performance (f^2 =0.076) has a small effect. However, experience → EC (f^2 =0.011) and EO → performance (f^2 =0.002) have no effect size.

Table 5. 17 Explanatory Power; the Effect Size (f^2)

<i>Predictor(s)</i>	<i>Outcome(s)</i>	<i>R² value</i>	<i>f-squared</i>	<i>Effect Size (f^2)</i>	<i>Q² predict</i>
Education	EC	0.155	0.031	Small effect	0.113
Experience			0.005	No effect	
Training			0.056	Small effect	
EC	EO	0.051	0.054	Small effect	0.025
EC	Learning Orientation	0.090	0.076	Small effect	0.149
EC	Performance	0.349	0.318	Medium effect	0.129
EO			0.002	No effect	
Learning Orientation			0.076	Small effect	

5.8.5 Step 5: Predictive Relevance (Q^2 value) Assessment by Blindfolding Method

It has been emphasised by Hair et al. (2017) for researchers to make use of the Q^2 value, which evaluates the model's predictive relevance or out-of-sample predictive power, as an additional approach alongside the R^2 value, which is a metric of predictive accuracy. This means how well the model can predict data that was not used to make the estimate.

It is necessary to perform a blindfolding procedure in order to determine the predictive relevance (Q^2 value). The blindfolding procedure is based on a resampling technique that systematically omits and predicts every data point of the indicators of the endogenous construct with a reflective measurement model specification (Sarstedt et al., 2014). This procedure is used to compare the original values with the predicted values. A minor difference in predicted and original values is said to have a higher predictive accuracy, thereby a higher Q^2 value. In particular, the omission distance (D), which is set at a re-determined distance between 5 and 10, removes every n th data point from the data set using a blindfold procedure (Jony and Serradell-Lopez, 2021). If the Q^2 value is greater than 0, it shows that a certain endogenous construct of the PLS-path model has predictive value.

5.8.5.1 Q^2 Value Interpretation and Reporting of this Study

Following the blindfold technique, the results are outlined in Table 5.17. All endogenous constructions' Q^2 values were **EC** (0.113), **EO** (0.025), and **learning orientation** (0.149), all of which have a Q^2 value

greater than zero, thereby establishing predictive relevance. The *firm performance* endogenous construct Q^2 value of **0.129** demonstrates that the model has weak predictive power.

5.8.6 Step 6: Out-of-Sample Predictive Power: PLSpredict Assessment

In any research, an essential aspect is assessing a statistical model's predictive power. According to Shmueli et al. (2019), several researchers place emphasis on evaluating the hypothesised directions; models are meaningful; and coefficients are significant as an overarching aim, as opposed to whether a model can predict new cases. Explanatory modelling, which tries to "test or quantify the underlying causal relationship between effects that can be generalised from the sample to the population of interest," has traditionally been given more weight in research than prediction (Shmueli et al., 2016, p. 4553). PLSpredict, built by Shmueli et al. (2016), is a holdout-sample-based approach that generates case-level predictions on a construct level or on an item to reap the benefits of predictive model assessment in PLS-SEM. PLSpredict proposes a way to measure a model's out-of-sample predictive power, or how well it can be used to predict the outcomes of new cases (Shmueli et al., 2019). R^2 and Q^2 are standard metrics for evaluating structural models.

5.8.6.1 Interpreting PLSpredict Outcome

When running PLSpredict, a key target construct or a specific endogenous construct needs to be selected that the researcher wants to test the predictive power of the model as opposed to addressing all of the endogenous constructs in the path model. According to Shmueli et al. (2019), researchers initially need to interpret the Q^2_{predict} statistics to ensure all indicators' Q^2_{predict} values outperform the most native benchmark, i.e., $Q^2_{\text{predict}} \leq 0$. The next step is to examine the prediction statistics, which means comparing the RMSE (or MAE) values of those indicators with a Q^2_{predict} value < 0 to the naïve LM benchmark. In most instances, RMSE is preferable to MAE; the latter should only be used when the distribution of predicted errors is extremely asymmetric. The following rules apply when comparing the value of the RMSE (or the MAE) with the LM value of each indicator (Hair et al., 2019).

Table 5. 18 Guideline for Interpreting PLSpredict

<i>Endogenous/dependent construct</i>	<i>PLS-SEM analysis smaller than LM</i>	<i>Guideline</i>
For none of the indicators	PLS-SEM < LM	A model lacks predictive power when none of the indicators of endogenous constructs in the PLS-SEM analysis yields lower prediction error in terms of RMSE/MAE compared to the naïve LM benchmark.
For a minority of the indicators	PLS-SEM < LM	The predictive power of a model is considered low when only a few of the indicators of endogenous constructs in the PLS-SEM analysis yield a smaller prediction error in terms of RMSE/MAE compared to the naïve LM benchmark.
For a majority of the indicators	PLS-SEM < LM	The predictive power of a model is medium when a majority number of the endogenous construct's indicators in the PLS-SEM analysis yield smaller prediction errors in terms of RMSE/MAE compared to the naïve LM benchmark.
For all indicators	PLS-SEM < LM	The predictive power of a model is high when it has lower RMSE/MAE values than the naïve LM benchmark for all indicators in a PLS-SEM analysis.

Source: Adapted from Shmueli et al. (2019)

5.8.6.2 Reporting PLSpredict Outcome

In order to do the analysis, PLS predicts divides the entire dataset into equal subgroups (k), leaving one sample as a holdout sample. The size of the holdout sample is an important consideration in order to produce a robust estimation. The recommended minimum size of the holdout sample, as per Hair et al. (2020), should be 30. To illustrate, in the present study, there are 307 cases; the number of subgroups is 10 ($307 \div 10 = 30.7$); the holdout sample is 30.7, which is above the recommended criterion of 30 by Hair et al. (2020); the analysis will run on ($30.7 * 9 = 276$). Another key relevance is that, when assessing the PLSpredict model, it is also important to concentrate on the main endogenous construct of the model. As a result, female firm performance is the key construct and the primary focus of analysis in the model. Nevertheless, the interpretation process must include all endogenous construct indicator prediction statistics.

In the initial step, it is observed that all the indicators yield a $Q^2_{predict}$ above zero, i.e., all the endogenous constructs outperform the native benchmark (see Table 5.19). Next, prediction statistics were examined in greater detail for a better understanding of prediction error. It was found that although the PLS-SEM errors are not normally distributed, the prediction errors are visually inspected to indicate that the distribution is not highly non-symmetrical. Thus, RMSE was used as the predictive power assessment in this study.

Table 5. 19 PLSpredict Assessment of Manifest Variables

	<i>PLS-SEM</i>		<i>LM</i>	
<i>Variable</i>	$Q^2_{predict} \leq 0$	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>PLS-SEM - LM RMSE</i>

Commitment	0.063	0.972	0.989	-0.017
Conceptual	0.069	0.968	0.987	-0.019
Opportunity	0.072	0.966	0.980	-0.014
Organising	0.076	0.965	0.978	-0.013
Relationship	0.077	0.964	0.971	-0.007
Strategy	0.038	0.985	0.995	-0.010
Innovativeness	0.016	0.996	1.009	-0.013
Proactiveness	0.028	0.990	0.995	-0.005
Risk-Taking	0.013	0.997	1.007	-0.010
LEO_1	0.112	1.531	1.281	0.250
LEO_2	0.100	1.494	1.281	0.213
LEO_3	0.068	1.502	1.385	0.117
LEO_4	0.080	1.408	1.274	0.134
LEO_5	0.086	1.433	1.262	0.171
LEO_6	0.093	1.496	1.267	0.229
PER_1	0.118	1.617	1.595	0.022
PER_2	0.078	1.430	1.433	-0.003
PER_3	0.097	1.535	1.529	0.006
PER_4	0.077	1.557	1.569	-0.012

The comparison of the PLS-SEM RMSE values with the native benchmark LM RMSE in Table 5.19 depicts that the model has medium predictive power as most of the variables had higher RMSE compared to LM RMSE (except PER_1 and PER_3).

Table 5. 20 Hypothesis Results

<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>Hypothesis relationship</i>	<i>Path Coefficient</i>	<i>Hypothesis Supported?</i>
H1a	Education has a positive direct impact on the EC development	0.166	yes

H1b	Previous work experience has a positive direct impact on the EC development	0.084	No
H1c	Business Training has a positive direct impact on the EC development	0.266	Yes
H2	EC has a positive direct effect on Firm performance	0.483	Yes
H3	EC has a positive direct effect on EO	0.227	Yes
H4	EO has a positive direct effect on firm performance	-0.036	No
H5	EO mediates the relationship between EC and firm performance	0.227 -0.036	No mediation
H6	EC has a positive direct effect on Learning Orientation	0.301	Yes
H7	Learning Orientation has a positive direct effect on firm performance	0.238	Yes

5.9 Summary

This chapter covers the quantitative part of the study, aiming to outline the data analysis process and present the results of the hypotheses. The data analysis is structured into three parts. In the first part, a data screening process is executed, involving various methods and tests on raw data, such as outlier assessment, normality tests, straight-lining tests, and common methods variance checks. The results indicate that the data satisfies the requirements of normality, collinearity, and common method variance. Out of the initially distributed 400 questionnaires, 345 responses were received, resulting in an 86.2% response rate. After excluding 330 responses due to mismatches in research criteria, 16 with missing data, 3 qualifying as unengaged data, and 4 containing outlier values, 307 usable responses remained. Descriptive statistics of participant characteristics reveal that a significant portion falls within the age group of 36–45 years (33.2%), holds a bachelor's degree (33.6%), and has attended business training (80.8%). Additionally, participants predominantly have 1-2 years of prior work experience (33.3%), 6-8 years of business operation (41.4%), a firm size of 3-4 employees (44.3%), and operate in the retail sector (36.5%).

Following the presentation of descriptive statistics, the next step involves assessing the measurement model. In part two, confirmatory factor analysis is conducted to evaluate the measurement model. The disjointed two-stage approach is adopted for better parameter recovery. Once lower-order constructs meet relevant criteria, latent variable scores are saved for later validation of entrepreneurial competencies and entrepreneurial orientation formative higher-order constructs. Using Sarstedt et al.'s (2019) suggestion, a three-step procedure, i.e., redundancy analysis (convergent validity), VIF for collinearity, and outer weight significance, was employed, and the formative EC and EO higher-order constructs provided clear support for the validity. Unlike the measurement model (see figure 5.2), the structural model comprises six constructs (see figure 5.5), where EC HOC now contains six indicators,

namely: commitment, conceptual, opportunity, organising, relationship, and strategy, whereas EO HOC contains three indicators, namely, innovativeness, proactiveness, and risk-taking, which are the latent score variables obtained from stage one.

In part three, the assessment of structural models begins by examining the relationships among the constructs. Analysis of the structural model, utilising bootstrapping with 5000 subsamples, indicate that all relationships in the structural model are statistically significant, except for H1b, H4, and the mediation of EO on EC and firm performance. The study also assesses the model through R^2 values, revealing varying degrees of predictive power for all dependent constructs (EO, EC, LO, and firm performance) and Q^2 values obtained from the blindfolding process. All endogenous constructs are found to be larger than zero. Utilising PLSpredict, the study also checks the main endogenous construct, firm performance, and discovers it has medium predictive power. The next chapter will delve into the qualitative phase results obtained from successful female entrepreneurs in Pakistan.

Chapter Six: Qualitative Data Analysis

6.1 An Overview

This chapter is built on the preceding chapter's inquiry and seeks to provide comprehensive knowledge of the phenomenon under investigation. An explanatory qualitative analysis was conducted to obtain evidence on how female business owners think about the dimensions of EC, EO, LO, and human capital and what factors are critical to their firms' performance. In light of the hypothesis results, the findings of the interview are analysed. A thematic analysis technique is applied to study the quantitative data (see Chapter 4). This chapter's aims are threefold: first, to give the interview data findings; second, to offer a secondary examination of the statistical results; and third, based on the quantitative and qualitative results, to validate the female-owned firm performance conceptual framework.

In pursuit of the chapter's stated objective, a semi-structured interview approach was utilised. As observed by Saunders et al. (2023), employing semi-structured interviews allows for the discovery of new perspectives and a deeper comprehension of the investigated phenomenon. The interview results are organised according to the significant factors outlined in the framework. Subsequently, overarching themes identified from the transcribed data are discussed under each category, providing a clearer insight into how Pakistani female entrepreneurs perceive various factors influencing their business performance. The analysis of the interview data prompts the need for some adjustments to the proposed framework, a discussion of which is thoroughly addressed in the following chapter.

This chapter is organised as follows: Section 6.2 delves into the components of human capital, while Section 6.3 examines the findings related to entrepreneurial competencies. Section 6.4 then explores the results pertaining to the entrepreneurial orientation dimension. The relationships between learning orientation, entrepreneurial competencies, and firm performance are outlined in Sections 6.5 and 6.6, respectively. The chapter concludes with a summary in Section 6.7.

6.2 Human Capital –Does it Plays any Role in Developing Entrepreneurial Competencies?

Three factors were considered when assessing the human capital of female business owners: educational achievement, prior work experience, and business training. Interestingly, human capital was found to be the more familiar and well-understood notion for all participants in this study. The interview began with a welcome and an explanation of the interview's objective. The female business owners were questioned about their human capital and the role it has played in the development of EC. The relevance of each human capital component is discussed below.

6.2.1 Education Attainment

According to Zainol et al. (2018), general education equips entrepreneurs with the capability to explore and exploit entrepreneurial opportunities. McCracken et al. (2017) state that individuals with higher education levels have an advantage when it comes to absorbing knowledge and skills, which makes

them more creative and productive while completing tasks. All the respondents, irrespective of their educational background, expressed the significance of education (general) in building competencies, particularly in the embryonic stage of business. The majority of the respondents (13 out of 15) mentioned the benefits of having a general education, including being committed to business, building relationships, and having the confidence to seize business opportunities. Several interviewees recalled similar stories, which are mentioned below.

“Education does have certain benefits, even if you are not working in that industry, education enables an individual to seize available business opportunities....” (WE-5)

“My university encouraged us to participate in several exhibitions, so I had a supportive educational system, and everything about that helped me to become a successful entrepreneur. Knowledge, attitude, and skills were developed at my master programmes, and when I attended those programmes, I got the opportunity to expand my network. This widened my exposure too.” (WE-10)

“My postgraduate degrees supported me in building my business by bringing down my shyness or fear of communication. I learned how to stay committed to my studies and pursue my goals in any circumstance.” (WE-6)

6.2.2 Previous Work Experience

The comprehensive examination of the interview transcript indicates that 80% of female business owners (12 out of 15) possessed prior experience in various sectors before initiating their businesses, with only three respondents having industry-specific job experience. Multiple factors were cited as to why these female business owners left their paid employment. The most frequently mentioned factors include work-life balance, given that all female entrepreneurs in the study sample are married. Another significant factor was marriage, followed by opportunity spotting and passion for pursuing something new. Surprisingly, none of the respondents who had previous work experience mentioned having a business in their field of work, and 9 out of 12 participants believed that their employment had not contributed to enhancing their entrepreneurial skills, revealing a gap in business-related knowledge. The responses of a few participants are as follows:

“Although I have been working in the banking sector for a couple of years, setting up a boutique was not an easy task. When I started my business, I felt I lacked the required experience. Running a boutique needs different skill sets....., If it weren't for my husband, I wouldn't have succeeded in establishing it.” (WE-5)

“I faced a lot of disappointment while running my business because of my lack of experience in the beauty industry. First, my job didn't equip me with the right skills needed to run my

business because of a different field. Second, people I knew in my circle who were from the same industry were unwilling to provide any information.” (WE-14)

“My professional career differed from my entrepreneurial venture....., so starting the catering business and attracting customers posed a significant challenge at the outset. Despite the initial struggle, with the guidance of my father and the utilisation of social media, I gradually began attracting customers.” (WE-9)

As noticed from the aforementioned statement, the majority of the participants stressed that differences in job experience and the business field do not inherently equip them with the essential knowledge and attitudes needed to cultivate the competencies required for initiating and managing their own businesses.

6.2.3 Business Training

Training is a comprehensive process that alters an individual's behaviour to align with pre-defined or specific patterns, serving as a systematic approach through which an individual's skills, talents, and knowledge are refined, aiming to enhance productivity. In the qualitative sample, only 2 female entrepreneurs have not received business training in their respective fields, yet all participants emphasised the necessity of such training in strengthening their entrepreneurial skills. A majority of the participants (13 out of 15) have undergone business training in their field of business, leading to opportunities for attracting new customers, introducing new products or service lines, and expanding their business knowledge. A few respondents expressed that:

“I have been participating in training sessions organised by various beauty colleges. These sessions have enriched my knowledge not only in areas related to new products, hairstyles, and makeup techniques but also in one's ability to believe in herself.” (WE-14)

" At the start of my practise (business), I attended numerous seminars of the Research Society of International Law at LUMS. It actually helped me learn various techniques for becoming a competent lawyer." (WE-12)

“My paid employment is entirely unrelated to my business, but to improve my soft skills, I've attended various workshops offered by the chamber. These workshops are brief, but they prove to be highly beneficial and informative for running the business.” (WE-13)

Training plays a vital role in learning how to do business, and the impact of training on building up the business is confirmed. Female entrepreneurs attending training indicated that they were seeking entrepreneurship skills related to new business trends, customer care, and other soft skills necessary to run the business.

The findings indicate that both education and business training were identified as pivotal contributors to entrepreneurial competencies, whereas prior job experience was deemed ineffective. This discrepancy may be attributed to the fact that a significant number of female entrepreneurs initiated businesses unrelated to their prior employment. Educational attainment levels among women entrepreneurs in Pakistan vary, with participants highlighting the role of education in seizing business opportunities. Furthermore, they emphasised that training not only equipped them with technical business knowledge but also enhanced their overall business skills.

6.3 Linking Competencies to Firm Performance

For any business to endure, owners must possess a comprehensive set of abilities, competencies, and skills crucial to the prosperity and sustained existence of their enterprise. The performance, success, and growth of SMEs are intricately tied to the competencies of the entrepreneur (Mitchelmore et al., 2014). The present study employs six sets of entrepreneurial competencies, i.e., organising, relationship, opportunity, strategic, commitment, and conceptual, as proposed by Man et al. (2002). The competencies of women are shaped by a multitude of factors, including demographic variables, institutional, socio-cultural, economic, and firm-specific elements. Therefore, to gain a deeper understanding of how competencies impact firm performance, female business owners were asked to shed light on their perceptions of the aforementioned set of competencies employed in enhancing their business performance.

6.3.1 Relationship Competencies

Establishing connections with a diverse array of individuals is crucial for entrepreneurs, as it provides them with access to information and other valuable resources. All 15 participants commend that cultivating good relationships with people, be they customers, suppliers, or employees, is the key to the smooth operation and improved performance of their business. This is due to the daily demands of their routines, which involve interacting with a significant number of people. Additionally, maintaining positive engagement with customers and suppliers was emphasised repeatedly by all respondents. Six participants specifically highlighted the significance of fostering effective relationships with their suppliers to ensure loyalty, negotiate favourable terms, and establish enduring business ties with customers by receiving timely products and services from suppliers. For instance, when asked about the importance of relationships with suppliers, a few participants responded that:

“Suppliers are the people from whom you buy your products. With an effective network and a good relationship, you can easily market your products even in different cities.” (WE-7)

“I spoke with many suppliers, and finally, after two years of searching, I found a few of them who are based in my city and offered me good rates as well as speedy delivery. It saved me both time and money.” (WE-9)

Participants also agreed that a good relationship not only builds customer trust and confidence but also persuades customers to purchase their products, services, or ideas. A few of the illustrations demonstrate the importance of client relationships within business.

"Success in business, uh... is characterised by the strength of the company's relationships with its consumers, staff, and suppliers. I feel that to achieve business stability and maintain customers, we must have a good relationship with our clients." (WE-5)

"Interaction is the key to success in service industry" (WE-13)

"If we don't communicate with our customers properly and don't interact with suppliers on client needs on time, we may not be able to expand our business." (WE-6)

Establishing and maintaining positive relationships with employees was also highlighted as significant by some entrepreneurs, who asserted that women need to be trained in the art of negotiating with employees to create a positive working climate where every member of the organisation can openly discuss and share their concerns to mitigate potential business threats. A few of the respondents replied as follows:

"My staff keeps me up to date, which I consider quite valuable because I feel that everyone has some degree of creativity and if some valuable point is raised from my staff, I do consider it." (WE-2)

"You know, the relationship with you staff and how you treat them is essential in business because they can easily let you or your business down if you treat them as they are nobody. So having good relationship with them is important. Although pleasing everyone is challenging, but I try to assist them if not monetary but in other ways, like compensating them during their needs, personal problems, illness or by recognising their effort." (WE-11)

The findings of this research reveal that female entrepreneurs value relationship competencies, which is consistent with Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014), who observed that women owned businesses place a high value on relationships with employees, suppliers, and clients and that female entrepreneurs often prioritise these relationships when making decisions.

6.3.2 Organising Competencies

Organising competencies are reflected in the ways the firm operates and executes. As business owners, entrepreneurs must undertake a variety of tasks and manage different functional areas, requiring the ability to organise numerous resources within the firm. Female owned businesses are typically small and resource-constrained and lack specific units to administer various resources. Therefore, the relevance of organising competencies is mandatory and is observed in all 15 participants in the study sample, where female entrepreneurs dedicated a significant amount of time to organising and arranging

numerous resources, ensuring that their business ran smoothly. For instance, when asked about the importance of organising in business, some interesting responses were:

"In my business, organising things is a must." (WE-9)

"Organising is critical in any business since organising saves time and effort, particularly when you have a large orders to replace." (WE-8)

"One of the challenging areas in fashion industry is planning and organising inventory. I faced this issue a few years ago, and it had a detrimental impact on my business." (WE-7)

Likewise, recruiting the appropriate individual or providing adequate training to staff is deemed an essential aspect of organising competency. All 15 respondents emphasised the need for recruiting the right person or training family members who they could trust as the most important aspect that contributes to the smooth operation of the business. They prioritised outsourcing various business operations, maintaining a lean staff, or relying on family members to bridge the gap. As expressed in the narratives of some entrepreneurs:

"I am accompanied by my sister, who handles all other tasks and is currently at the shop, as well as my niece, brother, and my son, who is also involved. I include my family in the business since no outsider will endure the strain alongside me, and because I perceive it as a family enterprise as well." (WE-9)

"One of the toughest parts of business is going outside to wholesale markets and dealing with male suppliers. If it weren't for my husband and my son, I wouldn't be able to get negotiable deals and succeed in my business." (WE-5)

"I've employed two experienced female employees to serve the customers. I've observed that when our female clients are served by female workers, they feel more at ease." (WE-4)

"I lack proficiency in accounting and tax, so I have recruited an expert for such tasks. It's crucial to hire individuals who excel in those areas, particularly when you lack knowledge in this field." (WE-12)

Referring to the above quotations, it is clear that the influence of organising competencies is noticeable in the current study. Despite operating on a small scale, the respondents demonstrate proficiency in organising the diverse resources essential for the firm. They effectively utilise both internal and external resources by investing substantial time in planning business activities, monitoring and organising resources, managing cash flow, and providing training and motivation to employees. Their emphasis lies in the effective management of human resources integral to their business operations.

6.3.3 Opportunity Competencies

According to Tang et al. (2012), opportunity development and recognition are fundamental to entrepreneurship, and all 15 participants concur that seizing profitable opportunities is the only way to keep the business running. The majority of interviewees (10 out of 15) are well aware of existing opportunities, yet they also acknowledge that identifying the right business opportunities is challenging and costly if they do not align with their plans. Additionally, participants discussed the difficulties they encounter in securing funds from banks or other financial institutions. A few interviewees (6 out of 15) also acknowledged challenges in capitalising on opportunities due to prevailing mindsets. Despite these challenges, participants remained determined to succeed and did so in time. According to some respondents:

"It is good to offer new services because it allows us to build new customers and retain old ones. However, recognising an opportunity and seizing an opportunity are two different things. You might have limited finances, inadequate people, or limited knowledge." (WE-5)

"Yes, we do look at other business options, but our primary focus is on our accounting firm's growth in Pakistan because most of our clients are in Pakistan." (WE-11)

"There is a lot of room for growth in the market for women, but they aren't aware of it. So being proactive is the key to new business opportunities and business success." (WE-6)

The significance of opportunity competencies is also associated with securing finance from formal institutions, including banks, which proved to be a challenge for many participants in the study sample. Only one respondent managed to secure formal credit to establish their business, while the remaining depended on personal savings or borrowed a loan from a close relative. This highlights the significance of entrepreneurs possessing the skills required to secure startup capital and other essential resources for initiating and sustaining their businesses. As expressed by some participants:

"I started my business using personal savings. As our credit history enhanced, reputable companies began placing orders with us, improving our reputation in the market. Now, local retailers also supply us with raw materials on credit for a six-week period." (WE-10)

"Getting a loan from bank is a myth in Pakistan." (WE-1)

"Recently Punjab government announced interest free loan for female entrepreneurs. I decided to apply for the loan for business extension. Despite fulfilling all the bank requirements my loan got rejected. Then I decided to borrow money from some close family member." (WE-14)

The above response indicates that just acknowledging the existence of opportunities does not enhance business outcomes. The crucial aspect lies in the capability to promptly respond to these opportunities by taking appropriate actions. This is evident in the study sample that female entrepreneurs have the

potential and time to work, and if business opportunities are provided to them, they can seize entrepreneurial opportunities despite the societal challenges.

6.3.4. Commitment Competency

Commitment to the business involves a strong belief in the venture, a spirit of conquest and independence, and engaging in enjoyable activities. These aspects contribute to their overall success in business. The findings of this study also suggest that commitment competencies are significant in the current study context. Participants indicated determination to succeed despite facing challenging conditions in their businesses. All 15 participants believe that staying committed is crucial for firm performance. This behaviour encourages business owners to actively accept work responsibilities, take initiative, and remain motivated to advance the business. For instance, when asked about the importance of commitment for business performance, some participants stated that:

"I am deeply committed to my business. If something doesn't work, I strive to find alternative solutions. In one way or another, I'll make sure to get there. So having a solid commitment on my part is necessary for that." (WE-15)

"What will I do if I quit? My business is my livelihood. I have a family to feed. My two daughters go to university, they are my responsibility and I have to pay their fee..., I do my best to make it work in fact it has to work. I have employees and they are poor people with families. So it's a chain" (WE-9)

"As I completely rely on my business, I need to stay focused, even when things go wrong. That's why commitment is very important in business." (WE-10)

All the quotations above support Ahmad et al.'s (2010b) findings that strong commitment aids entrepreneurs in overcoming challenges posed by the environment and keeps them motivated to pursue their business goals. Consequently, the results indicated a clear and consistent emphasis on the significance of commitment and determination among all the participants. Entrepreneurs conveyed a strong belief that the success of their businesses hinged on their efforts, underscoring the pivotal role of commitment.

6.3.5 Conceptual Competency

Mitchelmore and Rowley (2013) mention that conceptual competencies are the mental ability to coordinate the business and its interests. This study also found evidence that conceptual competencies characterised the sample under investigation. Conceptual competency involves the skills of thinking creatively, frequently demonstrated through the ability to inspire novel thought patterns and generate innovative ideas and concepts that may occasionally necessitate deviating from the normal procedure of doing things. A majority of the participants (11 out of 15) considered this competency essential, especially in decision-making and risk-taking. Interestingly, respondents that are purely service-based

(8 out of 15) favoured conceptual competency in terms of "creative thinking," "managing ambiguity and risk," and "showing professionalism." As quoted by a few participants:

"Nowadays, people look for professionalism and perfection. Work will come when you are an expert, so you need to keep on enhancing your skills, evaluate your skill sets when taking risky projects, and learn from your failures so you don't repeat mistakes." (WE-13)

"Managing ambiguity is the only way to deal with fear of failure, especially when you have invested a huge amount in business."(WE-6)

"In today's business environment, where the market is fiercely competitive and the fashion industry undergoes rapid changes, success hinges not only on being proactive, taking risk, responsive, and flexible but also on delivering unique work, particularly to retain customers. This is achieved through creative thinking." (WE-4)

"Keep an eye on your competitors, their strengths, and their strategies so that you can revise your plans to compete and outperform them." (WE-14)

Entrepreneurs, particularly those in SME contexts, encounter numerous situations demanding swift decisions. Therefore, possessing the ability to engage in high-level conceptual activities is crucial for the success and survival of the business.

6.3.6 Strategic Competency

An entrepreneur's ability to think strategically, envision the future, and undertake strategic actions that involve looking beyond day-to-day operations entails strategic competency. Consequently, this competency enables entrepreneurs to adjust and customise their business operations to align with current industry demands, particularly in dynamic environments (Ahmad et al., 2010). However, the interview data offers inconsistent results regarding female entrepreneurs' perspectives on strategic competencies, indicating only a partial relationship to female firm performance. Notably, respondents who operate purely in the service sector (8 out of 15) favoured strategic competency in conducting business research and formulating strategies. Other interviewees rely on "gut feelings" when making business decisions and operational judgments. Examples of statements covering both phenomena are as follows:

"In the present business environment, there is fierce competition despite the market's vast size. It is essential for me to formulate effective strategies to stay competitive." (WE-10)

"I've been thinking about what to do if things don't go as planned or doesn't actually succeed. So, I always come up with a backup plan to make sure the business can still run even if it doesn't succeed as expected." (WE-2)

“For the real success of a business, I believe a significant factor lies in being innovative, establishing a clear direction and devising effective strategies to achieve it. Failure to do so can greatly impede a business's chances of success.” (WE-13)

Interestingly, seven participants emphasised relying on their "gut feeling" irrespective of potential risks. While women are often thought to “follow their gut” or trust their instincts in decision-making, this inclination was not prominent in the interviews. This could be attributed to a more cautious approach to risk-taking among female entrepreneurs, as evident in their emphasis on research, evaluating costs and benefits, and staying vigilant about competitors' actions.

“ Sometimes, the most prudent course of action is to trust one's instincts, and personally, I find that about 99% of the time, my instincts prove to be accurate.” (WE-4)

“No, I rely on my individual judgment.” (WE-6)

“Having managed this business for over a decade, I rely on my own judgment and the experiences gained in its operation. I've also encouraged my employees to offer advice on ways we can elevate the business to new heights.” (WE-5).

Strategic competencies showed the least contribution to business performance. Surprisingly, seven out of fifteen interviewees who operate solely as service providers (selling no physical commodities) were aware of the significance of supplier relationships.

Participants in the study are aware of the importance of relationships, organising, commitment, and opportunity competencies. However, conceptual and strategic competencies showed the least contribution towards business performance. Few female entrepreneurs discussed finance, and only one participant was granted a loan to increase their business, while others mentioned that they started their business either by borrowing money from their husbands and family members or using their personal savings. This indicates that female entrepreneurs in Pakistan are affected by a lack of financial resources, which keeps them from taking advantage of opportunities and which makes unable to develop their businesses to their full potential.

6.4 Entrepreneurial Orientation – Does EO Matter?

In the present study, the EO construct comprises three dimensions, namely, risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness. Although business performance is largely contingent on entrepreneurs' ability to take deliberate action to capitalise on an emerging opportunity by scanning and monitoring the environment for existing and new customer demand, the relationship between EO and performance (Chaston and Sadler-Smith, 2012) is far more complex, as this link is contingent on numerous other factors, including firm settings and several internal characteristics. The interviews support the H5 results, demonstrating that the EO and firm performance have no significant relationship. Participants are well aware of the

EO dimensions, and they believe the EO construct is a resource-intensive activity, whereas female entrepreneurs are reported to be resource-constrained. A detailed analysis is as follows:

6.4.1 Risk-taking

While all business endeavours involve a certain level of risk, participants generally exhibit a tendency to avoid risk-taking. According to Rauch et al. (2009), engaging in risk-taking entails daring actions, such as exploring unfamiliar territories, borrowing extensively, or allocating substantial resources to enter uncertain environments. All participants acknowledge some form of risk-taking in supporting their businesses. Interestingly, few participants (5 out of 10) related risk-taking to occasions when they borrowed funds or acquired a loan from sources other than a bank. While other interviewees (9 out of 15) asserted that risk-taking behaviours are essential for firm sustainability rather than improving performance. Consequently, female entrepreneurs' perspectives on risk-taking exhibit a range of opinions. Some of the statements in response to risk-taking are:

"It was a big risk for me to take money from a close family member because I didn't know how I would pay it back. (WE-9)

I believe in taking risks, but always have a plan B ready with plan A so I can use it when plan A fails. Never take a risk when you don't have a backup plan in place; else, you'll end up losing money." (WE-1)

"If I see a good opportunity, I do consider it. However, I believe it's not always the right act because it's costly. I don't feel the need to pump more money in if my business is making enough profit. You have to keep some money with you to cover unexpected business expenses or to meet the business end needs, especially in difficult times." (WE-2)

The statements above reflect a cautious approach to risk-taking. However, they align with the existing entrepreneurship literature, suggesting that a willingness to take risks doesn't always predict the success of new ventures (Tajeddini and Mueller, 2012). Entrepreneurs decide on things by considering risks that can be calculated but not insured, hoping for sales for future profit. Participants tend to favour a defensive strategy and avoid more active, creative, and forward-looking approaches that involve a lot more risk. So, in this context, taking risks means being ready to go after goals but taking a moderate or calculated amount of risk.

6.4.2 Innovativeness

One crucial and enduring attribute of entrepreneurs is their ability to think creatively and independently. Rauch et al. (2009) describe entrepreneurs as creative and ambitious individuals who identify "new combinations of production" to capture a new market, create a novel product, or innovate in technology design. In the study sample, being innovative is associated with female entrepreneurs' ability to either develop or offer new products and services based on client preferences or current market trends. This

is because the participants operate in industries that are traditional and non-high-tech sectors. Interviewees agreed that employing innovative ideas and adopting current trends are important but not essential. Although participants linked innovativeness with the introduction of new products and services, many of them (11 out of 15) argued that they are reluctant to invest their available financial resources in new products or services because of the uncertainty of how well those products or services will do in the future. For instance, a few interviewee responses are:

"People always say that to be successful in business, you need to look for new and innovative products, but from my personal experience, this is not true. No doubt, displaying new designs does increase customer footsteps but not all new products are profitable." (WE-4)

"Not necessarily, I agree that innovativeness is beneficial for business, but once a certain level of establishment is reached, it may not be essential." (WE-8)

"Introducing a new service entails risk as there is uncertainty about their marketability and how clients will respond to them." (WE-10)

The aforementioned quote indicates that innovativeness did not seem to define the sample. While numerous interviewees recognised the business landscape's need for innovation and novelty due to competition, the participants were more inclined towards seeking security. This inclination hinders them from exploring unfamiliar products and services. As argued by Fuentes-Fuentes et al. (2015), women owned firms tend to display a lower level of innovativeness due to factors such as their small size, association with traditional industries characterised by low innovation rates, and limited access to resources.

6.4.3 Proactiveness

Being proactive is defined by the ability to foresee opportunities for creating novel products and services, coupled with responsiveness to market signals. Interestingly, the participants in this study exhibited proactive behaviour by actively monitoring and scanning the changing environment, as well as actively seeking emerging opportunities to address new customer demands. Thirteen (out of fifteen) participants are aware of clients' needs and take a proactive approach in meeting those needs. Despite being risk-averse when it comes to competition, they are following a proactive approach in response to their clients' needs. They do this by maintaining good relationships with their customers and taking timely action to respond to their demands. A few notable statements made by the interviewee are:

"I always look for customer demand. I know my regular customers, and if they need something that is not available in the market, I usually take the initiative to introduce it." (WE-5)

"Yes, without remaining proactive, you will be unable to capitalise on the current market." (WE-14)

“Certainly, if a client wants a certain products that we don’t do we specially purchase that product to facilitate them and this is a common practice in our business” (WE-1)

Respondents are well aware of the latest market trends and business opportunities available in the market. This finding is consistent with the literature and the relationship found by Kungwansupaphan and Leihaothabam (2019). The proactive approach adopted by participants enabled them to identify shifts in market trends and customer preferences. As a result, their proactiveness empowered them to identify areas for improvement well in advance, thereby enhancing their overall performance.

However, due to the business's inherent nature and the limited financial resources available, the interview data lacks evidence supporting a proclivity for risk-taking and innovativeness. As suggested by Hughes and Morgan (2007), the dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation can vary depending on environmental and organisational contexts. The absence of risk-taking and innovativeness within the sample in this study may be linked to industry characteristics, where businesses offer similar products or services, resulting in uniform pricing. Moreover, this finding might be indicative of cultural influences within the research context. Additionally, respondents are observed to face constraints in resource availability for the development of EO.

6.5 Entrepreneurial Competencies and Learning Orientation

Entrepreneurs are required to apply competencies to effectively execute their entrepreneurial roles, thereby necessitating ongoing learning and recognising the pivotal role of learning. The interviewees in this sample were unanimous in their belief that EC improves LO. Participants were clearly learning from their knowledge and the experience of the industry in which they operated. For instance, the majority of the interviewees (nine out of fifteen) stated that they had gained a great deal of knowledge from their product or service failures and other past experiences. Others reported that EC has facilitated them in organising business resources. A few examples reflecting this behaviour are stated below:

"Learning is essential to business's success. I have learned a lot from business. I really had some bad experiences in terms of suppliers, labour, customers, and business opportunities. All these experiences made me proactive, shaped my business vision and taught me how to deal with different people in different situations." (WE-6)

"I attribute my success to my commitment to continuous learning and the application of new skills in my business." (WE-14)

"I am a shy person and it was really hard for me to interact and relate with my suppliers. But with the help of my husband I learned how to deal with them." (WE-8)

"Since I have been running my business for more than a decade, I have made numerous mistakes and these mistakes has actually helped me in shaping my entrepreneurial skills."
(WE-1)

The confirmation of the influence of entrepreneurial competencies on cultivating a learning orientation is apparent. Upon examining the aforementioned quotations, it becomes evident that women exhibit greater capability and enhance their skills through a consistent dedication to learning. Furthermore, participants unanimously underscored the crucial role of continuous learning in achieving successful entrepreneurial performance. They contend that, for a firm to endure and thrive in a fiercely competitive environment, one must have good relationships with different stakeholders, be committed, learn from one's mistakes, adapt, and make adjustments to changes in the business environment.

6.6 Learning Orientation and Firm Performance

Individuals with a learning-oriented mindset can not only acquire information and knowledge about their markets but also about various other stakeholders. Real et al. (2014). These individuals engage in activities within a firm to gather and apply knowledge, thereby enhancing the firm's performance. The interview data unequivocally supports the idea that a learning orientation is a crucial factor for improving business performance. While all participants acknowledged the value of a learning orientation for their business, eight of them specifically described learning as a process of adaptability, i.e., the application of acquired knowledge into practical situations. According to a few interviewees:

"Continuous learning is crucial in an XYZ firm because accounting standards are constantly changing. So not learning with the changes will result in a loss of technical skills, business opportunities, potential clients, and profit." (WE-11)

"Because the market is competitive, learning is critical and learning makes you competent and uh....., if you wish to remain at the top, you must always work on yourself and improve. Otherwise, someone will undoubtedly outperform you and seize control." (WE-8)

"Learning comes with time and experience." (WE-4)

"Learning, and knowledge help keep a business afloat." (WE-6)

"Whatever your business deals in....., if someone knows how to put knowledge in practice, I believe this skill is enough to run a business." (WE-7).

Female entrepreneurs in the study sample appear to be very talented. The study suggests a higher likelihood of these participants managing their firms with a nurturing approach that encourages a culture of consensus and tolerance for mistakes. As per Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014), women owned businesses, typically smaller, demonstrate an adeptness at embracing learning due to their flexible and decentralised structures, potentially positively impacting their overall performance. In sum, all fifteen

participants support the role of learning as an essential factor in enhancing firm performance, as they are able to improve business performance through an on-going commitment to learning.

6.7 Summary

This chapter delves into the qualitative findings and offers a more in-depth explanation of the quantitative study. The interview data affirms the relevance of competencies such as relationship, opportunity, organising, conceptual, and commitment within the context of Pakistan. The analysis of interview data further indicates that, within the scope of this study, entrepreneurial orientation does not significantly contribute to enhancing business performance. Entrepreneurial orientation is characterised as a resource-intensive activity, and female business owners in Pakistan face constraints, particularly in terms of limited financial resources.

Likewise, educational attainment and business training emerge as robust indicators of entrepreneurial competencies, while there is no evident link with prior work experience. This suggests that running a firm demands a unique set of skills and knowledge that may not necessarily be acquired through previous work experience. Participants also demonstrate a keen awareness of the benefits of learning as a crucial determinant of firm performance. Table 6.1 below provides an overview of how research questions, qualitative and quantitative findings interlink with each other.

Following this, a thorough discussion that integrates both qualitative and quantitative findings is presented, supported by previous studies. Based on this discussion, the final conclusion is drawn in the following chapter.

Table 6. 1 Relationship between Research Questions, Qualitative and Quantitative Findings

<i>Construct</i>	<i>Research Questions</i>	<i>Themes/Factors</i>	<i>Examples of Behaviours</i>	<i>Quantitative Results</i>
Entrepreneurial Competencies	How do the entrepreneurial competencies reported in the literature (i.e., opportunity, commitment, strategic, conceptual, organising and relationship) affect performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan?	Relationship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Trust building with suppliers, customers and employees. ❖ Develop and maintain relationship. ❖ Listening and communication. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Support H2 result: EC has a positive and direct effect on firm performance. ❖ Support H3 results: EC has a positive and direct effect on EO.
		Organising	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Identify and recruit staff. ❖ Planning and organising. ❖ Training and Motivating employees. 	
		Opportunity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Identify and recognise business opportunities ❖ Be proactive. ❖ Limited resources/financial constrain. 	
		Commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Stay committed despite fear of failure. 	

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Commit to personal goals. ❖ Sacrifice time to ensure business goes well. 	
		Conceptual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Professionalism ❖ Managing ambiguity and risk ❖ Creative thinking/innovativeness 	
		Strategic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Formulate Strategies ❖ Come up with backup plans. ❖ Gut instinct 	
Entrepreneurial Orientation	How does entrepreneurial orientation (i.e., risk-taking, innovativeness and proactiveness) affect the performance of women owned SMEs in Pakistan?	Risk-taking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Risk adverse ❖ Take calculative risk only when necessary. ❖ Linking risk with borrowed funds. 	❖ Support H4 result: EO has a positive and direct effect on firm performance.
	Does entrepreneurial orientation mediate the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and firm performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan?	Proactiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Being proactive in fulfilling customer needs. ❖ Understand customer needs. 	❖ Support H5 result: EO mediates the relationship between EC and Learning Orientation.
		Innovativeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Uncertain about profit ❖ Risky endeavour ❖ Vague customer responds 	
Human Capital	How does human capital (i.e., education attainment, previous work experience, and business training) affect entrepreneurial competencies and ultimately firm performance in	Education Attainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Building self confidence ❖ Expanding network ❖ Building skills 	❖ Support H1a result: Education has a positive direct impact on the EC development. ❖ Support H1b result: Previous work experience has a positive direct impact on
		Previous Work Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Poor business planning ❖ no previous business experience. ❖ Lacks business start-up knowledge. 	
		Business Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Improved soft skills ❖ Awareness of new product or service. 	

	women owned SMEs in Pakistan?		❖ Building network	the EC development. ❖ Support H1c result: Business training has a positive direct impact on the EC.
Learning Orientation		Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Learning by doing things in routine ❖ Learning from past experience ❖ Learning from mistake ❖ Adaptability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ Support H6 result: EC has a positive direct effect on Learning Orientation. ❖ Support H7 result: Learning Orientation has a positive direct effect on firm performance.

Source: Researcher

Chapter Seven: Discussion of Findings

7.1 An Overview

Finding factors that enhance the performance of the business is essential to success, especially for SMEs. While SMEs play a crucial role in any economy, their access to limited financial resources may pose a threat to their success. Based on the analysis of six firm performance models and the existing literature review, four key factors of firm performance were identified, namely, EC, EO, LO, and human capital. With the goal of constructing a firm performance framework specifically for female entrepreneurs, a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach was employed. This approach involved an initial examination of hypotheses through quantitative analysis, followed by a qualitative investigation to comprehensively understand the identified key factors. This chapter uses the results of both quantitative and qualitative studies to write a critical discussion of the findings and improve the conceptual framework based on the results of Chapters 5 and 6.

Based on the analysis of a qualitative study, the researcher identified four additional key success factors of female firm performance that are context-specific, namely, family support, networking, a skilled workforce, and self-confidence, which are presented in figure 7.1 below.

Figure 7. 1 Key Success Factors of Female Firm Performance

This chapter begins with a discussion of the findings concerning the hypothesis and relationships. Section 7.2 delves into the discussion of human capital as an antecedent of EC, followed by the elaboration of the direct EO relationship with EC in Section 7.3. Section 7.4 pertains to the EO and firm performance relationship, while Section 7.5 delves into the discussion of the direct association between EC and firm performance. The relationship between EC and learning orientation is explored in Section 7.6, while Section 7.7 discusses the direct relationship between LO and firm performance, followed by the discussion of mediating effect relationships in Section 7.8. Section 7.9 delves into the key success factors identified through in-depth analysis of qualitative findings, and Section 7.10 presents the revised conceptual model based on both quantitative and qualitative findings.

7.2 Human Capital as an Antecedent of Entrepreneurial Competencies

According to Passaro et al. (2018), human capital is a factor strongly impacting the entrepreneurial process. It can influence the possibility to cultivate, share, exchange, and acquire new knowledge (Martini et al., 2016) as well as assist businesses in coping with the global and changing business environment (Kungwansupaphan and Siengthai, 2014). Human capital in this study refers to female entrepreneurs, education, previous work experience, and business training.

▪ *Previous Work Experience*

Human capital aspects such as prior work experience have been cited as a major constraint for female entrepreneurs in the context of entrepreneurship. The prior work experience, referred to as "generic experience," provides business owners with general knowledge. Surprisingly, this study found no relationship between previous work experience and EC, which appears to be quite odd, as claimed in the literature. Ployhart and Moliterno (2011), for instance, acknowledged generic experience as a crucial success factor. Whereas Prasad et al. (2013) portray prior work experience as the most important component in giving female business owners a competitive advantage over others in business. Similarly, Mandawa (2016) found previous work experience to be an influential factor in building the EC of Zambian female entrepreneurs. However, the narratives of respondents in this study clearly show that prior work experience is irrelevant. For instance, WE-4 had previously worked as a customer service officer at a reputed bank. She discussed the challenges she had during the start-up phase, including unreliable suppliers, pricey raw materials, and a lack of business exposure. She further added how her training in the textile industry had assisted her in developing business skills. Many participants recalled similar stories about the problems they encountered due to inappropriate business skills, the difficulties they faced in starting up their businesses, and the risks to which they exposed their families in building their businesses. One reasonable explanation is that the skills and knowledge necessary to create and maintain a start-up business as an entrepreneur may be very different from those obtained while a wage-earning employee in various other industries (for instance, establishing legitimacy, identifying business opportunities, and upscaling business operations) (Jiao et al., 2021). Hence, founders might not always have the knowledge and skills they need to turn their general work experience into the skills entrepreneurs need to run their own businesses.

▪ *Education and Business Training*

Female entrepreneurs have a disadvantage when compared to their male counterparts in terms of education and business training. The statistical results evidence that education attainment and business training have a significant impact on EC. Interestingly, business training has more influence on the enhancement of EC compared to education in the current research context. It follows that an entrepreneur's implicit knowledge, creativity, and skills are embedded in their mind, allowing them to not only earn a living but also serve as a tool for extracting the best solution for their firms. Interesting,

the study participants are highly educated and have attended several business training sessions within the course of their business operations. Another explanation is that business training equips female entrepreneurs with the necessary skills they need to cope with the constant changes that characterise the industry. This supports the findings of Roomi et al. (2018) that, over time, female business owners in Pakistan are more skilled and resourceful than their predecessors. The interview data also revealed similar perceptions; for example, respondents emphasised the significance of training in their area, which has not only bolstered their confidence but also enhanced their ability to manage day-to-day business operations. Others have discussed how business training has educated them to use different new tools or introduce new products or services. This result supports Adom and Asare-Yeboah's (2016) findings that the education and business training of female entrepreneurs in Ghana make them more effective at completing tasks and achieving success.

Nevertheless, multiple factors affect entrepreneurial activities, including entrepreneurial education, training facilities, availability of and access to finance, socio-cultural norms, research and development, company registration procedures, the economy, and infrastructural policies (Bosma and Kelley, 2018). In Pakistan, not all women have similar situations or equal opportunities, notably those living in rural areas where feudal lords deprive them of their fundamental rights, such as employment, education, ownership of their own property, and participation in decision-making (Roomi and Parrott, 2008).

7.3 The Direct effect of EC on EO

The significance of EC cannot be underestimated in enhancing the level of EO in small businesses. Competencies aid female entrepreneurs in developing their EO so that it can be applied in dynamic and competitive environments to outperform their rivals. The findings also support the notion that a small businesses strategic posture reflects the founder's inherent characteristics (Altinay and Wang, 2011). In his investigation into female entrepreneurs in Zambia, Mandawa (2016) also reported that EC had a positive impact on EO. In the present research, when each EC dimension is analysed separately with the EO construct, only opportunity, relationship, organising, and conceptual competencies are found to be significantly correlated with the EO construct (*see Appendix I*). Interestingly, the current research finds no significant correlation between strategic and commitment competences with the EO construct, indicating that these two competencies are irrelevant to an entrepreneur's capacity to reflect on their strategic position. One contributing factor could be that Pakistani female led firms are featured as informal in terms of managerial practice, whereas strategic competency is perceived as more of an attribute of professional management. Thus, the irrelevance of strategic competency in the Pakistani context comes as no surprise because female business owners are mostly home-based, resource constrained, necessity-driven, and interested in short-term performance.

However, the lack of commitment to EO is astonishing, as long-term commitment to EO can improve business performance. Females might be reluctant to execute EO wholeheartedly because of the risk-

taking downside. Respondents' narratives also indicated a lack of willingness to engage in risk-taking initiatives. One reasonable explanation is that female entrepreneurs are predominantly driven by the necessity to support their families. The study's respondents pursue entrepreneurship because it enables them to finance their children's education, save for rainy days, and maintain family health. Sample respondents appear to be committed to business, but they also acknowledge that taking additional risks is not always beneficial to the business and that there could be situations in which such an action would be detrimental to the firm.

The findings also demonstrate that opportunity competency has the highest correlation with all the EO constructs (*see Appendix I*). This means that EO and opportunity competencies act as catalysts for exploiting business opportunities. The necessity of grasping opportunities and being proactive was also seen as an important factor in the interview data by the majority of female entrepreneurs. In addition, the Pakistani government has implemented a variety of measures to encourage women to engage in self-employment. Providing technical information and support as well as developing managerial skills are their primary focuses. Moreover, a national internship programme (NIP) has been established by the Pakistani government, which aims to improve the practical abilities of Pakistani youth and grow the country's human capital. Unfortunately, across Pakistan, entrepreneurial knowledge is not uniform (Dakhan, 2019). Similarly, a firm's ability to develop and survive is contingent on the availability of financial resources, among other things. Despite their willingness to embrace opportunities, female entrepreneurs in Pakistan have been shown to be less capable than their male counterparts. The primary culprit is a lack of financial access to seize opportunities. Interview data reinforces this result and shows that respondents were well aware of the fact that grabbing opportunities is vital to stay in business, as the ability to assess and react results in business outcomes. This is consistent with the literature stating that entrepreneurship is defined by the exploitation and recognition of profitable business opportunities (Bechir, 2017). In essence, the findings imply that entrepreneurial behaviour in small and medium-sized businesses in general, and female firm owners in Pakistan in particular, relies heavily on opportunity competencies.

7.4 The EO and Firm Performance Relationship

The concept of EO is based on the behavioural and strategic orientations that give firms a foundation for making decisions and entrepreneurial actions. In this study, the EO construct consists of three dimensions: risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness. Studies on female entrepreneurship have shown that EO has a considerable impact on firm performance (see, e.g., Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014; Fuentes-Fuentes et al., 2015). Surprisingly, the findings of this study did not support the direct impact of EO on Pakistani female-owned firm performance.

The insignificant negative association between these two constructs supports the entrepreneurship contingency approach, which argues that certain market or structural factors do not always favour high

levels of EO (Miller, 2011; Rauch et al., 2009). For instance, a negative effect of EO on business performance was found by Frank et al. (2010) in a particular configuration. According to that research, firm performance and EO had a negative relationship, especially in a dynamic business environment featuring restricted access to financial capital. The findings imply that opportunity exploitation requires access to financial capital. Likewise, a study involving Austrian and Hungarian SMEs (Filser et al., 2014) discovered that financial resource availability positively affects EO. This indicates that firms with limited financial resources are more likely to survive by concentrating on short-term profit.

The reasoning of limited access to financial resources may well apply in the current study setting, as interview data show that financial constraints limit Pakistani female entrepreneurs' willingness to innovate and take risks in business. The condition of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan differs not just from that of their male counterparts but also from that of western and non-western nations (Rehman and Roomi, 2012). Aside from the volatile business environment, societal beliefs and norms about gender roles deprive female business owners of many opportunities (Lindvert et al., 2017). More precisely, female owned firms are primarily operating in industries that are highly competitive and have low entry or exit barriers (World Bank, 2017). Respondents' narratives also indicated a lack of willingness to engage in risk-taking initiatives. Study respondents were found to have limited capital to invest in their businesses. For instance, respondent WE-7 explained that lack of access to formal finance puts women in an awkward position as it becomes challenging to raise funds internally for business. In addition, due to late payments from suppliers, poor workers suffer wage delays. Similarly, interviewee WE-5 attempted to secure financing from a variety of institutions but was unsuccessful. Access to financing is the most significant barrier for Pakistani female business owners seeking to develop or establish a new business, a finding supported by the World Bank's report (2017).

Furthermore, the majority (about 84%) of firms in the survey sample have been in operation for fewer than 9 years (see Section 5.4.5), making them young businesses that cannot afford many resources. Su et al. (2011) proved this when they looked at the relationship between EO and performance in new and old businesses. They found that EO and firm performance were positive in old businesses (i.e., those older than 8 years) but not in young businesses. The relationship was inverse U-shaped and negative. The study highlighted that a mismatch between business structure, supporting resources, and EO can have detrimental effects on a firm's performance. Besides this, EO is acknowledged as a resource-intensive activity that requires a substantial number of resources to carry out actions such as risk-taking, proactiveness, and innovation (Hughes et al., 2015). Hence, young ventures with limited financial resources may find it difficult to fully adopt it. As a result, a high EO reduces the profitability of new ventures by making the acquired products or services less cost-effective.

7.5 The EC and Firms Performance

The statistical results and transcribed data evidence that EC are strong predictors of business performance. The outcome is in line with prior research (e.g., Barazandeh et al., 2015; Mandawa, 2016; Ahmad et al., 2017) exhibiting that EC can enhance firm performance. Interestingly, participants were found to be naturally competent in areas like networking, human capital development, opportunity seizing, and innovativeness and were confident in their ability to successfully manage their business operations. Moreover, the interviewed female entrepreneurs were highly educated, experienced, and supported by their immediate close environment (i.e., parents or husbands). This finding supports Ahmad et al.'s (2010) and Gibb's (2005) observation that, despite limitations caused by business size, entrepreneurs' aptitude permits SMEs to gain and maintain a competitive edge. In a similar vein, Kelley et al. (2013) note that if women believe they possess competencies or capabilities for entrepreneurship, they are more inclined to believe that entrepreneurial opportunities exist. For example, one of the interviewees (WE-4) belongs to a well-off family, she perceived an opportunity to open a boutique and decided to sell branded ready-to-wear dresses. However, her close relatives, including in-laws, criticised her for starting a business and argued that such an act would bring shame to the family as they were respected town peers (Noble). However, with her husband's support, she was able to turn her idea into reality and become a role model in her family. The interviewer argued that opportunity does exist, but the problem is with people's mindsets. In Pakistan, the concept of "Izzat," or honour, plays a significant role in societies where women are discouraged from working outside the home (Lindvert et al., 2017). Women in Pakistan continue to be stigmatised because of the widespread belief that men are superior and possess superior innate skills, making women unsuited to create and manage a business (Zeb and Ihsan, 2020). However, with the right support, even in patriarchal societies like Pakistan, women can take advantage of business opportunities.

On examination, the individual construct of EC reveals that Pakistani female entrepreneurs place more value on relationship competencies. Similarly, opportunity, organising, conceptual, and commitment competencies appear to be critical for Pakistani women entrepreneurs. Nonetheless, the strategic domain contributes the least in all of EC, as this competency appears to be industry-specific. The following sections explore the significance of each of the competencies individually.

- ***Relationship Competency***

In this study, relationship competences made the greatest contribution to the EC construct. Female entrepreneurs interact with a diverse range of stakeholders, including employees, suppliers, customers, competitors, and government officials, which is why their prominence is unsurprising. Female entrepreneurs need this kind of engagement because it opens up a channel for the exchange of information and other useful resources (Simao and Franco, 2018; Vosta and Jalilvand, 2014). The qualitative data also emphasised the importance of relationship competencies in operating a business.

Respondents believe it is important to maintain positive relationships with employees, customers, and suppliers. Female entrepreneurs in Pakistan operate in service sectors, which place a high value on their ability to deal directly with customers (Roomi, 2011). Additionally, the service sector suffers from fierce competition, and the majority of its customers are women, giving them strong bargaining power. This necessitates the development of relationship skills, including effective communication, negotiation skills, and the ability to persuade customers (Kaur and Bains, 2013), which are essential for business support. All the respondents reported having friendly relationships with their customers and suppliers. For instance, one of the interviewees (WE-6) highlighted that establishing trust among customers is crucial since it allows them to maintain existing clients and attract new ones. She further added that having family support is the key to maintaining good relationships with customers and suppliers. Similar to WE-6, many respondents agreed that to overcome socio-cultural barriers, they must demonstrate agency, i.e., enlisting a man's help to ensure better prices from suppliers, taking inspiration from an entrepreneurial parent or husband, or getting support from a family member within the joint family system. The lack of respect and social recognition for Pakistani female businesswomen due to gender bias may be the driving force behind these behaviours (Roomi et al., 2018). According to this, Pakistani female entrepreneurs are using their relationship competencies beyond business premises to achieve business success.

- ***Opportunity Competency***

Due to patriarchal norms, female entrepreneurs in Pakistan have to face unfair treatment. For this reason, women in Pakistan are less likely to opt for entrepreneurship as their career. There are numerous obstacles that prohibit Pakistani women from taking advantage of business opportunities, including social norms, capitalists, and the actions of powerful feudal lords (Roomi and Parrott, 2008; Roomi et al., 2018). Despite this, female entrepreneurs are aware of the significance of business opportunities and agree that they do exist. However, because of financial constraints, family obligations, and people's mindsets, they are unable to capitalise on them. Yet, all participants felt confident in their ability to seize the opportunity. Based on this result, it can be asserted that female entrepreneurs, contrary to socio-cultural norms, are driven by the business opportunities they perceive and capitalise on. As stated by Tang et al. (2012), entrepreneurship is based on the recognition and pursuit of opportunities. Mitchelmore et al. (2014) also highlighted that the ability of female business owners to successfully identify an opportunity is demonstrated in their capability to recognise clients' needs and perceive services or goods that consumers want. This entails that the entrepreneurial process is centred on an entrepreneur's ability to identify and utilise business opportunities (Cooney, 2012). Another factor could be that female entrepreneurs in Pakistan are concentrated in low-growth-oriented firms. Their industry's dynamic nature necessitates that they be alert to the latest trends and respond accordingly, making opportunity competencies particularly relevant in this study. Additionally, a competitive edge can be

gained by business owners who are able to recognise client demands and discover the services or products that clients want (Sullivan and Marvel, 2011).

- ***Organising Competency***

Organising competency is undeniably important for the success of any business, as many internal and external resources, including human, financial, technological, and physical resources, are required. This means that the organising competency domain is related to managing a small business, nonetheless, this competency is context-specific (Lans et al., 2011). For female business owners, organising finances can be a struggle. In this study, organising competency is important because they need to cope with financial challenges. Access to formal finance has been identified as a serious obstacle in qualitative findings (see Chapter 5). Surprisingly, access to formal capital or credit has also been identified as a significant impediment to the development of female entrepreneurs in many South Asian countries, including Bangladesh (Solotaroff et al., 2019) and India (Chaudhuri et al., 2020). In Pakistan, women rely largely on their family and friends for financial support (World Bank, 2017). High interest rates and lengthy application and approval processes are responsible for this issue (Roomi et al., 2018). In Pakistan, where 89% of businesses are unregistered, the informal business status of female entrepreneurs may also be a contributing factor in their inability to secure funds from financial institutions, especially in Lahore (World Bank, 2017). Despite being skilled at financial planning, respondents reported difficulty obtaining formal finance to grow their business. Organising competency is a prerequisite for female entrepreneurs in Pakistan, as they must find other sources of funding to fund both their ongoing operations and new investments as they occur.

- ***Conceptual Competencies***

A small business owner's ability to make swift decisions is critical to the firm's long-term survival and success (Ahmad et al., 2010b). For female entrepreneurs in Pakistan, conceptual competency is as crucial as other categories, particularly in the service sector, where they encounter stiff competition. Despite having a passion for business, most interviewees highlighted that starting a business in a patriarchal society was extremely difficult. Surprisingly, 86% of participants claimed to have started a home-based business prior to venturing out into the market. They gained a great deal of knowledge and experience in the early stages of their firm, which helped in building their confidence, taking calculated risks, being innovative, and their ability to make sound business decisions. Although many participants acknowledged that having conceptual competency is essential for quickly determining whether a new product has a market based on their prior experience, this competency appears to be of utmost importance in industries that are completely service-based, such as the law and design sectors. For instance, WE-12 discussed the value of creative thinking and analytical decision-making in the law sector. This means that the fast-growing and rapidly changing competitive environment of the service industry in Pakistan necessitates their becoming more plan-oriented. Consequently, the findings are

aligned with Man and Lau (2005), suggesting that EC is influenced or refined by external factors such as industry sector requirements, which leads to uniform patterns in ranking entrepreneurial competency.

- ***Commitment Competency***

In Pakistan and other similar contexts, female business entrepreneurs encounter several obstacles to successfully running and managing their businesses, emphasising the importance of commitment. Pakistani female business owners employ a strategy of great commitment to meet their business needs, even in an extremely challenging socio-cultural and business environment. The fact that female entrepreneurs in Pakistan are not as fortunate as their male counterparts when it comes to accessing business opportunities entails them demonstrating strong commitment. The respondents revealed that "financial security, doing their best for children, and improving family living standards" were the three biggest motivations to be committed towards their business. Findings also reveal that female entrepreneurs prioritise professional commitment over personal commitment. For instance, respondents stated that they spend long hours in their business and ensure that businesses are open on weekends when, ideally, the business needs to be closed. This supports the findings of Rehman and Roomi (2012) that Pakistani women make large personal sacrifices over professional commitment. Consistent with this argument, Zimmerer et al. (2008) portray an entrepreneur's commitment to his or her work as the most admirable characteristic. Such female business owners will go above and beyond to ensure that their customers are happy with the results of their work and effort. Therefore, individuals that possess this competency are willing to make significant personal sacrifices, such as working long hours until success is attained (Zainol et al., 2018).

- ***Strategic Competency***

Long-term performance through planning is the primary focus of strategic competencies. Surprisingly, unlike other sets of competencies, strategic behaviour was found to have little impact on the EC construct. Consequently, mixed reviews were found in interviews pertaining to this competency. 47% of the respondents in the qualitative study did not see this competence as a part of their behaviour. Instead, they highlighted the need for intuitive or instinctive thinking, indicating the use of "*gut instinct*" in making business decisions, while 53% of the participants emphasised the need for this competency in decision-making. Based on the qualitative analysis, female entrepreneurs concentrated in "*buying*," "*selling*," and "*retail*" categories perceive this competency to be less demanding than in "*purely service-based*" sectors. One significant factor in this outcome is the heterogeneous nature of the service sector. For example, entrepreneurs in the former category face a highly competitive business environment with few opportunities for innovation and a low demand for new services. Over 75% of Lahore's female entrepreneurs operate in this service sector (World Bank, 2017), which makes this sector extremely competitive. These findings align with the existing study by Ahmad et al. (2011), who note that Australian business owners, when making business decisions, rely heavily on gut instinct. The purely

service-based category is one in which only a handful of women are entrepreneurs who operate growth-oriented businesses and possess this competency, to be of paramount importance. For instance, female business owners in the education, law, and design industries view these competencies as demanding. As pointed out by Solesvik (2012), strategic competencies are a managerial attribute commonly found in medium- and large-sized enterprises. Clearly, the disparities in this competency can be related to the heterogeneity of various industry settings. As stated in prior studies, the competencies of entrepreneurs are triggered by a myriad of factors, so they vary from one context to another depending on cultural values, globalised market competition, and rapid economic transformation (Tittel and Terzidis, 2020).

7.6 The EC and LO Relationship

The empirical evidence also reveals that EC has a positive and significant impact on learning orientation. The findings support the notion that an entrepreneur's capacity to learn is defined as the ability to develop entrepreneurial competencies, gain valuable experience, and generate new information (Ettl and Welter, 2010). To fulfil an entrepreneurial role, female business owners must employ EC successfully, which includes identifying services or products that meet customer needs, seizing high-quality business opportunities, and driving the firm to fruition. However, continuous learning is required to fully fulfil an entrepreneurial role, which enables businessowners to realise the importance of learning (Kungwansupaphan and Siengthai, 2014).

Female entrepreneurs in Pakistan face an environment devoid of family and moral support, as well as unfavourable working conditions that hinder their ability to contribute to the country's economic growth (Rehman and Roomi, 2012). The results highlight a compelling observation that in a patriarchal society like Pakistan, characterised by a robust feudal value system where a woman pursuing employment outside her home is deemed unfavourable, these female entrepreneurs exhibit remarkable commitment and determination. They actively acquire new skills to achieve their goals, demonstrating resilience in the face of numerous challenges.

The fact that all respondents in this study were highly educated, about 80% of female entrepreneurs had prior work experience, and immediate support from the close environment could be because respondents reside in urban areas, and the importance of attaining a high education could be due to easy access to public transport, better infrastructure, a high standard of education, and manufacturing growth. It could also be because, unlike the rural population in Pakistan, the urban populace is highly capable and skilled so they can better take advantage of financial and other opportunities available to them.

The finding also suggests that few respondents (20%) in the study sample possessed prior industry-specific expertise. This implies that the key factor that contributed to their business success was education. As the literature suggests, education plays a critical role in seizing business opportunities. The results further indicate an improvement in women's human capital after embarking on their entrepreneurial journeys, owing to their engagement with various recurring business scenarios. This

exposure equips them with essential business skills, valuable experience, and knowledge, collectively enhancing their capacity to excel in their ventures (business value). They adopted a "*learning by doing*" or "*doing things in routine*" business strategy. This entails that female business owners were their own masters, gaining knowledge of various business aspects over time and self-taught various skills, thereby enhancing their entrepreneurial capabilities. Therefore, over time, female entrepreneurs appear to be very skilled and resourceful in terms of cognitive aspects (Roomi et al., 2018). Previous studies (e.g., Ettl and Welter, 2010; Ekanem, 2015) also confirm that learning by doing has a major impact on the intellectual ability of entrepreneurs and contributes to their human capital throughout the entrepreneurial process. Entrepreneurs, from the start of an idea to the exploitation stage, gain exposure in terms of knowledge, decision-making, and judgement skills. This method provides the entrepreneur with the knowledge necessary to make better judgements and act in times of uncertainty.

7.7 The LO and Firm Performance Relationship

According to De Clercq et al. (2013), LO reflects individuals' proclivity to continuously update their current knowledge base; it taps into people's cognitive abilities. The study's empirical results support this as female entrepreneurs develop their competencies in the course of running their businesses, which has positively influenced their firm's performance. The results correspond with an existing study by Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al. (2014) that found LO is positively associated with female firm performance in Mexico. Entrepreneurs need to keep up with fast-paced changes and intense competition by constantly learning and adopting. Female firm owners often lack the resources necessary to recover from delays. This is especially true for Pakistani female entrepreneurs, as they still need their husband's, parents', or in-laws' permission to pursue any activity. Despite institutional transformation in Pakistani society, patriarchal forces prevail (Roomi et al., 2018), making learning a critical factor in their business success because female-related activities have the potential to improve overall socio-economic conditions and reshape society.

Interestingly, the respondents in the study sample were found to be opportunity-driven (93%), i.e., they started a business to capitalise on opportunities, an outcome supported by the World Bank (2017). Individuals with this orientation are more likely to cultivate entrepreneurial passion, engaging in entrepreneurship by choice. Another factor that contributes to their LO is education. The majority of respondents in the study sample believe that their education, diploma, or short courses have given them the competitive edge to lead the business not only by meeting customer needs but also by leading and motivating employees. This aligns with Adom and Asare-Yeboah's (2016) findings, where they note that Ghana's female entrepreneurs' level of education is the thriving factor in succeeding their firms.

Another explanation could be that female entrepreneurs need to organise and manage human resources (employees), which necessitates an ongoing commitment to learning as the business grows. Lack of competent and skilful workers might hinder female business owners' success as uneducated men,

who are often rough and rude, make up the labour force and are unwilling to accept the authority of women (Roomi and Harrison, 2010). Therefore, to cope with males whose socio-cultural attitudes preclude them from accepting female leadership or similar treatment as their male counterparts, women must be stern and tough to deal with such men effectively. This is the area where females wanted to learn how to better deal with males because they rely on their team (staff) to execute various tasks and take their business ahead.

7.8 The Mediating Effect of EO on the Relationship Between EC and Firm Performance

The present research tested the mediating effect of EO on EC and firm performance. The empirical evidence lacks support for the mediating effect of EO on entrepreneurial competencies and firm performance, and this may seem surprising. The results are inconsistent with the findings of Mandawa (2016) and defy the notion that EO is known by the personality, competencies, and the role of entrepreneur (Camuffo et al., 2012). Additionally, this study gives further rationale for the call by scholars (George and Marino, 2011) to include additional characteristics or executives as potential antecedents that represent entrepreneurial behaviour in firms. However, the current findings align with the contention from contingency perspectives that specific market and structural conditions might hinder the impact of EO, while others may facilitate it (Miller, 2011; Rauch et al., 2009). For instance, Poon et al. (2006), in this study of SMEs, found that EO did not have a mediating relationship between internal locus of control and firm performance. Following Lumpkin and Dess's (1996) suggestion that only those EO dimensions that are value-adding should be manipulated by SMEs, to maximise the benefits of female entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial skills in the present study context, female entrepreneurs must focus on proactive orientation.

As is evident from the interview data, all the respondents claim to be proactive in terms of anticipating opportunities and are well aware of customer needs. Although the respondents seem to positively perceive the phrase "risk taking" within the qualitative phase, the argument is that when entrepreneurs are satisfied with firm performance, they are likely to elevate future performance goals without engaging in risky endeavours (Mahto and Khanin, 2015). Such behaviour is evidenced in respondents' narratives, suggesting that these female entrepreneurs have framed their decision "being a successful female entrepreneur" as again suggesting that female entrepreneurs with elevating profit and high firm performance satisfaction are unlikely to engage in risky behaviour.

While it is without question that small firms are prone to high mortality risk with limited resources, the researchers support the suggestion of Hughes and Morgan (2007) that an ad hoc EO implementation can be harmful since it inadvertently wastes resources and hence unwittingly undermines the firm's performance. Another possible avenue is that female entrepreneurs in the study sample should focus on building strong EC instead of emphasising the application of an EO, as this would result in considerable improvements in business performance.

7.9 Success Factors of Female Firm Performance in Pakistan

In light of the qualitative findings, four pivotal success factors have been identified: networking, a skilled workforce, self-confidence, and the positive role of family members or husbands. These critical success factors are elaborated upon in detail below.

7.9.1 Networking

An important factor in the success of small-scale businesses is the availability of external networks. Given the small size of their businesses, female entrepreneurs must rely on their external networks to obtain the essential business inputs they need to survive and expand. Scholars (e.g., Diaz-Garcia and Carter, 2009) have claimed that women's access to networks is allegedly limited, they hold fewer centralised positions, and they tend to use their networks more as sounding boards rather than to source acquisitions. Interestingly, the study participants indicate that they are well aware of the business environment and available opportunities, but that pursuing the right opportunities requires access to the appropriate resources. "Networking" is cited as the most valuable resource by the majority of respondents in the interview data. Respondents reveal that one must have the "right connections," such as supportive family friends for borrowing or suppliers to buy inventory on reasonable and credit-based terms. Only a few respondents (26%) indicate the importance of having links with business advisors or other professionals in dealing with business aspects. Past studies have also highlighted the use of social capital as the most effective solution to the funding problems of enterprises, for example, to acquire the necessary or additional funds (Perreault et al., 2007) as well as enhance the entrepreneurial skills of individuals (De Carolis and Saporito, 2006). Female entrepreneurs in Pakistan, on the other hand, are said to spend less time networking due to socio-cultural norms that make it difficult for females to start or grow their businesses (Roomi et al., 2018). The study respondents, prior to starting their businesses, were mostly restricted to their homes. Once they entered into entrepreneurship, they established professional ties, which mainly include their market clients and suppliers. The findings also reveal that, despite operating for more than a decade, these women's networks are primarily informal, with close ties to intimate friends, relatives, and family members who provide social, emotional, and professional advice and support. Women are able to access such networks by becoming entrepreneurs because they are able to interact with other people regularly. This means that a network of female entrepreneurs adds value to business success by becoming a source of support for female business owners.

7.9.2 Skilled Work Force

The hiring of appropriate and skilled personnel is another important factor that contributes to the effective performance of a business. Study respondents believe that skilled employees are crucial for the proper functioning of a business, especially in the absence of the business owner. The findings demonstrate that employees are a valuable resource for fostering creativity in organisations because of their knowledge, competency, and skillsets. This entails that female entrepreneurs not only arrange essential resources, including finance, for the proper functioning of the business but also hire a skilled

workforce through their organising competencies. A skilled workforce, according to Tariq et al. (2016b), is a company's most valuable asset. Regardless of the ideas, strategies, financial resources, and opportunities available, everything might be wasted if a firm has an ineffective workforce for implementing the ideas while employing the financial resources to seize an opportunity. This entails that a firm's workforce can either support or impede its growth and development (Rosa and Sylla, 2018). Within the context of this study, this role is particularly demanding because the majority of women business owners rely on their employees (staff) to execute a variety of duties to move their businesses ahead. One possible explanation could be that women in Pakistan lack previous employment in relevant fields or business experience prior to launching a business (World Bank, 2017) therefore, they supplement their own weaker skills by using the skills of their staff or recruiting people with those skills. This finding is consistent with Bamiatzi et al. (2015), who found that UK female entrepreneurs complement their own weaker competencies by recruiting workers with these skills. Along these lines, innovation comes from employees' creativity, experience, abilities, and knowledge (Delgado-Verde et al., 2016). As a result, female business owners in Pakistan tend to have more confidence and create change when employees are highly educated and skilled (Fu et al., 2021).

7.9.3 Positive Role of Family Members or Husband

The key factor in achieving business success is having the support of family members. Previous studies have also recognised the value of family support in business operations; for instance, a longitudinal study in the UK revealed that female entrepreneurs rely on their husbands for professional business advice (Ekanem, 2015). Similarly, research in Lebanon found that female domestic obligations are not perceived as impediments to their careers; rather, their spouses' support facilitates their progress (Tlaiss and Kauser, 2011). Likewise, factors such as support from family, education, and encouragement have favourably impacted women entrepreneurs in Oman (Belwal et al., 2014). Welsh et al. (2016) assert that women entrepreneurs may benefit or suffer from the moral support or lack of it from their families. The narratives of the interviewed participants also captured similar findings. For example, WE-14 discussed her experience opening a beauty salon and the difficulties she encountered. She uncovered a peculiar Pakistani prejudice that beauty parlours are sometimes regarded as hidden brothels, and this prevented her from opening them. With her husband's support, she began her business as a home-based parlour in order to avoid creating that image. She was able to open a successful salon outside her home once she gained the trust of her in-laws. Such narratives highlight how Pakistani society's internalised norms and people's mindsets operate against women who desire to acquire resources, become entrepreneurs, or establish a business, and how the positive role of supportive husbands in terms of encouragement or assistance has influenced their business. These findings are consistent with those of Lindvert et al. (2017), who observed that many Pakistani men encourage their wives to start their own businesses in order to contribute to the country's economic growth. This means that in order to overcome the business challenges inherent in socio-cultural norms, especially in a patriarchal society like

Pakistan, female entrepreneurs must build good relationships and gain the trust of their families and spouses.

7.9.4 Self-Confidence

An entrepreneur's confidence level affects their judgement and behaviour in establishing a business. Similarly, confidence levels have a specific impact on financial access and business success (Kirkwood, 2009). Over the decade, scholars have begun to pay more attention to self-efficacy and confidence in entrepreneurship (Schmitt et al., 2018; Santos and Liguori, 2019). Among the study participants, self-confidence was found to be the driving factor in establishing their own business. It is apparent that the respondents' high degree of confidence led to their decision to leave a secure job and establish a new business.

Literature has also acknowledged the importance of self-confidence for female entrepreneurs. For instance, a study on Turkish female entrepreneurs has determined that confidence is the most crucial factor in becoming an entrepreneur (Ufuk and Ozgen, 2001). Similarly, a study by Kirkwood (2009) found that females, compared to their male counterparts, exhibit lower levels of self-confidence. In her study, women's confidence as entrepreneurs appears to develop over the course of time. However, for other female entrepreneurs, a lack of self-confidence continues to act as a barrier, hindering their ability to secure financing and keeping them from reaching their full potential. This study's findings support this notion, which is consistent with previous research on the broad understanding of self-confidence. In addition to stressing the relevance of self-confidence in business success, the World Bank report (2017) also reveals that a lack of confidence is one of the main obstacles Pakistani female entrepreneurs face. As a result, self-confidence needs to be added as an essential factor in supporting EC and female firm performance.

7.10 Revised Conceptual Framework

The above discussion, along with the analysis presented in Chapters 5 and 6, allow a conclusion to be drawn on the elements that have a substantial effect on the performance of female entrepreneurship in Pakistan. The conceptual framework, initially developed in Chapter 3 (refer to Figure 3.1), was rooted in the literature review and grounded in six firm performance models. Nevertheless, to incorporate the findings from the explanatory analysis (both quantitative and qualitative), the proposed conceptual framework underwent revision. According to findings discussed in this chapter, four new elements, namely networking, skilled workforce, family/husband support, and self-confidence, are added, as these factors are deemed important in the context of Pakistani female entrepreneurs' performance. Only the proactive dimension of the EO construct has a direct relationship with firm performance. Innovation and risk-taking are solely influenced by EC and do not have a direct association with firm performance, as female entrepreneurs in Pakistan tend to be risk-averse and less inclined towards innovation.

Figure 7. 2 The Refined Conceptual Framework of Firm Performance

Chapter Eight: Conclusion and Recommendation

8.1 An Overview

This chapter marks the conclusion of the current study, which endeavours to examine the pivotal success factors significantly impacting the performance of female entrepreneurship in Pakistan. The primary goal is to establish a conceptual framework that underlies these success factors, aiming to optimise the performance of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. The chapter starts with Section 8.2, which discusses the research objectives and their attainment, while Section 8.3 delineates the research contributions and novelty. Recommendations are provided in Section 8.4, and the study's limitations are discussed in Section 8.5. The chapter concludes by proposing future work in Section 8.6 and presenting a summary in Section 8.7.

8.2 Research Objectives

This section discusses how the research objectives are achieved and what the results are. This study proposed four investigative objectives.

Objective One: To evaluate the effects of the entrepreneur's competencies on firm performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan.

To accomplish this objective, the study developed a hypothesis (H2) that examined the direct relationship between entrepreneurial competence and the performance of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan. Specifically, the research identified that competencies like organising, commitment, relationship, conceptual, and strategic are pertinent within the Pakistani context. The study revealed that the impact of entrepreneurial competencies on performance was most pronounced. The qualitative aspect of the research also corroborates a direct association between entrepreneurial competence and enhanced firm performance. However, the qualitative exploration of strategic competency yielded mixed results. Female-owned businesses in Pakistan are predominantly necessity-driven, with entrepreneurs focusing on managing the business for immediate survival and livelihood rather than long-term planning. The small size of these firms suggests that the entrepreneurs rely on informal management practices, such as personal judgement or gut instinct, for decision-making rather than employing the sophisticated planning and control methods used in more established businesses.

Objective Two: To determine the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on firm performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan.

This study examined a hypothesis (H4) aiming to assess the influence of entrepreneurial orientation on firm performance. Surprisingly, the current study's results reveal a negative and statistically insignificant relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance within the context of this research. Other studies have yielded mixed or equivocal findings, which have been linked to several factors, including the firm's stage of development (Hughes and Morgan, 2007), performance

measures used (Soininen et al., 2012), availability of financial resources (Eggers et al., 2013), and environmental dynamism (Frank *et al.*, 2010). These findings therefore challenge the widely accepted view that EO improves firm performance and call for this relationship to be viewed from a contingency perspective, where organisational context is considered.

The findings present empirical evidence suggesting that EO individual dimensions (i.e., proactiveness, risk-taking, and innovativeness) may have varied impacts on firm performance. Consequently, firms may not necessarily need to pursue all three dimensions of the construct. In the scope of this research, innovativeness and risk-taking do not exhibit a significant association with firm performance, whereas proactiveness shows a notable positive correlation. The qualitative aspects also support the quantitative findings. This interesting finding advances our understanding of EO and its dimensions, particularly risk-taking in the context of women owned businesses. Women owned businesses in Pakistan operate in industries that are highly competitive and have low entry or exit barriers. Additionally, female entrepreneurs in Pakistan are mostly financially constrained, and women see investing a higher level of their assets as risky.

Objective Three: To determine if human capital variables (i.e. education attainment, previous work experience, business training) serve as antecedents of entrepreneurial competencies.

This study formulated three sub-hypotheses (namely, H1a, H1b, and H1c) to assess how education, prior work experience, and business training impact entrepreneurial competencies. The study findings revealed that different human capital factors exert varying influences on the development of entrepreneurial competencies. For instance, in the current research context, educational attainment and business training emerged as robust antecedents to entrepreneurial competencies, whereas prior entrepreneurship experience exhibited no significant association with these competencies. Surprisingly, interview data also support the quantitative findings. Education appears to enhance an individual's efficacy and self-confidence, thereby augmenting their ability to identify and pursue opportunities. Similarly, the training offered to women entrepreneurs is effective at developing the relevant skills and knowledge needed to cope with constant changes in a changing environment.

Objective Four: To determine how entrepreneurial orientation affects the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and firm performance.

This objective is addressed by formulating and testing a hypothesis (H5) that examines the mediating relationship between entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial competencies, and firm performance. It was found that entrepreneurial orientation does not affect the relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and firm performance. This result emphasises that entrepreneurial competencies directly influence firm performance and do not have an indirect effect through the mediating role of EO. When incorporating qualitative research to provide insights into quantitative findings, the findings reveal that female entrepreneurs in Pakistan tend to be risk-averse. They are in view that when entrepreneurs are

satisfied with firm performance, they are likely to elevate future performance goals without engaging in risky endeavours (Mahto and Khanin, 2015). Additionally, female owned firms generally face resource constraints, making the implementation of risky strategies potentially too costly for them. Therefore, taking risks may not be a necessary strategy for firms of this size operating in the service industry.

8.3 Research Contribution and Novelty

According to the literature, economic growth and development are both facilitated by entrepreneurial activities. Over the years, much research has linked entrepreneurship to economic and human development. So far, in many instances, the research is not gender-specific but comprehensive. Unlike males, females in Pakistan encounter multiple challenges and obstacles; therefore, gender-based entrepreneurial studies may aid in the enhancement and development of women's owned firms (Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014). Taking this existing gap into account, this study focuses on individual- and business-level characteristics that improve female firm performance in the context of a slow-growth country like Pakistan. This study's results are novel, and as a result, it makes numerous contributions to theory, managerial and practical spheres. The key research contributions to theory, methodology, and practice are as follows:

8.3.1 Contribution to Theory

The key theoretical contribution of this study comes from the building and testing of a conceptual framework that integrates both individual-level and firm-level factors that influence the performance of female business owners, with a specific emphasis on the context of Pakistan. The conceptual model developed in this study is unique and, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, is the first of its kind in the context of Pakistan, making it a novel contribution to knowledge. Given that the majority of existing models and theories on female-owned SMEs originate from a Western context (Al-Dajani and Marlow, 2010), the present research significantly contributes to the ongoing discourse on the factors influencing women owned firms in a non-industrialised setting.

Additionally, four main literature streams are merged in this study, which investigates the interrelationship among key constructs: human capital theory, competency approach, learning orientation, and entrepreneurial orientation, which have generally been studied as separate constructs. Additionally, the current study extends the boundary of knowledge by challenging the general assumption that EO enhances firm performance and providing empirical evidence for the argument that this relationship is context-specific, thereby extending the boundary of knowledge. Previous studies (e.g., Fuentes-Fuentes et al., 2015; Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014) have reported a positive relationship between the two constructs, leading to this assumption achieving broad scholarly acceptance in entrepreneurship literature. As posited by Miller (2011), certain structural and market conditions may not consistently facilitate a high level of EO. In the context of this research, the adverse

and statistically insignificant correlation between EO and firm performance could be associated with inadequate financial resources hindering the effective implementation of resource-intensive EO strategies. This research further challenges existing literature (Rauch et al., 2009; Covin and Slevin, 1989), advocating for the consideration of EO as a unidimensional construct rather than a multidimensional one (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996).

This study also extends knowledge by demonstrating that different human capital dimensions have varying effects on the development of EC. For instance, while education attainment and business training are strong antecedents of entrepreneurial competencies in the current research context, previous work experience was found to have no association with EC. The lack of a meaningful relationship between prior entrepreneurship experience and entrepreneurial competencies may suggest that entrepreneurs rely on specific skill sets for job tasks, while different competencies essential for business approaches may not have been acquired through prior experiences. Furthermore, the uniqueness of each entrepreneurial venture implies that success may hinge on a distinct set of skills and knowledge possessed by the entrepreneur.

This present study also enhances our understanding of the subject by providing empirical evidence that EC serve as robust predictors of firm performance in small businesses owned by women in Pakistan. The findings underscore the significance of interpreting firm performance through the perspective of EC, offering entrepreneurs insights into how they should manage their businesses and prompting awareness of the potential positive or negative impacts of their behaviour. Furthermore, it extends earlier works on EC by showing the significant role they play in the performance of small firms.

Thus, this study widens the frontiers of current knowledge. Despite the fact that similar studies are frequently found in other management domains, there is a scarcity of these studies in the entrepreneurship field (Seet et al., 2021). Only a few studies (e.g., Poon et al., 2006; Mandawa, 2016) have investigated how individual-level and firm-level outcomes are related in a single study, highlighting the literature's neglect of both entrepreneurial competence and entrepreneurial orientation constructs. Thus, this study presents a clear insight into the association between these two notions and how the relationship between them affects firm performance. Self-employed individuals usually have a substantial influence on the businesses they create, especially at an embryonic stage of business development. When a business is still in its infancy, it may be difficult to understand its performance by focusing solely on the firm's behaviour or only on the individual entrepreneur in isolation. Examining human capital (individual entrepreneur construct) as an antecedent to entrepreneurial competency (firm-level construct) offers a more holistic view of firm performance drivers. As a result, this study, by offering a model for understanding female led firms' performance, makes an important contribution to the existing literature devoted to building or evaluating conceptual frameworks. In light of the critical role small firms play, particularly female entrepreneurs in both established and emerging

nations, in terms of economic progress, social cohesion, innovation, and job creation, the subject of small business performance is gaining a growing amount of attention from the academic community (GME, 2015; World Bank, 2017).

8.3.2 Managerial Implication

These research findings have important implications for women business owners and aspiring female entrepreneurs in service industries in the context of Pakistan. Overall, this study sheds light on the significant role that a female entrepreneur plays in determining a firm's performance in terms of its entrepreneurial behaviour, capabilities, and individual skills.

According to the study's findings, possessing certain entrepreneurial competencies by an entrepreneur has a robust impact on firms' performance. The competencies equip female entrepreneurs with information on which capabilities or skills are helpful in enhancing the performance of their businesses. This information represents an important first step towards developing behaviours that mirror those specific competencies. As the literature suggests, SMEs in general and female entrepreneurs in particular have limited access to a few resources (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016). Entrepreneurs need to concentrate on activities that can positively influence firm performance. Therefore, entrepreneurs need to concentrate on practicing behaviours that result in positive performance or engage themselves in training programmes that focus on the enhancement of such behaviours within the scope of this study. For instance, relationship and commitment competencies, according to study findings, are essential in the current context. Likewise, learning is regarded as the firm's only resource for sustaining its competitive advantage (Baker et al., 2022). Consequently, entrepreneurs should focus on adopting behaviours that are consistent with these abilities.

Similarly to competencies and learning, the findings show that education level and business training have a positive and significant impact on entrepreneurial competencies. This conclusion implies that obtaining a higher education is beneficial for businesses, especially in Pakistan, as it contributes to women's knowledge building and determination. Studies in developing countries (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016; Mandawa, 2016) also provide evidence that education improves entrepreneurial skills. Similarly, entrepreneurs who lack business training can benefit from mentorship programmes by participating in such programmes to improve their business skills.

The next implication stems from the observation that EO has no influence on female firm performance. According to this study, female entrepreneurs believe that executing EO is not necessarily advantageous for small firms and that "becoming more entrepreneurial should not be an objective per se" for female firm owners (Lechner and Gudmundsson, 2014, p. 18). On reviewing EO components individually, the finding suggests female business owners only adopt proactive strategies, as it enhances female entrepreneurs' business performance by allowing them to gain a first-mover advantage through anticipating rival activities and monitoring market trends. In contrast, innovative and risk-taking

strategies need to be implemented with caution, as this study found no relationship between innovativeness, risk-taking, and firm performance.

8.3.3 Contribution to Policy and Practice

The current study makes a novel contribution that could serve as a foundation for Pakistani authorities to develop programmes to support and facilitate female business ownership and start-up businesses. Research has shown that entrepreneurial competences have a favourable and robust impact on female business performance, even in Pakistan's patriarchal sociocultural environments. This is an important first step that arises from this finding. Therefore, in light of this, government support programmes should place emphasis on introducing initiatives that aid in maintaining and developing the competencies of female entrepreneurs so that firm performance can be enhanced. In addition, the business training programme content for entrepreneurs must be designed with the aim of achieving the specific competency requirements of Pakistani business owners. These requirements should address things like business commitment, investment in stakeholder relationships, including employees, customer and supplier relationships, and the ability to organise financial resources. Likewise, business training positively influences firm performance, suggesting it affects women's ability to manage enterprises successfully. Therefore, with the assistance of the government and other non-profit organisations, training opportunities for female business owners ought to be made accessible to all female business owners in all sectors and all regions of Pakistan in order to equip women with the knowledge and abilities required to successfully run their firms.

From the study findings, the evidence that formal education plays a robust role in developing EC requires educators and policymakers to enlighten students on the value of attaining higher education not only for pursuing a formal career but also when they opt for entrepreneurship as a career. Consequently, the business training course must be revised to include a curriculum that focuses on fostering the entrepreneurial competencies' development.

The research also shows how important operational capital is to the performance of female-owned businesses, since female entrepreneurs in Pakistan have a difficult time getting formal loans. As a way to help women business owners, policymakers should think about making it easier for them to do so. Utilising measures such as working with financial institutions to help set up a loan programme with better terms for women owned businesses. Furthermore, female entrepreneurs in the study sample have the perception that financial institutions are unwilling to lend them money, and therefore, the majority lack the confidence to approach banks about granting funds. Female business owners should be encouraged to seek formal credit in a deliberate manner, e.g., through advertisements and promotional campaigns. Furthermore, the government or policymakers should enforce laws that promote property ownership among women to address the issue of meeting collateral requirements, which is the primary criterion for securing bank loans. One strategy to change the cultural practice of favouring male property

ownership is to run country-wide campaigns. Financial institutions may also implement other procedures, such as determining an individual's credit worthiness on the basis of remittance behaviour, savings, or conditional future credit on timely payments.

In addition to making it easier for women entrepreneurs to access formal financing, policymakers should think about starting programmes that offer mentoring or training, such as those led by a highly experienced business professional or a successful woman entrepreneur. These programmes should be designed specifically for less experienced business owners or aspiring female business owners, and they should be focused on helping them better manage the financial resources available.

The concluding recommendations for the government include exploring the feasibility of establishing a dedicated firm registration system specifically designed for female entrepreneurs. Creating an official registry of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) categorised by industry, activity, and location could prove beneficial in formulating initiatives to encourage entrepreneurs to register businesses in both urban and rural areas of Pakistan. Additionally, such a system could streamline data collection for research projects like the present study.

8.4 Recommendations

The fact that female owned SMEs are low in number, even in the largest commercial centres of Pakistan, is of great concern. This means that, despite a reasonable proportion of women in higher education, only a few of them pursue business as a career. So, encouraging more women to pursue entrepreneurship is a significant priority. The following are the points focusing on critical areas where future support for women entrepreneurs is needed:

- I. ***Creating a business-friendly atmosphere*** for women is crucial for improving their participation in entrepreneurship and the overall economy. Legislation could also boost women's economic participation by, for example, making workplaces safer and implementing laws or programmes that increase women's access to key services, such as public transportation. Women's empowerment should also be fostered by legislation; their working environments should be secure; and policies should be developed to provide them with a sense of safety and security. These steps will make it easier for women to take part in the economy, which will make it more likely for them to start their own businesses.
- II. ***Peer engagement and networking*** are the most beneficial forms of support for female entrepreneurs. Their isolation from their peers and business networks has a direct impact on their access to information and knowledge, their markets, and their opportunities for progress. However, female entrepreneurs have limited networking opportunities, which hinders their growth and causes them to fall behind. As a result, there should be an appropriate support programme to help them acquire communication and negotiation skills so that they can remain competent.

- III. ***To increase the managerial abilities of female owned businesses***, improvements in women's entrepreneurship support programmes are desperately needed. Women-led businesses in Pakistan also need to improve their management practices. To scale up entrepreneurship, it's important to have high quality training programmes (either in person or online,) and the delivery methods used should be easy to access.
- IV. ***Supportive initiatives aimed at strengthening*** women's liberty and reducing social constraints must be prioritised. For instance, a common feature of female entrepreneurs is a lack of autonomy, ranging from whether and how to form a business to the time allocated to business operations and successful marketing. Traditions in Pakistan limit women's access to and connectivity to male-dominated settings (such as markets and trading centres), thereby limiting their economic engagement and impact on public life. Supportive networks and mentoring are essential to opening up these areas to women's roles and presence. In addition to mentoring and support initiatives, awareness is also necessary to change people's mindsets. Social norms impose restrictions. Women's home autonomy may take longer to alter, and enhancing female domestic autonomy will most likely be an ongoing, progressive process aided by methods that engage cultures, communities, and men. In order to improve women's access to public spaces like transportation, decision-making, and paid caregiving, one strategy would be to raise public awareness about these issues. Women should be allowed to make their own decisions, but this will be a gradual process. To do this, the government needs to discover strategies to foster and strengthen women's independence while removing cultural constraints.
- V. ***The role of finance in women's entrepreneurship*** must be well comprehended and planned. Despite the fact that access to finance was one of the most frequently cited obstacles among women entrepreneurs in the research, they did not view formal finance as a feasible alternative because of their abhorrence of interest payments, inadequate knowledge about the repercussions of incurring debt, and the presumption that interpersonal influence such as friends and family would be incapable of accommodating their financial requirements. As a result, financial assistance suited to female entrepreneurs' specific needs may be essential.
- VI. ***Female entrepreneurial support programmes*** should be customised. Transforming entrepreneurs from "necessity" to "opportunity" is one of the most challenging tasks of current support programmes for women entrepreneurs. When it comes to female entrepreneurship, human capital can play an important role. Marketing and communication are the next two major challenges. The vast majority of women owned enterprises are not members of any alliances and run their businesses independently. Female entrepreneurs tend to view new organisations like the Women's Chambers of Commerce as hostile, as they are perceived as inhospitable by female business owners. Building women's networks through hubs, academies, SME development agencies, business groups, and universities should be a top priority for both aspiring and established female entrepreneurs. Thirdly, training should place greater emphasis on

managerial and leadership skills than on technical difficulties. Fourthly, these programmes should strive to increase women's autonomy and capacity to make business decisions by incorporating male and older family members and friends into programmes addressing societal norms on financial control and decision-making.

8.5 Limitation of the Study

Certainly, this study has made a meaningful contribution to the existing female entrepreneurship literature, both practically and theoretically. Nonetheless, this study is not without limitations that need consideration. Firstly, while the outcome of this study may be relevant and broadly applicable to other emerging nations, the research is based on country-specific data. Moreover, the data is gathered from the service sector in the city of Lahore, Pakistan. Consequently, the outcomes may not be applicable to other contexts because of the diverse contextual elements, including economic conditions (Su et al., 2011). Hence, their generalisability is yet to be determined. Another potential limitation is single-informant self-reported data. Given the size of the businesses chosen, this technique was necessary because of the sensitivity of the data needed, which could only be collected from entrepreneurs. Moreover, using this method to assess a firm's entrepreneurial competencies has been highly recommended (Chandler and Jansen, 1992) and is consistent with prior research (e.g., Bamiatzi et al., 2015; Ahmad et al., 2010; Wang, 2008). Yet, it could lead to the emergence of common method bias as the same survey instrument is used to gather data for both exogenous and endogenous variables. While this study does not encounter common method bias, as indicated by "Harman's one-factor test," it is noteworthy that the surveys were completed by a single informant, which could potentially lead to an exaggeration of her business. Thus, in light of this restriction, the researcher recommends that the findings be interpreted in light of this limitation. Similarly, this study incorporated a cross sectional approach, meaning that the data was gathered during a specific time period. The concern here comes with the limitation that literature imposes on EO strategies to have long-term effects on business performance (Madsen, 2007). This illustrates that a longitudinal design may be preferable, as a cross-sectional design does not completely explain the link between the two constructs in full depth. In this study, only subjective measures of firm performance are employed, possessing another key limitation. Business owners often promote their firm positively to safeguard its success, which limits the author's ability to represent the business's genuine position. As a result, performance measures that are "subjective" can lead to biased outcomes. Scholars (Miller, 2011; Vij and Bedi, 2016) have widely recommended the use of objective performance measures. However, obtaining such data, particularly in small businesses, is a major challenge due to the non-availability of archival data. Secondly, small business owners are generally reluctant to release sensitive information to outsiders. However, numerous studies (Fuentes-Fuentes et al., 2015; Rodriguez-Gutierrez et al., 2014; Wang, 2008) have adopted subjective performance measures to investigate small businesses' performance and success. A final limitation of this study is that the framework was constructed using data gathered solely from

female business owners. There is also a population of business owners that is mostly made up of men, and this model might not work for some potential male business owners.

8.6 Future Research Direction

The conceptual model established and validated in the present research needs to be tested in other contexts, particularly those nations sharing similar characteristics as Pakistan. This would strengthen the validity and generalisability of the findings of the current research.

- I. Future studies could benefit from examining the applicability of critical success factors such as "*family support, networking, a skilled workforce, and self-confidence*" to female entrepreneurs in different cities of Pakistan. Similarly, future research into the role played by the business environment is needed in order to shed light on the development of certain entrepreneurial competencies applicable in the Pakistani context. For instance, investigation in terms of the specific business sectors or the role that national culture plays in shaping female entrepreneurs' competencies. This study could be expanded to other cities and particularly to rural female entrepreneurs, as the majority of the population resides in rural areas of Pakistan. Moreover, this study could be expanded to include comparisons with other nations that have similar socio-economic characteristics to Pakistan (e.g., India, Bangladesh) in order to acquire a deeper understanding of cultural influences on entrepreneurial competencies. As argued by Muzychenko (2008), context-specific cultural values influence the formation of entrepreneurial competencies.
- II. Another promising area of further study is the investigation of the relationship between EO and firm performance, as the present study reported an inconsistent relationship, questioning the generally held belief that EO is beneficial for small firms. Additional Further research is required to explore this relationship across diverse industries, such as high-technology and low-technology intensive firms, as well as different business sizes, including medium, small, and micro enterprises. In addition, researchers should use a longitudinal approach in future studies to investigate the long-term effects of human capital, EC, EO, and LO on firm performance. By doing so, it will aid in understanding how these relationship change over time.
- III. Finally, the findings in the current study are primarily based on female entrepreneurs. A sample of both male and female business owners could be used in future studies to evaluate how the associations examined in this study differ between genders. Such an examination might offer further light on why some human capital components have an insignificant effect on entrepreneurial competence in the present study. Research question like these can provide addition insight in human capital variables difference, for instance; do human capital components effect men entrepreneurship in the same way as those owned by women? Is there any difference in business training given to both genders?

8.7 Summary

The importance of SMEs is enormous in the economy of a country, as they are the key source of employment, innovation, technological development, and enhanced industrialisation. However, female owned firms are vulnerable to poor performance and eventually fail to be in operation due to a lack of resources as compared to large firms. The resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) enable firms to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage, which in turn enhances firm performance. Four key constructs, namely, EC, EO, LO, and human capital, are identified as those specific capabilities that can generate sustainable competitive advantages and lead to better firm performance.

Building on the resource-based view of the firm as a main theoretical foundation, this study has identified four key firm performance factors from six firm performance models, such as entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, competency approach, and human capital. This research develops and tests a conceptual model of individual-level and firm-level factors affecting performance in women owned SMEs in Pakistan. In this research, the positivism paradigm was adopted, and a sequential explanatory mixed-method approach was implemented in two stages: a quantitative study carried out as the main study, where the hypotheses were developed and tested, followed by qualitative analysis to get an in-depth understanding of the phenomena under study. The study uses the findings of both the quantitative and qualitative studies to refine the conceptual model.

This study concludes that entrepreneurial competencies are strong predictors of firm performance in the current research context, and that formal education and business training contribute to their development. The study also challenges widely accepted knowledge that EO enhances firm performance and provides empirical evidence for the argument that this relationship is context-specific. It further demonstrates that the individual dimensions of EO may have varying effects on firm performance, suggesting that it is better to view the EO construct as a multidimensional rather than unidimensional construct.

Although there are several limitations associated with the research, the main limitation is that the sample was taken from female entrepreneurs operating in Lahore, Pakistan, from service sectors. Similarly, the analysis of the data collected from female entrepreneurs in a cross-sectional setting delivered unexceptional but valuable contributions. A longitudinal approach is recommended for future studies to investigate the long-term effects of human capital, EC, EO, and LO on firm performance. By doing so, it will aid in understanding how these relationship change over time. Despite its limitations, this study is innovative because it links the individual human capital aspects of the lead self-employed individual or founding entrepreneur with firm-level latent variables (EO and EC) to performance. Overall, the research helps in furthering the knowledge of the extent to which antecedent factors,

previously identified in the self-employment literature, are relevant to firm-level outcomes in the context of Pakistan, an economy undergoing significant transformation.

References

- Aaltio, I., Kyro, P. and Sundin, E. (2008). *Women Entrepreneurship and Social Capital: A Dialogue and Construction*. Gylling: Copenhagen Business School Press.
- Abor, J. Y. and Biekpe, N. (2006) SMEs' access to debt finance: A comparison of male-owned and female-owned businesses in Ghana. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, pp. Vol. 7(2), pp. 105-112.
- Abu Bakar, A. R., Ahmad, S. Z., Wright, N. S. and Skoko, H. (2017) The propensity to business startup: Evidence from Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) data in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 9(3), pp. 263-285.
- Acedo, F. J., Barroso, C. and Galan, J. L. (2006) The resource-based theory: Dissemination and main trends. *Strategic Management Journal*, 27(7), pp. 621–636.
- Acocella, I. (2012) The focus groups in social research: advantages and disadvantages. *Quality and Quantity Journal*, 46(4), pp. 1125–1136.
- ADB (2019). *Asian Development Bank*. [Online] Available at <https://www.adb.org/countries/pakistan/poverty> [Accessed 22/1/2020].
- Adeel, M. and Yeh, A. G. O. (2018) Gendered immobility: influence of social roles and local context on mobility decisions in Pakistan. *Transportation Planning and Technology*, 41(6), pp. 660-678.
- Adom, K. and Asare-Yeboah, I. T. (2016) An evaluation of human capital theory and female entrepreneurship in sub-Saharan Africa: Some evidence from Ghana. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 8(4), pp. 402-423.
- Aftab, J., Veneziani, M., Sarwar, H. and Ishaq, M. I. (2021) Entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial competencies, innovation, and performances in SMEs of Pakistan: Moderating role of social ties. *Business Ethics, the Environment and Responsibility*, 31(2), pp. 419-437.
- Afza, T. and Rashid, M. A. (2009) Marginalized women social well-being through enterprise development: A glimpse of remote women status in Pakistan. *Journal of Chinese Entrepreneurship*, 1(3), pp. 248-267.
- Agbionu, E. O., Agbionu, C. U., Ikon, M. A. and Chinwe, O. V. (2015) Women Entrepreneurship and Poverty Alleviation in Awka Metropolis. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Organisation Management*, 4(4), pp. 1-9.
- Agca, V., Topal, Y. and Kaya, H. (2012) Linking intrapreneurship activities to multidimensional firm performance in Turkish manufacturing firms: an empirical study. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 8(1), pp. 15-33.

- Agha, N., Syed, G. K. and Mirani, D. A. (2018) Exploring the Representation of Gender and Identity: Patriarchal and Citizenship Perspectives from the Primary Level Sindhi Textbooks in Pakistan. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 66, pp. 17-24.
- Agier, I. and Szafarz, A. (2013) Microfinance and Gender: Is There a Glass Ceiling on Loan Size?. *World Development*, 42, pp. 165-181.
- Ahl, H. (2006) Why Research on Women Entrepreneurs Needs New Directions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(5), pp. 595-621.
- Ahmad, N. H. (2007) *A cross cultural study of entrepreneurial competencies and entrepreneurial success in SMEs in Australia and Malaysia*. Doctoral Dissertation : University of Adelaide, Australia.
- Ahmad, N. H., Halim, H. A. and Zainal, S. R. M. (2010b) Is Entrepreneurial Competency the Silver Bullet for SME Success in a Developing Nation?. *International Business Management*, 4(2), pp. 67 - 75.
- Ahmad, N. H., Ramayah, T., Wilson, C. and Kummerow, L. (2010) Is entrepreneurial competency and business success relationship contingent upon business Environment? A study of Malaysian SMEs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 16(3), pp. 182-203.
- Ahmad, N. H. and Seet, P. S. (2009) International Journal of Entrepreneurial Venturing. *Understanding business success through the lens of SME founder-owners in Australia and Malaysia*, 1(1), pp. 72 - 87.
- Ahmad, N. H. et al. (2017) Entrepreneurial Competencies and Firm Performance in Emerging Economies: A Study of Women Entrepreneurs in Malaysia. In: V. Ratten, V. Braga and C. S. Marques, eds. *Knowledge, Learning and Innovation: Research Insights on Cross-Sector Collaborations*. Cham: Springer, pp. 5-26.
- Ahmad, N. H., Wilson, C. and Kummerow, L. (2011) A Cross-Cultural Insight into the Competency-Mix of SME Entrepreneurs in Australia and Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Management Science*, 4(1), pp. 33-50.
- Ahmad, S. Z. (2011b) Evidence of the characteristics of women entrepreneurs in the Kingdom of Saudi. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 3(2), pp. 123-143.
- Ahmed, A. (2018) *Pakistan among worst performers on gender equality: WEF*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.dawn.com/news/1452284> [Accessed 25/1/2020].
- Aidis, R., Welter, F., Smallbone, D. and Isakova, N. (2007) Female entrepreneurship in transition economies: the case of Lithuania and Ukraine. *Feminist Economics*, 13(2), pp. 157-183.
- Akman, G. and Yilmaz, C. (2019) Innovative Capability, Innovation Strategy and market Orientation: An Empirical Analysis in Turkish Software Industry. In: A. Brem, J. Tidd and T. U. Daim, eds. *Managing Innovation:*

What Do We Know About Innovation Success Factors?. London: World Scientific Publishing Europe Ltd., pp. 153.

Alalawi, G. N. S. (2020) *The Influence of Entrepreneurship Orientation on Omani SMEs' Performance*. Doctoral dissertation: University of Plymouth.

Alam, M. S., Biswas, K. and Sulphery, M. M. (2021) A Case Study on the Entrepreneurial Process of Push and Pull Women Entrepreneurs. *South Asian Journal of Business and Management Cases*, 10(2), p. 207–217.

Alam, S. S., Jani, M. F. M. and Omar, N. A. (2011) An Empirical Study of Success Factors of Women Entrepreneurs in Southern Region in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 3(2), pp. 166-175.

Al-Dajani, H., Akbar, H., Carter, S. and Shaw, E. (2019) Defying contextual embeddedness: evidence from displaced women entrepreneurs in Jordan. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 31(3-4), pp. 198-212.

Al-Dajani, H. and Marlow, S. (2010) Impact of women's home based enterprise on family dynamics: Evidence from Jordan. *International Small Business Journal*, 28(5), pp. 470-486.

Alecchi, B. A. (2020) Toward Realising the Potential of Latin America's Women Entrepreneurs: An Analysis of Barriers and Challenges. *Latin American Research Review*, 55(3), pp. 496-514.

Alegre, J. and Chiva, R. (2013) Linking Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance: The Role of Organizational Learning Capability and Innovation Performance. *Journal of small business management*, 51(4), pp. 491-507.

Alene, E. T. (2020) Determinants that Influence the Performance of Women Entrepreneurs in Micro and Small Enterprises in Ethiopia. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 9(1), pp. 1-20.

Ali, H. Y., Khan, M. K. and Asrar-ul-Haq, M. (2019) Factors affecting the performance of women entrepreneurs in SMEs: a case study of Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal for International Business and Entrepreneurship Development*, 12(1), pp. 67-82.

Ali, I., Hatta, Z. A., Azman, A. and Islam, S. (2016) Microfinance as a Development and Poverty Alleviation. *Asian Social Work and Policy Review*, 11(1), pp. 4-15.

Ali, R. S. (2018) Determinants of female entrepreneurs growth intentions. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 25(3), pp. 387-404.

Alshboul, O. et al. (2021) Deep and machine learning approaches for forecasting the residual value of heavy construction equipment: a management decision support model. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*.

- Altan-Olcay, O. (2014) Entrepreneurial Subjectivities and Gendered Complexities: Neoliberal Citizenship in Turkey. *Feminist Economics*, 20(4), pp. 235-259.
- Altan-Olcay, O. (2016) The Entrepreneurial Woman in Development Programs: Thinking through Class Differences. *Social Politics*, 23(3), pp. 389-414.
- Altinay, L. and Wang, C. L. (2011) The influence of an entrepreneur's socio-cultural characteristics on the entrepreneurial orientation of small firms. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 18(4), pp. 673-694.
- Alvarez, S. A. and Busenitz, L. W. (2001) The entrepreneurship of resource-based theory. *Journal of Management*, 27(6), pp. 755-775.
- Amjad, R. (2013) Why Pakistan has not reaped its demographic dividend?. In: Z. A. Sathar, R. Royan and J. Bongaarts, eds. *Capturing the Demographic Dividend in Pakistan*. Islamabad: The Population Council, pp. 25-40.
- Amrita, K., Prakash, C. G. and Singh, S. (2018) Modelling the Critical Success Factors of Women Entrepreneurship using Fuzzy AHP Framework. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 10(1) pp. 81-116.
- Ananke, 2015¹. *In search of Entrepreneurial Diversity in Pakistan*. [Online] Available at: <https://anankemag.com/2015/07/21/in-search-of-entrepreneurial-diversity-in-pakistan-2/> [Accessed 8/3/2020].
- Anderson, B. S. and Eshima, Y. (2013). The influence of firm age and intangible resources on the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and firm growth among Japanese SMEs. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28, pp. 413–429.
- Anderson, B.S., Kreiser, P.M., Kuratko, D.F., Hornsby, J.S. and Eshima, Y. (2015) Reconceptualizing Entrepreneurial Orientation. *Strategic management journal*, 36(10), pp.1579-1596.
- Antonakis, J., Bendahan, S., Jacquart, P. and Lalive, R. (2010) On Making Causal Claims: A Review and Recommendations. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 21(6), pp. 1086-1120.
- Antwi, S. K. and Kasim, H. (2015) Qualitative and Quantitative Research Paradigms in Business Research: A Philosophical Reflection. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(3), pp. 217-225.
- Anwar, M., Clauss, T. and Issah, W. B. (2022) Entrepreneurial Orientation and New Venture Performance in Emerging Markets: the Mediating Role of Opportunity Recognition. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16(3), pp. 769–796.

- APP (2020). *Pakistan ranks 154th on UN's Human Development Index*. [Online] Available at: <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2276065/pakistan-ranks-154th-on-uns-human-development-index> [Accessed 3/12/2020].
- Ashraf, M. A. (2018) Islamized Ideologies in the Pakistani Education System: The Need for Religious Literacy. *Religious Education*, 113(1), pp. 3-13.
- Aslam, S., Latif, M. and Aslam, M. W. (2013) Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs and Their Impact on Working Efficiency of Women in Pakistan. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 18 (8), pp.1204-1215.
- Audretsch, D. B. and Hinger, J. R. (2014) From entrepreneur to philanthropist: two side of the same coins?. In: M. L. Taylor, R. J. Strom and D. O. Renz, eds. *Handbook of Research on Entrepreneurs Engagement in Philanthropy: Perspectives*. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 24-42.
- Aziz, S. (2017) *Microfinancing Pakistan's female entrepreneurs*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/indepth/features/2017/09/microfinancing-pakistans-women-entrepreneurs-170930112423093.html> [Accessed 3/9/2019].
- Backes-Gellner, U. and Werner, A. (2007) Entrepreneurial Signaling via Education: A Success Factor in Innovative Start-Ups. *Small Business Economics*, 29(1-2), pp. 173-190.
- Baker, S. E., Edwards, R. and Doidge, M. (2012) *How many qualitative interviews is enough?: Expert voices and early career reflections on sampling and cases in qualitative research*. National Centre for Research Methods, Southampton, UK: National Centre for Research Methods, Southampton.
- Baker, W. E., Mukherjee, D. and Perin, M. G. (2022) Learning orientation and competitive advantage: A critical synthesis and future direction. *Journal of business research*, 144, pp. 863-873.
- Baker, W. E. and Sinkula, J. M. (2007) Does Market Orientation Facilitate Balanced Innovation Programs? An Organizational Learning Perspective. *Journal of product innovation management*, 24(4), pp. 316-334.
- Bamiatzi, V., Jones, S., Mitchelmore, S. and Konstantinos, N. (2015) The Role of Competencies in Shaping the Leadership Style of Female Entrepreneurs: The Case of North West of England, Yorkshire, and North Wales. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(3), pp. 627-644.
- Baranik, L. E., Gorman, B. and Wales, W. J. (2018) What makes Muslim Women Entrepreneurs Successful? A Field Study Examining Religiosity and Social Capital in Tunisia. *Sex Roles*, 78(3), pp. 208-219.
- Barazandeh, M., Parvizian, K., Alizadeh, M. and Khosravi, S. (2015) Investigating the effect of entrepreneurial competencies on business performance among early stage entrepreneurs Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM 2010 survey data). *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(1), pp. 1-12.

- Barbara, B. and Candida, B. (2002) A gendered perspective on organizational creation.. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 26(3), pp. 41-65.
- Barcala, M. F., Perez, M. J. S. and Gutierrez, J. A. T. (1999) Training in small business retailing: testing human capital theory. *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 23(7), pp. 335-352.
- Barney, J. (1991) Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17(1), pp. 99-120.
- Batool, H. and Ullah, K. (2017) Successful Antecedents of Women Entrepreneurs: A Case of Underdeveloped Nation. *Entrepreneurship Research Journal*, 7(2), pp. 2016-0066.
- Batool, H. and Ullah, K. (2018) Pakistani women entrepreneurs and ICT intervention. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 21(1), pp. 1-15.
- Baum, J. R., Locke, e. A. and Smith, K. G. (2001) A Multidimensional Model of Venture Growth. *Academy of Management Journal*, 44(2), pp. 292-303.
- Baum, J. R., Frese, M., Baron, R. A. & Katz, J. A. (2014) Entrepreneurship as an Area of Psychology Study: An Introduction. In: J. R. Baum, M. Frese and R. A. Baron, eds. *The Psychology of Entrepreneurship*. New York: Taylor and Francis Group, pp. 1-18.
- Baumüller, M. (2007) *Managing Cultural Diversity: An Empirical Examination of Cultural Networks and Organizational Structures as Governance Mechanisms in Multinational Corporations*. Oxford: Peter Lang.
- Beath, A., Christia, F. and Enikolopov, R. (2012) Empowering Women; Evidence from a Field Experiment in Afghanistan. *The World Bank, Impact Evaluation Series no. 76.*, Policy Research Working Paper 6269.
- Beaver, G. and Jennings, P. (2005) Competitive advantage and entrepreneurial power: The dark side of entrepreneurship. *Journal of small business and enterprise development*, 12(1), pp. 9-23.
- Bechir, M. (2017) The Recognition of Business Opportunity in Female: State of Play in a Tunisian Context. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Emerging Economies*, 3(2), pp. 148-154.
- Becker, G. S. (1964) *Human Capital*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Becker, J.-M., Klein, K. and Wetzels, M. (2012) Hierarchical Latent Variable Models in PLS-SEM: Guidelines for Using Reflective-Formative Type Models. *Long Range Planning*, 45(5-6), pp. 359-394.
- Belwal, S., Belwal, R. and Saidi, F. A. (2014) Characteristics, motivations, and challenges of women entrepreneurs in Oman's Al-Dhahira region. *Journal of Middle East Women's Studies*, 10(2), pp. 135-151.
- Benzing, C. and Chu, H. M. (2005) Entrepreneurial Behavior in Andhra Pradesh, India. *Proceedings of the Association of Global Business*, Miami Beach, Florida.

- Benzing, C., Chu, H. M. and Kara, O. (2009) Entrepreneurs in Turkey: A factor analysis of motivations, success factors and problems. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 47(1), pp. 58-91.
- Bernard, H. R. (2017) *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative*. 6th ed. London: Rowman and Littlefield.
- Bhattacharjee, A. (2012) *Social Science Research: Principles, Methods, and Practices*. 2nd ed. California: Creative Commons.
- Bhatt, P. and Garikipati, S. (2019) *Culture, Collectivism and Empowerment: The Role of Feminist Ideologies in Women's Work and Organization*. University of Liverpool, Working Paper No. 202108. Available at <https://www.liverpool.ac.uk/media/livacuk/schoolofmanagement/research/economics/Culture,,Collectivism,and,Empowerment.pdf> [Accessed: 3/12/23].
- Bird, B., (2019) Toward a Theory of Entrepreneurial Competency. In: J. A. Katz and A. C. Corbett, eds. *Seminal Ideas for the Next Twenty-Five Years of Advances*. Bengley, UK: Emerald Publishing Limited, pp. 115-131.
- Bird, B. and Brush, C. (2002) A Gendered Perspective on Organizational Creation. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 26(3), pp. 41-65.
- Birdsall, N., Levine, R. and Ibrahim, A. (2005) Towards Universal Primary Education: investments, incentives, and institutions. *European Journal of Education*, 40(3), pp. 337-349.
- Birkner, S., Ettl, K., Welter, F. and Ebbers, I. (2018) Women's Entrepreneurship in Europe: Research Facets and Educational Foci. In: S. Birkner, K. Ettl, F. Welter and I. Ebbers, eds. *Women's Entrepreneurship in Europe. FGF Studies in Small Business and Entrepreneurship*. Cham: Springer, pp. 2-13.
- Blackburn, R. A., Hart, M. and Wainwright, T. (2013) Small business performance: business, strategy and owner-manager characteristics. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 20(1), pp. 8-27.
- Blanche, M. T., Blanche, M. J. T., Durrheim, K. and Durrheim, K. (2006) *Research in practice: Applied methods for the social sciences*. South Africa: Juta and Company Ltd.
- Blashill, A. J. (2010) Elements of male body image: Prediction of depression, eating pathology and social sensitivity among gay men. *Body Image*, 7(4), pp. 310-316.
- Blumberg, B., Cooper, D. and Schindler, P. (2014) *Business Research Methods*. 4th ed. New York: McGraw Hill.
- Boddy, C. R. (2016) Sample size for qualitative research. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 19(4), pp. 426-432.
- Boden, R. J. and Nucci, A. R. (2000) On the survival prospects of men's and women's new business ventures. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 15(4), pp. 347-362.

- Bolarinwa, K. O. and Okolocha, C. C. (2016) Entrepreneurial Skills Needed by Farm Youths for Enhanced Agricultural Productivity. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 7(16), pp. 65–71.
- Bosma, N. and Kelley, D. (2018) *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor: 2018-19 Global Report*. London: Babson College.
- Boso, N., Story, V. M. and Cadogan, J. W. (2013) Entrepreneurial orientation, market orientation, network ties, and performance: Study of entrepreneurial firms in a developing economy. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 26(6), pp. 708-727.
- Bougie, R. and Sekaran, U. (2019) *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. 8 eds. New Jersey: John Wiley, and Sons.
- Boukamcha, F. (2015) Impact of training on entrepreneurial intention: an interactive cognitive perspective. *European Business Review*, 27(6), pp. 593-616.
- Box, M., Lin, X. and Gratzner, K. (2016) Linking Entrepreneurship and Economic Growth in Sweden, 1850–2000. In: Dieter Bogenhold, M. Dejardin, J. Bonnet and D. Garcia-Perez-de-Lema, eds. *Contemporary Entrepreneurship*. Switzerland: Springer, pp. 31-50.
- Bradley, S. W., Shepherd, D. A. and Wiklund, J. (2011) The Importance of Slack for New Organizations Facing ‘Tough’ Environments. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(5), pp. 1071-1097.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3 (2), pp. 77-101.
- Brettel, M., Chomik, C. and Flatten, T. C. (2015) How Organizational Culture Influences Innovativeness, Proactiveness, and Risk-Taking: Fostering Entrepreneurial Orientation in SMEs. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(4), pp. 868–885.
- Brettel, M. and Rottenberger, J. D. (2013) Examining the Link between Entrepreneurial Orientation and Learning Processes in Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 51(4), pp. 471-490.
- Brinckmann, J. (2008) *Competence of Top Management Teams and Success of New Technology-Based Firms: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis Concerning Competencies of Entrepreneurial Teams and the Development of Their Ventures*. Wiesbaden: Gabler Publishing.
- Brixiova, Z., Kangoye, T. and Tregenna, F. (2020) Enterprising women in Southern Africa: When does land ownership matter. *Journal of Family and Economic Issues*, 41(1), pp. 37-51.
- Brown, T. A. (2015) *Confirmatory Factor Analysis for Applied Research*. 2nd ed. New York: Guilford Publications.

- Brug, J. V. (2013). *The Global Rise of Female Entrepreneurs*. [Online] Available at: <https://hbr.org/2013/09/global-rise-of-female-entrepreneurs> [Accessed 8 /5/2019].
- Brush, C. G. (1992) Research on Women Business Owners; Past Trends, a New Perspective and Future Directions.. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 16 (4), pp.5-30.
- Brush, C. G., Bruin, A. D. and Welter, F. (2009) A gender-aware framework for women's entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 1(1), pp. 8-24.
- Brush, C. G. and Chaganti, R. (1999) Businesses without glamour? An analysis of resources on performance by size and age in small service and retail firms. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 14, pp. 223–258.
- Brush, C. G. and Hisrich, R. D. (1991) Antecedent influences on women owned businesses. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 6(2), pp. 9-16.
- Bryman, A. (2016) *Social Research Methods*. 5th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bryman, A. and Bell, E. (2015) *Business Research Methods*. 4 ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bula, H. O. (2012) Performance of Women in Small Scale Enterprises (SSEs): Marital Status and Family Characteristics. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(7), pp. 85-99.
- Burch, J. (2019) *Advantages and Disadvantages of Having a Marketing Orientation in an Organization*. [Online] Available at: <https://yourbusiness.azcentral.com/advantages-disadvantages-company-becoming-customerfocused-business-13245.html> [Accessed 22/5/2021].
- Burns, P. (2013) *Corporate Entrepreneurship: Innovation and Strategy in Large Organizations*. 3rd ed. Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Byabashaija, W. and Katono, I. (2011) The impact of college entrepreneurial education on entrepreneurial attitudes and intention to start a business in Uganda. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 16(1), pp. 127–144.
- Byrne, B. M. (2016) *Structural Equation Modeling with Amos*. 3 ed. New York: Routledge.
- Caca, E. (2010) The Factors Influencing SMEs in Countries in Transition: The Albania. *The International Journal of Interdisciplinary Social Sciences: Annual Review*, 5(3), pp. 139-148.
- Calantone, R. J., Cavusgil, T. and Zhao, Y. (2002) Learning orientation, firm innovation capability, and firm performance. *Industrial marketing management*, 31(6), pp. 515-524.
- Calcagnini, G., Giombini, G. and Lenti, E. (2015) Gender Differences in Bank Loan Access: An Empirical Analysis. *Italian Economic Journal*, 1(2), pp. 193-217.

- Camuffo, A., Camuffo, A. and Gubitta, P. (2012) Competencies matter: modeling effective entrepreneurship in northeast of Italy small firms. *Cross Cultural Management*, 19(1), pp. 48-66.
- Canina, L., Palacios, D. and Devece, C. (2010) Management theories linking individual and organizational level analysis in entrepreneurship research. *The International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 8(3), pp. 271-284.
- Capaldo, G., Iandoli, L. and Ponsiglione, C. (2004) Entrepreneurial competencies and training needs of small firms: A methodological approach. *Paper presented at 14th Annual International Entrepreneurship Conference, Napoli.*
- Caputo, A., Mehtap, S., Pellegrini, M. M. and Al-Refai, R. (2016) Supporting Opportunities for Female Entrepreneurs in Jordan. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 27(2/3), pp. 384-409.
- Carlsson, B. et al. (2013) The Evolving Domain of Entrepreneurship Research. *Small Business Economics*, 41(4), pp. 913-930.
- Carranza, E., Dhakal, C. and Love, I. (2018) *Female Entrepreneurs: How and Why Are They Different?* Washington D.C: The World Bank.
- Carter, S., Shaw, E., Lam, S. and Wilson, F. (2007) Gender, Entrepreneurship, and Bank Lending: The Criteria and Processes Used by Bank Loan Officers in Assessing Applications. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 31(3), pp. 427-444.
- Cassar, G. (2006) Entrepreneur opportunity costs and intended venture growth. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 21(5), pp. 610-632.
- Castrillon, C. (2019). *Why More Women Are Turning To Entrepreneurship*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/carolinecastrillon/2019/02/04/why-more-women-are-turning-to-entrepreneurship/?sh=26db041f542a> [Accessed 27/8/2020].
- Cesaroni, F. M. and Sentuti, A. (2018) The Leaders, the Outcasts and the Others: Which Role for Daughters in Family Businesses? In: J. Heinonen and K. Vainio-Korhonen, eds. *Women in Family Business*. New York: Routledge, pp. 179-198.
- Chandler, G. N. and Hanks, S. H. (1993) Measuring the performance of emerging businesses: A validation study. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 8(5), pp. 391-4088.
- Chandler, G. N. and Hanks, S. H. (1994) Founder competence, the environment, and venture performance. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 18(3), pp. 7-89.

- Chandler, G. N. and Hanks, S. H. (1998) An examination of the substitutability of founders human and financial capital in emerging business ventures. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 13(5), pp. 353-369.
- Chandler, G. N. and Jansen, E. (1992) The founder's self-assessed competence and venture performance. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 7(3), pp. 223-236 .
- Chang, H. H. and Ku, P. W. (2009) Implementation of relationship quality for CRM performance: Acquisition of BPR and organisational learning. *Total Quality Management*, 20(3), pp. 327-348.
- Chaston, I. and Sadler-Smith, E. (2012) Entrepreneurial Cognition, Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Capability in Creative Industries. *British Journal of Management*, 23(3), pp.415-432.
- Chaudhuri, K., Sasidharan, S. and Raj , R. S. N. (2020) Gender, small firm ownership, and credit access: some insights from India. *Small Business Economics*, 54, pp. 1165–1181.
- Cheah, J.H., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C.M., Ramayah, T. and Ting, H. (2018) Convergent validity assessment of formatively measured constructs in PLS-SEM: On using single-item versus multi-item measures in redundancy analyses. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 30(11), pp. 3192-3210.
- Chell, E., Wicklander, D. E., Sturman, S. G. and Hoover, L. W. (2008) *The Entrepreneurial Personality: A Social Construction*. 2 ed. New York: Routledge.
- Chetty, P. (2020) *Sociological theories of entrepreneurship*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.projectguru.in/sociological-theories-of-entrepreneurship/> [Accessed 19/6/2020].
- Chin, W. W. (2010) How to write up and report PLS analyses. In: H. Wang, J. Henseler, V. E. Vinzi and W. W. Chin, eds. *Handbook of partial least squares: Concepts, methods and applications*. Germany: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 655–690.
- Chiva, R., Ghauri, P. and Alegre, J. (2014) Organizational learning, innovation and internationalization: A complex system model. *British Journal of Management*, 25(4), pp.687-705.
- Chowdhury, F., Audretsch, D. B. and Belitski, M. (2019) Institutions and Entrepreneurship Quality. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(1), pp. 51–81.
- Chu, H. M., Benzing, C. and Mcgee, C. (2007) Ghanaian and Kenyan entrepreneurs: A comparative analysis of their motivations, success characteristics and problems. *Journal of developmental entrepreneurship*, 12(3), pp. 295-322.
- Civelek, M. E. (2018) *Essentials of Structural Equation Modeling*. Lincoln: Zea Books.
- Civera, A. and Meoli, M. (2023) Empowering Female Entrepreneurs Through University Affiliation: Evidence from Italian Academic Spinoffs. *Small Business Economics*, 61, pp. 1337–1355.

- Clarke, V. and Braun, V. (2013) Teaching thematic analysis: Overcoming challenges and developing strategies for effective learning. *The psychologist*, 26(2), pp. 120-123.
- Cliff, J. E. (1998) Does one size fit all? Exploring the relationship between attitudes towards growth, gender, and business size. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 13(6), pp. 523-542.
- Cole, A. H. (1968) Meso-Economics: A contribution from Entrepreneurial History. *Explorations in Entrepreneurial History*, 6(1), pp. 3-33.
- Coleman, S. (2016) Gender, Entrepreneurship, and Firm Performance: Recent Research and Considerations of Context.. In: M. L. Connerley and J. Wu, eds. *Handbook on Well-Being of Working Women*. Dordrecht: Springer Science, pp. 375-391.
- Collis, J. and Hussey, R. (2014) *Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate and Postgraduate Students*. 4th ed. Hampshire: UK: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cooke, F. L. and Xiao, M. (2021) Women Entrepreneurship in China: Where are We Now and Where are We Heading. *Human Resource Development International*, 24(1), pp. 104-121.
- Cooper, A., Gimeno-Gascón, F. J. and Woo, C. Y. (1994) Initial Human and Financial Capital as Predictors of New Venture Performance. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 9(5), pp. 371-395.
- Correa, V.S., da Silva Brito, F.R., de Lima, R.M. and Queiroz, M.M. (2021) Female entrepreneurship in emerging and developing countries: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*.
- Costa, S. F., Caetano, A. and Santos, S. C. (2016) Entrepreneurship as a Career Option: Do Temporary Workers Have the Competencies, Intention and Willingness to Become Entrepreneurs? *The Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 25(2), pp. 111-264.
- Courrent, J.-M., Chassé, S. and Omri, W. (2018) Do entrepreneurial SMEs perform better because they are more responsible? *Journal of Business Ethics*, 153(2), pp. 317–336.
- Coviello, N. E. and Jones, M. V. (2004) Methodological issues in international entrepreneurship research. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 19(4), pp. 485 – 508.
- Covin, J. G. and Miles, M. P. (1999) Corporate Entrepreneurship and the Pursuit of Competitive Advantage. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 23(3), pp. 47–64.
- Covin, J. G. and Slevin, D. P. (1991) The Conceptual Model of Entrepreneurship as Firm Behavior. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 16(1), pp. 7–25.
- Covin, J. G. and Wales, W. J. (2018) Crafting High-Impact Entrepreneurial Orientation Research: Some Suggested Guidelines. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 43(1), pp. 3-18.

- Cowling, M., Marlow, S. and Liu, W. (2020) Gender and Bank Lending After the Global Financial Crisis: Are Women Entrepreneurs Safer Bets? *Small Business Economics*, 55, pp. 853–880.
- Creswell, J. W. and Creswell, J. D. (2018) *Research design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed-Methods Approaches*. 5th ed. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J.W. and Plano Clark, V.L. (2017) *Designing and Conducting Mixed-Methods Research*. California: Sage Publication.
- Cypress, B. S. (2017) Rigor or Reliability and Validity in Qualitative Research: Perspectives, Strategies, Reconceptualization, and Recommendations. *Dimensions of Critical Care Nursing*, 36(4), pp. 253-263.
- Daily Times (2017) Pakistan second-worst on Global Gender Gap index. [Online] Available at: <https://dailytimes.com.pk/133689/pakistan-second-worst-global-gender-gap-index/> [Accessed 8/2/2021].
- Dakhan, S. A. (2019) *Aspiring Female Entrepreneurs in Pakistan: Entrepreneurial Intentions, Motivation and the Role of Religion*. Doctoral Dissertation: University of the West of Scotland.
- Danho, E. J., Dann, Z., Doyle, A., Ekinsmyth, C., Huang, S., Johnston, K., Pickernell, D. G., and Yarrow, E. L. (2021) *Baseline Report 1 - Entrepreneurial Ecosystems in France and the UK: The perspectives of disadvantaged female entrepreneurs and stakeholders in the entrepreneurial ecosystem: Accelerating Women's Enterprise*.
- Darlington, R. B. and Hayes, A. F. (2016) *Regression analysis and linear models: Concepts, applications, and implementation*. Guilford Publications.
- Davidsson, P., Achtenhagen, L. and Naldi, L. (2010) What Factors Facilitate or Hinder Growth?. In: *Small Firm Growth*. Hanover, MA, USA: Now Publishers Inc, pp. 29-44.
- Davidsson, P. and Wiklund, J. (2000) Conceptual and empirical challenges in the study of firm growth. In: D. Sexton and H. Landström, eds. *The Blackwell handbook of entrepreneurship*. Oxford, MA: Blackwell, pp. 26-44.
- Davis, P. J. (2012) The global training deficit: the scarcity of formal and informal professional development opportunities for women entrepreneurs. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 44(1), pp. 19-25.
- Dawa, S., Namatovu, R., Mulira, F., Kyejjusa, S., Arinaitwe, M. and Arinaitwe, A. (2021) Entrepreneurial competences and growth of female-owned enterprises: the mediation role of absorptive capacity. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 13(1), pp. 30-49.
- De Carolis, D. M. and Saporito, P. (2006) Social Capital, Cognition, and Entrepreneurial Opportunities: A Theoretical Framework. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 30(1), pp. 41 - 56.

- De Clercq, D., Honig, B. and Martin, B. (2013) The roles of learning orientation and passion for work in the formation of entrepreneurial intention. *International Small Business Journal*, 31(6), pp. 652-676.
- Dean, B. L. (2007) Creating subjects for gender apartheid: A critical study of an english language Pakistani textbook.. In: R. Qureshi and J. F. A. Rarieya, eds. *Gender and education in Pakistan*. Karachi: Oxford University Press, pp. 170-193.
- Debrulle, J. and Maes, J. (2015) Start-ups' Internationalization: The Impact of Business Owners' Management Experience, Start-up Experience and Professional Network on Export Intensity. *European Management Review*, 12(3), pp. 171-187.
- Dele-Ijagbulu, O., Moos, M. and Eresia-Eke, C. (2020) The Relationship Between Environmental Hostility and Entrepreneurial Orientation of Small Businesses. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Emerging Economies*, 6(2), pp. 347–362.
- Delgado-Verde, M., Martín-de Castro, G. and Amores-Salvadó, J. (2016) Intellectual capital and radical innovation: Exploring the quadratic effects in technology-based manufacturing firms. *Technovation*, 54, pp. 35-47.
- Delmar, F. (1996) *Entrepreneurial behavior and business performance*. Doctoral Dissertation: Stockholm: Stockholm School of Economics.
- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (2017) *The SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Research*. 5th ed. London: SAGE Publication.
- Dess, G. G. and Lumpkin, G. T. (2005) The Role of Entrepreneurial Orientation in Stimulating Effective Corporate Entrepreneurship. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 19(1), pp. 147-156.
- De Vos, J., Schwanen, T., Van Acker, V. and Frank, F. (2013) Travel and Subjective Well-Being: A Focus on Findings, Methods and Future Research Needs. *Transport Reviews*, 33(4), pp. 421-442.
- Dhaliwal, S. (2007) Dynamism and enterprise: Asian female entrepreneurs in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Immigration and Refugee Studies*, 5(2), pp. 45-64.
- Dewis, P. (2018) Data Collection Using Quantitative Methods. In: C. Carter, 2 ed. *Successful Dissertations: The Complete Guide for Education, Childhood and Early Childhood Studies Students*. London: Bloomsbury, pp. 167-194.
- Diaz-Garcia, M. C. and Carter, S. (2009) Resource mobilization through business owners' networks: is gender an issue?. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 3(1), p. 226–252.
- Diaz-Garcia, M. C. and Brush, C. G. (2012) Gender and business ownership: questioning “what” and “why”. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 18(1), pp. 4-27.

- Dijkstra, T. K. and Henseler, J. (2015) Consistent Partial Least Squares Path Modeling. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 39(2), pp. 297-316.
- Dimov, D. (2010) Nascent Entrepreneurs and Venture Emergence: Opportunity Confidence, Human Capital, and Early Planning. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(6), pp. 1123-1153.
- Dixon, N. M. (2017) *The Organizational Learning Cycle: How We Can Learn Collectively*. 2nd ed. London: Routledge.
- Dornyei, Z. and Dewaele, J.-M. (2022) *Questionnaires in Second Language Research: Construction, Administration, and Processing*. 3rd ed. New York: Taylor and Francis.
- Drine, I. and Grach, M. (2012) Supporting Women Entrepreneurs in Tunisia. *European Journal of Development Research*, 24(3), pp. 450-464.
- Dzisi, S., Meyer, D. D., Buckley, P. and Selvarajah, C. (2009) The Success of Ghanaian Women Entrepreneurs: Human and Cash Capital Factor. *Journal of Business and Enterprise Development*, pp. 102-111.
- Eddleston, K. A. and Powell, G. N. (2008) The Role of Gender Identity in Explaining Sex Differences in Business Owners' Career Satisfier Preferences. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 23(2), pp. 244-256.
- Edelman, L. F., Brush, C. G. and Manolova, T. (2005) Co-alignment in the resource–performance relationship: strategy as mediator. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 20(3), pp. 359-383.
- Edelman, L. F., Brush, C. G., Manolova, T. S. and Greene, P. G. (2010) Start-up Motivations and Growth Intentions of Minority Nascent Entrepreneurs. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 48(2), pp. 174-196.
- Edwards, R. and Mauthner, M. (2002) Ethics and feminist research: Theory and practice. *Ethics in qualitative research*, 2, pp. 14-28.
- Eggers, F., Kraus, S. and Hughes, M. (2013) Implications of customer and entrepreneurial orientations for SME growth. *Management Decision*, 51(3), pp. 524-546.
- Ekanem, I. (2015) Entrepreneurial Learning: gender difference. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 21(4), pp. 557-577.
- Ennis, C. A. (2019) The gendered complexities of promoting female entrepreneurship in the Gulf. *New Political Economy*, 24(3), pp. 365-384.
- Ensley, M. D. (2014) *Entrepreneurial Teams as Determinants of New Venture Performance*. New York: Routledge.
- Ermolayev, V. and Matzke, W. E. (2007) Towards Industrial strength Business Performance Management. In: V. Marik, V. Vyatkin and A. W. Colombo, eds. *International Conference on Industrial Applications of Holonic and Multi-Agent Systems*. Heidelberg, Berlin: Springer, pp. 387-400.

- Ettl, K. and Welter, F. (2010) Gender, context and entrepreneurial learning. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 2(2), pp. 108-129.
- Fairlie, R. W. and Robb, A. M. (2009) Gender differences in business performance: evidence from the Characteristics of Business Owners survey. *Small Business Economics*, 33(4), pp. 375-395.
- Fastre, G. and Gils, A. V. (2007) Competence development in Entrepreneurship – The role of University Education. In: M. K. McCuddy, et al. eds. *The Challenges of Educating People to Lead in a Challenging World*. Netherlands: Springer, p. 385–398.
- Fatemi, F. (2019) *The Value of Investing in Female Founders*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/falonfatemi/2019/03/29/the-value-of-investing-in-femalefounders/#7349eb225ee4> [Accessed 9/6/2020].
- Fayolle, A. and Gailly, B. (2015) The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on Entrepreneurial Attitudes and Intention: Hysteresis and Persistence. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(1), pp. 75-93.
- Fellnhöfer, K. and Kraus, S. (2015) Examining Attitudes towards Entrepreneurship Education: A Comparative Analysis among Experts. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Venturing*, 7(4), pp. 396-411.
- Fielden, S. L. and Davidson, M. J. (2010) *International Research handbook on Successful Women Entrepreneurs*. Edward: Elgar Publishing.
- Filser, M., Eggers, F., Kraus, S. and Malovics, E. (2014) The effect of financial resource availability on entrepreneurial orientation, customer orientation and firm performance in an international context: an empirical analysis from Austria and Hungary. *Journal for East European Management Studies*, pp. 7-30.
- Fis, A. M., Ozturkcan, S. and Gur, F. (2019) Being a Woman Entrepreneur in Turkey: Life Role Expectations and Entrepreneurial Self-efficacy. *SAGE Open*, 9(2).
- Fornell, C. and Larcker, D. F. (1981) Structural equation Models with unobserved variables and measurement error: algebra and statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3), pp. 382-388.
- Foss, N. J. (2011) Entrepreneurship in the Context of the Resource-based View of the Firm. In: K. Mole & M. Ram, eds. *Perspectives in Entrepreneurship*. London: Red Globe Press, pp. 120.
- Frank, H., Kessler, A. and Fink, M. (2010) Entrepreneurial Orientation and Business Performance — A Replication Study. *Schmalenbach Business Review*, 62(2), pp. 175–198.
- Frese, M., Brantjes, A. and Hoorn, R. (2002) Psychological Success Factors of Small Scale Businesses in Namibia: The Roles of Strategy Process, Entrepreneurial Orientation and the Environment. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 7(3), pp. 259-282.

- Fuentes-Fuentes, M. D. M., Bojica, A. M. and Matilde, R. A. (2015) Entrepreneurial orientation and knowledge acquisition: effects on performance in the specific context of women owned firms. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 11, pp. 695–717.
- Fuller-Love, N. (2008) Female Entrepreneurship. In: M. Galindo, J. Guzman and D. Ribeiro, eds. *Entrepreneurship and Business – A Regional Perspective*. Heidelberg, Germany: Springer, pp. 291-308.
- Furlan, A. (2019) Startup Size and Pre-Entry Experience: New Evidence from Italian New Manufacturing Ventures. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(2), pp. 679–692.
- Fu, Y. et al. (2021) “Lean in”: the moderating effect of female ownership on the relationship between human capital and organizational innovation". *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 22(4), pp. 792-814.
- Galbreath, J. and Galvin, P. (2008) Firm factors, industry structure and performance variation: New empirical evidence to a classic debate. *Journal of Business Research*, 61(2), pp. 109-117.
- Gali, N. K. (2018) *Effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation on Firm Performance and Failure: A Longitudinal Analysis*. Doctoral Dissertation: Durham University.
- Garcia-Morales, V. J., Verdu-Jover, A. J. and Llorens, F. J. (2009) The influence of CEO perceptions on the level of organizational learning: Single-loop and double-loop learning. *International Journal of Manpower*, 30(6), pp. 567-590.
- Gartner, W. (1985) A Conceptual Framework for Describing the Phenomenon of New Venture Creation. *The Academy of Management Review*, 10(4), pp. 696-706.
- Garvin, D. A. (1993) Building a Learning Organization. *Harvard Business Review*, pp. 78-91.
- Gasse, Y., d’Amboise, G., Simard, G. and Lasker, K. (1997) *Entrepreneurial-Managerial Competencies and Practices of Growing SMEs – Summary of Results from an Empirical Study (Preliminary)*: Centre for Entrepreneurship and SME and Entrepreneuriat Laval, Universite Laval, Montreal.
- Gawel, A. and Mroczek-Dabrowska, K. (2022) Gender Pay Gap in Explaining Female Entrepreneurship – Industry Perspective of Selected European Countries. *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(9), pp. 42-59.
- GEM (2018) *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor 2018/2019 Women’s Entrepreneurship Report*, London: Global Entrepreneurship Research Association.
- Genis-Gruber, A. and Ogut, H. (2014) Environmental factors affecting innovation strategies of companies: Customers and suppliers effect. *companies: Customers and suppliers effect*, 150, pp. 718 – 725 .
- George, B. A. and Marino, L. (2011) The Epistemology of Entrepreneurial Orientation: Conceptual Formation, Modeling, and Operationalization. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(5), pp. 989-1024.

- Ghani, E., Kerr, W. R. and O'Connell, S. D. (2013) Local Industrial Structures and Female Entrepreneurship in India. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 13(6), pp. 929-964.
- Ghani, E., Kerr, W. R. and O'Connell, S. D. (2014) Political Reservations and Women's Entrepreneurship in India. *Journal of Development Economics*, 108, pp. 138-153.
- Ghauri, P., Gronhaug, K. and Strange, R. (2020) *Research Methods in Business Studies: A Practical Guide*. 5th ed. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ghosh, P. and Cheruvalath, R. (2007) Indian female entrepreneurs as catalysts for economic growth and development. *Indian Female Entrepreneurs as Catalysts for Economic Growth and Development*, 8(2), pp. 139-147.
- Ghouse, S. M., McElwee, G. and Durrah. O. (2019), Entrepreneurial Success of Cottage-Based Women Entrepreneurs in Oman. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 25(3), pp.480-498.
- Ghouse, S., McElwee, G., Meaton, J. and Durrah, O. (2017) Barriers to Rural Women Entrepreneurs in Oman. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research* 23(6), pp. 998-1016
- Gibb, A. A. (2005) The entrepreneur as the core competence of the firm: implication for management educators. *Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Small Business Network*, (2)2.
- Gielnik, M. M., Uy, M. A., Funken, R. and Bischoff, K. M. (2017) Boosting and sustaining passion: A long-term perspective on the effects of entrepreneurship training. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 32, pp. 334–353.
- Gieure, C., Benavides-Espinosa, M. d. M. and Roig-Dobon, S. (2020) The entrepreneurial process: The link between intentions and behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 112, pp. 541-548.
- GEM (2015) *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor: 2015 Report on Women and Entrepreneurship*, Wellesley, MA.: Babson College.
- Glassman, W. and Hadad, M. (2013) *Approaches to Psychology*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Gobbi, M. S. D., Dhakal, N. H. and Hijaz, S. T. (2005) *Nepal and Pakistan - Micro-finance and microenterprise development: Their contribution to the economic empowerment of women*, Nepal, Pakistan: International Labour Organization.
- Gong, Y., Huang, J.-C. and Farh, J.-L. (2009) Employee learning orientation, transformational leadership, and employee creativity: the mediating role of employee creative self-efficacy. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(4), pp. 765-778.
- Gonzalez, S. V. M. (2018) Self-Employment, Knowledge and Economic Growth: An Empirical Study for Latin American Countries. *Contemporary Economics*, 12(4), pp. 473-484.

- Gooptu, N. and Chakravarty, R. (2018) Skill, Work and Gendered Identity in Contemporary India: The Business of Delivering Home-Cooked Food for Domestic Consumption. *Journal of South Asian Development*, 13(3), pp. 293-314.
- GOP (2014) *Highlights of Pakistan Economic Survey 2014-15*. Economic Adviser's Wing, Finance Division, Islamabad: Government of Pakistan.
- Grant, R. M. (2015) *Contemporary strategy analysis*. United States: John Wiley and Sons.
- GSMA (2021) *Addressing the Mobile Gender Gap in Pakistan*, London: GSMA.
- Guest, G., Namey, E. E. and Mitchell, M. L. (2013) *Collecting Qualitative Data: A Field Manual for Applied Research*. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications.
- Guillemin, M. and Gillam, L. (2004) Ethics, Reflexivity, and “Ethically Important Moments” in Research. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 10(2), pp. 261-280.
- Gundry, L. K., Kickul, J. R., Iakovleva, T. and Carsrud, A. L. (2014) Women Owned Family Businesses in Transitional Economies: Key Influences on Firm Innovativeness and Sustainability. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 3(1), pp. 1-17.
- Guo, Z. and Jiang, W. (2020) Risk-taking for Entrepreneurial New Entry: Risk-Taking. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 16, pp. 739–781.
- Gupta, N. and Mirchandani, A. (2018) Investigating Entrepreneurial Success Factors of Women Owned SMEs in UAE. *Management Decision*, 56(1), pp. 219-232.
- Gupta, P. D., Guha, S. and Krishnaswami, S. S. (2013) Firm Growth and its Determinants. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 2(15), pp. 1-14.
- Gupta, V. K., Nirajan, S. and Erik, M. (2020) Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance: the Mediating Role of Generative and Acquisitive Learning through Customer Relationships. *Review of Managerial Science*, 14(5), pp. 123–1147.
- Gutierrez, P. R., Fuentes, M. d. M. F. and Ariza, L. R. (2014) Strategic Capabilities and Performance in Women Owned Businesses in Mexico. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 52(3), pp. 541–554.
- Haber, S. and Reichel, A. (2007) The cumulative nature of the entrepreneurial process: The contribution of human capital, planning and environment resources to small venture performance. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 22(1), pp. 119-145.

- Hafizullah, Ahmad, Z. M., Manzoor, S. R. and Hussain, M. (2012) Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs in Kohat City of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa-Pakistan. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 2(1), pp. 73-111
- Hair, J., Black, W., Babin, B. and Anderson, R. (2010) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. 7th ed. Boston: Pearson Education.
- Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J. and Anderson, R. E. (2013) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. London: Pearson Education Limited.
- Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M. (2011) PLS-SEM: Indeed a Silver Bullet. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 19(2), pp. 139-152.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M. and Ringle, C. M. (2019) When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), pp. 2-24.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M. and Mena, J. A. (2012) An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 40(3), pp. 414-433.
- Hair, J. J., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M. (2017) *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publication.
- Halabisky, D. (2018) *Policy Brief on Women's Entrepreneurship, OECD SME and Entrepreneurship Papers, No. 8*, Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Hamilton, R. T. (2012) How firms grow and the influence of size and age. *International Small Business Journal*, 30(6), pp. 611-621.
- Hanif, M. I., Meryem, M., Rao, H. and Nawaz, M. K. (2017) Women's Entrepreneurship in Rural Areas of Punjab, Pakistan: How are Women Possess and Supervising Home-Based Businesses Aggravated to Grow. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 6(3), pp. 308.
- Hardaker, J. B., Lien, G., Anderson, J. R. and Huirne, R. B. M. (2015) *Coping with risk in agriculture: Applied decision analysis*. 3 ed. Oxfordshire, UK: CABI.
- Harris, C. M., Pattie, M. W. and McMahan, G. C. (2015) Advancement along a career path: the influence of human capital and performance. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 25(1), pp. 102-115.
- Hart, S. L. (1992) An Integrative Framework for Strategy-Making Processes. *The Academy of Management Review*, 17(2), pp. 327-351.
- Hasan, F. S. and Almubarak, M. . M. S. (2016) Factors influencing women entrepreneurs' performance in SMEs. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 12(2), pp. 1-22.

- Hatch, M. J. (2018) *Organisation Theory: Modern, Symbolic, and Postmodern Perspectives*. 4th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Hazudin, S. F. et al. (2015) Discovering Small Business Start up Motives, Success Factors and Barriers: A Gender Analysis. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 31, pp. 436 – 443.
- Heirman, A. and Clarysse, B. (2006) The Early Growth of Research-Based Start-Ups. In: J. Wiklund, D. Dimov, J. A. Katz and D. Shepherd , eds. *Entrepreneurship: Frameworks And Empirical Investigations From Forthcoming Leaders Of European Research*. Bingley: Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp. 195-227.
- Hendratmi, A. and Sukmaningrum, P. S. (2018) Role of Government Support and Incubator Organisation to Success Behaviour of Woman Entrepreneur: Indonesia Women Entrepreneur Association. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 17(1), pp.105-115.
- Henry, C., Foss, L. and Ahl, H. (2016) Gender and Entrepreneurship Research: A Review of Methodological Approaches. *International Small Business Journal*, 34(3), pp. 217–241.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M. and Sarstedt, M. (2015) A New Criterion for Assessing Discriminant Validity in Variance-Based Structural Equation Modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43, pp. 115–135.
- Hernandez, K.-A. C. and Ngunjiri, F. W. (2016) Relationships and Communities in Autoethnography. In: T. E. Adams, S. H. Jones and C. Ellis, eds. *Handbook of Autoethnography*. New York: Routledge, pp. 262-272.
- Hisrich, R. D. (2014) *Advanced Introduction to Entrepreneurship*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Hisrich, R., Langan-Fox, J. and Grant, S. (2007) Entrepreneurship Research and Practice: A Call to Action for Psychology. *American Psychologist*, 62(6), pp. 575-589.
- Hlady-Rispal, M. and Jouison-Laffitte, E. (2014) Qualitative Research Methods and Epistemological Frameworks: A Review of Publication Trends in Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 52(4), pp. 594-614.
- Hohenthal, J. (2006) Integrating qualitative and quantitative methods in research on international entrepreneurship. *Journal of International Entrepreneurship*, 4(4), pp. 175-190.
- Hollstein, B. (2014) *Mixed-Methods Social Networks Research. Design and Applications*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Hossain, S. F. A., Nurunnabi, M., Hussain, K. and Shan, X. (2020) Smartphone-based m-shopping behavior and innovative entrepreneurial tendency among women in emerging Asia. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 12(2), pp. 173-189.

- Hoyle, R. H. (2014) *Handbook of Structural Equation Modeling*. London: Guilford Publications.
- Hsiao, C., Lee, Y.-H. and Chen, H.-H. (2016) The effects of internal locus of control on entrepreneurship: the mediating mechanisms of social capital and human capital. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(11), pp. 1158–1172.
- Hughes, K. D. (2006) Exploring motivation and success among Canadian women entrepreneurs. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 19(2), pp. 107-120.
- Hughes, M., Eggers, F., Kraus, S. and Hughes, P. (2015) The Relevance of Slack Resource Availability and Networking Effectiveness for Entrepreneurial Orientation. *International journal of entrepreneurship and small business*, 26(1), pp. 116-138.
- Hughes, M. and Morgan, R. E. (2007) Deconstructing the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and business performance at the embryonic stage of firm growth. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 36(5), p. 651–661.
- Hunt, J. M. (1988) Toward the development of a competency model of family firm leadership. *Paper presented to the 12th Annual National Conference. United States Association for Small Business and Entrepreneurship, Clearwater, FL, January*, pp. 5-18.
- Hussain, J., Mahmood, S. and Scott, J. (2019) Gender, Microcredit and Poverty Alleviation in a Developing Country: The Case of Women Entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *Journal of International Development*, 31(3), p. 247–270.
- Hyder, S. and Lussier, R. N. (2016) Why businesses succeed or fail: a study on small businesses in Pakistan. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 8(1), pp. 82-100.
- Hyman, L., Lamb, J. and Bulmer, M. (2006) *The Use of Pre-Existing Survey Questions: Implications for Data Quality*. Cardiff, The Conference on Quality in Survey Statistics.
- Ibidunni, A. S., Ogunjana, O. M. and Okonkwo, A. (2021) Entrepreneurial Competencies and the Performance of Informal SMEs: The Contingent Role of Business Environment. *Journal of African Business*, 22(4), pp. 468-490.
- Iftikhar, N. (2016) *Pakistani society averse to entrepreneurship*. [Online] Available at: <https://tribune.com.pk/story/1086714/avoiding-risks-pakistani-society-averse-to-entrepreneurship> [Accessed 20/5/2020].
- Inan, G. G. and Bititci, U. S. (2015) Understanding organizational capabilities and dynamic capabilities in the context of micro enterprises: a research agenda. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 210, pp. 310-319.

- Insights, 2016. *OCED Insights Debate the Issues*. [Online] Available at: <http://oecdinsights.org/2016/07/12/gender-inequality-emerging-economies/> [Accessed 13/9/2019].
- Inyang, B. and Enuoh, R. (2009) Entrepreneurial Competencies: The Missing Links to Successful Entrepreneurship in Nigeria. *International Business Research*, 2(2), pp. 62-71.
- Irene, B. N. O. (2016) *Gender and Entrepreneurial Success: A Cross Cultural Study of Competencies of Female SMEs Operators in South Africa*. Doctoral dissertation: Cardiff Metropolitan University.
- Irvine, A. (2011) Duration, Dominance and Depth in Telephone and Face-to-Face Interviews: A Comparative Exploration. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 10(3), pp. 202-220.
- Isa, S. M., Musa, M. Shuib, R. Osman, I. Selamat, N. H., and Abu Baker, S. (2016) Exploring Women's Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Micro Business. In: k. Grant and S. Wise, eds. *ICIE 2016 Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship: ICIE2016*. Toronoto: Academic Conferences and Publishing Limited, pp. 88-94.
- Ishaq, S. (2022) *Small and Medium Enterprises' (SMEs) Access to Islamic Banking Finance in Pakistan*, Doctoral Disserataion: Aston University.
- Ismail, H. C., Shamsudin , F. M. and Chowdhury , M. S. (2012) An Exploratory Study of Motivational Factors on Women Entrepreneurship Venturing in Malaysia. *Business and Economic Research*, 2(1).
- Ivankova, N. V., Creswel, J. W. and Stick, S. L. (2006) Using Mixed-Methods Sequential Explanatory Design: From Theory to Practice. *Field Methods*, 18(1), pp. 3-20.
- Jabeen, F. and Faisal, M. N. (2018) Imperatives for Improving Entrepreneurial Behavior among Females in the UAE: An Empirical Study and Structural Model. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 33(3), pp. 234-252.
- Jaim, J. (2021b) Bank Loans Access for Women Business Owners in Bangladesh: Obstacles and Dependence on Husbands. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 59, pp. S16-S41 .
- Jaim, J. (2021) Women's Entrepreneurship in Developing Countries from a Family Perspective: Past and future. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 41(1), pp. 31-45.
- Jamali, D. (2009) Constraints and Opportunities Facing Women Entrepreneurs in Developing Countries: A Relational Perspective. *Gender in Management*, 24(4), pp. 232-251.
- Jancenelle, V., Storrud-Barnes, S. F. and Buccieri, D. (2022) Market Orientation and Firm Performance: can there be too Much of a Good Thing? *Management Decision*, 60(6), pp. 1683-1701.

- Javalgi, R. G. and Todd, P. R. (2011) Entrepreneurial Orientation, Management Commitment, and Human Capital: The Internationalization of SMEs in India. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(9), pp. 1004-1010.
- Jayachandran, S. (2015) The Roots of Gender Inequality in Developing Countries. *Annual Review of Economics*, 7(1), pp. 63-88.
- Jayawarna, D., Jones, O. and Macpherson, A. (2014) Entrepreneurial Potential: The Role of Human and Cultural Capitals. *International Small Business Journal*, 32(8), pp. 918–943.
- Jebb, A. T., Parrigon, S. and Woo, S. E. (2017) Exploratory Data Analysis as a Foundation of Inductive Research. *Human Resource Management Review*, Volume 27, pp. 265-276.
- Jennings, J. E. and Brush, C. G. (2013) Research on Women Entrepreneurs: Challenges to (and from) the Broader Entrepreneurship Literature? *The Academy of Management Annals*, 7(1), pp. 663-7157.
- Jennings, J. E. and Mcdougald, M. S. (2007) Work-Family Interface Experiences and Coping Strategies: Implications for Entrepreneurship Research and Practice. *The Academy of Management Review*, 32(3), pp. 747-760.
- Jha, S. and Bhattacharyya, S. S. (2013) Learning Orientation and Performance Orientation: Scale Development and Its Relationship with Performance. *Global Business Review*, 14(1), pp. 43-54.
- Jiang, C. X., Zimmerman, M. A. and Guo, C. (2012) Growth of Women Owned Businesses: The Effects of Intangible Resources and Social Competence. *Journal of Business Diversity*, 12(1), pp. 47-71.
- Jiang, K., Takeuchi, R. and Lepak, D. P. (2013) Where do We Go From Here? New Perspectives on the Black Box in Strategic Human Resource Management Research. *Journal of Management Studies*, 50(8), pp.1448-1480.
- Jiao, K., Ling, Y. and Kellermanns, F. W. (2021) Does prior experience matter? A meta-analysis of the relationship between prior experience of entrepreneurs and firm performance. *Journal of Small Business Management*, pp. 1-48.
- Johnson, S. G., Schnatterly, K. and Hill, A. D. (2013) Board Composition Beyond Independence: Social Capital, Human Capital, and Demographics. *Journal of Management*, 39(1), pp. 232-262.
- Jony, A. I. and Serradell-Lopez, E. (2021) A PLS-SEM approach in evaluating a virtual teamwork model in online higher education: why and how?. In: A. Visvizi, M. D. Lytras and N. R. Aljohani, eds. *Research and Innovation Forum 2020: Disruptive Technologies in Times of Change*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, pp. 217-232.
- Kakabadse, N.K., Tatli, A., Nicolopoulou, K., Tankibayeva, A. and Mouraviev, N. (2018) A Gender Perspective on Entrepreneurial Leadership: Female Leaders in Kazakhstan. *European Management Review*, 15(2), pp. 155-170.

- Kao, R. W. (1993) Defining Entrepreneurship: Past, Present and ? *Creative and Innovative Management*, 2(1), pp. 69-70.
- Karami, M. and Tang, J. (2019) Entrepreneurial orientation and SME international performance: The mediating role of networking capability and experiential learning. *International Small Business Journal*, 37(2), pp. 105-124.
- Kaur, H. and Bains, A. (2013) Understanding The Concept Of Entrepreneur Competency. *Journal of Business Management and Social Sciences Research*, 2(11), pp. 31-33.
- Kazmi, K. H. (2018) *Significance of Women Entrepreneurship in Pakistan*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.pakistangulfeconomist.com/2018/10/29/significance-of-women-entrepreneurship-in-pakistan/> [Accessed 19/5/2018].
- Keh, H. T., Nguyen, T. T. M. and Ng, H. P. (2007) The effects of entrepreneurial orientation and marketing information on the performance of SMEs. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 22(4), pp. 592–611.
- Keith, J. L. (2014) *Enterprise Risk Management: Developing a Strategic ERM Alignment Framework-Financial Sector*. London: Brunel University.
- Kelley, D. J., Singer, S. and Herrington, M. D. (2013) *Global entrepreneurship monitor 2012 report: Women's entrepreneurship worldwide*. London, Global Entrepreneurship Research Association (GERA).
- Khan, T. H., and MacEachen, E. (2022). An Alternative Method of Interviewing: Critical Reflections on Videoconference Interviews for Qualitative Data Collection. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 21.
- Khan, K. and Ramachandran, S. (2012) Conceptual Framework for Performance Assessment: Competency, Competence and Performance in the Context of Assessments in Healthcare – Deciphering the terminology. *Medical Teacher*, 34(11), pp. 920-928.
- Khuraibet, S. (2015) *The Role of Business Model Information Systems and Human Capital in the Barriers to the Growth of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Kuwait*. Doctoral Dissertation: Royal Holloway, University of London.
- Khoshmaram, M., Shiri, N., Shinnar, R. S. and Savari, M. (2020) Environmental Support and Entrepreneurial Behavior among Iranian Farmers: The Mediating Roles of Social and Human Capital. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 58(5), pp. 1064-1088.
- Kiggundu, M. N. (2002) Entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship in Africa: what is known and what needs to be done. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 7(3), pp. 239-258.
- Kimosop, J., Korir, M. and White, M. (2016) The Moderating Effect of Demographic Characteristics on the Relationship between Strategic Capabilities and Firm Performance in Women-Owned Entrepreneurial Ventures

in Nairobi, Kenya. *Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences/Revue Canadienne des Sciences de l'Administration*, 33(3), pp. 242-256.

Kim, Y. et al. (2019) Straightlining: Overview of Measurement, Comparison of Indicators, and Effects in Mail–Web Mixed-Mode Surveys. *Social Science Computer Review*, 37(2), pp. 214-233.

Kiril, T. (2014) The Entrepreneur as a Strategist and Improviser: Subject of Activity and Objective of Understanding. In: K. Todorov and D. Smallbone, eds. *Handbook of Research on Strategic Management in Small and Medium Enterprises*. Pennsylvania: IGI Global, pp. 98-123.

Kirkwood, J. (2009) Is a lack of self-confidence hindering women entrepreneurs? *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 1(2), pp. 118 - 133.

Kirkwood, J. and Walton, S. (2010) What motivates ecopreneurs to start businesses?. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 16(3), pp. 204-228.

Kivunja, C. and Kuyini, A. B. (2017) Understanding and Applying Research Paradigms in Educational Contexts. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 6(5), pp. 26-41.

Kirzner, I. M. (1973) *Competition and Entrepreneurship*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Kline, R. B. (2016) *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling*. 4th ed. New York: Guilford Publications.

Knight, M. (2016) Raceing, Classing and Gendering Racialized Women's Participation in Entrepreneurship. *Gender, Work and Organization*, 23(3), pp. 310-327.

Konsti-Laakso, S., Pihkala, T. and Kraus, S. (2012) Facilitating SME innovation capability through business networking. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 31(1), pp. 93-105.

Koporcic, N. and Tornroos, J.-A. (2019) Understanding Basic Methodological Issues of Interactive Network Branding. In: *Understanding Interactive Network Branding in SME Firms*. Leeds: Emerald Publishing Limited, pp. 97-102.

Koudstaal, M., Randolph, S. and Praag, V. M. (2016) Risk, Uncertainty, and Entrepreneurship: Evidence from a Lab-in-the-Field Experiment. *Management Science*, 62(10), pp. 2897-2915.

Krasniqi, B. A. and Mustafa, M. (2016) Small firm growth in a post-conflict environment: the role of human capital, institutional quality, and managerial capacities. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 12(4), pp. 1165-1207.

- Kraus, S., Rigtering, J. P. C., Hughes, M. and Hosman, V. (2012) Entrepreneurial orientation and the business performance of SMEs: a quantitative study from the Netherlands. *Review of Managerial Science*, 6(2), pp. 161-182.
- Kuada, J. (2015) The human factor in economic development. In: J. Kuada, ed. *Private Enterprise-Led Economic Development in Sub-Saharan Africa: The Human Side of Growth*. Hampshire, UK: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 53.
- Kumar, R. (2014) *Research Methodology: A Step-By-Step Guide For Beginners*. California: Sage Publications.
- Kungwansupaphan, C. and Leihaothabam, J.K.S., 2019. Entrepreneurial orientation, performance, and the moderating role of institutional capital: A case study of female entrepreneurs in Thailand. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 24(02), pp.1-20.
- Kungwansupaphan, C. and Siengthai, S. (2014) Exploring entrepreneurs' human capital components and effects on learning orientation in early internationalizing firms. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 10(3), pp. 561-587.
- Kuschel, K., Lepeley, M.-T., Espinosa, F. and Gutiérrez, S. (2017) Funding Challenges of Latin American Women Start-up Founders in the Technology Industry. *Cross Cultural and Strategic Management*, 24(2), pp. 310-331
- Kwong, C., Evans, D. J. and Thompson, P. (2012) Differences in perceptions of access to finance between potential male and female entrepreneurs: Evidence from the UK. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 18(1), pp. 75-97.
- Lahiri, D. (2014) Identifying 'anchor' micro-enterprises – an empirical study. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 27(1), pp. 1-26.
- Lampadariou, E., Kyriakidou, N. and Smith, G. (2017) Towards a New Framework for SMEs Success: a Literature Review. *International Journal of Business and Globalisation*, 18(2), pp. 194-232.
- Langevang, T. (2017) Fashioning the Future: Entrepreneurship in Africa's Emerging Fashion Industry. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 29(4), pp. 893-910.
- Langevang, T., Hansen, M. W. and Rutashobya, L. K. (2018) Navigating Institutional Complexities: The Response Strategies of Tanzanian Female Entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 10(3), pp. 224-242.
- Lans, T., Verhees, F. and Verstegen, J. (2016) Social Competence in Small Firms --Fostering workplace learning and performance. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 27(3), pp. 321-348.

- Lans, T., Verstege, J. and Mulder, M. (2011) Analysing, pursuing and networking: Towards a validated three-factor framework for entrepreneurial competence from a small firm perspective. *International Small Business Journal*, 29(6), pp. 695–713.
- Leavy, P. (2017) *Research design: Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed Methods, Arts-Based, and Community-Based Participatory Research Approaches*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press.
- Lechner, C. and Gudmundsson, S. V. (2014) Entrepreneurial Orientation, Firm Strategy and Small Firm Performance. *International Small Business Journal*, 32(1), pp. 36-60.
- Lee, K. and Carter, S. (2012) Creating, Developing and Maintaining competitive Advantage. In: 3, ed. *Global Marketing Management*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, p. 273.
- Lee, T. and Chu, W. (2013) How Entrepreneurial Orientation, Environmental Dynamism, and Resource Rareness Influence Firm Performance. *Journal of Management and Organization*, 19(2), pp. 167-187.
- Lee, C., Lee, K. and Pennings, J. M. (2001) Internal Capabilities, External Networks, and Performance: a Study on Technology-Based Ventures. *Strategic Management Journal*, 22(6-7), pp. 615-640.
- Lee, C. and Yuhua, B. Z. (2016) SMEs, Competition Law, and Economic Growth. In: M. T. Schaper and C. Lee, eds. *Competition Law, Regulation and SMEs in the Asia-Pacific: Understanding the Small Business Perspective..* Singapore: ISEAS Yusof Ishak Institute, pp. 17-48.
- Lerner, M. and Almor, T. (2002) Relationships among Strategic Capabilities and the Performance of Women Owned Small Ventures. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 40(2), pp. 109-125.
- Lerner, M., Brush, C. G. and Hisrich, R. D. (1997) Israeli Women Entrepreneurs: An Examination of Factors Affecting Performance. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 12(4), pp. 315-339.
- Lerner, M. and Sigal, H. (2001) Performance factors of small tourism ventures: The interface of tourism, entrepreneurship and the environment. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 16(1), pp. 77-100.
- Ligaya, A. (2018) *Women owned businesses generate \$68,000 less revenue than men's: survey*. [Online] Available at: <https://business.financialpost.com/entrepreneur/women-owned-businesses-generate-68000-less-revenue-than-mens-survey> [Accessed 9/6/2020].
- Lim, S. and Enwick, B. R. (2013) Gender and entrepreneurial orientation: a multi-country study. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 9, pp. 465–482.
- Lindvert, M., Patel, P. C. and Wincent, J. (2017) Struggling with social capital: Pakistani women micro entrepreneurs' challenges in acquiring resources. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 29(7-8), pp. 759-790.

- Lock, R. and Smith, H. L. (2016) The Impact of Female Entrepreneurship on Economic Growth in Kenya. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 8(1), pp. 90-96.
- Lockyer, J. and George, S. (2011) What women want: barriers to female entrepreneurship in the West Midlands. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 4(2), pp. 179-195.
- Lonial, S. C. and Carter, R. E. (2015) The impact of organizational orientations on medium and small firm performance: A resource-based perspective. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(1), pp. 94-113.
- Luke, A. (2018) Genres of power: Literacy education and the production of capital. In: A. Luke, ed. *Critical Literacy, Schooling, and Social Justice*. New York: Routledge, pp. 161-185.
- Lu, L., Lin, X. and Leung, K. (2012). Goal Orientation and Innovative Performance: The Mediating Roles of Knowledge Sharing and Perceived Autonomy. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 42, pp. 180-197.
- Lumpkin, G., Cogliser, C. C. and Schneider, D. R. (2009). Understanding and Measuring Autonomy: An Entrepreneurial Orientation Perspective. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(1), pp. 47-69.
- Lumpkin, G. T., Brigham, K. H. and Moss, T. W., (2010) Long-term orientation: Implications for the entrepreneurial orientation and performance of family businesses.. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 22(3-4), pp. 241-264.
- Lumpkin, G. T. and Dess, G. G., (1996) Clarifying the Entrepreneurial Orientation Construct and Linking It to Performance. *The Academy of Management Review*, 21(1), pp. 135-172.
- Madhani, P. M. (2010) Resource Based View: Concept and Practice. In: *Resource Based View (RBV) of Competitive Advantage: An Overview*. Hyderabad, India: Icfai University Press, pp. 3-22.
- Madsen, E. L. (2007) The significance of sustained entrepreneurial orientation on performance of firms – A longitudinal analysis. *Entrepreneurship and regional development*, 19(2), pp. 185-204.
- Mahmood, B., Sohail, M. M. and Khalid, S. (2012) Gender Specific Barriers to Female Entrepreneurs in Pakistan: A study in Urban Areas of Pakistan. *British Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 2(4), pp. 339-352.
- Mahmood, S. (2011) Microfinance and women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 3(3), pp. 265-274.
- Mahto, R. V. and Khanin, D. (2015) Satisfaction with Past Financial Performance, Risk Taking, and Future Performance Expectations in the Family Business. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(3), pp. 801–818.

- Malcolm, C. (2014) Reviewed Work: Comparing Institution-Building in East Asia: Power Politics, Governance and Critical Junctures by Hidetaka Yoshimatsu. *Contemporary Southeast Asia: A Journal of International and Strategic Affairs*, 36(3), pp. 483-485.
- Mandawa, B., (2016) *Enhancing the performance of women owned small and medium-sized enterprises in developing countries – A study of Zambia*. Doctoral Dissertation: University of Manchester.
- Mandipaka, F., (2014) Overview of Women Entrepreneurs in South Africa. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(9), pp. 127-130.
- Mandongwe, L. and Jaravaza, D. C. (2020) Women Entrepreneurial Intentions in Subsistence Marketplaces: The Role of Entrepreneurial Orientation and Demographic Profiles in Zimbabwe. *Cogent Business and Management*, 7(1), pp. 1818365.
- Man, T. W. and Lau, T. (2005) The context of entrepreneurship in Hong Kong: An investigation through the patterns of entrepreneurial competencies in contrasting industrial environments. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 12(4), pp. 464-481.
- Man, T. W., Lau, T. and Chan, K. (2002) The competitiveness of small and medium enterprises: A conceptualization with focus on entrepreneurial competencies. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 17(2), pp. 123-142.
- Man, T. W. Y., 2006. Exploring the behavioural patterns of entrepreneurial learning: A competency approach. *Education + Training*, 48(5), pp. 309-321.
- Man, T. W. Y. and Lau, T. (2000) Entrepreneurial competencies of SME owner/managers in the Hong Kong services sector: a qualitative analysis. *Journal of Enterprising Culture*, 8(3), pp. 235-254.
- Manolova, T. S., Carter, N. M., Manev, I. M. and Gyoshev, B. S., (2007) The differential effect of men and women entrepreneurs' human capital and networking on growth expectancies in Bulgaria. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 31(3), pp. 407-426.
- Markovi, M. R. (2007) The change of women' roles through centuries–confrontation of tradition with new challenges. *The perspective of women's entrepreneurship in the age of globalization*, pp.3-13.
- Marlow, S. and McAdam, M. (2013) Gender and Entrepreneurship: Advancing Debate and Challenging Myths: Exploring the Mystery of the Under-Performing Female Entrepreneurs.. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 19(1), pp. 114–124.
- Marlow, S. and Patton, D. (2005) All Credit to Men? Entrepreneurship, Finance, and Gender. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 27(7), pp. 717-735.

- Marques, C.S., Leal, C.T., Santos, G., Marques, C.P. and Alves, R. (2017) Why do Some Women Micro-Entrepreneurs Decide to Formalise their Businesses? *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 30(2), pp. 241-258.
- Martiana, A. (2018) Motivation and obstacles faced by women halal fashion entrepreneurs and role of the business on women's economic empowerment in Yogyakarta Indonesia. *Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews*, 6(2), pp. 106-110.
- Martin, B. C., McNally, J. J. and Kay, M. J. (2013) Examining the formation of human capital in entrepreneurship: A meta-analysis of entrepreneurship education outcomes. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28(2), pp. 211–224.
- Martini, B. S., Corvino, A., Doni, F. and Rigolini, A. (2016) Relational capital disclosure, corporate reporting and company performance: Evidence from Europe. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 17(2), pp. 186-217.
- Marvel, M. R., Davis, J. L. and Sproul, C. R. (2016) Human capital and entrepreneurship research: A critical review and future directions.. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 40(3), pp. 599-626.
- Mathew, V. (2019) Women Entrepreneurship in Gulf Region: Challenges and strategies in GCC. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management*, 10(1), pp. 94-108.
- Maziriri, E. T., Mapuranga, M., Tafadzwa, C. M. and Nzewi, O. I. (2019) Navigating on the Key Drivers for a Transition to a Green Economy: Evidence from Women Entrepreneurs in South Africa. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 7(2), pp. 1689-1703.
- Mbaruku, M. and Mutalemwa, D. (2015) Success Stories of Tanzanian Women Entrepreneurship Programs in Alleviating Poverty: Insights from WORTH Program. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 3(1), pp. 87.
- McClelland, D. C. (1961) *The Achieving Society*. New York: The Free Press.
- McCracken, M., McIvor, R., Treacy, R. and Wall, T. (2017) *Human Capital Theory: Assessing the Evidence for the Value and Importance of People to Organisational Success*, Belfast, Northern Ireland: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.
- McDaniel, C., McDaniel, C. and Gates, R. (2018) *Market Research*. 11th ed. New Jersey: Wiley.
- McDonald, S., Gan, B.C., Fraser, S.S., Oke, A. and Anderson, A.R. (2015) A Review of Research Methods in Entrepreneurship 1985-2013. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 21(3), pp. 291-315.

- McGowan, P., Redeker, C. L., Cooper, S. Y. and Greenan, K. (2012) Female Entrepreneurship and the Management of Business and Domestic Roles: Motivations, Expectations and Realities, *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 24(1-2), pp. 53-72.
- McGregor, J. and Tweed, D. (2001) Gender and Managerial Competencies: Support for Theories of Andrology? *Women In Management Review*, 16(6), pp. 279-287.
- McIntosh, J. C. and Islam, S. (2010) Beyond the Veil: The Influence of Islam on Female Entrepreneurship in a Conservative Muslim Context.. *International Management Review*, 6(1), pp. 103-109.
- McKim, C. A. (2017) The Value of Mixed Methods Research: A Mixed Methods Study. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 11(2), pp. 202-222.
- Medina, V. E. and Dua, P. (2018) The Promises and Pitfalls of Microfinance in Pakistani Women's Lives. In: M. Najafizadeh and L. Lindsey, eds. *Women of Asia: Globalization, Development, and Gender Equity*. New York: Routledge, pp. 319-332.
- Meece, J. L., Blumenfeld, P. C. and Hoyle, R. H. (1988) Students' goal orientations and cognitive engagement in classroom activities. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 80(4), pp. 514-523.
- Mehtap, S., Ozmenekse, L. and Caputo, A. (2018) I'ma Stay at Home Businesswoman: An Insight into Informal Entrepreneurship in Jordan. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 11(1), pp. 44- 65.
- Merriam, S. B. and Tisdell, E. J. (2015) *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. 4th ed. San Francisco: John Wiley and Sons.
- Michalos, A. C. (2014) *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Netherlands: Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
- Miller, D. (1983) The Correlates of Entrepreneurship in Three Types of Firms. *Management Science*, 29(7), pp. 770-791.
- Miller, D. (2011) Miller (1983) Revisited: A Reflection on EO Research and Some Suggestions for the Future. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(5), pp. 873-894.
- Minimol, M. C. (2020) Women Entrepreneurship in Coastal Kerala: Role of Self Help Groups in Developing a Sustainable Community. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 7(4), pp. 3426.
- Mitchell, R. K., Smith, B., Seawright, K. W. and Morse, E. A. (2000) Cross-Cultural Cognitions and the Venture Creation Decision. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 43(5), pp. 974-993.
- Mitchelmore, S. and Rowley, J. (2010) Entrepreneurial Competencies: A Literature Review and Development Agenda. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 16(2), pp. 92-111.

- Mitchelmore, S. and Rowley, J. (2013) Entrepreneurial Competencies of Women Entrepreneurs Pursuing Business Growth. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 20(1), pp. 125-142.
- Mitchelmore, S., Rowley, J. and Shiu, E. (2014) Competencies Associated with Growth of Women-Led SMEs. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 21(4), pp. 588-601.
- Molina-Azorin, J. F., López-Gamero, M. D., Pereira-Moliner, J. and Pertusa-Ortega, E. M. (2012) Mixed Methods Studies in Entrepreneurship Research: Applications and Contributions. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 24(5–6), pp. 425–456.
- Montalvo, M. (2021) *Why Entrepreneurs Ignore A Formal Plan, The Root Cause Of Business Failure*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesbusinesscouncil/2021/05/04/why-entrepreneurs-ignore-a-formal-plan-the-root-cause-of-business-failure/?sh=74fcda735945> [Accessed 20/6/2021].
- Morris, M. H., Kuratko, D. F., Schindehutte, M. and Spivack, A. J. (2012) Framing the Entrepreneurial Experience. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 36(1), pp. 11-40.
- Moser, A. and Korstjens, I. (2018) Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 3: Sampling, data collection and analysis. *European Journal of General Practice*, 25(1), pp. 9-18.
- Mozumdar, L., Hagelaar, G., Velde, G. v. d. and Omta, S. (2020) Determinants of the Business Performance of Women Entrepreneurs in the Developing World Context. *Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal*, 3, pp. 215-235.
- Mueller, R. O. (2012) *Basic Principles of Structural Equation Modeling: An Introduction to LISREL and EQS*. New York: Springer Science and Business Media.
- Muniady, R. A. et al. (2015) The Effect of Cognitive and Relational Social Capital on Structural Social Capital and Micro-Enterprise Performance. *Sage One*, 5(4), pp. 1-9.
- Murphy, G. B., Trailer, J. W. and Hill, R. C. (1996) Measuring performance in entrepreneurship research. *Journal of Business Research*, 36(1), pp. 15-23.
- Mutonyi, B. R., Slatten, T. and Lien, G. (2020) Empowering leadership, work group cohesiveness, individual learning orientation and individual innovative behaviour in the public sector: empirical evidence from Norway. *International Journal of Public Leadership*, 16 (2), pp. 175-197.
- Muzychenko, O. (2008) Cross-cultural entrepreneurial competence in identifying international business opportunities. *European Management Journal*, 26, pp. 366– 377.
- Naegels, V., Mori, N. and D’Espallier, B. (2018) An institutional view on access to finance by Tanzanian women owned enterprises. *Venture Capital*, 20(2), pp. 191-210.

Nag, R., Neville, F. and Dimotakis, N. (2020) CEO scanning behaviors, self-efficacy, and SME innovation and performance: An examination within a declining industry. *Journal of Small Business Management* , 58(1), pp. 164-199.

Narjis, R., Khan, S. K. and Shaikh, T. B. (2014) Gender: shaping personality, lives and health of women in Pakistan. *BMC Womens Health*, 14(1).

Nasution, H. N., Mavondo, F., Matanda, M. J. and Ndubisi, N. O. (2011) Entrepreneurship: Its Relationship with Market Orientation and Learning Orientation and as Antecedents to Innovation and Customer Value. *Industrial Marketing Management* , 40(3), pp. 336-345.

Naveed, A., 2022. *Pakistan's gender gap in mobile connectivity*. [Online] Available at: <https://tribune.com.pk/story/2344177/pakistans-gender-gap-in-mobile-connectivity> [Accessed 5/7/2022].

Naude, W. (2010) Entrepreneurship in the Field of Development Economics. In: B. Urban, ed. *Frontiers in Entrepreneurship*. New York: Springer, pp. 85-114.

Nemoto, T. and Beglar, D. (2014) *Developing Likert-scale questionnaires*. JALT2013 Conference Proceedings. Tokyo: JALT, N. Sonda and A. Krause (Eds.).

Neneh, B. N. (2017) Family Support and Performance of Women owned Enterprises: The Mediating Effect of Family-to-Work Enrichment. *The Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 26(2), pp. 196-219.

Ng, K. S. and Fu, P. P. (2018) actors driving foreign women entrepreneurship in China. *Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review*, 6(4), pp. 49-69.

Ngoasong, M. Z. and Kimbu, A. N. (2019) Why Hurry? The Slow Process of High Growth in Women-Owned Businesses in a Resource-Scarce Context. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(1), pp. 40-58.

Nielsen, K. (2014) Human capital and new venture performance: the industry choice and performance of academic entrepreneurs. *Journal of Technological Transfer*, 40(3), pp. 453-474.

Noor, S., Isa, F. M. and Nor, L. M. (2021) Women Empowerment Through Women Entrepreneurship: A Comparison Between Women Entrepreneurs and Fulltime Housewife in Pakistan. *Iranian Journal of Management Studies*, 14(2), pp. 347-363.

NWBC, 2016. *Research on Undercapitalization as a Contributor to Business Failure for Women Entrepreneurs*, Orlando, FL: Premier Quantitative Consulting, Inc.

Nybakk, E. (2012) Learning orientation, innovativeness and financial performance in traditional manufacturing firms: a higher-order structural equation model.. *International Journal of innovation management*, 16(5), pp. 1250029.

- OECD, (2017a) *OECD Regional Development Studies The Geography of Firm Dynamics: Measuring Business Demography for Regional Development*. Paris: OECD Publishing.
- OECD (2017b) Women Entrepreneurship in Canada. In: OECD Studies on SMEs and Entrepreneurship SME and Entrepreneurship Policy in Canada. Paris: OECD Publishing, pp. 197.
- Ogundari, K. and Awokuse, T. (2018) Human capital contribution to economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa: Does health status matter more than education?. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 58, pp. 131-140.
- Olamide, A. and Ogbachie, R. (2021) Social capital and business performance: a study of female-owned SMEs in the Nigerian informal sector. *Small Enterprise Research*, 28(2), pp. 190-205.
- Olu-Owolabi, F.E., Amoo, E., Samuel, O., Oyeyemi, A. and Adejumo, G. (2020) Female-Dominated Informal Labour Sector and Family (in) Stability: The Interface between Reproduction and Production. *Cogent arts and humanities*, 7(1), pp. 1-13.
- Omisakin, O. M., Nakhid, C., Littrell, R. and Verbitsky, J. (2016) Entrepreneurial Orientation among Migrants and Small and Medium Enterprises. *Journal of Business Administration Research*, 5(1), pp. 7-22.
- Onalan, M. S. and Magda, R. (2020) Intolerance to Uncertainty and Motivational Persistence among Turkish Females According to Entrepreneurial Intention. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 21(2), pp. 285-300.
- Onyusheva, I. and Meyer, N. (2020) The Features of Female Entrepreneurship Development in Kazakhstan: An Analytical Survey. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 21(1), pp. 265-282.
- Orser, B. and Dyke, L. (2009) The Influence of Gender and Occupational-Role on Entrepreneurs' and Corporate Managers' Success Criteria. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 22(3), pp. 327-353.
- Osei, C. D. and Zhuang, J. (2020) Rural Poverty Alleviation Strategies and Social Capital Link: The Mediation Role of Women Entrepreneurship and Social Innovation. *Sage Open*, 10(2).
- Owalla, B. and Ghafri, A. A. (2020) Bitten by the Entrepreneur Bug—Critiquing Discourses on Women Owner-Managers/Entrepreneurs in the Kenyan and Omani Newspapers. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 35(6), pp. 529-551.
- Ozbilgin, M. F., Beauregard, A. T., Tatli, A. and Bell, M. P. (2011) Work–Life, Diversity and Intersectionality: A Critical Review and Research Agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 13, pp. 177-198.
- Padda, I. U. H. and Hameed, A. (2018) Estimating multidimensional poverty levels in rural Pakistan: A contribution to sustainable development policies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 197, pp. 435-442.

- Pakistan Bureau of Statistics (2018) *Labour Force Survey 2017-18. Statistics Division: Government of Pakistan.* [Online] Available at: <http://www.pbs.gov.pk/content/labour-force-survey-2017-18-annual-report> [Accessed 6/5/2020].
- Pallant, J. (2016) *SPSS Survival Manual: A Step by Step Guide to Data Analysis Using SPSS Program.* 6th ed. London, UK: McGraw-Hill Education.
- Palos, R. and Stancovici, V. V. (2016) Learning in organization. *The Learning Organization*, 23(1), pp. 2-22.
- Pamela, B. (2018) *Minorities and Deviance: Coping Strategies of the Power-Poor.* New York: Lexington Books.
- Panda, S. (2018) Constraints faced by women entrepreneurs in developing countries: review and ranking. *Gender in Management*, 33(4), pp. 315-331.
- Parker, S. C. and Praag, M. V. (2006) Schooling, Capital Constraints, and Entrepreneurial Performance. *Journal of Business and Economic Statistics*, 24(4), pp. 416-431.
- Parveen, F., Jaafar, N. J. and Ainin, S. (2016) Social media's impact on organizational performance and entrepreneurial orientation in organizations. *Management Decision*, 54(9), pp. 2208-2234.
- Passaro, R., Quinto, I. and Thomas, A. (2018) The impact of higher education on entrepreneurial intention and human capital. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 19(1), pp. 135-156.
- Patterson, N. and Mavin, S. (2009) Women Entrepreneurs: Jumping the Corporate Ship and Gaining New Wings. *International Small Business Journal*, 27(2), pp. 173-192.
- Patton, M. Q. (2015) *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods: Integrating Theory and Practice.* 4 ed Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Pedersen, S. M. and Lind, K. M. (2017) *Precision Agriculture: Technology and Economic Perspectives.* Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Peng, G. (2011) *Inter-organizational information exchange, supply chain compliance and performance.* Wageningen, Netherlands: Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- Peric, I., Grladinovic, T., Kropivsek, J. and Greger, K. (2017) Relationship between Entrepreneurial Competencies and Firm Performance: A Study on Furniture Manufacturing SMEs in Croatia. In *28th International Conference on Wood Science and Technology: Implementation of Wood Science in Woodworking Sector*, pp. 59-64.
- Perreault, C., Brenner, G.A., Menzies, T.V., Filion, L.J. and Ramangalahy, C. (2007) Social capital and business performance: ethnic enterprises in Canada. *International Journal of Business and Globalisation*, 1(2), pp. 2-18.

- Pidiha, M. N. and Singh, R. (2015) Challenges and Prospects of Start-up India, Stand-up India - An Entrepreneurship Program. In: S. Gangwar, ed. *Entrepreneurship Development- Economic and Social Issues*. India: Horizon Books, pp. 237-244.
- Pines, A. M., Lerner, M. and Schwartz, D. (2010) Gender Differences in Entrepreneurship: Equality, Diversity and Inclusion in Times of Global Crisis.. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion: An International Journal*, 29(29), pp. 186-198.
- Ployhart, R. E. and Moliterno, T. P. (2011) Emergence of the Human Capital Resource: A Multilevel Model. *The Academy of Management Review*, 36(1), pp. 127-150.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J. L. and Podsakoff, N. P. (2003) Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of applied psychology*, 88(5), pp. 879.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B. and Podsakoff, N. P. (2012) Sources of method bias in social science research and recommendations on how to control it. *Annual review of psychology*, 63(1), pp. 539-569.
- Poon, J. M. L., Ainuddin, R. A. and Junit, S. H, (2006) Effects of Self-concept Traits and Entrepreneurial Orientation on Firm Performance. *International Small Business Journal*, 24(1), pp. 61-82.
- Prasad, V. K. et al. (2013) Women entrepreneurs and business venture growth: an examination of the influence of human and social capital resources in an Indian context. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 26(4), pp. 341-364.
- Pratono, A. H. and Mahmood, R. (2015) Entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance: How can micro, small and medium-sized enterprises survive environmental turbulence? *Pacific Science Review B: Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(2), pp. 85-91.
- Pulka, B. M., Ramli, A. and Mohamad, A. (2021) Entrepreneurial competencies, entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial network, government business support and SMEs performance. The moderating role of the external environment.. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 28(4), pp. 586-618.
- Purnamawati, I. M., Utama, M., Suartana, I. and Marhaeni, A. I. (2020) Women's Entrepreneurship and Local Wisdom: The Role of Sustainable Subjective Wellbeing. *Management Science Letters*, 10(16), pp. 3879-3890.
- Qureshi, J. and Herani, G. M. (2011) The Role of Small and Medium-size Enterprises (SMEs) in the Socio-economic Stability of Karachi. *Indus Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 4(2), pp. 30-44.
- Quresh, U. (2019) *Pakistan has Highest Gender Wage Gap in World*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.dawn.com/news/1471148/pakistan-has-highest-gender-wage-gap-in-world> [Accessed 1/1/2020].

- Rahman, M. S. (2017) The Advantages and Disadvantages of Using Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches and Methods in Language “Testing and Assessment” Research: A Literature Review. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 6(1), pp. 102-112.
- Rahman, S. A., Ahmad, N. H. and Taghizadeh, S. K. (2016) Entrepreneurial competencies of BoP entrepreneurs in Bangladesh to achieve business success. *Journal of General Management*, 42(1), pp. 45-63.
- Raju, P., Lonial, S. C. and Crum, M. D. (2011) Market orientation in the context of SMEs: A conceptual framework. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(12), pp. 1320-1326.
- Ramadani, V., Gerguri, S., Dana, L. P. and Tasaminova, T. (2013) Women Entrepreneurs in the Republic of Macedonia: Waiting for Directions. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 19(1), pp. 95-121.
- Ramayah, T. et al. (2018) *Consumer Dilemma to Purchase Hybrid Car*. Malaysia: Pearson.
- Randa, I. O. (2020) Intensive Market and Enterprise Growth Through Public-Private Partnership for Local. In: N. Baporikar, ed. *Handbook of Research on Entrepreneurship Development and Opportunities in Circular Economy*. India: IGI Global, pp. 459.
- Rashid, S. and Ratten, V. (2020) A Systematic Literature Review on Women Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies While Reflecting Specifically on SAARC Countries. In: V. Ratten, ed. *Entrepreneurship and Organizational Change: Contribution to management science*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Rauch, A. and Frese, M. (2000) Psychological approaches to entrepreneurial success: A general model and an overview of findings. In: C. L. Cooper and I. T. Robertson, eds. *International Review of Industrial and Organizational Psychology*. Chichester: Wiley, pp. 101-142.
- Rauch, A. and Frese, M. (2007) Let's Put the Person Back into Entrepreneurship Research: A Meta-Analysis on the Relationship Between Business Owners' Personality Traits, Business Creation, and Success. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 16(4), pp. 353-385.
- Rauch, A., Wiklund, J., Lumpkin, G. T. and Frese, M. (2009) Entrepreneurial Orientation and Business Performance: An Assessment of past Research and Suggestions for the Future. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 33(3), pp. 761-787.
- Raza, S., Minai, M.S., Zain, A.Y.M., Tariq, T.A. and Khuwaja, F.M. (2018) Dissection of Small Businesses in Pakistan: Issues and Directions. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 22(4), pp. 1-13.
- Real, J. C., Roldan, J. L. and Leal, A. (2014) From Entrepreneurial Orientation and Learning Orientation to Business Performance: Analysing the Mediating Role of Organisational Learning and the Moderating Effects of Organisational Size. *British Journal of Management*, 25(2), pp. 186-208.

- Redmond, J., Walker, E. A. and Hutchinson, J. (2017) Self-employment: is it a long-term financial strategy for women?. *Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*, 36(4), pp. 362-375.
- Rehman, S. and Roomi, M. A. (2012) Gender and work-life balance: a phenomenological study of women entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 19(2), pp. 209-228.
- Reijonen, H. et al. (2015) The impact of entrepreneurial orientation on B2B branding and business growth in emerging markets. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 51, pp. 35-46.
- Reinartz, W., Haenlein, M. and Henseler, J. (2009) An empirical comparison of the efficacy of covariance-based and variance-based SEM. *International Journal of research in Marketing*, 26(4), pp. 332-344.
- Rekarti, E., Bahari, Z., Zahari, N.M., Doktoralina, C.M. and Ilias, N.A. (2019) The Sustainability of Muslim Women Entrepreneurs: A Case Study in Malaysia. *International Journal of Financial Research*, 10(5), pp. 430-439.
- Renko, M., Carsrud, A. and Brännback, M. (2009) The effect of a market orientation, entrepreneurial orientation, and technological capability on innovativeness: A study of young biotechnology ventures in the United States and in Scandinavia. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 47(3), pp. 331-369.
- Reuber, A. R. and Fischer, E. (1999) Understanding the consequences of founders' experience. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 37(2), pp. 30-45.
- Reynold, P. D. (1992) Sociology and Entrepreneurship: Concepts and Contributions. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 16(2), pp. 47-70.
- Reza, M., Manurung, D., Kolmakov, V. and Alshebami, A. (2020) Impact of Education and Training on Performance of Women Entrepreneurs in Indonesia: Moderating Effect of Personal Characteristics. *Management Science Letters*, 10(16), pp. 3923-3930.
- Rhee, J., Park, T. and Lee, D. H. (2010) Drivers of innovativeness and performance for innovative SMEs in South Korea: mediation of learning orientation. *Technovation*, 30(1), pp. 65-75.
- Riaz, S. (2014) The Educational System in Pakistan and the Place of Islamic Schooling. In: S. Riaz, ed. *New Islamic Schools: Tradition, Modernity, and Class in Urban Pakistan*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 49-86.
- Ritchie, J., Lewis, J., Nicholls, C. M. and Ormston, R. (2014) *Qualitative Research Practice: A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Robeyns, I. (2006) Three models of education rights, capabilities and human capital. *Theory and Research in Education*, 4(1), pp. 69-84.
- Robichaud, Y., Cachon, J.-C. and McGraw, E. (2015) Why Are Female-Owned Businesses Smaller? An Empirical Study in Canada and the United States. *Journal of Management Policy and Practice*, 16(1), pp. 62-75.

- Robinson, P. B., Stimpson, D. V., Huefner, J. C. and Hunt, H. K. (1991) An Attitude Approach to the Prediction of Entrepreneurship. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 15(4), pp. 13-32.
- Rodriguez-Gutierrez, M. J., Moreno, P. and Tejada, P. (2015) Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of SMEs in the services industry. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 28(2), pp. 194-212.
- Rodriguez-Gutierrez, P., Fuentes Fuentes, M. d. M. and Ariza, L.-R. (2014) Strategic Capabilities and Performance in Women Owned Businesses in Mexico. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 52(3), pp. 541–554.
- Roessingh, C. and Nuijten, M. (2012) Female self-employment among the Kleine Gemeinde in the Mennonite settlement of Blue Creek, Northern Belize. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 15(4), pp. 397-410.
- Roomi, M. A. (2011) Entrepreneurial capital, social values and Islamic traditions: Exploring the growth of women owned enterprises in Pakistan. *International Small Business Journal*, 31(2), pp. 175–191.
- Roomi, M. A. (2013) Entrepreneurial Capital, Social Values and Islamic Traditions: Exploring the Growth of Women Owned Enterprises in Pakistan. *International Small Business Journal*, 31(2), pp. 175-191.
- Roomi, M. A. and Harrison, P. (2010) Behind the veil: women-only entrepreneurship training in Pakistan. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 2(2), pp. 150-172.
- Roomi, M. A. and Harrison, P. (2011) Entrepreneurial Leadership: what is it and how should it be taught?. *International Review of Entrepreneurship*, 9(3), pp. 1-48.
- Roomi, M. A., Harrison, P. and Beaumont-Kerridge, J. (2009) Women owned small and medium enterprises in England: analysis of factors influencing the growth process. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 16(2), pp. 270-288.
- Roomi, M. A. and Parrott, G. (2008) Barriers to Development and Progression of Women Entrepreneurs in Pakistan. *The Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 17(1), pp. 59–72.
- Roomi, M. A., Rehman, S. and Henry, C. (2018) Exploring the normative context for women’s entrepreneurship in Pakistan: a critical analysis. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 10(2), pp. 158-180.
- Rosa, J. M. and Sylla, D. (2018) A comparison of the performance of majority female-owned and majority male-owned small and medium-sized enterprises. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 35(3), pp. 282-302.
- Rotondo, D. M., Carlson, D. S. and Kincaid, J. F. (2003) Coping with multiple dimensions of work-family conflict. *Personal Review*, 32(3), pp. 275–296.

- Rowe, C. (1995) Clarifying the use of competence and competency models in recruitment, assessment and staff development. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 27(11), pp. 12-17.
- Rowley, C. and Lee, J. S. K. (2014) Why Women Say No to Corporate Boards and What Can Be Done: “Ornamental Directors” in Asia. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, 24(2), pp. 205–207.
- Roxas, H. B. and Chadee, D. (2011) A Resource-Based View of small export firms' social capital in a Southeast Asian Country. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 16(2), pp. 1-28.
- Ruiz-Arroyo, M., Fuentes-Fuentes, M. d. M., Bojica, A. M. and Rodríguez-Ariza, L. (2012) Innovativeness and Performance in Women Owned Small Firms: The Role of Knowledge Acquisition. *Journal of Small Business and Entrepreneurship*, 25(3), pp. 307-326.
- Runyan, R., Droge, C. and Swinney, J. (2008) Entrepreneurial orientation versus Small Business Orientation: What Are Their Relationships to Firm Performance?. *Journal of small business management*, 46(4), pp. 567-588.
- Ryan, J. C., Tipu, S. A. and Zeffane, R. M. (2011) Need for achievement and entrepreneurial potential: a study of young adults in the UAE. *Education, Business and Society: Contemporary Middle Eastern Issues*, 4(3), pp. 153-166.
- Saddique, H. (2018) *Workplace gender discrimination remains rife, survey finds*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2018/sep/13/workplace-gender-discrimination-remains-rife-survey-finds> [Accessed 14/8/2019].
- Saeed, S., Yousafzai, S. Y., Yani-De-Soriano, M. and Muffatto, M. (2015) The Role of Perceived University Support in the Formation of Students' Entrepreneurial Intention. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(4), pp. 1127-1145.
- Saeed, J. (2012) The rising world-status of China within the Global Economy in the 21st Century: A Cultural Knowledge based Strategy for Conducting Successful Businesses in China. In: J. Saeed, ed. *China and the Global Economy in the 21st Century*. London: Routledge, pp. 76-89.
- Safavian, M. (2012) . *Are Pakistan's Women Entrepreneurs Being Served by the Microfinance Sector?*, Washington, DC: World Bank.
- Safavian, M. and Haq, A. (2013) *Are Pakistan's Women Entrepreneurs Being Served by the Microfinance Sector? Directions in Development--Finance*. Washington, D.C.: The World Bank.
- Saffu, K., 2003. The role and impact of culture on South Pacific island entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 9(2), pp. 55-73.

- Sajjad, W., Sajjad, A. and Asif, M. (2020) Impact of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Access to Finance and Strategic Flexibility on SMEs Performance. *Journal of Management and Research*, 7(1), pp. 1-23.
- Salkind, N. J. (2010) *Encyclopedia of Research Design*. SAGE Publications: Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Sally, N., Newman, C. and Lancaster, K. (2019) Qualitative Interviewing. In: *Handbook of Research Methods in Health Social Sciences*. Singapore: Springer, pp. 391–410.
- Sampathirao, P. (2016) Integrating Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods in Health Communication Research. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 3(3), pp. 177-183.
- Sanchez, J. (2012) The influence of entrepreneurial competencies on small firm performance. *Revista Latinoamericana de Psicología*, 44(2), pp. 165-177.
- Sandhu, N., Hussain, J. and Matlay, H. (2012) Barriers to finance experienced by female owner/managers of marginal farms in India. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 19(4), pp. 640-655.
- Santarelli, E. and Tran, H. T. (2013) The Interplay of Human and Social Capital in Shaping Entrepreneurial Performance: the Case of Vietnam. *Small Business Economics*, 40, pp. 435–458.
- Santos, G., Marques, C. S. and Ferreira, J. J. (2018) A Look Back Over the Past 40 Years of Female Entrepreneurship: Mapping Knowledge Networks. *Scientometrics*, Volume 115, pp. 953–987.
- Santos, S. C. and Liguori, E. W. (2019) Entrepreneurial Self-Efficacy and Intentions: Outcome Expectations as Mediator and Subjective Norms as Moderator. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 26(3), pp. 400-415.
- Sanzo, M. J., Santos, M. L., Garcia, N. and Trespalacios, J. A. (2011) Trust as a moderator of the relationship between organizational learning and marketing capabilities: Evidence from Spanish SMEs. *International Small Business Journal*, 30(6), pp. 700–726.
- Sapienza, H. J. and Grimm, C. M. (1997) Founder characteristics, start-up processes, and strategy/structure variables as predictors of short line railroad performance. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 22(1), pp. 5-24.
- Sarstedt, M. et al. (2019) How to Specify, Estimate, and Validate Higher-Order Constructs in PLS-SEM. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 27(3), pp. 197-211.
- Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Henseler, J. and Hair, J. F. (2014) On the Emancipation of PLS-SEM: A Commentary on Rigdon (2012). *Long Range Planning*, 47(3), pp. 154-160.
- Saunders, M. N., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2019) *Understanding research philosophy and approaches to theory development*. 8 ed. London: Pearson.

- Saunders, M. N., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2023) *Research Methods for business Students*. 9 ed. London: Pearson Education Limited.
- Savitha, C. M., Siddaramaiah, B. S. and Shankara, M. H. (2014) Factors contributing to entrepreneurial behavior of rural and urban women. *International Journal of Farm Science*, 5(2), pp. 217–223.
- Schmitt, A., Rosing, K., Zhang, S. X. and Leatherbee, M. (2018) A dynamic model of entrepreneurial uncertainty and business opportunity identification: Exploration as a mediator and entrepreneurial self-efficacy as a moderator. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 40(6), pp. 835-859.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1934) *The Theory of Economic Development*. London : Oxford University Press.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1942) *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy*. New York: Harper and Brothers.
- Seet, P.S., Lindsay, N. and Kropp, F. (2021) Understanding early-stage firm performance: the explanatory role of individual and firm level factors. *International Journal of Manpower*, 42(2), pp. 260-285.
- Segal, G., Borgia, D. and Schoenfeld, J. (2010) Founder human capital and small firm performance: an empirical study of founder-managed natural food stores. *Journal of Management and Marketing Research*, 4, pp. 71-83.
- Selamat, N. H. and Endut, N. (2020) Bargaining with Patriarchy' and Entrepreneurship: Narratives of Malay Muslim Women Entrepreneurs in Malaysia. *Kajian Malaysia: Journal of Malaysian Studies*, 38, pp.11-31
- Sen, A. (2017) More Than 100 Million Women Are Missing. In: N. Naffine, ed. *Gender and Rights*. London: Routledge, pp. 81-84.
- Sena, V., Scott , J. and Roper, S. (2012) Gender, borrowing patterns and self-employment: some evidence for England. *Small Business Economics*, 38(4), pp. 467–480.
- Sen, D. (2018) Entrepreneurs or Organic Tea Farmers? Entrepreneurialism, Resilience and Alternative Agriculture in Darjeeling, India. *Journal of Political Ecology*, 25(1), pp. 732-747.
- Setini, M., Yasa, N.N.K., Supartha, I.W., Ketut Giantari, I.G.A., Rajiani, I. (2020) The Passway of Women Entrepreneurship: Starting from Social Capital with Open Innovation, Through to Knowledge Sharing and Innovative Performance. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(2), pp. 25.
- Shabbir, A. and Gregorio, S. D. (1996) An examination of the relationship between women's personal goals and structural factors influencing their decision to start a business: the case of Pakistan.. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 11(1), pp. 507-529.
- Shakeel, M., Yaokuang, L. and Gohar, A. (2020) Identifying the Entrepreneurial Success Factors and the Performance of Women Owned Businesses in Pakistan: The Moderating Role of National Culture. *SAGE Open*, 10(2), pp. 1-17.

- Shane, S. and Venkataraman, S. (2000) The Promise of Entrepreneurship as a Field of Research. *The Academy of Management Review*, 25(1), pp. 217-226.
- Shapiro, I. and Wendt, A. (2005) The difference that realism makes: Social science and the politics of consent.. In: I. Shapiro, ed. *The flight from reality in the human sciences*. New Jersey: Princenton University Press, pp. 19-50.
- Sheikh, S. (2019) *Value Creation Through Female Entrepreneurship in Pakistan*, Doctoral Dissertation: Cardiff University
- Sheng, S., Zhou, K. Z. and Li, J. J. (2011) The Effects of Business and Political Ties on Firm Performance: Evidence from China. *Journal of Marketing*, 75(1), pp. 1-15.
- Shmueli, G., Ray, S., Estrada, J. M. V. and Chatla, S. B. (2016) The elephant in the room: Predictive performance of PLS models. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(10), pp. 4552-4564.
- Shmueli, G. et al. (2019) Predictive model assessment in PLS-SEM: guidelines for using PLSpredict. *European Journal of Marketing*, 53(11), pp. 2322-2347.
- Shoma, C. D. (2019) Financing female entrepreneurs in cottage, micro, small, and medium enterprises: Evidence from the financial sector in Bangladesh 2010–2018. *Asia and the Pacific Policy Studies*, 6(3), pp. 397-416.
- Shoubaki, A. E., Laguir, I. and Besten, M. d. (2019) Human capital and SME growth: the mediating role of reasons to start a business. *Small Business Economics*, 54(4), pp. 1107–1121.
- Sihotang, J., Puspokusumo, R. A. A. W., Sun, Y. and Munandar, D. (2020) Core Competencies of Women Entrepreneur in Building Superior Online Business Performance in Indonesia. *Management Science Letters*, 10(7), pp. 1607-1612.
- Silverstein, M. (2019) *Innate vs. Acquired Qualities*. [Online] Available at: <https://blog.criteriacorp.com/innate-vs-acquired-qualities/> [Accessed 22/12/2020].
- Simao, L. and Franco, M. (2018) External knowledge sources as antecedents of organizational innovation in firm workplaces: a knowledge-based perspective. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 22(2), pp. 237-256.
- Singh, R. K., Garg, S. K. and Deshmukh, S. G. (2008) Strategy Development by SMEs for Competitiveness: a Review. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 15(5), pp. 525-547.
- Simpeh, K. N. (2011) Entrepreneurship Theories and Empirical Research: A Summary Review of the Literature. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(6).
- Simpson, M., Padmore, J. and Newman, N. (2012) Towards a New Model of Success and Performance in SMEs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 18(3), pp. 264-285.

- Sinkula, J. M., Baker, W. E. and Noordewier, T. (1997) A Framework for Market-Based Organizational Learning: Linking Values, Knowledge, and Behavior. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 25(4), pp. 305–318.
- Siringi, E. M. (2011) Women's Small and Medium Enterprises for Poverty Alleviation in Sub-Saharan Africa: Lessons from Kenya. *Management Research Review*, 34(2), pp. 186-206.
- Slater, S. F. and Narver, J. C. (1995) Market orientation and the learning organization. *Journal of Marketing*, 59(3), pp. 63–74.
- Slotte-Kock, S. and Coviello, N. E. (2010) Entrepreneurship research on network processes: a review and ways forward. *Entrepreneurship: Theory and Practice*, 34(1), pp. 31-57.
- Sobel, R. S. (2008) Testing Baumol: Institutional quality and the productivity of entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 23(6), pp. 641–655.
- Soininen, J., Martikainen, M., Puumalainen, K. and Kylaheiko, K., (2012) Entrepreneurial orientation: Growth and profitability of Finnish small- and medium-sized enterprises. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 140(2), pp. 614-621.
- Soininen, J.S., Puumalainen, K., Sjögrén, H., Syrjä, P. and Durst, S. (2013) Entrepreneurial orientation in small firms – values-attitudes-behavior approach. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research*, 19(6), pp. 611-632.
- Solanki, N. (2019) Women Entrepreneurship: a Paradigm Shift. *Humanities and Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(1), pp. 501-504.
- Solesvik, M. Z. (2012) *Entrepreneurial Competencies in Emerging Economy Context*. Helsinki, Finland 23-25 May. 2012., 17th Nordic Conference on Small Business Research.
- Soriano, D. R. and Castrogiovanni, G. J. (2012) The impact of education, experience and inner circle advisors on SME performance: Insights from a study of public development centers.. *Small Business Economics*, 38(3), pp. 333–349.
- Spicer, D. and Sadler-Smith (2006) Organizational Learning in Smaller Manufacturing Firms. *International Small Business Journal*, 24(2), pp. 133-158.
- Sreejesh, S., Mohapatra, S. and Anusree, M. R. (2014) *Business Research Design: Exploratory, Descriptive and Causal Designs*. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing.
- Stam, W. and Elfring, T. (2008) Entrepreneurial Orientation and New Venture Performance: The Moderating Role of Intra- And Extraindustry Social Capital. *Academy of Management Journal*, 51(1), pp. 97–111.
- Starc, M. (2017) Ethics and the Ethical Attitude. *Jung journal*, 11(1), pp. 47-52.

- Steffens, P., Davidsson, P. and Fitzsimmons, J. (2009) Performance configurations over time: implications for growth–and profit–oriented strategies. *Entrepreneurship theory and practice*, 33(1), pp. 125-148.
- Stockemer, D. (2019) *Quantitative Methods for the Social Sciences*. Cham: Springer.
- Subagyo, Kumar, V. and Ernestivita, G. (2020) Entrepreneurial parameters and performance of MSMEs in East Java province of Indonesia. *International Journal of Business Innovation and Research*, 23(2), pp. 267-282.
- Suleymenova, K. and Syssoyeva-Masson, I. (2017) *Improving gender outcomes for regional trade programmes*, K4D Helpdesk Report. Brighton, UK: Institute of Development Studies..
- Sullivan, D. M. and Marvel, M. R. (2011) Knowledge Acquisition, Network Reliance, and Early-Stage Technology Venture Outcomes. *Journal of Management Studies*, 48(6), pp. 1169-1193.
- Sullivan, G. M. and Feinn, R. (2012) Using Effect Size-or Why the P Value Is Not Enough.. *Journal of graduate medical education*, 4(3), pp. 279-282.
- Su, Z., Xie, E. and Li, Y. (2011) Entrepreneurial Orientation and Firm Performance in New Ventures and Established Firms. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 49(4), pp. 558-577.
- Syed, I. (2018) *Shall I Feed My Daughter, or Educate Her?*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2018/11/12/shall-i-feed-my-daughter-or-educate-her/barriers-girls-education-pakistan> [Accessed 23/1/2020].
- Syed, J. (2012) Women and small business entrepreneurship in Pakistan. In: S. Fielden and M. Davidson, eds. *International Research Handbook on Successful Women Entrepreneurs*.. New York: Edward Elgar, pp. 117-131.
- Tabachnick, B. G. and Fidell, L. S. (2016) *Using Multivariate Statistics*. 6th ed. Needham Height, MA: Allyn and Bacon.
- Tajeddini, K. (2011) Customer Orientation, Learning Orientation, and New Service Development: An Empirical Investigation of the Swiss Hotel Industry. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Research*, 35(4), pp. 437-468.
- Tajeddini, K. and Mueller, S. L. (2012) Corporate Entrepreneurship in Switzerland: Evidence from a Case Study of Swiss Watch Manufacturers. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 8(3), pp. 355–372.
- Tambunan, T. (2009) Women entrepreneurship in Asian developing countries: Their development and main constraints. *Journal of development and Agricultural Economics*, 1(2), pp. 27-040.
- Tang, J., Kacmar, K.M.M. and Busenitz, L. (2012) Entrepreneurial Alertness in the Pursuit of New Opportunities. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 27(1), pp. 77-94.

- Tang, J., Tang, Z., Marino, L.D., Zhang, Y. and Li, Q. (2008) Exploring an Inverted U-Shape Relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation and Performance in Chinese Ventures. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 32(1), pp. 219-239.
- Tariq, J. (2016) *Exploring Entrepreneurial Motivations and Barriers: a study of female business owners in Pakistan*, : Doctoral Dissertation, University of Hull.
- Tariq, S., Jan, F. A. and Ahmad , M. S. (2016b). Green employee empowerment: a systematic literature review on state-of-art in green human resource management. *Quality and Quantity*, 50, pp. 237–269.
- Tehseen, S. and Anderson, A. R. (2020) Cultures and entrepreneurial competencies; ethnic propensities and performance in Malaysia. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 12(5), pp. 643-666.
- Tehseen, S., Qureshi, Z. H., Johara, F. and Ramayah, T. (2020) Assessing dimensions of entrepreneurial competencies: A type ii (reflective-formative) measurement approach using pls-sem. *Journal of Sustainability Science and Management*, 15(2), pp. 108-145.
- Tehseen, S. and Ramayah , T. (2015) Entrepreneurial competencies and SMEs business success: The contingent role of external integration. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1), pp. 50-61.
- Teoh, W. M. Y. and Chong, S. C. (2007) Theorising a Framework of Factors Influencing Performance of Women Entrepreneurs in Malaysia. *J. Asia Entrepreneurship and Sustainability*, 3(2), pp. 42-59.
- Teo, T. S. H., Srivastava, S. C. and Jiang, L. (2008) Trust and Electronic Government Success: An Empirical Study. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 25(3), pp. 99-132.
- Terjese, S. and Ratten, V. (2007) La Vita Imprenditoriale female and male entrepreneurs in Italy. In: M. R. Markovi, ed. *The Perspective of Women's Entrepreneurship in the Age of Globalization*. Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publishing, INC., pp. 49.
- Thapa, S. K. and Xheneti, M. (2018) Formalising Women Entrepreneurs in Kathmandu, Nepal: Pathway Towards Empowerment? *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 38(7-8), pp.526-541.
- Thapa, K., Xheneti, M. and Madden, A. (2020) To Formalise or not to Formalise: Women Entrepreneurs' Sensemaking of Business Registration in the Context of Nepal. *Journal of Business and Ethics*, 173(4), pp. 687-708.
- The News, (2017). *World Bank says Pakistan ranks lowest among countries with women entrepreneurs*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/243346-World-Bank-says-Pakistan-ranks-lowest-among-countries-with-women-entrepreneurs> [Accessed 5/14 /2020].

- Thomas, N. and Thomas, A. V. (2017) Regression Modelling for Prediction of Construction Cost and Duration. In *Applied Mechanics and Materials*, (857, pp. 195-199). Trans Tech Publications Ltd.
- Thornton, P. H., Ribeiro-Soriano, D. and Urbano, D. (2011) Socio-cultural factors and entrepreneurial activity: An overview. *International Small Business Journal*, 29(2), pp. 105-118.
- Tidd, J., (1997) Complexity, Networks and learning: Integrative themes for research on innovation management. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 1(1), pp. 1–21.
- Timans, R., Wouters, P. and Heilbron, J. (2019) Mixed Methods Research: what it is and what it could be. *Theory and Society*, Volume 48, p. 193–216.
- Tittel, A. and Terzidis, O. (2020) Entrepreneurial competences revised: developing a consolidated and categorized list of entrepreneurial competences. *Entrepreneurship Education*, 3(1), pp. 1-35.
- Tlaiss, H. A. (2013) Entrepreneurial Motivations of Women: Evidence from the United Arab Emirates. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*, 33(5), pp. 562-581.
- Tlaiss, H. A. and Kauser, S. (2019) Entrepreneurial Leadership, Patriarchy, Gender, and Identity in the Arab World: Lebanon in Focus. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 57(2), pp. 517-537.
- Tlaiss, H. and Kauser, S. (2011) The Impact of Gender, Family, and Work on the Career Advancement of Lebanese Women Managers. *Gender in Management: An International Journal*, 26(1), pp. 8-36.
- Townsend, D. M., Busenitz, L. W. and Arthurs, J. D. (2010) To Start or Not to Start: Outcome and Ability Expectations in the Decision to Start a New Venture. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 25(2), pp. 192–202.
- Trequattrini, R., Manfredi, S., Lardo, A. and Cuzzo, B. (2019) Social Media as a New Opportunity for Female Entrepreneurs: An Analysis of the Fashion Industry. In: P. Paoloni and R. Lombardi, eds. *Advances in Gender and Cultural Research in Business and Economics*. Cham: Springer, pp. 287-298.
- Turk, S., Zapkau, F. B. and Schwens, C. (2020) Prior entrepreneurial exposure and the emergence of entrepreneurial passion: The moderating role of learning orientation. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 58(2), pp. 225-258.
- Tzelepis, D. and Skuras, D., (2006). Strategic performance measurement and the use of capital subsidies. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 55(7), pp. 527-538.
- Ufuk, H. and Ozgen, O., (2001) The profile of women entrepreneurs: a sample from Turkey. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 25(4), pp. 299-308.

- Umar, A., Cob, C. M. S. C., Omar, C. M. Z. C. and Hamzah, M. S. G. (2019) Determinants of Entrepreneurial Competencies Development in Small and Medium Enterprises. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 14(1), pp. 147-158
- Ummah, M. A. C. S., Choy, C. S. and Khatibi, A. (2019) Impact of Social Capital (SC) on Business Performance (BP) of Muslim Women Entrepreneurs (MWEs) in the Eastern Province of Sri Lanka (EPSL). *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(4), pp. 7541-7548.
- UNDP. (2015) *Human Development Report 2015: Beyond Scarcity: Power, Poverty and the Global Water Crisis*, New York: UNDP.
- Unger, J. M., Rauch, A., Frese, M. and Rosenbusch, N. (2011) Human capital and entrepreneurial success: A meta-analytical review. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 26(3), pp. 341–358.
- United Nations. (2010) *Thematic Paper on MDG3: Promote Gender Equality and Empower Women*,: United Nations Development Group.
- Uy, M. A., Sun, S. and Foo, M. D. (2017) Affect spin, entrepreneurs' well-being, and venture goal progress: The moderating role of goal orientation. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 32(4), pp. 443-460.
- Vandewalle, D. (1997) Development and Validation of a Work Domain Goal Orientation Instrument. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 57(6), pp. 995–1015.
- Vasan, M. (2020) Moderating Effect of Demographic and Business Characteristics on Performance of Women Owned Small Enterprises: Empirical Evidence from India. *Serbian Journal of Management*, 15(2), pp. 319-333.
- Verheul, I., Carree, . M. and Thurik , R. (2009) Allocation and productivity of time in new ventures of female and male entrepreneurs. *Small Business Economics*, 33, pp. 273–291.
- Verheul, I., Stel , A. V. and Thurik, R. (2006) Explaining female and male entrepreneurship at the country level. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 18(2), pp. 151-183.
- Vershinina, N., Rodgers, P., Tarba, S., Khan, Z. and Stokes, P. (2020) Gaining Legitimacy through Proactive Stakeholder Management: The Experiences of High-Tech Women Entrepreneurs in Russia. *Journal of Business Research*, 119, pp. 111-121.
- Vij, S. and Bedi, H. S. (2016) Are Subjective Business Performance Measures Justified? *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 65(5), pp. 603-621.
- Vinesh, L. (2014) Role of Women Entrepreneurs in India. *Global Journal of Finance and Management*, 6(5), pp. 473-480.

- Viswanathan, M. and Kayande, U. (2012) Commentary on “Common Method Bias in Marketing: Causes, Mechanisms, and Procedural Remedies. *Journal of Retailing*, 88(4), pp. 556-562.
- Voorhees, C. M., Brady, M. K., Calantone, R. and Ramirez, E. (2016) Discriminant validity testing in marketing: an analysis, causes for concern, and proposed remedies. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 44(1), pp. 119–134.
- Vossenbergh, S. (2013) *Women Entrepreneurship Promotion in Developing Countries: What explains the gender gap in entrepreneurship and how to close it?*, Netherlands: Maastricht School of Management.
- Vosta, L. N. and Jalilvand, M. R. (2014) Examining the influence of social capital on rural women entrepreneurship : An empirical study in Iran. *World Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Sustainable Development*, 10(3), pp. 209-227.
- Wach, K., Głodowska, A. and Maciejewski, M. (2018) Entrepreneurial Orientation, Knowledge Utilization and Internationalization of Firms. *Sustainability*, 10(12), pp. 1-23.
- Wales, W. J. (2016) Entrepreneurial orientation: A review and synthesis of promising research direction. *International Small Business Journal*, 34(1), pp. 3-15.
- Wales, W. J., Gupta, V. K. and Mousa, F.-T. (2011) Empirical Research on entrepreneurial orientation: An assessment and suggestion for future research. *International Small Business Journal*, 31(4), pp. 357-383.
- Wales, W., Monsen, E. and McKelvie, A. (2011b). The organizational pervasiveness of entrepreneurial orientation. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(5), pp. 895-923.
- Walker, H., Chicksand, D., Radnor, Z. and Watson, G. (2015) Theoretical perspectives in operations management: an analysis of the literature. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 58(8), pp. 1182-1206.
- Wang, C. (2008) Entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, and firm performance. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 32(4), pp. 635-657.
- Wang, H. K. and Yen, Y.-F. (2012) An empirical exploration of corporate entrepreneurial orientation and performance in Taiwanese SMEs: a perspective of multidimensional construct. *Total Quality Management*, 23(9), pp. 1035–1044.
- Warnecke, T., Hernandez, L. and Nunn, N. (2012) Female Entrepreneurship in China: Opportunity-or Necessity-Based? *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 15(4), pp. 411-434.
- Wasim, M. (2021) *The Relationships Between Organisational Orientations, Financial Resources and Scottish SMEs Performance*. Doctoral dissertation: University of the West of Scotland.

- Watson, J. (2003) Failure Rates for Female-Controlled Businesses: Are They Any Different? *Journal of Small Business Management*, 41(3), pp. 262-277.
- Watson, J. (2020) Exposing/Correcting SME Underperformance Myths. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 12(1), pp. 77-88.
- Waugh, R. (2019) *SME success is dependent on location, location, location*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/business/challenges/sme-success-location/> [Accessed 7/6/2020].
- Weinzimmer, L. G., Nystrom, P. C. and Freeman, S. J. (1998). Measuring Organizational Growth: Issues, Consequences and Guidelines. *Journal of Management*, 24(2), pp. 235-262.
- Weiss, A. N. (2012). *Moving forward with legal empowerment of women in Pakistan*. *Special Report*, United States: Institution of Peace.
- Wellalage, N. H. and Locke, S. (2016) Informality and credit constraints: evidence from Sub-Saharan African MSEs. *Applied Economics*, 48(29), pp. 2756–2770.
- Wellalage, N. and Locke, S. (2017) Access to credit by SMEs in South Asia: do women entrepreneurs face discrimination. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 41, pp. 336-346.
- Welsh, D. H. B., Kaciak, E. and Shamah, R. (2018a) Determinants of Women Entrepreneurs' Firm Performance in a Hostile Environment. *Journal of Business Research*, 88, pp. 481-491.
- Welsh, D. H., Kaciak, E., Memili, E. and Minialai, C. (2018b) Business-Family Interface and the Performance of Women Entrepreneurs: The Moderating Effect of Economic Development. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*, 13(2), pp. 330-349.
- Welsh, D. H., Kaciak, E., Memili, E. and Zhou, Q. (2017) Work-Family Balance and Marketing Capabilities as Determinants of Chinese Women Entrepreneurs' Firm Performance. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 30(3), pp. 174-191.
- Welsh, D. H., Memili, E. and Kaciak, E. (2016) An Empirical Analysis of the Impact of Family Moral Support on Turkish Women Entrepreneurs. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 1(1), pp. 3-12.
- Welter, F. (2011) Contextualizing Entrepreneurship—Conceptual Challenges and Ways Forward. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 35(1), pp.165-184.
- Welter, F., Baker, T., Audretsch, D. B. and Gartner, W. B. (2017) Everyday entrepreneurship—a call for entrepreneurship research to embrace entrepreneurial diversity. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 41(3), pp. 311-321.

- West, G. P. and Noel, T. W. (2009) Toward a deeper understanding of the roles of personal and business networks and market knowledge in SMEs' international performance. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 47(1), pp. 1–22.
- Wetzels, M., Odekerken-Schröder, G. and Van Oppen, C. (2009) Using PLS path modeling for assessing hierarchical construct models: Guidelines and empirical illustration. *MIS quarterly*, 33(1), pp. 177-195.
- WGEA. (2019). *Gender Segregation in Australia's workforce*, Australia: workplace Gender Equity Agency.
- Wiklund, J. and Shepherd, D. (2005) Entrepreneurial Orientation and Small Business Performance: a Configurational Approach. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 20(1), pp. 71-91.
- Wilson, J. (2014) *Essentials of Business Research: A Guide to Doing your Research Project*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publication.
- Wise, J., 2022. *Women in Business Statistics 2022: Female Owned Businesses*. [Online] Available at: <https://earthweb.com/women-in-business-statistics/> [Accessed 3/9/2022].
- Witbooi, M. and Ukpere, W. (2011) Indigenous female entrepreneurship: Analytical Study on Access to Finance for Women Entrepreneurs in South Africa. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(14), pp. 5646-5657.
- World Bank Group. (2020) *Shining the Spotlight : Gender-Lens Investments Enable Women Entrepreneurs to Thrive in Pakistan*, Washington, DC: World Bank Group.
- World Bank. (2017). *Pakistan Development Update, November 2017: Managing Risks for Sustained Growth*, Islamabad: World Bank.
- World Bank, (2022) *Labor Force, Wemale (% of Total Labor Force)*. [Online] Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SL.TLF.TOTL.FE.ZS> [Accessed 28/12/2019].
- Wunderlich, P. (2013) *Green Information Systems in the Residential Sector*. Berlin: Springer.
- Xheneti, M., Karki, T. S. and Madden, A. (2019a) Negotiating Business and Family Demands within a Patriarchal Society—the Case of Women Entrepreneurs in the Nepalese Context. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 31(3-4), pp. 259-278.
- Xheneti, M., Madden, A. and Karki, S. T. (2019b) Value of Formalisation for Women Entrepreneurs in Developing Contexts: A Review and Research Agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 21(1), pp. 3-23.
- Xiong, L., Ukanwa, I. and Anderson, A. R. (2018) Institutional Influence and the Role of Family in Poor Women's Micropreneurship. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour and Research*, 26(1), pp. 122-140.

- Xu, L. and Zia, B. (2016) Financial literacy around the world: an overview of the evidence with practical suggestions for the way forward. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*, (6107).
- Yen, Y. S., Chen, M. C. and Su, C.H. (2020) Social capital affects job performance through social media. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 120(5), pp. 903-922.
- Yuan, Y., Feng, B., Lai, F. and Collins, B. J. (2018) The role of trust, commitment, and learning orientation on logistic service effectiveness. *Journal of Business Research*, 93, pp. 37-50.
- Zahra, S. A. (1993) A Conceptual Model of Entrepreneurship as Firm Behavior: A Critique and Extension. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 17(4), pp. 5-21.
- Zainol, N. R., Al Mamun, A., Hassan, H. and Muniady, R. L. (2017) Examining the Effectiveness of Microenterprise Development Programs in Malaysia. *Journal of International Studies*, 10(2), pp. 292-308.
- Zainol, N. R., Al-Mamun, A., Ahmad, G. B. and Simpong, D. B. (2018) Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Competencies towards Performance of Informal Microenterprises in Kelantan, Malaysia. *Economics and Sociology*, 11(4), pp. 31-50.
- Zainol, N. R. and Mamun, A. A. (2018) Entrepreneurial Competency, Competitive Advantage and Performance of Informal Women Micro-Entrepreneurs in Kelantan, Malaysia. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 12(3), pp. 299-321.
- Zeb, A. and Ihsan, A. (2020) Innovation and the Entrepreneurial Performance in Women Owned Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Pakistan. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 79, pp. 102342.
- Zehir, C., Gurol, Y., Karaboga, T. and Kole, M. (2016) Strategic Human Resource Management and Firm Performance: The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Orientation. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 235, pp. 372 – 381.
- Zhang, W. and White, S. (2016) Overcoming the liability of newness: Entrepreneurial action and the emergence of China's private solar photovoltaic firms. *Research Policy*, 45(3), pp. 604–617.
- Zhao, X., Lynch, J. G. and Chen, Q. (2010) Reconsidering Baron and Kenny: Myths and Truths about Mediation Analysis. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37(2), pp. 197-206.
- Zigon, J. (2002) How to Measure Employee Performance. Zigon Performance Group. Retrieved March, 15, p. 2014.
- Zimmerer, T., Scarborough, N. M. and Wilson, D. (2008) *Essentials of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management*. Upper Saddle River N.J: Prentice Hall.

Zin, S. M. and Manaf, K. A. (2019) Role of Intellectual Capital in WomenEntrepreneur's Business Performance. In: T. Florica, N. Kumar, N. Clifton and D. Hyams-Ssekasi, eds. *Women Entrepreneurs and Strategic Decision Making in the Global Economy*. Hershey, PA, USA: IGI Global, pp. 209-230.

Zolin, R., Stuetzer, M. and John , W. (2013) Challenging the female underperformance hypothesis. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship*, 5(2), pp. 116-129.

Zukauskas, P., Vveinhardt, J. and Andriukaitiene, R. (2018) *Philosophy and Paradigm of Scientific Research*. london: Intech Open.

Appendices A: Ethical Approval Form

17/01/2022

Dear Ayesha Razzak,

Your application 17344: Enhancing the Growth of Existing Female Enterprise in an emerging economy – A Perspective of Pakistan, submission reference 14709, has been approved, with conditions, by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below:**

Please ensure you store your data on an encrypted server such as the UWS OneDrive.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendices B: Participants Sheet

*Enhancing the Performance of Existing Female Enterprise in an emerging economy – A Perspective of
Pakistan*

Dear Participant,

You are invited to participate in a study conducted by Mrs. Ayesha Razzak, a Doctorate (DBA) candidate at the University of the West of Scotland in the United Kingdom. The title of the research is “*Enhancing the Performance of Existing Female Enterprise in an Emerging Economy – A Perspective of Pakistan*”. The study will aim to investigate factors that aid in the growth of female-owned firms in Pakistan, particularly in Lahore, Punjab Province.

The researcher recognised that the future of female entrepreneurs in Pakistan depends largely on the efforts of SME owners such as yourself. Therefore, the researcher is eager to learn about your successful business experience. In particular, the researcher seeks information about factors that determine performance in SMEs. The researcher thinks that your contribution could be put right into efforts to help more businesses in Pakistan be successful.

What you have been asked to do

In this research, participants will be invited to have a face-to-face in-depth interview session, which will last about 30 minutes. Participants in this study can withdraw at any time as their participation is entirely voluntary. This interview will be arranged according to the participants' convenience, i.e., a specific time, location, and date. Participants have the right and freedom to ask questions during the interview sessions and afterwards by contacting the researcher. Lastly, a participant can choose not to answer any question if they don't feel comfortable doing so.

The interview questions are designed to gather in-depth information about factors that can enhance the growth of firms in Pakistan. Any information obtained from this study will be held anonymous and will not be disclosed unless with your permission. All of the information you give during the interview will be stored and used in accordance with the Data Protection Act of 2018 and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Thank you for your kind co-operation.

Best regards,

DBA Candidate

Ayesha Razzak

Business School

University of the West of Scotland

Email:

Personal details withheld.

Appendices C: Participants Consent Form

Consent Form

Title of Project: *Enhancing the Performance of Existing Female Enterprise in an emerging economy – A Perspective of Pakistan*

Name of Researcher: Ayesha Razzak

Personal details withheld.

Study ID Number: [REDACTED]

Participant to complete this section:

Please initial each box:

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions, and have them satisfactorily answered.	
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.	
3. I agree to take part in the above study.	

Your signature will certify that you have voluntarily decided to take part in this research study, having read and understood the information in the sheet for participants. It will also certify that you have had an adequate opportunity to discuss the study with the researcher and that all questions have been answered to your satisfaction. All of the information provided by you in the interview will be stored and processed in accordance with the Data Protection Act 2018 and the associated General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Name of Participant:

Signature:

Date:

Name of researcher: Ayesha Razzak

Signature:

Appendices D: Research Questionnaire

Section 1- General Information

1.1 What is your age Group? Please Circle

Under 25 years	26 to 35	36 to 45	46 to 55	Above 55
----------------	----------	----------	----------	----------

1.2 What is the highest level of education you have successfully completed? Please Circle

No Education	Basic Education (1 to 9)	Secondary (10 to 12)	College
Bachelor's degree	Diploma	Master's degree	PhD
Other (please specify)			

1.3 Did you have prior work experience before starting the business? Please Circle

Yes (How many years?.....)	No
-------------------------------	----

1.4 Have you attended any business training? Please Circle

Yes	No
-----	----

1.5 For how long are you in this business? Please Circle

Less than 2 years	3 – 5 years	6 -8 years	9 – 15 years	Above 15 years
-------------------	-------------	------------	--------------	----------------

1.6 In which industry do you operate? Please Circle

Education	Retail	Personal care	Health care	Legal/professional service
-----------	--------	---------------	-------------	----------------------------

1.7 How many employees do you have?

0-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10
------------	------------	------------	------------	-------------

Section 2- Human Capital

<i>Please use the following scale to describe your opinion towards human capital</i>						
<i>2.1 Education</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Slightly disagree</i>	<i>Slightly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
My education has help me in identifying and seizing business opportunities.	1	2	3	4	5	6
My area of education has help me in handling various business challenges independently.	1	2	3	4	5	6
My education has equipped me with a wide range of skills and knowledge that is useful in running my business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>2.2 Previous Work Experience</i>						
My job experience has equipped me in handling daily business operation.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I can solve my business problems based on my previous job experience.	1	2	3	4	5	6
My job experience has help me to stay organised in my business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
<i>2.3 Business Training</i>						
My training has affected on greater customer satisfaction.	1	2	3	4	5	6
My training has helped me in acquiring knowledge on business skills.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Training is necessary for the development of any business.	1	2	3	4	5	6

Section 3- Entrepreneurial Orientation

<i>Please use the following scale to describe your opinion towards entrepreneurial orientation</i>						
3.1 Risk taking	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Slightly disagree</i>	<i>Slightly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Taking risk is seen as a positive trait in my business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
In my business, I take calculated risks with new ideas.	1	2	3	4	5	6
My business always look for new opportunities and give it a go.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.2 Innovativeness						
My business is always making effort to improve and introduce new ideas in business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
My business is creative in the ways of doing business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
My business searches for new ways to do things.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.3 Proactiveness						
My business is usually the first to introduce new product/service which other firms copy.	1	2	3	4	5	6
If our business see opportunity, we like to respond before other firms do.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Our business is good at finding profitable opportunities.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Global single item of EO						
In general, my business is innovative, actively looking for new products/services and willing to take risk.	1	2	3	4	5	6

Section 4- Entrepreneurial Competencies

<i>Please use the following scale to describe your opinion towards entrepreneurial competencies</i>						
3.1 Commitment	<i>Strongly Disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Slightly disagree</i>	<i>Slightly Agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>

I am going to do everything I can to make my business work.	1	2	3	4	5	6
To help my business succeed, I make a lot of sacrifices on a personal level.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I have no plans to leave this business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Most of my time is spent working at my business to make it successful.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.2 Organising						
I decide how the business will run.	1	2	3	4	5	6
To get the job done, I organise my staff.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I motivate my workers by giving them bonuses, meals, money for transportation, etc.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I take steps to solve day-to-day issues and problems that my business faces.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I plan how various resources in the firm, such as funds and staff, will be organised.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.3 Strategy						
I make sure that what I am doing now meets my long-term business goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I monitor my business progress in reaching my long-term business goals.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am aware of the future trends in the market and how they could affect my business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I often look at short-term, day-to-day tasks in the context of long-term goals and see how they fit together.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.4 Conceptual						
I know how ideas, issues, and monitoring impact business in general.	1	2	3	4	5	6

I am willing to take moderate risks in my work.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I monitor the profit of my risky investments.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I make business decisions with careful planning.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I will proactive and be open to changes.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.5 Relationship						
By being friendly to consumers, I make them feel welcome.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I encourage feedback from customers and use it to improve our service.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I settle arguments between employees.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I keep in touch with customers and staff on a daily basis.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I respond quickly to customer complaints.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.6 Opportunity						
I offer services or products that customers want but are not offered by my competitors.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I find out what products or services my customers want.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I capture profitable business opportunities.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am always on the lookout for products or services that really help customers.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3.7 EC Global Single Item Measurement						
The extent to which you think you have all of the above skills to run your business.	1	2	3	4	5	6

Section 5- Learning Orientation

Please use the following scale to describe your opinion towards entrepreneurial competencies						
5.1 Learning Orientation	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly disagree	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

I often read things (articles, internet, books, etc.) to improve my knowledge and business skills.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like to take on challenging tasks from which I can learn a lot.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am willing to take a risk because I care about improving my skills.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I often look for opportunities to develop new skills and knowledge.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like doing hard and challenging things that can help me learn new skills.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I like to work in situations where I need a lot of skill and talent.	1	2	3	4	5	6

Section 6- Firm Performance

Please circle the option that best describes your firms performance during the last three years based on the following statements:

<i>Firm Performance</i>						
Customer is satisfied with the service and products.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I have been successful in maintaining relationships with our existing customers.	1	2	3	4	5	6
I am satisfied with the overall performance of my business.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Compared to my competitors, my business sales have increased over the past three years.	1	2	3	4	5	6
Compared to my competitors, my business market share has increased over the past three years.	1	2	3	4	5	6

Thank you for completing the questionnaire.

1.1 آپ کی عمر کا گروپ کیا ہے؟ برائے مہربانی دائرہ بنائیں

25 سال سے کم	26 سے 35	36 تا 45	46 تا 55	55 سے اوپر
--------------	----------	----------	----------	------------

1.2 آپ نے کتنی تعلیم مکمل کر لی ہے؟ برائے مہربانی دائرہ بنائیں

کوئی تعلیم نہیں	بنیادی تعلیم (1 سے 9)	ثانوی (10 سے 12)	کالج
بیچلر کی ڈگری	ڈپلومہ	ماسٹر ز کی ڈگری	پی ایچ ڈی
دیگر (وضاحت براہ مہربانی).....			

1.3 آپ کے پاس کاروبار شروع کرنے سے پہلے کتنے سال کی ملازمت کا تجربہ تھا؟ برائے مہربانی دائرہ بنائیں

ہاں (کتنے سال؟.....)	نہیں
-------------------------	------

1.4 کیا آپ نے کسی کاروباری تربیت میں شرکت کی ہے؟ براہ کرم دائرہ بنائیں

ہاں	نہیں
-----	------

1.5 آپ اس کاروبار میں کتنے سالوں سے ہیں؟ براہ کرم دائرہ بنائیں

2 سال سے بھی کم	3 - 5 سال	6-8 سال	9 - 15 سال	15 سال سے اوپر
-----------------	-----------	---------	------------	----------------

1.6 آپ کس صنعت میں کام کرتے ہیں؟ براہ کرم دائرہ بنائیں

تعلیم	خوردہ	ذاتی نگہداشت	صحت کی دیکھ بھال	قانونی/پیشہ ورانہ خدمت
-------	-------	--------------	------------------	------------------------

1.7 آپ کے پاس کتنے ملازمین ہیں؟

0-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10
-----	-----	-----	-----	------

سیکشن 2- انسانی سرمایہ

براہ کرم انسانی سرمائے کے بارے میں اپنی رائے بیان کرنے کے لئے درج ذیل پیمانے کا استعمال کریں
--

2.1 تعلیم					
سختی سے اختلاف	تھوڑا سا اختلاف	تھوڑا سا اتفاق کرنا	اتفاق کرنا	سختی سے متفق ہوں	
1	2	3	4	5	6
میری تعلیم نے کاروباری مواقع کی شناخت اور فائدہ اٹھانے میں میری مدد کی ہے۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میری تعلیم نے مجھے مختلف کاروباری چیلنجوں سے آزادانہ طور پر نمٹنے میں مدد کی ہے۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میری تعلیم نے مجھے وسیع پیمانے پر مہارتوں اور علم سے آراستہ کیا ہے جو میرے کاروبار کو چلانے میں مفید ہے۔					
2.2 پچھلے کام کا تجربہ					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میری ملازمت کے تجربے نے مجھے روزانہ کے کاروباری مسائل سے نمٹنے میں مدد کی ہے۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میں اپنے پچھلے ملازمت کے تجربے کی بنیاد پر اپنے کاروباری مسائل حل کر سکتی ہوں۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میری ملازمت کے تجربے نے مجھے اپنے کاروبار میں منظم رہنے میں مدد کی ہے۔					
2.3 کاروباری تربیت					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میری کاروباری تربیت سے گاہکوں کو اطمینان ملا ہے۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میری کاروباری تربیت نے کاروباری مہارتوں پر علم حاصل کرنے میں میری مدد کی ہے۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
کسی بھی کاروبار کی ترقی کے لئے تربیت ضروری ہے۔					

سیکشن 3- کاروباری رجحان

براہ کرم کاروباری رجحان کے بارے میں اپنی رائے بیان کرنے کے لئے درج ذیل پیمانے کا استعمال کریں					
3.1 خطرہ اٹھانا					
سختی سے اختلاف	تھوڑا سا اختلاف	تھوڑا سا اتفاق کرنا	اتفاق کرنا	سختی سے متفق ہوں	
1	2	3	4	5	6
خطرہ مول لینا میرے کاروبار میں ایک مثبت خصوصیت کے طور پر دیکھا جاتا ہے۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
اپنے کاروبار میں، میں نئے آئیڈیاز کے ساتھ حسابی خطرات لینا ہوں۔					
1	2	3	4	5	6
میرا کاروبار ہمیشہ نئے مواقع تلاش کرتا ہے اور اسے آزما رہا ہے۔					
3.2 اختراع					

6	5	4	3	2	1	میرا کاروبار ہمیشہ کاروبار میں نئے خیالات کو بہتر بنانے اور متعارف کرانے کی کوشش کرتا ہے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میرے کاروبار کا کام کرنے کا انداز تخلیقی ہے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میرا کاروبار کام کرنے کے نئے طریقوں کی تلاش کرتا ہے۔
3.3 فعالیت						
6	5	4	3	2	1	میرا کاروبار عام طور پر نئی مصنوعات/ سروس متعارف کرانے والا پہلا کاروبار ہوتا ہے جسے دیگر فرمیں نقل کرتے ہیں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	اگر ہمارا کاروبار موقع دیکھتا ہے، تو ہم دوسری فرموں سے پہلے جواب دینا پسند کرتے ہیں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	ہمارا کاروبار منافع بخش مواقع تلاش کرنے میں اچھا ہے۔
ای او کی گلوبل سنگل انٹم						
6	5	4	3	2	1	عمومی طور پر، میرا کاروبار اختراعی ہے، نئی مصنوعات/ خدمات کی تلاش میں ہے اور خطرہ مول لینے کے لئے تیار ہے۔

سیکشن 4- کاروباری اہلیت

براہ کرم کاروباری صلاحیتوں کے بارے میں اپنی رائے بیان کرنے کے لئے درج ذیل پیمانے کا استعمال کریں						
4.1 عزم						
سختی سے متفق ہوں	اتفاق کرنا	تھوڑا سا اتفاق کرنا	تھوڑا سا اختلاف	اختلاف	سختی سے اختلاف	
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اپنے کاروبار کو چلانے کے لئے ہر ممکن کوشش کرنے کو تیار ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	اپنے کاروبار کو کامیاب بنانے کے لئے میں ذاتی سطح پر بہت سی قربانیاں دیتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میرا اس کاروبار کو چھوڑنے کا کوئی ارادہ نہیں ہے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میرا زیادہ تر وقت میرے کاروبار کو کامیاب بنانے کے لئے کام کرنے میں صرف ہوتا ہے۔
4.2 تنظیم						
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں فیصلہ کرتی ہوں کہ کاروبار کیسے چلے گا۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	کام مکمل کرنے کے لئے، میں اپنے عملے کو منظم کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اپنے کارکنوں کو بونس، کھانا، نقل و حمل کے لئے رقم وغیرہ دے کر ترغیب دیتی ہوں۔

6	5	4	3	2	1	میں روز مرہ کے مسائل کو حل کرنے کے لئے اقدامات کرتی ہوں جن کا میرے کاروبار کو سامنا ہے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں منصوبہ بناتی ہوں کہ کس طرح فرم میں مختلف وسائل، جیسے کہ فنڈز اور عملہ کو منظم کیا جائے گا۔
4.3 حکمت عملی						
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اس بات کو یقینی بناتی ہوں کہ اب میں جو کچھ کر رہی ہوں وہ میرے طویل مدتی کاروباری اہداف کو پورا کرے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اپنے طویل کاروباری اہداف تک پہنچنے میں اپنی کاروباری پیشرفت کی نگرانی کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں بازار میں مستقبل کے رجحانات سے واقف ہوں اور وہ میرے کاروبار کو کس طرح متاثر کرسکتے ہیں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اکثر اپنے طویل اور قلیل مقاصد کا تنازنا کرتی ہوں اور روزمرہ کے کاموں کو دیکھتی ہوں اور دیکھتی ہوں کہ وہ کس طرح ایک ساتھ فٹ ہوتے ہیں۔
4.4 تصوراتی						
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں جانتی ہوں کہ کاروباری خیالات، مسائل اور نگرانی عام طور پر کاروبار پر کس طرح اثر انداز ہوتے ہیں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اپنے کام میں معتدل خطرات اٹھانے کو تیار ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اپنی جوکھم بھری سرمایہ کاری کے منافع کی نگرانی کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں محتاط منصوبہ بندی کے ساتھ کاروباری فیصلے کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں متحرک رہوں گی اور تبدیلیوں کے لئے تیار رہوں گی۔
4.5 رشتہ						
6	5	4	3	2	1	صارفین کے ساتھ دوستانہ سلوک کر کے، میں انہیں خوش آمدید محسوس کروا تی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں صارفین کی رائے کی حوصلہ افزائی کرتی ہوں اور اسے اپنی سروس کو بہتر بنانے کے لئے استعمال کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں ملازمین کے مسائل حل کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں گاہکوں اور عملے سے روزانہ رابطے میں رہتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں گاہکوں کی شکایات کا فوری جواب دیتی ہوں۔
4.6 موقع						
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں ایسی خدمات یا مصنوعات پیش کرتی ہوں جس کی میرے صارفین کو ضرورت ہے لیکن میرے حریفوں کی طرف سے ویسی خدمات پیش نہیں کی جاتی ہیں۔

6	5	4	3	2	1	میں مشاہدہ کرتی ہوں کہ میرے صارفین کون سی مصنوعات یا خدمات چاہتے ہیں
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں منافع بخش کاروباری مواقع پر قبضہ کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں ہمیشہ ایسی مصنوعات یا خدمات کی تلاش میں رہتی ہوں جو واقعی صارفین کی مدد کرتے ہیں۔
4.7 ای سی گلوبل سنگل انٹم پیمائش						
6	5	4	3	2	1	آپ کے خیال میں آپ کے پاس اپنا کاروبار چلانے کے لئے مندرجہ بالا تمام مہارتیں کس حد تک ہیں۔

سیکشن 5- سیکھنے کا رجحان

براہ کرم کاروباری صلاحیتوں کے بارے میں اپنی رائے بیان کرنے کے لئے درج ذیل پیمانے کا استعمال کریں						
سختی سے متفق ہوں	اتفاق کرنا	تھوڑا سا اتفاق کرنا	تھوڑا سا اختلاف	اختلاف	سختی سے اختلاف	5.1 سیکھنے کا رجحان
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اکثر اپنے علم اور کاروباری مہارتوں کو بہتر بنانے کے لئے چیزیں (مضامین، انٹرنیٹ، کتابیں وغیرہ) پڑھتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں چیلنجنگ کام کرنا پسند کرتی ہوں جن سے میں بہت کچھ سیکھ سکتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں خطرہ مول لینے کو تیار ہوں کیونکہ مجھے اپنی مہارتوں کو بہتر بنانے کی فکر ہے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اکثر نئی مہارتوں اور علم کو فروغ دینے کے مواقع تلاش کرتی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	مجھے سخت اور چیلنجنگ چیزیں کرنا پسند ہے جو مجھے نئی مہارتیں سیکھنے میں مدد کر سکتی ہیں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں ایسے حالات میں کام کرنا پسند کرتی ہوں جہاں مجھے بہت زیادہ مہارت اور صلاحیت کی ضرورت ہے۔

سیکشن 6- فرم کارکردگی

براہ کرم اس اختیار کا چکر لگانے جو درج ذیل بیانات کی بنیاد پر پچھلے تین سالوں کے دوران آپ کی فرموں کی کارکردگی کو بہترین طور پر بیان کرتا ہے:						
مضبوط کارکردگی						
6	5	4	3	2	1	گاہک سروس اور مصنوعات سے مطمئن ہے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اپنے موجودہ صارفین کے ساتھ تعلقات برقرار رکھنے میں کامیاب رہی ہوں۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میں اپنے کاروبار کی مجموعی کارکردگی سے مطمئن ہوں۔

6	5	4	3	2	1	میرے حریفوں کے مقابلے میں گزشتہ تین سالوں کے دوران میری کاروباری فروخت میں اضافہ ہوا ہے۔
6	5	4	3	2	1	میرے حریفوں کے مقابلے میں گزشتہ تین سالوں کے دوران میرے کاروباری مارکیٹ شیئر میں اضافہ ہوا ہے۔

سوالنامہ مکمل کرنے کے لئے آپ کا شکریہ۔

Appendices E: Interview Questions

<i>Interview Questions</i>	
The results of the first phase of the survey indicate that the majority of women agree that " Human Capital Components " facilitate the development of business skills.	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Can you explain how your education has helped in enhancing your business skills? ➤ Can you explain why your previous job experience did not have any impact on your business skills? ➤ Please explain how your business training has improved your business skills. 	
The majority of women surveyed in the first phase concurred that " Entrepreneurial skills (competencies) " are essential for business performance.	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Can you explain why staying committed to the business can increase your firms' performance? ➤ How well do you communicate with customers or suppliers so that your business does well? (If yes, why?) ➤ How are various resources (finance/staff/technology) planned in your business? Is the organising of various resources vital for business performance? (If yes, why?) ➤ Does spotting and seizing business opportunities increase your firms' performance? (If yes, how?) ➤ Do you consistently plan for the future of your business? How does it help you achieve firm performance? ➤ To what extent do you agree that having critical thinking can help a business do better? 	
According to the findings of the first phase of the study (survey), " Entrepreneurial orientation " does not contribute to business performance.	

- Why do you think taking a risk is not important for business performance?
- How often do you introduce new products or services into your business? Can you explain why such innovativeness is not important for firm performance?
- Do you continuously monitor market trends and identify further customer needs? Do you think such business proactiveness is important? (If yes/no, why?)
- How do your business skills or your ability have an impact on the entrepreneurial orientation dimensions (risk-taking, innovativeness, and proactiveness)?

According to the findings of the first phase of the survey, "**Learning Orientation**" has a significant impact on the company's performance.

- Please explain how your business skills have improved your learning.
- How has your learning helped you to do business better/increase business performance?

Appendices F: Descriptive Statistics

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Skewness</i>			<i>Kurtosis</i>		
			<i>Statistic</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Z-score</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Z-score</i>
Performance	PER_1	307	-0.246	0.139	-1.770	-1.297	0.277	-4.682
	PER_2	307	-0.422	0.139	-3.036	-0.927	0.277	-3.347
	PER_3	307	-0.389	0.139	-2.799	-1.096	0.277	-3.957
	PER_4	307	-0.485	0.139	-3.489	-0.962	0.277	-3.473
	PRE_5	307	0.628	0.139	4.518	-1.222	0.277	-4.412
Proactive	PRO_EO_1	307	-0.238	0.139	-1.712	-1.208	0.277	-4.361
	PRO_EO_2	307	-0.148	0.139	-1.065	-1.153	0.277	-4.162
	PRO_EO_3	307	-0.177	0.139	-1.273	-1.219	0.277	-4.401
Innovativeness	INN_EO_4	307	-0.228	0.139	-1.640	-1.023	0.277	-3.693
	INN_EO_5	307	-0.105	0.139	-0.755	-1.100	0.277	-3.971
	INN_EO_6	307	-0.319	0.139	-2.295	-1.025	0.277	-3.700
Risk-Taking	RIS_EO_7	307	-0.346	0.139	-2.489	-0.987	0.277	-3.563
	RIS_EO_8	307	-0.289	0.139	-2.079	-0.889	0.277	-3.209
	RIS_EO_9	307	-0.173	0.139	-1.245	-1.071	0.277	-3.866
Commitment	COM_EC_1	307	-0.795	0.139	-5.719	-0.534	0.277	-1.928
	COM_EC_2	307	-0.588	0.139	-4.230	-0.501	0.277	-1.809

	COM_EC_3	307	-0.830	0.139	-5.971	-0.220	0.277	-0.794
	COM_EC_4	307	-0.924	0.139	-6.647	-0.268	0.277	-0.968
Conceptual	CON_EC_1	307	-0.595	0.139	-4.281	-0.847	0.277	-3.058
	CON_EC_2	307	-0.452	0.139	-3.252	-0.962	0.277	-3.473
	CON_EC_3	307	-0.447	0.139	-3.216	-1.025	0.277	-3.700
	CON_EC_4	307	-0.543	0.139	-3.906	-0.946	0.277	-3.415
	CON_EC_5	307	-0.153	0.139	-1.101	-0.960	0.277	-3.466
Organising	ORG_EC_1	307	-0.855	0.139	-6.151	-0.176	0.277	-0.635
	ORG_EC_2	307	-0.698	0.139	-5.022	-0.514	0.277	-1.856
	ORG_EC_3	307	-0.615	0.139	-4.424	-0.962	0.277	-3.473
	ORG_EC_4	307	-0.630	0.139	-4.532	-0.639	0.277	-2.307
	ORG_EC_5	307	-0.776	0.139	-5.583	-0.307	0.277	-1.108
Strategy	STA_EC_1	307	-0.265	0.139	-1.906	-1.091	0.277	-3.939
	STA_EC_2	307	-0.279	0.139	-2.007	-1.133	0.277	-4.090
	STA_EC_3	307	-0.321	0.139	-2.309	-1.078	0.277	-3.892
	STA_EC_4	307	-0.148	0.139	-1.065	-1.059	0.277	-3.823
Opportunity	OPP_EC_1	307	-0.730	0.139	-5.252	-0.542	0.277	-1.957
	OPP_EC_2	307	-0.783	0.139	-5.633	-0.215	0.277	-0.776
	OPP_EC_3	307	-0.772	0.139	-5.554	-0.518	0.277	-1.870
	OPP_EC_4	307	-0.806	0.139	-5.799	-0.345	0.277	-1.245
Relationship	REL_EC_1	307	-0.641	0.139	-4.612	-0.520	0.277	-1.877
	REL_EC_2	307	-0.680	0.139	-4.892	-0.544	0.277	-1.964
	REL_EC_3	307	-0.488	0.139	-3.511	-0.563	0.277	-2.032
	REL_EC_4	307	-0.724	0.139	-5.209	-0.563	0.277	-2.032
	REL_EC_5	307	-0.412	0.139	-2.964	-0.776	0.277	-2.801
	REL_EC_6	307	-0.458	0.139	-3.295	-0.966	0.277	-3.487
Learning	LEO_1	307	-0.482	0.139	-3.468	-1.044	0.277	-3.769

	LEO_2	307	-0.490	0.139	-3.525	-0.952	0.277	-3.437
	LEO_3	307	-0.216	0.139	-1.554	-1.148	0.277	-4.144
	LEO_4	307	-0.240	0.139	-1.727	-1.046	0.277	-3.776
	LEO_5	307	-0.474	0.139	-3.410	-0.855	0.277	-3.087
	LEO_6	307	-0.477	0.139	-3.432	-0.905	0.277	-3.267
Education	EDU_HC_1	307	-0.432	0.139	-3.108	-0.764	0.277	-2.758
	EDU_HC_2	307	-0.221	0.139	-1.590	-0.648	0.277	-2.339
	EDU_HC_3	307	-0.035	0.139	-0.252	-1.079	0.277	-3.895
Training	TRA_HC_1	307	-0.434	0.139	-3.122	-0.709	0.277	-2.560
	TRA_HC_2	307	-0.509	0.139	-3.662	-0.678	0.277	-2.448
	TRA_HC_3	307	-0.425	0.139	-3.058	-0.917	0.277	-3.310
Experience	EXP_HC_1	307	-0.303	0.139	-2.180	-1.071	0.277	-3.866
	EXP_HC_2	307	-0.395	0.139	-2.842	-1.075	0.277	-3.881
	EXP_HC_3	307	-0.424	0.139	-3.050	-1.050	0.277	-3.791
EO_GSL	Global Single item	307	-0.263	0.139	-1.892	-0.967	0.277	-3.491
EC_GSL	Global Single item	307	-0.394	0.139	-2.835	-0.817	0.277	-2.949
Valid N	Valid N	307						

Appendices G: Normality Test

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Commitment	.192	307	.000	.873	307	.000
Conceptual	.158	307	.000	.904	307	.000
Organising	.168	307	.000	.915	307	.000
Strategy	.130	307	.000	.932	307	.000
Opportunity	.167	307	.000	.918	307	.000
Relationship	.139	307	.000	.923	307	.000
Proactiveness	.163	307	.000	.913	307	.000
Innovativeness	.131	307	.000	.933	307	.000
Risk_Taking	.147	307	.000	.938	307	.000
Performance	.150	307	.000	.913	307	.000
LearningOrientation	.137	307	.000	.916	307	.000
Education_attainment	.124	307	.000	.947	307	.000
Job_experience	.177	307	.000	.908	307	.000
Business_training	.173	307	.000	.915	307	.000

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Appendices H: Common Method Variance

Total Variance Explained						
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.624	21.396	21.396	11.865	20.11	20.11
2	5.777	9.792	31.188			
3	4.387	7.436	38.624			
4	2.619	4.439	43.063			
5	2.584	4.379	47.442			
6	2.147	3.638	51.080			
7	1.832	3.105	54.185			
8	1.518	2.573	56.759			
9	1.328	2.251	59.009			
10	1.221	2.069	61.079			
11	1.156	1.960	63.039			
12	1.137	1.926	64.965			
13	1.034	1.752	66.717			
14	0.983	1.667	68.383			
15	0.932	1.580	69.964			
16	0.887	1.504	71.467			
17	0.817	1.385	72.852			
18	0.754	1.278	74.129			
19	0.717	1.216	75.345			
20	0.668	1.132	76.477			
21	0.644	1.091	77.568			
22	0.629	1.065	78.633			

23	0.590	1.000	79.633			
24	0.575	0.974	80.607			
25	0.553	0.937	81.544			
26	0.541	0.916	82.460			
27	0.513	0.870	83.330			
28	0.512	0.868	84.198			
29	0.479	0.811	85.009			
30	0.474	0.803	85.812			
31	0.466	0.790	86.602			
32	0.457	0.775	87.377			
33	0.442	0.749	88.126			
34	0.431	0.730	88.856			
35	0.395	0.670	89.526			
36	0.385	0.653	90.178			
37	0.370	0.628	90.806			
38	0.363	0.615	91.421			
39	0.341	0.579	91.999			
40	0.323	0.548	92.547			
41	0.320	0.542	93.089			
42	0.319	0.540	93.629			
43	0.314	0.533	94.162			
44	0.300	0.508	94.670			
45	0.279	0.473	95.143			
46	0.255	0.432	95.575			
47	0.251	0.426	96.001			
48	0.248	0.420	96.421			
49	0.239	0.405	96.825			

50	0.233	0.395	97.221			
51	0.221	0.375	97.595			
52	0.210	0.356	97.952			
53	0.199	0.338	98.289			
54	0.190	0.321	98.611			
55	0.182	0.309	98.919			
56	0.176	0.298	99.217			
57	0.167	0.283	99.500			
58	0.165	0.280	99.780			
59	0.130	0.220	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring.						

Appendices I: Correlation between EC and EO

Correlations

		Commitment	Conceptual	Organising	Strategy	Opportunity	Relationship	EO
Commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	.262**	.535**	.325**	.521**	.589**	.087
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.127
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Conceptual	Pearson Correlation	.262**	1	.432**	.265**	.282**	.465**	.171**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.003
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Organising	Pearson Correlation	.535**	.432**	1	.360**	.544**	.611**	.130*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.022
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Strategy	Pearson Correlation	.325**	.265**	.360**	1	.257**	.340**	.069
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.227
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Opportunity	Pearson Correlation	.521**	.282**	.544**	.257**	1	.531**	.174**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.002
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Relationship	Pearson Correlation	.589**	.465**	.611**	.340**	.531**	1	.163**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.004
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
EO	Pearson Correlation	.087	.171**	.130*	.069	.174**	.163**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.127	.003	.022	.227	.002	.004	
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Appendices J: Correlation between EC and Firm Performance

Correlations

		Commitment	Conceptual	Organising	Strategy	Opportunity	Relationship	Performance
Commitment	Pearson Correlation	1	.262**	.535**	.325**	.521**	.589**	.412**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Conceptual	Pearson Correlation	.262**	1	.432**	.265**	.282**	.465**	.348**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Organising	Pearson Correlation	.535**	.432**	1	.360**	.544**	.611**	.403**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Strategy	Pearson Correlation	.325**	.265**	.360**	1	.257**	.340**	.287**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Opportunity	Pearson Correlation	.521**	.282**	.544**	.257**	1	.531**	.389**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Relationship	Pearson Correlation	.589**	.465**	.611**	.340**	.531**	1	.475**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307
Performance	Pearson Correlation	.412**	.348**	.403**	.287**	.389**	.475**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	307	307	307	307	307	307	307

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Appendices K: Correlation between EO and Firm Performance

Correlations

		Proactiveness	Innovativeness	Risk_Taking	Performance
Proactiveness	Pearson Correlation	1	.649**	.578**	.128*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.025
	N	307	307	307	307
Innovativeness	Pearson Correlation	.649**	1	.661**	.096
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.093
	N	307	307	307	307
Risk_Taking	Pearson Correlation	.578**	.661**	1	.082
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.153
	N	307	307	307	307
Performance	Pearson Correlation	.128*	.096	.082	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.025	.093	.153	
	N	307	307	307	307

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).